

An exploration of the role of online language education in developing the oral English skills of Chinese students in preparation for university study in the UK

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Abstract

This thesis, set against the backdrop of globalisation and the internationalisation of higher education, explores how online language learning can enhance the English-speaking proficiency of Chinese students. The study emphasises that English-speaking skills play a crucial role in promoting international academic exchange, improving the study abroad experience, and increasing students' competitiveness in the global job market. It examines how the rise of online language learning, accelerated by the COVID-19 pandemic, has introduced both opportunities and challenges to higher education, such as bridging cultural differences, overcoming language barriers, and fostering student self-discipline.

The primary aim of this research is to assess whether online language learning can effectively improve the oral English proficiency of future Chinese students studying at UK universities. To achieve this, the study considers the educational backgrounds of Chinese students, China's online learning policies, and existing literature. Drawing on theoretical frameworks such as motivation, social capital, cultural capital, and habitus, the research investigates the impact of online language learning on student motivation, oral communication skills, and their integration into social and academic life in the UK. The research methods include online observations and interviews, revealing how online instructional strategies influence students' oral proficiency, while also identifying the technological challenges faced by Chinese students engaging in online education.

Additionally, the study formulates four key research questions to explore the multidimensional effects of online language learning, with a particular focus on its role in language development for Chinese students during the global pandemic. This comprehensive approach not only provides students with effective strategies to overcome the challenges of online language learning but also aims to serve as a valuable resource for educators, universities, and educational platforms in advancing the development and application of digital language education.

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Author's Declaration

I declare that, except where explicit reference is made to the contribution of others, this thesis is the result of the researcher's work and has not been submitted for any other degree at the University of the West of Scotland or any other institution.

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List of Abbreviations

CET-4: College English Test Band 4

CLT: Communicative Language Teaching

COVID-19: Coronavirus disease 2019

ELT: English Language Teaching

ERL: Emergency Remote Learning

HEIs: Higher education institutions

ICT: Communication Technology

IELTS: International English Language Testing System

IL2S: the Ideal L2 Self

IT: Information technology

L1: First language

L2: Second language

L2MSS: L2 Motivational Self System

LMS: Learning Management System

MOE: Ministry of Education

MOOCs: Massive Open Online Courses

NHS: National Health Service

OECD: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development

OER: Open Educational Resources

OL2S: Ought-to L2 Self

SDL: Self-directed Learning

SDT: Self-determination Theory

SLA: Second Language Acquisition

SLLE: Second Language Learning Experience

SNS: Social Networking Services

TandL: Teaching and Learning

TBLT: Task-Based Language Teaching

TNE: Transnational Education

TOEFL: Test of English as a Foreign Language

UNESCO: United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization

VPN: Virtual Private Network

VR: Virtual Reality

WHO: World Health Organization

Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Overview

In the context of globalization, the internationalization of higher education has become a key driver of academic progress and innovation, significantly influencing the development of the global academic landscape. This process involves not only the integration of international perspectives and practices but also the consolidation of global educational resources and innovations in teaching methods. Internationalisation in higher education encourages cross-cultural exchanges, enabling the blending of diverse academic traditions cultures and methodologies. In this context, English, as the predominant language of academia, has gained increasing prominence, particularly in terms of the requirement for English-speaking skills, which are essential for both learners and providers of education across all levels and areas of academic engagement.

Firstly, English-speaking skills are fundamental in promoting international academic exchange and cooperation. In higher education, international collaboration has become an essential means of advancing academic research and development (DeLaquil *et al.*, 2022). English, as a bridge for international communication, enables scholars from different countries and regions to overcome the challenges of understanding key concepts in what might be a variety of languages, allowing them to engage in effective communication, share research findings, and cooperate on academic projects. This capability is key to the dissemination of knowledge and the creation of global research networks that drive forward innovation and scholarly advancement.

Secondly, English-speaking skills are a key pathway to enhancing a scholar's international academic influence. On the international academic stage, strong English-speaking abilities enable scholars to present their research achievements and

academic standing more effectively, earning recognition and respect from international peers. The ability to confidently articulate complex ideas in English helps scholars participate actively in international conferences, publish in prestigious journals, and contribute meaningfully to global academic dialogues.

However, we must also consider the post-colonial establishment of English and the related issues of power as a lingua franca. Mackenzie (2022) discusses how the spread of English in developing countries, such as Colombia, is linked to broader issues of economic development and social mobility. While English can provide advantages in domains like employment and trade, it also reinforces the dominance of the global North interests, perpetuating inequalities in developing regions. Jahan (2024) explores such linguistic imperialism in the context of cultural hegemony, particularly among indigenous communities in Canada. The study underscores how English, as a dominant language, can lead to the decline of indigenous languages and emphasizes the importance of revitalization efforts to combat the cultural and linguistic erosion caused by this dominance.

Because of this linguistics imperialism, English-speaking skills are essential in improving university students' employability in the global job market. In today's interconnected world, students with strong English language abilities are generally more competitive. They are better equipped to adapt to international work environments and to communicate effectively with colleagues and clients from diverse cultural backgrounds, thereby gaining more employment opportunities and career development prospects. This proficiency in English can enable them to excel in roles that require cross-cultural communication, making them valuable assets in multinational organisations.

However, improving English-speaking skills is not an overnight process; it requires long-term effort, practice, and exposure to various authentic communicative contexts. In the process of internationalisation, higher education institutions have increasingly emphasised English-speaking learning and teaching, aiming to enhance exchanges

and collaboration with the international academic community. This emphasis provides students with more opportunities for international exchange and practical language application, helping them build the language skills necessary to succeed in a globalised academic and professional environment.

Concurrently, the rise of online learning has instigated significant transformations in higher education (Wang, Guo, Gao and Zhao, 2024). The rapid advancement of digital technologies has not only enhanced the accessibility and distribution of educational resources but has also introduced more flexible and diverse pedagogical approaches (Zhou, Wu, Zhou and Li, 2020). These innovations have democratized access to education, allowing learners from diverse geographical locations to engage in academic activities at any time, thereby dismantling the traditional constraints of temporal and spatial limitations inherent in conventional classroom settings (Xie, Siau and Nah, 2020). This shift toward digital education has the potential to promote equity in learning, though it also presents new challenges related to digital literacy, learner engagement, and the quality of online instructional design.

However, this new educational model also brings a series of challenges. Cultural differences, language barriers, and the digital divide have become increasingly prominent, significantly affecting, at times, the effectiveness and quality of online learning. The digital divide refers to the gap between individuals or groups who have access to modern information and communication technologies (such as high-speed internet and digital devices) and those who do not (Aissaoui, 2022; Su *et al.*, 2021). This divide is influenced by factors like socioeconomic status, geographical location, and education level. In the context of online learning, the digital divide can significantly affect the quality and effectiveness of education, as students who lack reliable internet access or appropriate devices may struggle to fully participate in online courses, thereby exacerbating educational inequalities.

These challenges can create disparities in student engagement and learning outcomes, particularly for international students who may face challenges in adapting to the

online environment and accessing necessary resources (Ali, Narayan and Sharma, 2021). These necessary resources include a stable high-speed internet connection, suitable digital devices (such as laptops or tablets), and a quiet, dedicated study space (Ren, Zhu and Liang, 2024). Additionally, students need access to online education platforms, digital textbooks, academic databases, and effective communication channels with tutors and peers (Asio *et al.*, 2021). For international students, language support resources, culturally relevant learning materials, and timely technical support are also critical (Ren, Zhu and Liang, 2024).

Notably, the unique of requirements brought about by the COVID-19 pandemic have greatly accelerated the popularisation and adoption of online learning. Faced with the severe challenges (such as technological barriers; inequality and access; emotional and so on) posed by the COVID-19 pandemic, higher education institutions had to quickly adjust their teaching strategies and move to online teaching models (Sim, Sim and Quah, 2021). While this shift alleviated some of the negative impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on education, it also exposed certain challenges with limitations of online learning. For instance, the lack of face-to-face communication and interaction, the increased difficulty in evaluating learning outcomes, and the challenge of maintaining student self-discipline are some of the current issues faced by online learning. These challenges have highlighted the need for innovative solutions to improve the effectiveness of online education, particularly in the realm of language learning (Huang, 2020).

This thesis conducts in-depth research on these key issues, aiming to explore the role of online learning in developing the English-speaking skills of Chinese students, particularly in social settings, with the goal of enhancing their cross-cultural educational experiences at UK universities. Specifically, the thesis investigates China's educational background and online learning policies, as well as reviews the relevant literature, to explore whether online learning can effectively improve students' oral proficiency. This chapter provides an introduction to the fundamental principles

of the research, establishing a solid foundation for the study. It introduces the rationale, as well as the purpose, and scope of the research, giving readers a clear understanding of the motivations for and significance of the study.

Additionally, the thesis examines the research objectives and questions in depth, offering insightful perspectives and proposing thought-provoking directions for further exploration. The selected research methods are also introduced, highlighting their strengths and limitations, and providing a clear rationale for their selection. The thesis explores the significance of the research, discussing its potential impact and contributions to the field, as well as its implications for educators, policymakers, and online learning platforms. Lastly, this chapter provides a detailed outline of the thesis, presenting the structure and organisation of the research, and guiding the reader through the subsequent chapters.

The thesis employs various theoretical frameworks, particularly motivation theory, social capital theory, cultural capital, and habitus theory, to analyse the impact of online language learning on student motivation, oral expression, and social integration in the UK. The research methods include online observations and interviews, which have enabled researchers to gain insights into the effects of online learning on students' speaking abilities. The researcher observed Chinese students' online classes, examined the relationship between teachers' teaching strategies and students' oral skills, and studied the online learning environments and technological challenges faced by students. Subsequently, the observation and interview results were analysed, revealing key themes and patterns in the data. Finally, the thesis concludes with recommendations and guidelines for future research, offering practical strategies for improving the online language learning experience for international students. Through its comprehensive analysis, this thesis aims to contribute to a deeper understanding of how online learning can be effectively leveraged to support language acquisition and cross-cultural adaptation in a globalised educational context.

1.2 Research Rationale

In recent decades, the rapid growth in the number of international students has become an increasingly important feature of higher education, particularly in Europe, Oceania, and North America, where the internationalization of education has expanded rapidly. Asian international students represent the largest student group studying abroad, accounting for 53% of the total number of international students Globally (Yu and Moskal, 2019). In this context, UK universities, having developed a reputation globally for their high-quality education, have experienced significant changes in student demographics. Over the past decade, the number of international students in the UK has steadily increased, with China being the largest source country. More and more Chinese students are opting to study abroad through 2+2 undergraduate UK English throughout programmes, 3+1 undergraduate UK English throughout programmes, and various Master's and doctoral programmes. According to a report by the Higher Education Statistics Agency (HESA) in 2021, the number of Chinese students increased in the UK by 51,140, reflecting a 56% growth from the 2015/16 to 2019/20 academic years (HESA, 2021). In 2019/20, 35% of non-EU international students in the UK were from China, at that point, the number out of every five international students in the UK is Chinese. Chinese students therefore made significant contributions to the UK in areas such as finance, the economy, academia, and culture.

This study focuses on the experiences of Chinese international students with online language learning, particularly in oral proficiency, during the COVID-19 pandemic. The pandemic has fundamentally altered the traditional definitions and practices of international education. De Wit and Altbach (2021) note that the pandemic shifted much of the teaching and learning online, leading to new modes of education such as hybrid and online learning, which were especially critical for international students and the continued development of their learning. Traditionally, Transnational Education (TNE) involves higher education institutions (HEIs) in one country

providing accredited educational services to students residing in another country. However, due to travel restrictions caused by COVID-19, institutions adapted by continuing to provide high-quality education through digital platforms (Hari, Nardon, and Zhang, 2023). The ways in which transnational education has changed practically during the post-COVID-19, therefore, is a key focus of my study, as I explore online language learning for students who are planning to come to English-speaking countries.

This shift has redefined the term "international student" now encompassing those participating in remote learning via digital platforms from their home countries. While physical mobility has historically been central to international education, De Wit and Altbach (2021) emphasize the growing importance of "internationalization at home" which includes curriculum development and global citizenship education to complement traditional mobility. In this context, oral proficiency becomes even more critical, as students learning from their bedroom or home environments often lack the opportunity to practice authentic language use in real-life settings. Without face-to-face interactions in diverse environments, the chances to engage in spontaneous conversations, develop fluency, and navigate cultural nuances are limited. This lack of authentic language practice can hinder a student's ability to achieve the level of oral proficiency required for real-world communication, especially in academic or professional contexts (Shu and Gu, 2018).

Alam *et al.*, (2020) further suggest that in the current context of higher education, TNE has the potential to become a cornerstone in rebuilding the international education system post-COVID-19.

The COVID-19 pandemic therefore had a profound impact on the global education system. Discovered in late 2019 in Wuhan, China, the virus spread rapidly worldwide, leading the World Health Organization (WHO) to declare it a global pandemic by March 2020. This caused widespread disruptions to economies, social structures, and education systems globally (Zhou *et al.*, 2020). Governments, including those in China

and the UK, quickly implemented policies to transition from offline classroom teaching to online platforms to mitigate the pandemic's impact on education (Kansal *et al.*, 2021). By September 2020, over 87% of students worldwide had been affected by lockdown measures (WHO, 2020b), with many institutions adopting online learning as an emergency measure (Kamal *et al.*, 2020).

With the widespread adoption of remote teaching strategies, digital platforms such as Microsoft Teams, Zoom, and Moodle have become essential tools for delivering education (UNESCO, 2020a). These platforms enabled universities to continue teaching international students despite the lack of in-person cross-border movement (Yıldırım *et al.*, 2021). Many countries have taken steps to improve access to educational resources, ensuring that students from different backgrounds can obtain high-quality educational materials without extra costs. Governments introduced policies to promote educational equity by expanding internet access and providing free access to educational websites and applications. These efforts aimed to make education more inclusive and equitable, addressing challenges in rural and underserved areas (Niranjan, 2020; Al-Samarrai, Gangwar and Gala, 2020).

While the shift to online learning mitigated the pandemic's impact on education, it also revealed several challenges, especially for international students. For Chinese international students enrolled in UK courses online, language learning barriers were particularly prominent. Online platforms, while essential, did not provide the same level of interactive learning as in-person classrooms (Varalakshmi and Arunachalam, 2020). Many students faced limited opportunities for informal, real-time communication with peers and lecturers, which hindered their ability to improve their oral English proficiency. Gao *et al.*, (2011) highlight the major challenges faced by Chinese international students, including language barriers (58.3%), communication difficulties (56.4%), and cultural adaptation (42.0%).

Based on my personal experience as a Chinese international student studying in the UK, I encountered significant challenges with language barriers, particularly in

listening comprehension and oral expression. These difficulties were compounded by differences between Chinese and UK teaching methods, educational systems, and communication norms; for example, the focus on interactive learning in the UK which is rare in China. As mentioned in Chapter 2, this experience is closely related to the concept of "face" in Chinese culture and the fear of "losing face" (Zhou, Wu, Zhou and Li, 2020). In Chinese society, maintaining one's social image and avoiding embarrassment or shame in public is of significant importance, especially in formal settings like academic discussions (Choi, 2015). Concerns about pronunciation, grammar, or clarity of expression often lead students to remain silent in class, as they may worry about "losing face" in front of peers or professors (Liu, 2021).

For Chinese students enrolled in one-year Master's programmes, these challenges are even more pronounced. Many report that their oral English skills did not improve significantly after a year of study in the UK, which negatively impacted their academic performance and social interactions with peers and lecturers.

Despite these challenges, online learning has the potential to play an increasingly important role in the future of education. Existing literature has focused primarily on the oral language adaptation challenges faced by Chinese students in the UK. However, there is limited research on their educational preparedness for international study in China and their experiences upon arrival in the UK during the COVID-19 pandemic. This includes not only the "temporary" transition challenges but also the long-term impacts of the pandemic on their educational experiences.

Given this backdrop, and from the literature review undertaken below, this study specifically focuses on oral proficiency because spoken language skills are central to effective communication, both in academic and professional settings. Oral proficiency enables students to express ideas clearly, engage in meaningful discussions, and build social connections, all of which are essential for success in an international educational environment. During the COVID-19 pandemic, as online learning replaced in-person classes, opportunities for real-time, face-to-face communication

diminished, significantly impacting students' ability to practice and improve their spoken language skills.

Additionally, developing oral proficiency in a foreign language, particularly English for Chinese students, presents unique challenges due to differences in phonetics, sentence structure, and cultural norms of communication. Without regular interactions in an authentic, real-world environment, students may struggle to develop the confidence and fluency needed to use the language effectively. Hence, the literature has suggested this study prioritizes oral proficiency to explore how students perceive these challenges and navigate the limitations of online language learning during the pandemic. This focus is essential for understanding the broader impact of the shift to online education on language development, particularly for skills that require interactive and immersive experiences. The research will assess both the benefits and challenges of this learning mode and provide insights into how online education can better support the academic growth of international students. By focusing on oral proficiency, this study contributes to a broader understanding of how educational experiences abroad influence the development of authentic oral skills in Chinese students.

1.3 Research Questions

Following my literature, the core idea that forms the foundation of my thesis is: "What is the role of online learning in improving the English-speaking skills of Chinese university students?" This question is broad in scope and requires an in-depth exploration of various aspects related to online learning, particularly in the context of language acquisition. To address this question effectively, I have formulated four research questions:

- Question 1: What do Chinese international students understand by online learning and how do they engage with it?

- Question 2: How did Chinese international students adapt to the rapid development in online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic, and how did this affect them?
- Question 3: What are the challenges faced by Chinese students while participating in online learning?
- Question 4: In what ways does the participation of Chinese international students in online learning affect their oral proficiency?

These questions are designed to provide a clear understanding of the concept of online language learning and the current level of English-speaking proficiency among Chinese students. Questions 1, 2 and 3 are addressed in the early chapters of this study. The answers to these questions are not merely presented but thoroughly analysed to offer a multifaceted understanding of the subject. In the subsequent chapters, these answers will be revisited in relation to the insights and findings gathered throughout this research. Question 4 is directly linked to my empirical research. Using data collected from online classroom observations (discussed in Chapter 6) and from online interviews (detailed in Chapter 7), I will further explore these questions, with a final discussion presented in Chapter 8.

1.4 Research Purpose

In the contemporary era, characterised by the continuous advancement of educational technology, learning methods and pedagogical approaches are undergoing significant transformation. Two key methodologies, ubiquitous learning and online learning, have garnered increasing attention in academic discourse. Initially, my research intention was to focus on the concept of ubiquitous learning, with the objective of promoting educational innovation by harnessing its flexibility and omnipresence.

Ubiquitous learning is conceptualised as a system "based on ubiquitous computing and technology-supported environments, which can be utilised universally and at all

times" (Virtanen *et al.*, 2017, p. 2566). The concept originated from Weiser's (1991) idea of "ubiquitous computing" which aims to achieve seamless integration and immersive learning experiences through the use of pervasive technologies such as mobile devices, embedded digital devices, and sensing technologies (Huang *et al.*, 2011; Sakamura and Koshizuka, 2005). Ubiquitous learning environments provide context-aware and personalised learning content, suggestions, or feedback based on time, location, or user activities (Hwang *et al.*, 2011; Marinagi *et al.*, 2013; Wu *et al.*, 2013). In such environments, learners can engage in activities anytime and anywhere through mobile devices and other embedded technologies, emphasising continuity, accessibility, immediacy, and interactivity in the learning process (Chin and Chen, 2013; Huang *et al.*, 2010).

There is a close relationship between ubiquitous learning and online language learning. Online language learning relies on the support of the internet and digital tools, enabling learners to engage with language courses, apps, and interactive platforms. Ubiquitous learning extends this approach further by introducing context-aware technologies, making learning activities more personalised and context-specific. For example, a ubiquitous learning environment can automatically suggest appropriate language learning content based on the learner's location, time of use, and progress (Hwang *et al.*, 2011; Wu *et al.*, 2013).

Despite the overlap in technological support, there are notable differences in the application of ubiquitous learning and online language learning. Online language learning often depends on online platforms and learning management systems (LMS), such as MOODLE and Blackboard, which provide structured course content, assessments, and interactive functions (Wang and Qi, 2009).

The abrupt emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic has profoundly altered the trajectory of global education, prompting a shift in focus towards online language learning. As educational institutions worldwide transitioned to online teaching methods to cope with restrictions and lockdowns, online language learning has

become particularly significant. This shift has underscored the need for more adaptable and accessible language learning solutions, highlighting the potential of integrating both ubiquitous and online learning approaches to address the evolving demands of learners.

Against the backdrop of the pandemic, online language learning has emerged as an important area for further investigation due to its increasing prevalence and the urgent need for innovative solutions in relation to education. I contend that the role of online language learning during this period not only holds considerable practical relevance but also presents significant research potential. As a result, my research focus has transitioned towards exploring the specific application of online language learning in enhancing the language acquisition process for Chinese international students.

The primary objective of this study is to conduct a comprehensive exploration of the role that online language learning plays in the development of oral English proficiency among Chinese international students, particularly within the context of cross-border education. By focusing on this area, the research aims to identify how online platforms, digital tools, and tailored pedagogical strategies can support these students in overcoming challenges and achieving greater success in their language learning journey.

In essence, the aim of this research is to develop a thorough understanding of the current role online learning occupies within higher education and to critically assess its impact on facilitating the academic transition of Chinese students from universities in China to institutions in the United Kingdom during and following the COVID-19 pandemic. Moreover, this study seeks to identify and analyse effective strategies for utilising online learning to enhance the oral language skills of Chinese international students. Through a detailed examination of the specific impact of online language learning, the research will investigate how it influences the integration of Chinese students into higher education and propose recommendations for improving their learning experiences within a global educational framework.

1.5 Research Method

This study was conducted within a qualitative research paradigm, chosen for its ability to provide in-depth insights into the experiences and perceptions of Chinese international students regarding online language learning. The decision to employ qualitative methods, rather than quantitative approaches, was made because the exploration of the impact of online language learning on this group involves a considerable human element, making it essential to capture the richness and complexity of their lived experiences. Unlike quantitative methods, which tend to focus on numerical data and statistical relationships, qualitative research allows for a more nuanced exploration of the intricate aspects of online learning, such as the development of oral English proficiency and the challenges associated with adapting to a new cultural and educational environment.

By employing online classroom observations and online semi-structured interviews as the two primary qualitative data collection methods, I was able to gather direct, detailed, and authentic data from the students. These methods enabled me to observe their learning behaviours in a natural setting, while interviews provided an opportunity for the students to express their thoughts, feelings, and experiences in their own words. This approach allowed for a more meaningful analysis and interpretation of their experiences, offering deeper insights into their perspectives on the challenges and benefits of online language learning. Additionally, through the use of open-ended questions during interviews, I was able to explore topics that were of particular importance to the participants, leading to unexpected insights that may not have emerged through more structured research methods.

Given that this study focused on a specific cohort of Chinese students studying at a Scottish university in the United Kingdom, qualitative research methods are particularly effective for capturing the unique experiences, challenges, and perspectives of this particular group. Unlike quantitative methods that might

generalise findings across a larger population, qualitative research allows for a context-sensitive analysis that considers the specific cultural, social, and academic context of the participants. This is especially important in the context of international education, where students' backgrounds and cultural differences can significantly shape their learning experiences and outcomes.

Therefore, qualitative research is more appropriate for this study as it enables the uncovering of the deeper significance behind the phenomena under investigation, offering a thorough understanding of Chinese international students' experiences with online language learning. It allows for a rich, interpretative exploration of how these students navigate the challenges of learning English in an online environment, how they perceive their own progress in oral English proficiency, and how they integrate into the broader academic community. The methodology, data collection process, and analysis will be discussed fully in Chapters 5, 6, and 7 of this thesis, providing a comprehensive overview of the research undertaken, as well as the themes and insights that emerged from the data. Through this approach, the study aims to contribute to a deeper understanding of the role of online language learning in supporting Chinese students' educational journeys in the UK.

1.6 Significance and Contributions of this Study

This study holds considerable significance in addressing the motivations and challenges faced by Chinese students studying in the UK, particularly in terms of their integration into both the educational and social dimensions of life in a foreign academic environment. By exploring the experiences of these students, the research highlights the critical role that online language learning resources played during the COVID-19 pandemic in enhancing their English-speaking proficiency and overall communicative competence. Understanding how these resources facilitated language acquisition is helpful for designing effective support systems tailored to the needs of Chinese international students. Moreover, the insights gained from this study can aid

Chinese universities and their UK partners in better-preparing students for the transition to studying abroad, ensuring that they receive the appropriate support and services to thrive in the UK.

The study also raises important considerations for various stakeholders involved in online education, particularly with regard to the development, refinement, and regulation of online language learning courses. By examining the effectiveness of these courses in supporting language development, the research provides a basis for platform providers to improve the functionality and user experience of existing online education platforms. This includes recommendations for incorporating more interactive learning tools, fostering environments that facilitate peer-to-peer interactions, and ensuring that Chinese students have access to a dynamic online academic setting enriched with international communication opportunities, diverse learning resources, and robust technological support. Such improvements can significantly enhance learning outcomes, increase students' engagement with their studies, and lead to greater satisfaction with the online learning experience.

Additionally, the study offers practical and specific recommendations for both educators and students aimed at optimising the online learning experience for Chinese students. These recommendations focus on strategies for the effective use of digital learning tools, ways to foster a more engaging and participative learning environment, and techniques for overcoming common challenges in online language learning. By providing actionable guidance, this research not only supports current teaching practices but also serves as a valuable reference point for future research in the field. It contributes to a deeper understanding of online language learning within the broader context of globalised education, shedding light on how digital learning methods can be leveraged to support language acquisition and cultural adaptation in an increasingly interconnected world. Ultimately, the study underscores the importance of adapting educational practices to meet the evolving needs of international students and enrich their academic journeys.

1.7 Limitations of This Study

This study primarily focuses on the experiences of Chinese international students in the UK regarding online language learning, exploring whether this approach has helped improve their oral proficiency and overall online learning experience. During my research on "the impact of online language learning on the English-speaking proficiency of Chinese students during the pandemic." I not only concentrated on data collection, analysis, and presentation of results but also deeply reflected on the entire research process. Through this reflection, I identified several limitations that warrant attention:

Methodological Limitations: This study was conducted during the COVID-19 pandemic, with all data collected through online observations and interviews. Due to pandemic restrictions, the research could not be conducted face-to-face, and all data were gathered through online observation and interviews. While this approach provided convenience, it also presented some limitations.

Firstly, one limitation of online observation is that the researcher was unable to fully capture participants' non-verbal behaviours, such as body language, facial expressions, and emotional reactions. These non-verbal cues are essential in traditional face-to-face observations for understanding participants' emotional states, interaction patterns, and engagement in class. Additionally, technical limitations such as connection issues, device discrepancies, and network delays may have influenced participants' behaviour, potentially compromising the authenticity of the data.

Sample Limitations: This study specifically examines the learning experiences of Chinese international students at a university in Scotland. Therefore, it did not investigate the online learning experiences of Chinese international students across all UK universities. While the research offers an in-depth, specific, and comprehensive investigation of this particular group, caution should be exercised when generalising the findings to other universities or student populations.

External Trustworthiness: External trustworthiness refers to the extent to which the findings of this study can be applied to contexts outside the educational sector, such as different countries, regions, or industries. As outlined in the sample limitations, the findings of this research may not be applicable to student populations in other countries or regions. In qualitative research, the focus is often on gaining an in-depth understanding of phenomena within specific contexts, rather than broad generalisation. As such, external validity was not the primary goal of this study.

Internal Trustworthiness: Internal trustworthiness assesses whether the methods and variables used in the study accurately measure and capture the phenomena or relationships being investigated. Several factors related to internal validity emerged during this research:

Firstly, the familiarity between participants may have influenced the accuracy of the observational data. During online observations, the level of familiarity between participants was not standardised. For instance, some participants may have known each other for a longer period, while others may have met for the first time in the online learning environment. These differences in familiarity could impact classroom interactions, levels of participation, and collaboration between students, potentially influencing the observational outcomes.

Secondly, the continuity between observation and interview participants presented a significant limitation. The participants observed were not always the same individuals who took part in the interviews, and some participants who were observed did not continue their studies after the observation phase, resulting in a lack of follow-up interviews. This discontinuity may have introduced gaps in longitudinal data collection, limiting the ability to comprehensively track participants' learning processes.

Additionally, although all students were Chinese nationals, differences in time zones may have led to variations in course schedules and daily routines, potentially affecting

students' learning habits, engagement levels, and understanding of course content. Online learning also demands strong self-management and discipline, and individual capabilities in these areas may differ, leading to variations in learning outcomes. However, these differences are likely to be more attributable to individual characteristics rather than geographical location.

Despite the limitations outlined above, these issues do not diminish the value of the research findings. On the contrary, acknowledging these limitations allows readers to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the study and provides guidance for future improvements and expansions in this field. While it is impossible to eliminate all limitations, I believe that by maintaining a rigorous research approach and employing appropriate methods, I have maximised the credibility of the study. This research contributes valuable insights to qualitative inquiry and offers useful references for further research and practice in related fields.

1.8 Structure of this thesis

This study is divided into nine chapters. Chapter 2 provides the background to the study, offering an overview of online learning in China, relevant policies on online language learning, and the challenges and opportunities of online language learning within the context of the COVID-19 pandemic. The chapter focuses particularly on the challenges Chinese international students face in terms of oral proficiency.

Chapter 3 reviews and discusses the relevant literature, critically analysing and supporting the central concepts of online learning, emergency remote learning, online language learning, and second language acquisition.

Chapter 4 introduces the theoretical frameworks adopted in this study, including motivation theory, social capital theory, cultural capital theory, and habitus theory. These theories are essential for understanding and interpreting the data collected during this research.

Chapter 5 outlines the research paradigm, research methods, and the epistemological and ontological assumptions underlying the study. It also discusses the theoretical framework for data analysis and provides a detailed examination of the research process. Ethical considerations, reliability, transferability, and the researcher's positionality are addressed in this chapter.

Chapter 6 presents the findings from online classroom observations. It explains the background of the observation groups and analyses students' oral performance in online courses. The main focus is on the relationship between teachers' instructional strategies and students' oral skills, the online learning environment, technical issues, and the role of the first language (L1) in online classrooms.

Chapter 7 expands on the findings of the online interviews, with interview questions informed by the observation notes from the online classes. Selected participants are introduced, and one-on-one semi-structured online interviews are conducted, narrowing the scope of the data through a detailed analysis. The main focus of this chapter is on online learning modes, the use of L1 in online classrooms, student participation in online courses, oral expression motivation, and the relationship between platform features and online learning.

Chapter 8 provides an in-depth discussion and analysis of the findings from Chapters 6 and 7, identifying the complex relationship between current online learning and oral English proficiency.

Chapter 9 concludes the study by discussing and evaluating the relevance of the research findings in relation to the research objectives and questions. The chapter summarises the study's findings and considers their implications for the future. It offers recommendations for educators, learners in China and the UK, and relevant stakeholders (such as online platforms). Additionally, the limitations of the study are discussed, and suggestions for future research directions are proposed.

1.9 Conclusion

This chapter introduced key concepts of globalization and the internationalization of higher education, emphasizing the central role of oral English proficiency in academic and professional contexts, particularly in fostering cross-cultural communication and collaboration. Additionally, the chapter examined the profound impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on global education systems, especially the rapid adoption of online learning and its challenges for the development of oral proficiency among Chinese international students. This study focuses on analyzing the influence of online learning on students' language development, particularly their speaking skills, highlighting its importance while explaining the research background and motivation. Through this chapter, a comprehensive understanding of the online learning environment has been established, providing a solid theoretical foundation and direction for the subsequent research.

The next chapter will delve into the online learning contexts in China and the UK, offering important background and a broader understanding of how Chinese students develop their oral English skills in these environments.

Chapter 2: Online Learning Context in China and the UK

2.1 Introduction

When discussing the development of spoken English proficiency among Chinese international students in the context of online learning, several key issues need to be further explored. Firstly, understanding the background of English education in China is crucial as it helps us uncover the current status and challenges Chinese students face in developing their spoken English skills. Secondly, researching the development of online learning in China is equally important as it allows us to observe the application of online learning in cross-border education in China and its impact on the development of spoken English proficiency among Chinese students. Furthermore, it is necessary to explore the development of online learning in China and its importance in responding to the COVID-19 pandemic. Moreover, understanding the internationalization of higher education for Chinese students can help us have a more comprehensive understanding of the opportunities and challenges they face in a cross-border education environment. Lastly, focusing on the online learning challenges faced by Chinese students in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, as well as the challenges and opportunities for the United Kingdom in this regard, will help me (the researcher) to comprehensively analyze and address the role of online learning in the development of spoken English proficiency among Chinese international students. In-depth research on these five issues will contribute to a deeper and more comprehensive understanding of the role of online learning in the development of spoken English proficiency among Chinese international students.

2.2 History of English Language Education in China

English language education in China originated in the late 19th and early 20th centuries when China faced the need for international communication and

modernisation. The following are the main stages and developments in the history of English language education in China:

2.2.1 Missionary Period (Late 19th to Early 20th Century)

Some scholars believe that China's official English language teaching (ELT) originated from the Beijing Tongwen Guan in the 1860s. Established in 1862, the Beijing Tongwen Guan was the first official foreign language school in China (Sun, 1996). It was a translation research institute under the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and played a significant role in English education during the late Qing Dynasty. Its purpose was to cultivate translation talents in response to the requirements of the Treaty of Tientsin (Lieberthal, 1980). Despite being initially underestimated, its status gradually increased as its graduates achieved success in fields such as diplomacy (Spence, 1999). This initiative propelled the modernization of education in China, leading to the establishment of more government-funded schools and emphasizing the importance of foreign language education, thus establishing China's autonomous position in the field of education. The Beijing Tongwen Guan can be seen as a precursor to modern foreign language education in China (Pan and Pan, 2015).

Other scholars argue that ELT first appeared in missionary schools with the arrival of Western missionaries in the early 19th century (Wu, 2022). In the 1830s, various Protestant missionaries introduced more formal ELT initiatives in Guangzhou and Macau (Evans, 2006). For example, in 1835, British missionary Robert Morrison established the first Sino-English school in Macau, known as the Morrison Education Society (Ford, 1988). During this period, Christian missionaries played a crucial role in China by opening schools and teaching English as a foreign language to Chinese students. They emphasized the development of students' English listening and speaking skills intending to spread the Christian faith. They also authored English textbooks and dictionaries, laying the foundation for English education (Wu, 2022).

In addition, in response to the rapid growth of modern schools, there was an urgent need to develop a comprehensive national curriculum to adapt to the ever-changing educational landscape. Therefore, in 1903, a groundbreaking curriculum was introduced, marking a significant milestone in the history of education. This curriculum not only recognized the importance of providing students with a solid foundation in Chinese and mathematics but also acknowledged the crucial role of foreign languages in nurturing well-rounded individuals. As a result, foreign languages were officially designated as one of the three core subjects that schools must teach (Pan, 2015). It is worth noting that with the introduction of this new curriculum, the number of government-funded modern schools saw an unprecedented surge, surpassing the previous dominance of missionary schools. This notable phenomenon demonstrates the widespread recognition and acceptance of government reforms and the modernization of the education framework, shaping the trajectory of education development in our country.

2.2.2 The republican period (1919-1949)

The New Culture Movement occurred from 1919 to 1949. It was a period in which China experienced a series of significant historical events, most notably the First World War and the May Fourth Movement, an internal youth-led movement in China. After the First World War, China signed the Treaty of Versailles and participated in the Paris Peace Conference, but failed to obtain reasonable guarantees for its territory and rights, which led to dissatisfaction among Chinese students and intellectuals, and subsequently the eruption of the May Fourth Movement (Pan, 2015, p.65). This movement gave rise to the New Culture Movement, in which a large amount of Western philosophy, literature, sociology, cultural studies, and ethics were introduced and translated into Chinese, laying a solid foundation for China's modernisation and the establishment of a modern society (Cheng and Chen, 2023). The main achievements of the New Culture Movement include reforms in literature, thought, and education, which also contributed to the development of English language

education (Pan, 2015, p.67). For example, Chen Duxiu believed that merely bringing in English teachers was not enough; rather, the focus should be on ensuring that the students were equipped with the necessary language skills to benefit from their instruction. He emphasized that without a foundation in English, the effectiveness of foreign teachers would be greatly diminished. Therefore, he advocated for a thorough assessment of students' English proficiency before making any hiring decisions (Tong and Shi, 2012).

2.2.3 The socialist revolutionary period (1949-1978)

The victory of the Communist Party in 1949 led to the establishment of a new social, political, and economic system in China, which in turn established a new education system. The Korean War in the early 1950s and the Cold War between the East and the West resulted in nationwide Resistance against America and aid to the Korean movement in China (Lee, 2001). During this period, China's education policy was influenced by socialist ideology, and Russian became the most important foreign language in Chinese primary, middle, and high schools. By the late 1950s, the Sino-Soviet split ended the Soviet model, and the concepts of independence and self-reliance were emphasized. The development slogan changed from "Learning from the Soviet Union" to "Learning from all advanced experiences in the world" (Dzau, 1990, p.19). In 1962, foreign languages became a required subject in the Chinese College Entrance Examination (Ross, 1993). In 1964, the "Seven-Year Outline for Foreign Language Education" was promulgated, with English designated as the first foreign language in China. At that time, there was an emphasis on developing students' English listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills. English textbooks and teaching methods also underwent changes, with a greater focus on cultivating students' practical application abilities. While China was actively engaging in educational exchanges with English-speaking countries to enhance the internationalization of its English language education, the initial promise of this approach did not translate into long-term success. Despite the initial optimism,

sustaining the momentum and achieving the desired outcomes proved to be challenging. From 1966 to 1976, China experienced the unprecedented nationwide political turmoil of the Cultural Revolution, which dealt a major setback to English language teaching. Most middle schools and universities were closed, and foreign languages, including English, were condemned.

2.2.4 China's Opening up of China (1978-present)

In 1984, under the leadership of Deng Xiaoping, the "reform and opening up" policy ushered in a new era of rapid development in Chinese society. English was once again seen as an important tool for achieving national development and modernization. In 1985, the first China International Symposium on English Teaching was held in Guangzhou (Hu, 2002). English teaching experts from China and abroad proposed directions and trends in English teaching research in areas such as education, psycholinguistics, and sociolinguistics, which promoted the research and teaching reform of English teaching methods in China, improved the quality of English teaching, and cultivated more English professionals. In the late 1990s, as China's reform and opening up continued to deepen and the political situation became increasingly stable, the status and role of English reached its peak since the founding of the People's Republic of China. In order to embrace new opportunities and challenges, the Ministry of Education decided in 2001 to start English teaching from the third grade of primary school (Wang, 2007). In the same year, China successfully joined the World Trade Organization (Lardy, 2004). From 2008 to 2011, China successfully hosted the Olympic Games, Asian Games, and World University Games, igniting another wave of enthusiasm for English learning throughout the country (Gong, 2012).

In summary, English language education in China has gone through different stages and developments, from the missionary period to modern educational reforms, and the importance of English education in China continues to grow. With the improvement of China's international status, the development of English education in China will

continue to receive attention and promotion. The study of the history of English language education in China is of great significance for understanding China's educational development and international exchanges.

2.3 Social-cultural context of education in China

China's education system has developed within a rich social and cultural background. Confucianism is an important part of Chinese traditional culture, founded by Confucius (the philosopher, 551—479 B.C.E.) and developed over generations into a complete philosophical system. The core of Confucianism is benevolence (Ren) which emphasizes love and respect between individuals, highlighting the importance of relationships such as family, friendship, and love, as well as personal moral cultivation and social harmony. In addition to "Ren", there are four other core concepts in Confucianism as explained by Uzma et al. (2022): righteousness (Yi), propriety (Li), wisdom (Zhi), and fidelity (Xin). Confucianism is deeply rooted in the thinking of the Chinese people and has evolved into a series of ideologies and values with the development of social structure, greatly influencing Chinese education.

Firstly, Confucianism emphasizes self-cultivation and moral improvement, which is consistently reflected in Chinese education. Confucianism believes education aims to cultivate individuals with virtues and abilities, rather than just imparting knowledge. Therefore, Chinese education focuses on students' moral education and comprehensive development, emphasizing their holistic growth (Guo, Hang and Zhang, 2019). Furthermore, Confucianism emphasizes the application of knowledge, stating that learning should be for practical use. This idea is fully embodied in Chinese education, which emphasizes cultivating students' practical abilities and problem-solving skills and integrating theoretical knowledge with practical applications (Guo, Hang and Zhang, 2019).

Secondly, Confucianism advocates for "teaching students in accordance with their aptitude," tailoring teaching methods based on student's individual characteristics and

learning levels (Chen, 2023). This concept has been widely applied in Chinese education. Chinese education emphasizes personalized education, nurturing students' personalities and strengths, as well as fostering their creativity and practical abilities (Zhu, 2019). In a large class teaching environment, teachers face significant challenges, especially middle school teachers. Their classes have a large number of students (50-70), and there may be significant differences in students' English learning backgrounds. Some students may have studied English for three years, while others may have never been exposed to English (Hu, 2007). This situation makes it difficult for teachers to allocate teaching resources and time to fully address the individualized needs and learning characteristics of each student, thus limiting the implementation of the principle of teaching according to students' aptitude. However, teachers can still meet students' individualized needs to some extent and achieve a certain degree of teaching according to students' individual aptitudes by adopting teaching strategies and methods such as group teaching and differentiated assignments (Lou, 2021). Teaching in large classes presents unique challenges. One of the most significant of these challenges is the sheer number of students present in the class. Because of this large number, teachers often find it difficult to cater to the individual needs of each student.

At the same time, understanding the relationship between Confucian culture in Chinese education and rote memorization can better understand the learning patterns of Chinese students. In traditional Chinese learning and teaching methods, memorization has been given significant emphasis, particularly in countries within the Chinese cultural sphere (McMahon, 2011). This emphasis on memorization reflects a belief in the value of committing information to memory through repetition, which is often seen as a necessary step towards achieving academic excellence (Biggs, 1996). However, this seemingly mechanical learning approach is built on a deep understanding of the text. Confucius once said, "Reviewing what you have learned and learning anew, you are fit to be a teacher." (McMahon, 2011). Furthermore, the learning method advocated by Confucianism is "Learning without thought is labour

lost, thought without learning is perilous," which means that learning must be combined with thinking. Through thinking, we can deepen our understanding of knowledge, and through practice, we can verify and consolidate what we have learned. This shows that by reviewing old knowledge, students can gain new insights and understanding, thereby deepening and internalizing knowledge (Rajaram and Rajaram, 2020).

In fact, within China's Confucian tradition, memory is not seen as the entirety of learning, but rather as the foundation for understanding knowledge. Students first master basic facts and concepts through memory, then build upon this foundation for deeper thought and understanding. This memory is not a simple repetition, but rather an internalization of knowledge as part of oneself through continuous review and thinking. Chinese students use various memory techniques in the learning process, such as association and constructing knowledge networks, which are all part of higher-order learning strategies. By linking new knowledge with existing knowledge, students can better understand and remember new information. This method not only improves the efficiency of memory but also promotes deep understanding of knowledge (Marton *et al.*, 1996).

However, when Chinese students find themselves in culturally different learning environments, such as Western universities, they may adjust their learning strategies, which sometimes may unfairly label them as "insensitive rote learners". This further highlights the importance of teaching according to students' aptitude in cross-cultural learning environments.

Based on the influence of Confucianism on Chinese education discussed above, there are also some negative effects on Chinese students. For example, the education system may suffer from issues of authority, and students may have a strong concern for their own and others' face-saving, or prefer to connect with people of their own culture (Song, Sun and Cai, 2022; Liu, 2013). In terms of English learning, these negative effects may manifest as Chinese students being overly reserved when

communicating with native English speakers, fearing that their language proficiency is insufficient and thus limiting their opportunities for language practice.

According to Confucianism, China has had a strict hierarchical social structure for thousands of years. In such a society, everyone is expected to follow the principle of propriety (Li) and behave correctly within their respective roles. It is believed that an ideal way to achieve a harmonious society is through a well-defined hierarchical system (King and Bond, 1985). Confucianism influences teacher-student relationships, student behaviour, and teaching methods (Choi and Han, 2023). In traditional Chinese culture, teachers are often seen as authorities in the classroom, holding greater power in terms of discourse. This notion of authority may to some extent affect the performance of Chinese students in the classroom, making them more reserved and less likely to actively participate in discussions. This is a cultural stereotype of the Chinese international student community. Wang, Ai and Williams (2022, p.3) propose that an essentialist view of culture limits its concept to be "static, holistic, homogeneous, deterministic and bounded", thereby confining it to ethnicity or race. In simpler terms, belonging to a specific culture, such as being American or Chinese, means internalizing a coherent set of psychological, physical, and social characteristics. This understanding of culture suggests that it is something shared or attributed to national, ethnic, or international groups (Labani, 2023). However, the essentialist cultural viewpoint (Holliday 2009) is harmful to Chinese international students as it hides individuals behind their culture, reducing them to representatives of a singular ethnic culture and fixed identity (Dervin, 2010). On the other hand, cultural non-essentialism focuses on "the complexity of culture as a fluid, creative social force ... both constructing and constructed by people in a piecemeal fashion to produce myriad combinations and configurations" (Holliday *et al.*, 2004, p. 4). This approach acknowledges the dynamic nature of culture and emphasizes its fluidity, creativity, and the agency of individuals within it.

The role of the learning environment is also acknowledged. For example, Rao and Chan (2010) emphasize the primary influence of the social context of learning, stating that it is the aspects of the social context that influence student learning rather than the cultural heritage itself. Heng (2018) argues that the attitudes, behaviours, and values of Chinese students can change depending on the environment. Additionally, there is increasing recognition of the connections between Chinese and Western students. Mullen (2019) demonstrates that Chinese students can exhibit essential and creative thinking skills similar to their Western counterparts when the environment encourages such skills. According to Wang and Williams (2022), the continuously changing educational environment in China demands researchers to adopt a non-essentialist approach. Factors such as the influence of Western educational beliefs, China's intention to reform teaching methods and curriculum, and the individual differences among Chinese learners highlight the importance of developing a more nuanced and dynamic understanding of culture and identity in educational settings.

Confucianism also emphasizes humility and face-saving, which also has an impact on Chinese students' classroom behaviours. In the classroom, Chinese students are often praised for being good listeners and note-takers but may be less willing to engage in classroom activities and discussions (Burrows, 2016). Influenced by the culture of humility, they tend to conform to norms and avoid drawing attention to themselves. They are often perceived as being cautious and humble in their classroom learning, treating others with humility and listening more (Pang, 2012). Face-saving is also highly valued by Chinese individuals and serves as a fundamental principle for social interactions in China and other Confucian societies (Redding, 1990). In social interactions, to maintain face, Chinese individuals are widely regarded as often avoiding standing out or taking risks in public settings, fearing failure, embarrassment, or ridicule from others (Wan, 2021).

Additionally, it is common in Chinese culture for individuals to place importance on others' faces and respect for their dignity and self-esteem (Min, 2016). To maintain

others' faces, they may choose to remain silent and not express their opinions to avoid causing inconvenience or disrespect. In the classroom environment, students may also engage in polite silence to preserve face, being hesitant to ask questions or express opinions to avoid causing embarrassment or challenging the authority of teachers (Choi, 2015).

Similar issues have also been observed among Japanese students influenced by Confucian culture. Nakano, Ng and Ueda (2016) conducted classroom observations on Japanese students studying abroad in Australia and found that due to the influence of silence being associated with respect and politeness in Japanese culture, compared to students from other cultural backgrounds, Japanese students tended to exhibit more silent behaviour in the classroom. Choi (2015) conducted interviews with two Korean students studying abroad in the United States and found that they were also influenced by Korean culture and face-saving, leading to silence in the classroom.

The phenomenon of "Chinese people sticking together" is based on the identification and affinity towards the same culture, also reflecting the spirit of "Ren" in terms of care and mutual assistance. In socialising outside of study, In Xie and Liu's (2021) study investigating Chinese students' social networks abroad, it was found that Chinese students tend to prefer to associate with people from the same cultural background when studying abroad, which reflects their common language and mutual understanding, facilitating the establishment of close and supportive relationships. However, when Chinese students interact with foreigners, they may encounter cultural differences and barriers, leading to feelings of exclusion or lack of trust. This situation may further lead to Chinese students lacking opportunities for oral communication with foreigners, thereby affecting their improvement in language skills and cultural communication techniques.

2.4 Online learning in China

2.4.1 IT and its applications in education

The invention of new methods and tools is a driving force for human progress (Roco and Bainbridge, 2013). The development of online technologies is closely related to the effective expansion of educational opportunities. Information technology (IT) plays a crucial role in online learning as the internet is considered an effective medium for connecting education and interaction. With advancements in communication technologies like 3G, 4G, and even 5G, the availability of information has significantly increased (Song *et al.*, 2020). One notable benefit of this progress is the emergence and rapid development of online learning (Almahasees *et al.*, 2021). The rapid development of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has had a profound impact on how we educate ourselves and others (Eristi *et al.*, 2011). Digital communication technologies, in comparison to traditional methods, are not only more practical but also provide access to the latest knowledge and information, allowing individuals to obtain information and communicate with others in a timely and convenient manner (Chen, 2020).

In terms of providing online education services, the development of communication technology is essential, and various digital media devices are also indispensable. Unlike in the past, today, online education does not require the use of a stationary computer. Content can be displayed on mobile phones (Kapenieks *et al.*, 2015; Albó *et al.*, 2019) and tablets (Fraszcyk, 2020; Nasongkhla and Sujiva, 2015) or using Virtual Reality (VR) goggles (Hurrell and Baker, 2021; Klimova, 2021). The significant improvement in the computational capabilities of these electronic devices has created favourable learning conditions for people at different times and locations (Haleem *et al.*, 2022).

The application of IT in education in China can be traced back to the late 20th century. In the 1990s, China began using devices such as overhead projectors and tape recorders as teaching aids, marking the initial application of information technology in education, known as "electronic education." With the development of multimedia technology (Luo, 2021; Losh, 2014), computers, projectors, and other devices

gradually became popular in Chinese schools in the early 2000s, and teachers started using PowerPoint for teaching (Liu and Da, 2020; Trelease, 2016). Around 2005, China witnessed the rise of distance education, utilizing the internet and multimedia technology to enable more students to receive education at home or other locations (Zhang, 2007). During the 2010s, Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) gained popularity in China. Online education platforms like "Netease Cloud Classroom" emerged one after another, offering students a wider range of learning options. In 2015, China began promoting smart education, emphasising the use of advanced technologies such as big data, cloud computing and artificial intelligence to improve the quality of education and achieve personalised teaching. In the 2020s, influenced by the requirements for the COVID-19 pandemic, schools and educational institutions in China shifted towards online education, with technologies such as live-streaming classes, online interactions, and digital exams being widely adopted (Chen *et al.*, 2020; Li, 2022).

2.4.2 Online learning policy and the COVID-19 pandemic

China's education technology has rapidly developed on the Internet due to several important policy initiatives. In 2009, the State Council of China issued the "China Education Modernization 2035 Plan," which provided macro guidance for online learning policies and emphasized the use of modern technology to accelerate the reform of talent training models. This plan encourages educational institutions to actively explore and apply new technologies to adapt to the rapidly changing educational environment and student needs. It sets long-term goals for education modernization, including online education as an important means to achieve these goals. That same year, the Chinese Ministry of Education (MOE) issued a document titled "Opinions on Strengthening the Application of Online Open Course Construction in Higher Education Institutions," which provided more specific guidance for the construction and management of online open courses. This document emphasizes the importance of resource sharing among universities, encourages

universities to collaborate in developing high-quality online courses, and opens them up to the whole society through a unified platform. (Liu, Zha and He, 2019).

In 2015, the PRC proposed the "Internet Plus" strategy, which gave rise to new ways of providing educational services and promoting a transformation in the education service model (South China Morning Post, 2015). It refers to the application of information technology, including the Internet, in traditional industries. This strategy combines various Internet technologies, such as mobile internet, cloud networks, big data, and the Internet of Things, to foster the development of new industries and businesses in China (China Daily, 2015). In the same year, the MOE expressed its intention to accelerate the high-quality development of educational informatization, actively develop "Internet Plus Education," improve the quality of higher education, and cultivate professionals to equip them for the information age.

According to data from the National Network Information Space (2020), the 47th "Statistical Report on Internet Development in China" states that "the scale of China's online education users will reach 342 million, accounting for 34.6% of the overall internet users, and the development of the online education industry is promising" (cace.org.cn). Especially in early 2020, with the MOE's call for the "School is out, but classes are on" policy, the first large-scale online teaching practice in the history of education in China was launched, giving a significant boost to the development of online education.

"School is out, but classes are on" was an online learning policy introduced during the COVID-19 pandemic in China (Zhang *et al.*, 2020). In a narrow sense, it means that during the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic, students could still communicate with each other online, ensuring the continuity of learning when they did not know when they could return to school. In a broader sense, "School is out, but classes are on" is not only about real-time synchronous learning but also about completing learning content through various asynchronous learning methods and means. This slogan was used to encourage students to continue their education even when schools

were not in session, and students could continue learning what they had been involved in their learning process (MOE, 2020; Zhou *et al.*, 2020). During that time, online education was implemented comprehensively in China, and all students were required to stay at home and continue their education through various online platforms. To cope with this emergency, universities across the country were required to provide reasonable and effective online teaching and learning resources for students, encouraging schools to use Internet platforms as an alternative to guiding students in their academic courses (Miller and Horst, 2020). As Bao (2020) described, to prevent the further spread of the COVID-19 pandemic, China's educational institutions shifted from traditional classroom environments to online learning environments. In a relatively short period, internet-based learning became an important and widespread education method in China.

The direct result was, according to data from the MOE (2020), "by the first week of May 2020, an unprecedented scale, 1,454 Chinese universities participated in nearly 1.1 million online courses, offering a total of 12.26 million courses. About 1.03 million teachers and over 17.75 million students participated in these courses" (Li, 2022, p.1). According to Liu, Yang, and Dasgupta (2020), implementing this policy affected 30 million students studying in different 3,000 schools. In response to the "School is out, but classes are on" policy, many educational institutions developed and started to provide mandatory free online learning platforms, as well as live-streamed and recorded courses, to help students complete their self-designed academic courses and plans. This included 22 online platforms offering free access to 24,000 higher education courses, ranging from 12 undergraduate subjects to 18 higher vocational education levels.

Through various online learning resource platforms, Chinese students were able to access a wide range of free educational opportunities and find high-quality teachers from various regions in China providing free high-quality teaching resources on the course platforms (Zhou *et al.*, 2020). For example, China University MOOC is an

online education platform tailored to the needs of Chinese university students. The platform offers numerous courses covering different subject areas, as well as a wealth of e-books to help students obtain additional learning resources (Huang *et al.*, 2020).

To mitigate the significant impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, Zhejiang University, one of China's most important educational institutions (Udoy *et al.*, 2023), implemented an innovative online education programme. This programme not only covered all the enrolled students of the university but also extended to affiliated students from other universities and even included international students residing in different countries. Within just two weeks of its launch, Zhejiang University provided over 5,000 different online courses for undergraduate and graduate students, both domestic and international. This comprehensive service ensured that learners could continue their studies uninterrupted amidst the restrictions of the COVID-19 pandemic. Furthermore, the university demonstrated its commitment to maintaining academic standards and timelines during the handling of thesis defenses and graduation ceremonies. Approximately 2,500 students successfully participated in online thesis defenses and graduated on schedule (Wu, 2020), which showcased the institution's adaptability and resilience in the face of unprecedented challenges.

Many Chinese scholars have given positive evaluations of the policy. Xie and Yang (2020) constructed an analytical model of online teaching methods during the COVID-19 pandemic prevention and control period, analyzing the dimensions and connotations of online teaching methods, effectively addressing the urgent need for innovation in the practice of "School is out, but classes are on" and providing valuable references for the healthy and sustainable development of online learning in the new era; Zhang *et al.*, (2021), based on large-scale online education practices centred around "School is out, but classes are on" proposed that if new ideas and thinking are applied, seizing the rare opportunity for the development of online education during the COVID-19 pandemic, promoting the transformation of education and teaching, disadvantages can turn into advantages. Some scholars, such as Xie, Siau, and Nah

(2020), have pointed out that many people believe that the COVID-19 pandemic has led to the popularization of online teaching. However, they emphasized that online teaching is not solely a product of the COVID-19 pandemic. While the COVID-19 pandemic may have accelerated this trend, it is also seen as an inevitable development in teaching and learning during the Internet era.

The previous section has presented positive evaluations of the solutions that online learning forms have brought to the challenges posed by the COVID-19 pandemic. However, on the other hand, online learning has also brought some challenges. Some scholars have expressed concerns about the future development of the "School is out, but classes are on" policy. For example, Zhu (2020) pointed out that "School is out, but classes are on" essentially needs a solution for students to enter school urgently, but whether the online courses provided under this policy can offer high-quality knowledge and skills and meet the needs of students' interaction with others may require exploration and verification in real online learning practices. As of March 2022, the digitalization reform of higher education in China has further deepened. The percentage of university teachers utilizing blended teaching has risen from 34.8% prior to the COVID-19 pandemic to 84.2%. This progress has essentially formed a comprehensive set of digital development plans for higher education in China, encompassing concepts, technology, standards, methods, and evaluation (MOE, 2022).

2.5 Internationalisation of Higher Education for Chinese Students

In a study on the internationalization of higher education, Knight (1994) suggested that the internationalization of higher education involves integrating an international dimension into the teaching/learning, research, and service functions of universities and colleges. This means incorporating international, intercultural, or global perspectives into the core functions, activities, or services of higher education institutions. This process includes aspects such as teaching, learning, and research. The definition by Altbach and Knight (2007) emphasizes that internationalization is

influenced by economic, political, and social factors, allowing higher education to participate in international processes. This implies that internationalization is not solely the concern of educational institutions but is also influenced by factors like the economy, politics, and society.

To address this view, Li et al. (2013) proposed a theoretical framework for the driving forces of internationalization in higher education, including politics, economics, socio-cultural factors, academia, and human resources as vertical coordinates, and that regions, international organizations, countries, and higher education institutions as horizontal coordinates. The interaction between the vertical and horizontal coordinates is evident at multiple levels. For instance, political and economic factors can influence a country's investment and policy formulation regarding higher education internationalization, which subsequently affects the specific practices of higher education institutions. Similarly, socio-cultural factors impact the attitudes and behaviours of students and teachers, thereby influencing the internationalization strategies of higher education institutions. Moreover, this interaction is also reflected in dynamic feedback mechanisms. The internationalization practices of higher education institutions provide countries and international organizations with experience and data to adjust and optimize their internationalization policies and strategies. Simultaneously, the adjustments made to these policies and strategies also influence the practices of higher education institutions, creating an ongoing cycle of influence.

This framework forms a comprehensive system of internationalization. The internationalization of higher education is a global phenomenon (Egroun-Polak and Hudson, 2014). The quality of higher education in a country and the concentration of world-class universities contribute to higher knowledge production capacity, global technological innovation, comprehensive brand effects, and the mobility of international students worldwide (Altbach, 1991; Perkins and Neumayer, 2014; Hou *et al.*, 2020). Additionally, the scale of higher education is an important factor in a

country's capacity to attract international students. The larger the scale of higher education, the greater the capacity to attract international students (Hou *et al.*, 2020).

Globalization is inherently interconnected with neoliberalism, manifesting itself as a key aspect of this economic and political ideology (Harvey, 2005). In the context of neoliberal marketization and economic globalization, higher education is viewed as an international service, and learning is regarded as a commodity that can be bought by students, and sold by universities. The number of self-funded international students in the UK has significantly increased, and the demand for international higher education continues to grow. This is particularly evident in China, where the number of Chinese students in the UK is expected to reach approximately 72,000 by 2020 (Böhm *et al.*, 2004). According to Giroux (2020, p. 1), the current crisis is not only closely linked to another crisis involving "substantial disparities in wealth, earnings, and influence," but also inseparable from crises stemming from threats to democracy, deficits in quality education, and environmental instability. It is worth noting that these disparities are intertwined with the view that "the COVID-19 pandemic is profoundly interconnected with the politicization of nature, exacerbated by neoliberal globalization's destructive onslaughts on the environment" (Giroux, 2020, p. 2). Furthermore, contemporary society exacerbates the issues of the digital divide and other social rifts. As emphasized by Nussbaum (2010, p.2), "losing ground as nations prefer to pursue short-term profit by the cultivation of the useful and highly applied skills suited to profit-making" highlights the impact of neoliberalism on the social sciences and humanities, revealing how its pursuit of short-term gains undermines the depth and breadth of humanistic and scientific research. In the field of education, the neoliberal economic growth model may particularly exacerbate inequality issues. Nussbaum further points out that if education is primarily based on profitability in the global market, it may lead to a range of negative effects: "Education based mainly on profitability in the global market magnifies parochialism, haste, sloppiness, selfishness, the narrowness of the spirit, in contrast to great rational and imaginative power in democracies, producing a greedy obtuseness and a technically trained

docility that threaten the very life of democracy itself" (Nussbaum, 2010, p. 142). Block (2018) argues that "the notion of the neoliberal citizen discussed above, as this body of scholarship is becoming a common frame in applied linguistics research which focuses on how the English language mediates new ways of being in contemporary societies." In fact, the ability to speak English is seen as a marketable skill and is a worldwide phenomenon, as evidenced by books such as Tan and Rubdy (2008) and Coleman (2011). This phenomenon reflects the high value placed on English language proficiency in the job market. In this global context, the widespread use and popularity of English are closely linked to neoliberalism and globalization, as English has become an essential tool for spreading neoliberalism and globalization worldwide (Holborow, 2012). Under neoliberalism, the understanding of the role of a single language emphasizes the importance of the market in determining language value (Ball, 2012). Educational enterprises provide language courses, teaching materials, and global testing services, and brand their products as a means of adding value to individual skill sets in promotional materials (Block and Gray, 2018). Under neoliberalism, the value of language has been redefined, shifting from a resource for making sense, self-expression, communication, and accessing cultural products, to a more instrumental and economic perspective (Flubacher and Del Percio, 2017).

However, internationalization also presents challenges. The term "international" implies cross-cultural interaction and the introduction of some "foreign" elements. Researchers have discussed various issues associated with internationalization, such as the problem of curriculum colonization/decolonization. English-medium instruction courses may promote Western values that may be inconsistent with local values, leading to unequal cross-cultural interactions (Barnard and Hasim, 2018). Successful internationalization of higher education occurs when international and local students engage in more cross-cultural communication and favourable conditions are created for such interactions, as suggested by Montgomery (2019). Some Western universities provide opportunities for international students to interact

with so-called "native English speakers" to enhance the attractiveness and appeal of Western education (Choudury and Pan, 2014).

Expectations are considered to play a key role in the entire adaptation process and the results of overseas studies, and the gap in expectations may affect the overall learning experience. Yu and Moskal (2019) believe that as the largest group of international students at UK universities, three-quarters of Chinese international students have different personal expectations for international experience in interviews, and personal goals vary from cultural participation to language improvement after arrival in the UK. However, some students with high expectations feel disappointed with their study abroad experience, and the actual problems after arrival bring cultural shocks. In the new environment, students face many challenges. Before the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic, it was not common for Chinese students to receive education from the UK through remote means within China. However, the emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic disrupted this norm and brought about a series of new challenges. In the context of this study, given the unique circumstances of the COVID-19 pandemic, Peters *et al.*, (2020) observed that Chinese students faced more complex challenges in terms of communication with foreigners and the internationalization of education when received online education from the UK within China. The values embedded in online course content may be incongruent with the values of international students, leading to a further sense of marginalization or exclusion among Chinese students, and any language deficit that may exist can exacerbate these challenges.

2.5.1 Motivation of Chinese students to study in the UK

Education has long been recognized as a means to promote individual social mobility, dating back to ancient times. Influenced by Chinese traditional culture, popular Chinese sayings such as "Study hard to achieve success" and "Education is the only way out of poverty" reflect the belief that education is essential for improving social status. Parents believe that education equips their children with professional skills and

secures a better future for them, potentially surpassing their own living conditions (Cortazzi and Jin, 1996). In today's knowledge economy, education plays a crucial role in determining social status. In China, people from all walks of life are willing to invest more in their children's education, viewing it as a tool for upward social mobility or maintaining social standing (Postiglione, 2015). From an individual perspective, Wu (2020) argues that international students possess transnational social capital, which provides them with more opportunities for personal development. Gong et al. (2021) found that international students excel in communication skills, as studying abroad involves constant interaction and engagement with people from different countries. This experience helps international students mature quickly and become more independent. Consequently, international students gain a competitive advantage in future workplaces.

However, the decision to study abroad is a complex process influenced by various factors. When selecting universities in different countries, international students consider the academic standards of the UK English programmes. Rankings and reputation of universities and programmes are of high importance to international students (De *et al.*, 2015). Admission policies of domestic higher education institutions and recognition of overseas degrees by home education institutions also influence international students' choice of destination country (OECD, 2018). Additionally, the cost of tuition is a significant consideration for students and their families, as it constitutes a substantial portion of the total cost of studying abroad (Counsell, 2011). Other factors, such as better career prospects, improvement of English language skills, cultural experiences, and the duration of study, may also influence the decisions of international students (Counsell, 2011).

Furthermore, the British education system offers relatively shorter programme durations, with undergraduate programmes typically lasting three years and master's programmes lasting one year. Compared to education systems in other countries, the British system is more compact, saving time and expenditure on tuition fees. Wu's

(2014) study on the motivations of Chinese mainland students pursuing master's degrees abroad found that the two most influential factors in choosing British education were high-quality programmes and the length and accessibility of postgraduate programmes.

2.5.2 Common Issues for Chinese Students Studying Abroad

Chinese students, like other international students studying in the UK, face various academic, social, and psychological challenges. Research reveals that Chinese international students are often subjected to unfavourable stereotypes, such as being perceived as passive learners with lower classroom engagement (Wu, 2015; Ruble and Zhang, 2013). They may also struggle with lecturers' accents and comprehension of course content (Dong and Tian, 2009). Delivering oral presentations is another common challenge (Li, 2018). Additionally, Chinese students are sometimes stereotyped as rote learners and "unessential thinkers" (Liyanage, Walker and Shokouhi, 2021). These perceptions often stem from long-standing educational traditions in China, influenced by Confucianism, which emphasizes respect for authority and concern for "face" The concept of "face," as defined by Hu (1944), is a social construct central to interpersonal interactions, reflecting cultural values of honour, respect, and reciprocity. This emphasis on maintaining "face" shapes how individuals navigate their roles and relationships within a collective society. Li (2023) further highlights that Chinese traditions prioritize collective harmony and social integration, in contrast to Western cultures, which often emphasize individualism and personal achievement. These cultural differences can significantly hinder the development of social networks (Brown, 2010). For Chinese international students, these challenges are compounded by limited social interactions with non-Chinese individuals (Busher, Lewis and Comber, 2016). Often, they are perceived to lack English proficiency and may predominantly form friendships with other Chinese students (Ruble and Zhang, 2013). Such patterns of interaction can hinder cultural exchange and deeper integration into the host environment.

Language proficiency is essential for the academic and social success of international students. Effective English communication skills are particularly important for meaningful social interactions, a key part of adapting to an international student role (Spencer-Oatey *et al.*, 2017). However, the authenticity of language testing is often questioned, as many exams prioritize knowledge and isolated skills over genuine communicative ability (Shohamy, 2008). Memorizing speaking topics or rehearsing answers often fails to reflect real-time, interactive speaking skills (Liu, 2014). Truly effective speaking requires fluency, organizational skills, cultural sensitivity, and adaptability (Bshara and Barahmeh, 2020).

Many Chinese students struggle with oral communication due to an education system focused on listening, reading, and writing, with limited emphasis on speaking. For example, high school English exams rarely include oral components, and the College English Test Band 4 (CET-4) introduced an optional speaking test in 2009 that remains non-mandatory (Xing and Bolden, 2019). This lack of focus on oral proficiency limits students' opportunities to develop real-world speaking skills. The disparity between this educational background and the demands of standardized tests like IELTS and TOEFL is significant. These exams emphasize oral communication, requiring students to think critically, express ideas fluently, and respond spontaneously under time constraints. Cultural factors, such as fear of making mistakes or being judged, further exacerbate these challenges, leading to anxiety and undermining performance in high-stakes testing situations (Xing and Bolden, 2019).

For Chinese students engaged in online oral language learning, these barriers are particularly pronounced. Cross-cultural communication requires not only linguistic competence but also an understanding of cultural norms (Colvin, 2007). The online learning environment, however, often limits opportunities for immersive and interactive communication. Language barriers, including unfamiliar accents, specialized terminology, and rapid speech patterns, further complicate the process (God and Zhang, 2019). In online settings, the absence of non-verbal cues, such as

facial expressions and body language, makes understanding and responding to conversations even more difficult. Technological issues, such as unstable internet connections and audio lag, add to the frustration and fatigue experienced by students. Consequently, these challenges may undermine their confidence in engaging with local speakers in real-life interactions.

The impact of these challenges extends beyond language acquisition. Spencer-Oatey et al. (2017) emphasize that communication difficulties often lead to feelings of isolation and frustration, and can significantly hinder students' social integration. In the context of online learning, this sense of isolation can be exacerbated by the asynchronous and impersonal nature of digital interactions. Without real-time feedback or the warmth of in-person exchanges, students may feel disconnected, further reducing opportunities for cultural exchange and meaningful friendships.

2.5.3 Challenges and opportunities for online learning in China since the COVID-19 pandemic

In 2020, the COVID-19 pandemic presented new opportunities and challenges for "Internet+ Education" in terms of fairness. Some argue that online learning does not help alleviate educational inequality. The same view was pointed out in the OECD Online Learning Report in 2015, stating that with the rapid development of global information technology, although the number of children from disadvantaged families gaining access to the Internet has increased, the gap between advantaged and disadvantaged students in terms of internet use and its effectiveness, known as the "digital divide", not narrowed but rather increased (OECD, 2015).

Taking China's administrative system structure as an example, the entire country is divided into 34 provincial-level administrative regions, including 23 provinces, 5 autonomous regions, 4 municipalities, and 2 special administrative regions (Gov.cn, 2005, n. pag.). There are significant differences in regional economic development among these provinces and cities, resulting in uneven distribution of educational

resources varying levels of network signals and availability of electronic devices in households. A nationwide survey by Zhao *et al.*, (2021) indicated that urban students mainly use various types of computers for online learning (70.62%), while rural students mainly use smartphones (74.98%) for online learning. The survey also revealed that the proportion of rural students facing network issues is 37.63% higher than that of urban students.

As a form of home-based learning, online learning disperses students' daily learning environment from a unified campus environment into different family environments. The differences in family backgrounds will further widen the gap between advantaged groups (usually referring to those with high income) and disadvantaged groups (usually referring to those with low income) in terms of receiving the impact of online learning. Although Chinese children enjoy equal rights to education, the growing social and economic disparities between urban and rural areas will lead to differences in educational levels (Guo *et al.*, 2019). Education development in China: Education return, quality, and equity. *Sustainability*, 11(13), p.3750.). For example, Mseleku (2020) referred to Ronnie *et al.* (2020) and found that in low-income families, students do not have a private learning space, making it difficult for them to learn online without disturbances. Therefore, home learning becomes challenging for this disadvantaged student group.

As of June 2020, according to the 46th China Internet Development Statistics Report, the number of Chinese internet users reached 940 million, an increase of 36.25 million from March 2020, with an internet penetration rate of 67.0%, an increase of 2.5 percentage points from March 2020. The number of online education users in China reached 381 million, accounting for 40.5% of the total. However, compared to China's total population, the scale of non-internet users in China is still 463 million, of which 43.8% are non-internet users in urban areas and 56.2% are non-internet users in rural areas. Non-internet users refer to individuals who have not registered for or used internet services, and non-internet users are still mainly from rural areas (CNNIC,

2020). Based on this background, Mishra, Gupta, and Shree (2020) stated in their research that the current experience of students participating in online learning can be described as somewhat unstable and objective. This is because some schools have not yet provided good conditions for remote students to access the internet, which may result in some students being unable to attend classes remotely. In rural areas of China, students may have difficulty connecting to the internet due to issues such as network latency. The instability of the online learning experience refers to the various technical and logistical challenges that students may face when accessing educational content remotely. One significant issue is the inconsistent availability and quality of internet connectivity, especially in rural or remote areas with limited infrastructure. For example, in certain parts of China, students might encounter network latency, which is the delay in data transmission over a network. This can lead to slow loading times for online resources, interrupted video streams, and dropped connections, all of which can seriously disrupt the learning process.

On the other hand, a significant segment of society believes that the utilization of the Internet has a positive impact on students' daily academic pursuits, particularly benefiting those from underserved communities. They argue that the internet serves as a gateway to limitless information and resources, which are crucial for expanding students' knowledge base and skill sets. Additionally, several empirical studies conducted by renowned scholars have provided compelling evidence to suggest that the Internet serves as a medium for expanding students' social networks, fostering diverse interactions, and facilitating their participation in a wide array of public and extracurricular activities. For example, a study conducted by Fang (2019) emphasizes that the Internet enhances students' cognitive abilities by exposing them to a plethora of ideas, perspectives, and cultures. This exposure not only broadens their horizons but also aids in developing their essential thinking and analytical skills. Furthermore, Liu (2018) argues that the Internet promotes students' learning abilities by providing easy access to educational materials, online tutorials, and interactive platforms that encourage self-directed learning and collaboration. Moreover, the Internet also plays a

pivotal role in bridging the educational gap between advantaged and disadvantaged students. It offers disadvantaged students an equal opportunity to access high-quality educational resources and tools, which were previously inaccessible to them due to financial or geographical constraints. By harnessing the power of the internet, these students can supplement their classroom learning, seek additional guidance and support, and engage in meaningful discussions with peers and mentors, thereby enhancing their overall academic performance and prospects.

Xie, Siau, and Nah (2020) discussed the benefits for vulnerable groups and individuals with disabilities, stating that through the Internet, they can access many free high-quality educational resources from around the world, which not only reduces their financial burden but also provides them with more opportunities to improve their abilities, contributing to breaking the vicious cycle of poverty in the future. Moreover, for individuals with disabilities, online education provides a convenient and adaptable learning method, thus achieving educational accessibility. In addition to publicly available learning resources and free online learning platforms, universities also provide economic assistance to students who cannot access sufficient high-quality internet or have inconsistent internet speeds. Some teachers choose to pre-record course content and upload it to the school's website to provide lecture replays and various course materials for students (Zhang *et al.*, 2020). Therefore, it can be said that online education has alleviated to some extent the issue of unequal distribution of educational resources.

2.6 Challenges and opportunities for education in the UK since the COVID-19 pandemic

Educational institutions at all levels (preschool, primary, secondary, and tertiary) in 188 countries were closed in 2020, affecting over 91% of the global student population (UNESCO, 2020). Universities in the UK closed from March 16, and face-to-face teaching was advised against by the government. Universities transferred all teaching

activities online and established communication platforms such as webpages and email flows to keep students informed of the evolving situation. Most higher education institutions in the UK start their academic year in August or September, with the cessation of face-to-face teaching occurring in the second or third semester. Educators were forced to quickly find solutions to many challenges, with some transitioning to online delivery within a matter of days. This unforeseen change prevented students from physically travelling to the UK. However, online learning effectively resolved this issue by overcoming geographical barriers. The government's education department issued guidance for students and educators (DES, 2020; GOV.UK, 2020a, b).

Despite the COVID-19 pandemic, data on international student enrollment in the UK was encouraging. The number of new international students (those starting their courses) for the 2020/21 academic year reached a record high, with a 4% increase compared to the previous year. Two main factors contributed to this growth. Firstly, many students studying at UK universities switched to remote learning (HESA, 2022), eliminating the need for a visa to enter the UK. Some participants in this study were also affected by this policy, receiving education from UK institutions while physically located in China. Secondly, Alstadsæter et al. (2020) found that the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic in Norway was greater on financially vulnerable groups, including parents with young children. Research by Zheng, Wu, and Zhao (2022) indicated that nearly 50% of university students have average or no confidence in employment, and 73.32% of university students believe that the current COVID-19 employment situation is not optimistic or average. The lack of confidence in employment among university students and the strong sense of crisis in the employment situation is also closely related to the heavy blow to the global economy by COVID-19. Economic downturn leads to a sluggish job market, normal job interviews are often obstructed, it is difficult for university students to study abroad, and internal job competition intensifies (Wang and Zhang, 2022). According to Hillman (2020), "Economic recessions often mean people want more education

because other choices - underemployment or unemployment - are worse, and having more skills can protect you from the recession." This statement underscores the importance of education in times of economic uncertainty and highlights the role it plays in providing a refuge from the adverse effects of a recessing economy.

Research consistently finds that international students have a positive impact on the UK economy. The major economic impact on students comes from their consumption in the UK, including tuition fees, accommodation, living expenses, and travel. Recent studies on the economic impact of international students have focused on *export earnings*: the expenditure on goods and services in the UK using funds brought from overseas (Walsh, 2022).

However, there were also many challenges faced by students during the COVID-19 pandemic in the UK. Concerns about the psychological impact of the pandemic on the general population arose early on (Holmes *et al.*, 2020), and for university students, and perhaps even more for international students, who were effectively "trapped" in a foreign country, the COVID-19 pandemic brought specific challenges. These challenges included the transition of more learning and support services online, with many students finding it difficult to effectively engage in them (Rapanta *et al.*, 2020), leading to increased anxiety and concerns about academic performance and long-term employability (Sundarasan *et al.*, 2020). Other impacts include the cancellation of study exchanges and graduation ceremonies, loss of part-time jobs, and increased uncertainty in career choices. Lockdowns and social distancing measures also limited opportunities for social activities, leading to increased reliance on social media, and social isolation that may result in long-term feelings of loneliness (Shah *et al.*, 2020). According to a survey by Chen and Lucock (2022), university students have higher levels of anxiety and depression in general. The survey also showed relatively low levels of resilience among university students, which they attributed to the reduced opportunities for engaging in beneficial coping strategies and activities due to restrictions and during the COVID-19 pandemic, rather than being a persistent

personality trait. While some students have a positive attitude towards online learning and find online resources useful (Ullah, Khan and Khan, 2017), according to the study by McNulty et al. (2006), the perceived usefulness of online resources for individual students depends on their personal preferences, making the transition to remote learning more challenging for some student groups.

2.7 Emergency Remote Learning

Emergency Remote Learning (ERL) refers to the rapid and temporary transition from in-person instruction to remote learning in response to a crisis, such as the COVID-19 pandemic. This section explores the definition, challenges, and implications of ERL.

The COVID-19 pandemic in 2020 necessitated a rapid and unprecedented global shift from traditional face-to-face education to digital platforms worldwide. To ensure educational continuity amidst the public health crisis, many institutions adopted ERL, a temporary instructional strategy designed to mitigate learning disruptions (Barbour *et al.*, 2020; Wang *et al.*, 2024). Unlike pre-planned online learning environments, ERL was a reactive measure implemented hastily, often within days or weeks, with the primary objective of keeping students engaged during a crisis (Bozkurt and Sharma, 2020), which is in the COVID-19 pandemic. While ERL during the COVID-19 pandemic ensured the continuity of education in a time of crisis, it also underscored the urgent need for enhanced digital infrastructure and better preparedness for future emergencies. Barbour et al. (2020) describe ERL as a rapid, stopgap solution designed to prevent educational disruption, unlike online learning, which is carefully planned over several months. While online learning prioritizes student engagement, interactive learning, and structured content, ERL often lacks these components due to its emergency nature (Wang *et al.*, 2024). The key intent of ERL is to maintain educational continuity during a crisis, not to create a fully developed online learning ecosystem.

Although ERL was far from an ideal solution to the challenges posed by the COVID-19 pandemic, it did offer several notable advantages during this period (Barbour *et al.*, 2020). Its most significant benefit was minimizing educational disruption during global lockdowns, enabling students to continue their studies despite school and university closures. Moreover, ERL introduced the widespread use of digital tools and platforms, which many institutions had previously underutilized, facilitating the development of new digital skills among both teachers and students (Van *et al.*, 2020). By utilizing synchronous (real-time video conferences) and asynchronous (pre-recorded lectures and materials) methods, ERL provided flexibility in learning, allowing students to progress at their own pace while maintaining some level of interaction with peers and teachers (Wang *et al.*, 2024).

The rapid implementation of ERL during the COVID-19 pandemic revealed numerous challenges in the areas of technology, pedagogy, and social interaction, as ERL exposed significant inequalities in access to technology. Ferri, Grifoni and Guzzo (2020) found that students, particularly those in rural or under-resourced areas, faced difficulties due to unreliable internet connections and a lack of digital devices, limiting their ability to participate fully in online learning. Many educators were unprepared for the transition to digital platforms, lacking the necessary skills to design and deliver effective online instruction. Lawanto *et al.* (2022) observed that the shift from face-to-face teaching to online platforms resulted in some unstructured and poorly designed educational interactions, with some reduction in student motivation and increasing anxiety and isolation. ERL also led to a sharp decline in social interaction between students and teachers. Ferri *et al.* (2020) highlighted that some students, especially those without adequate physical learning spaces at home, struggled with feelings of isolation and a lack of support, as parents were often preoccupied with their own remote work responsibilities. This absence of social presence during taught sessions heightened emotional challenges, such as anxiety and uncertainty (Lawanto *et al.*, 2022). Student motivation appeared to be closely linked to emotional engagement during ERL. In the absence of timely feedback from teachers

or meaningful interactions with peers, some students reported feelings of frustration, anxiety, and loneliness, which seemed to affect their ability to focus and engage fully in their studies (Ferri *et al.*, 2020). This reduced emotional engagement, therefore, may have contributed to a decline in motivation for some learners. Thus, these challenges could have played a role in diminishing learning outcomes, underscoring the importance of emotional support in remote learning contexts.

2.8 Differences Between ERL and Online Learning

Online learning typically involves meticulous planning over several months. Educators and instructional designers collaborate to create a structured learning environment that prioritizes student engagement, meaningful interaction, and well-organized content, ensuring an effective and manageable learning experience (Barbour *et al.*, 2020). In contrast, ERL is a crisis-response measure implemented quickly to avoid educational disruption. This lack of preparation often results in lower-quality education, fewer opportunities for interaction, and diminished engagement (Bozkurt and Sharma, 2020). The challenges seen in ERL, such as technological inequalities and inadequate pedagogical training, are less common in traditional online learning environments, where these issues are addressed during the design phase. For example, in general, online courses are structured to facilitate regular interaction through discussion forums, group projects, and assessments, while ERL often lacks such interactive elements due to its reactive nature (Van *et al.*, 2020). As a researcher, I am aware of these distinctions and their potential implications, striving to account for the unique limitations and contextual factors of ERL when examining its impact on student engagement and learning outcomes.

2.9 Conclusion

This chapter introduced the historical, educational, and socio-cultural background of English education in China, online learning, the internationalisation of higher

education for Chinese students studying in the UK, as well as Emergency Remote Learning and the differences between ERL and online learning. Research indicates that Chinese students faced greater challenges in online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic compared to their experiences with traditional in-person education before the COVID-19 pandemic.

Therefore, the next chapter will review the literature in this area to examine current research and deepen the understanding of strategies for enhancing oral language skills among Chinese international students. This will include an emphasis on introducing relevant learning theories, exploring effective online learning approaches, and analyzing the conceptual processes underpinning language acquisition, which form the foundation of this study.

Chapter 3: Literature Review

3.1 Introduction

This chapter reviews key literature on learning, online learning, and language acquisition, drawing from various fields. The goal of the literature review is to uncover the factors that influence the learning motivation of Chinese students and to understand the current role of online learning in English language acquisition specifically for Chinese international students who study at UK universities. It also aims to identify the challenges of online learning, considering the unique circumstances of COVID-19. Additionally, this study explores language acquisition among Chinese international students who participate in online learning. These literature and theoretical foundations guide the research methodology for this study.

3.2 Different Ways of Learning

Ways of learning have long been a central topic in psychology and education. Researchers have developed numerous theories to explain what learning is, how

humans learn, and how they acquire and apply knowledge and skills. Over time, the understanding of learning has evolved from speculative ideas to scientific inquiry, giving rise to various learning theories. Learning is recognized as a core human behaviour (Olasina, 2019). Modern educational research increasingly leans towards qualitative methods, reflecting a deeper appreciation for the complex and multifaceted nature of the learning process (Thelwall and Nevill, 2021).

With the widespread use of the internet, learning is now defined as a process in which learners' cognitive or behavioural abilities undergo sustained changes to adapt to specific environmental changes (Ben-Eliyahu, 2021). The internet has made learning materials easily accessible to anyone (Engelbrecht, Llinares and Borba, 2020).

In this study, the focus of learning is on the development of oral English skills entails the application of knowledge, which in turn guides the development of other skills for applying that knowledge. It is important to note that this study examines learning at a micro-level, specifically focusing on the learning activities of Chinese international students in the UK during the COVID-19 period, particularly in oral language learning activities. Based on this, this chapter then reviews the humanistic and constructivist learning theories and self-directed learning of the 20th century to deepen our understanding of learning.

3.2.1 Humanistic Learning Approaches

Humanistic learning theory is relevant to this study because its emphasis on active participation, learner-centred approaches, and the role of emotions aligns closely with the challenges and strategies for improving oral language skills among Chinese international students in online learning environments. Understanding learners as active meaning-makers and considering their individual interests and emotions can provide insights into designing more effective, engaging online language-learning experiences. For example, Roger's (1970) focus on experiential and self-directed learning supports the idea that oral language development requires not only structured

instruction but also opportunities for personalized, meaningful, and contextually relevant practice, which is particularly important in remote learning settings (Alamri *et al.*, 2020).

The theories developed from Maslow's (1943) hierarchy of needs highlight the role of a supportive environment for optimal learning, addressing both cognitive and emotional needs (Navy, 2020). Moskowitz (1978) extended humanistic principles to language teaching, promoting self-actualization and autonomy, while Stevick (1996) emphasized a communicative, student-centred approach, where balanced teacher control and student agency enhance learning outcomes.

Humanistic principles hold significant value in modern foreign language teaching, particularly as second language acquisition research increasingly emphasizes learner-teacher interactions (Eraldemir-Tuyan, 2019). In the context of online learning, the reduction in physical interaction may significantly impact students' social relationships and mental well-being. This aligns with findings around declining mental health among Chinese students during the COVID-19 pandemic, driven by stressors such as loneliness, insecurity, academic concerns, and a lack of face-to-face support (Cao *et al.*, 2020; Son *et al.*, 2020). Zheng, Wu and Zhao (2022) observe that restricted interactions in online learning environments can negatively affect emotional well-being and engagement. Similarly, Li *et al.* (2021) report that teachers noted a decline in student attention and participation in online classes. These challenges highlight the importance of enhancing online oral language proficiency for Chinese international students during the COVID-19 pandemic by facilitating meaningful communication where interactions are perceived as worthwhile, validated, and encouraging active participation. Addressing these aspects is essential, as doing so can provide valuable insights into overcoming engagement and motivation barriers, ultimately improving their overall learning experiences in online settings.

3.2.2 Constructivist Learning Theory

Constructivist learning theory emphasizes that knowledge is actively constructed by individuals through interactions with their environment, rather than simply transmitted by teachers. This theory identifies key elements in learning environments: context, collaboration, conversation, and resources. Piaget (1955) laid the groundwork for constructivism, focusing on learners' active role and creativity in building knowledge. Piaget's theory, later refined in his 1970 work on "genetic epistemology," proposed that knowledge is constructed through stages, involving assimilation, adaptation, and innovation. Rathee and Islam (2016) further elaborate on Piaget's four developmental stages, where cognitive tasks progressively evolve with environmental interactions.

Vygotsky (1978) emphasized social constructivism, arguing that knowledge is co-constructed through social interaction, language, and cultural context. His concept of the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) highlights how learning occurs when learners work within their developmental capacity, with teacher support gradually decreasing as students gain independence, a process known as scaffolding. Bruner (1960) viewed learning as an active process, proposing that any subject can be taught in an accessible form at any developmental stage. He emphasized discovery learning, where students engage in learning by exploring and solving problems, enhancing critical thinking and problem-solving skills.

In constructivist classrooms, students are encouraged to take responsibility for learning through problem-solving, experiential learning, and peer collaboration (Williams and Burden, 1997; Diep, 2019). Teachers play a vital role by interacting, challenging students' thinking, and designing effective questions that build on prior knowledge to enhance motivation (Sepulveda-Escobar and Morrison, 2020).

In summary, constructivist learning theory highlights the active construction of knowledge through meaningful engagement and interaction, providing valuable insight for designing effective, student-centred learning environments. The emphasis on active knowledge construction, meaningful interaction, and scaffolded support

provides a valuable framework for exploring how Chinese international students develop oral language skills in virtual environments, where traditional face-to-face interactions are limited, and in which the skills explored in constructivist learning can be helpful to foster self-directed learning, critical thinking, and adaptive communication strategies essential for navigating online language challenges.

3.2.3 English Language Teaching

Constructivist principles advocate for a transition towards more interactive and communicative methodologies in English Language Teaching (ELT), with a notable emphasis on approaches like Communicative Language Teaching (CLT). Rooted in constructivist theory, ELT suggests that rather than simply transmitting knowledge, teachers should facilitate the creation of knowledge among students through diverse methods. This approach aims to boost students' English proficiency and their overall learning capacity (Xie and Zhang, 2012). The essence of CLT theory is that the practice of language skills and engagement in communicative activities are fundamental to learning and applying language effectively (James, Mahamud and Ni-Ana, 2024). Moss and Ross-Feldman (2003) argue that all tasks involving speaking and listening necessitate communication and that communicative tasks are crucial for overcoming obstacles, acquiring information, articulating thoughts, and gaining cultural insights. Furthermore, Jeyasala (2014) underscores the importance of teachers fostering students' communicative abilities by offering ample opportunities for interaction and participation in speaking activities, thereby improving their proficiency in the target language.

This perspective is important for this study as it indicates that current modes of online learning have certain limitations. For example, learning activities that involve motor skills or require hands-on abilities may have limited situational and interactive aspects in online learning. Online platforms may not always provide the immediate or nuanced oral feedback that face-to-face interaction offers. This could hinder the development of pronunciation, intonation, and fluency (Leon, 2023). Learners might

encounter fewer opportunities to engage in spontaneous verbal exchanges, which are crucial for practising conversational skills and learning how to navigate through English dialogues and negotiations (Peimani and Kamalipour, 2021).

Lave and Wenger's (1991) views enhance the theoretical meaning of constructivism. They argue that learning should not be confined to transmitting abstract, decontextualized knowledge. Instead, it should be a social process where knowledge is organized collaboratively. This perspective highlights two crucial aspects of constructivism: cooperative learning and social learning. In cooperative learning, learners build knowledge by collaboratively solving problems and sharing resources and perspectives. In social learning, learners gain new knowledge and skills by participating in social activities, observing, and practising. Thus, foreign language learning from the constructivist perspective goes beyond language instruction.

It highlights the process by which learners build and grasp the meaning of language within authentic social contexts, facilitated by cooperation and interaction, as mentioned in the previously discussed ELT theories. This learner-centred, interaction-based learning philosophy greatly aids in enhancing foreign language teaching effectiveness and fostering learners' holistic development.

Blended learning provides a new organization of learning opportunities for electronic, online spaces, and ICT enhancements. As the importance and direction of knowledge dissemination continue to evolve, the process of knowledge construction by students under constructivist educational theory has received increasing attention. This theory emphasizes the importance of student engagement, applicability to the real world, and interactive learning. Scrivener (2005) emphasizes the individualized characteristics and diversity of learners. Specifically, it notes that learners differ in their skills, abilities, levels of knowledge, language proficiency, beliefs, and past learning experiences. Moreover, learners exhibit individual differences in their learning styles, preferences for teaching methods, the pace of learning, topics of interest, sense of humour, types of motivation, as well as in their ability to concentrate and

susceptibility to distraction. Therefore, the educational process should take into account the uniqueness and personalized needs of each learner. Emphasizing learner ownership and participation is often associated with 21st-century learning skills.

3.2.4 Task-Based Language Teaching

Scrivener (2005) proposed a definition of "task" and its application in language learning. He defines a task as an activity that learners engage in, which requires them to use or process language to achieve a specific outcome. He further notes that these outcomes might be related to the use of language in the real world, such as ordering food in a restaurant through role-play or designed for learning purposes, like completing a gap-fill exercise. Based on language teaching activities, it can be considered either a task or "a situational grammar exercise" (Ellis, 2009, p. 223). Long (2016) also states, "based on such a miscellany of activities, skills, modalities, pedagogic procedures, language, conversational moves, and cognitive processes, it would be impossible to define task or task type" (p. 5).

In the field of foreign language teaching, Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) is often seen as a constructivist learning method, referring to the use of tasks as the core unit of planning and instruction in language teaching. It has been defined as an approach to language education in which students are given functional tasks that invite them to focus primarily on meaning exchange and to use language for real-world, non-linguistic purposes (Van den Branden, 2016).

TBL refers to tasks performed in the classroom, characterized by: a) goal-oriented, b) content-centered, c) real-world outcomes, and d) using real language to solve real problems (Prahbu, 1990).

Research has confirmed that TBLT supports the most critical aspects of foreign language learning: fluency, accuracy, and complexity (Ellis, 2003). In practice, teachers usually guide language learners to complete meaning-based tasks and

develop accuracy through form-based tasks (Ellis, 2000). Integrating fluency and accuracy into language teaching can ensure a comprehensive learning experience. Meaning-based tasks encourage learners to actively use language, fostering fluency and spontaneity, while form-based tasks help improve their control of the language, thereby enhancing accuracy. This dual approach to teaching allows learners to master the skills necessary for effective communication and gain a deep understanding of language structure, thereby improving their overall language proficiency.

In summary, Constructivism values learners' individual experiences and emphasizes two key outcomes: first, teachers should consider and adapt to the unique thinking patterns and learning styles of each student during the educational process, rather than merely concentrating on delivering standardized subjects and course content (Piaget, 1972; Vygotsky, 1978); the second is that the explanation process is inherently limited by the meanings learners derive from knowledge, which are shaped by the experiences they have gained (Suhendi, Purwarno and Chairani, 2021). During the COVID-19 pandemic, when real-world interactions were significantly limited, TBLT provided opportunities for Chinese international students to practise and develop oral language skills in online environments. This approach is helpful for my study as it offers a practical framework to understand how task-based activities can support effective language learning under such challenging circumstances.

3.2.5 Self-directed learning

Houle (1961) researched the learning motivation of adult learners and proposed the concept of learning orientation, laying the foundation for the theory of self-directed learning. Subsequently, Allen Tough (1966) first proposed the theory of "self-directed learning" (SDL), which emphasizes the active role of learners in the educational process. Knowles (1975) further identified SDL as a developmental process consisting of three core stages: planning, execution and monitoring, and evaluation and reflection. This theory also highlights the importance of learner autonomy and agency, suggesting that learners should actively participate in the learning process, think

critically, solve problems, and continuously enhance their learning abilities through reflection and experience.

Ho and Crookall (1995) believe that autonomous learning is best cultivated in a real environment that is relevant and meaningful to students. Learning responsibility is similar to learning other skills, it requires active participation and practice. Only learners can truly learn, and this learning is obtained through practice. Students must take steps towards autonomous learning and actively exercise autonomy. Hedge (2001) believes that independently planning and assessing one's development entails taking responsibility for one's own learning, which aligns with the learner-centered stance advocated by constructivism. The primary definition of learner autonomy, still considered crucial in describing learner autonomy, is "the ability to take charge of or responsibility for, one's own learning. Godwin-Jones (2019) found that although teachers and students have a positive attitude toward autonomous learning, their understanding of autonomous learning is still insufficient. Teachers are proactive in promoting student autonomy, while students need more guidance and help. In addition, the study found that the misconceptions teachers and students have about autonomous learning may be related to a lack of understanding of the concept of autonomous learning. Enhancing teachers' and students' knowledge and understanding of autonomous learning requires more practice and training.

3.2.6 Online Self-directed Learning

As online learning continues to expand, the relationship between self-directed learning (SDL) and online learning has become a key focus. Researchers emphasize the importance of cultivating SDL skills, which are essential for success in online environments (Morris and Rohs, 2021). Karatas and Arpaci (2021) argue that SDL is critical for individual development in the 21st century. Encouraging learners to actively participate in online learning helps them plan their learning pace and strategies, thereby enhancing their SDL skills (Lai, 2011). Lian et al. (2021) found that online learning environments support SDL by enabling students to pause and replay

videos, use productivity apps, and manage their learning plans. However, challenges such as distractions and a lack of face-to-face supervision may reduce learning efficiency. Despite recognizing the novelty and efficiency of online learning, students often express a preference for face-to-face classes and traditional campus life (Murray *et al.*, 2022).

Social media has shown potential for enhancing interactivity and engagement in language learning, particularly in online education. Sari and Wahyudin (2019) suggest that Instagram can serve as an effective platform to support language teaching in higher education. Its practicality allows for non-classroom learning and greater student engagement, with students reporting that Instagram learning activities are enjoyable and accessible anytime and anywhere. These findings highlight Instagram's potential to complement traditional teaching methods and foster meaningful language use in non-traditional environments. However, further research is needed to examine factors influencing professional learning in English as a foreign language classrooms.

The study environment also plays a critical role in self-directed online learning. Closs, Mahat, and Imms (2022) define the learning environment as the social, physical, psychological, and pedagogical contexts that influence student achievement and attitudes. Flexible classroom arrangements and adjustable furniture promote effective interactions between students and teachers, fostering a dynamic and student-centred approach (Asino and Pulay, 2019). Conversely, unfamiliar or unconventional spaces can lead to discomfort and disorientation (Ramsay *et al.*, 2017). However, achieving this in practice is not always straightforward. Online learning environments often present challenges such as limited access to technology, unstable internet connections, or distractions in home settings, which can hinder the creation of an optimal study environment (Nartiningrum, Novrika, and Arif Nugroho, 2020; Ahmadon, Ghazalli, and Rusli, 2020).

3.3 Online Learning

3.3.1 Definition of Online Learning

Researchers have gathered numerous definitions of online learning from various online resources and written works to study this concept and term. The term "online learning" was not used until 1995. The earliest electronic learning system designed for the American higher education model was the Learning Management System (LMS), which is a globally accessible electronic learning platform. Nowadays, the concept of online learning has evolved to include a wide range of ideas, some of which are similar and referred to by different names such as "distance education," "e-learning," "online learning," and "blended learning" (Sun and Chen, 2016, p. 160). It is important to emphasize that the unified term used in this study is "online learning".

Contrasting with online learning is face-to-face learning. Although the term "face-to-face" is also applicable to certain online learning scenarios, in this research, "face-to-face" refers specifically to learning in the same physical room as other learners and teachers. Face-to-face learning refers to the learning and interaction between teachers and students in a physical environment through traditional classroom teaching methods. In this mode of learning, teachers and students can directly communicate, discuss, and answer questions, and students can engage in real-time interaction and collaboration. In the subsequent sections, the differences between online learning and face-to-face learning, as well as their impact on students' English oral language learning, will be discussed. Before exploring the impact of online learning on the acquisition of English oral skills, it is necessary to define the types of online learning.

3.3.2 Types of Online Learning

Currently, online learning can be divided into three types: synchronous online learning, asynchronous online learning, and blended online learning.

Synchronous online learning: This mode utilizes live teaching tools to create virtual

classrooms and implement one-on-one or one-to-many synchronous online teaching (Li and Oladele, 2021). According to Islam and Mondal (2022), teachers should play five roles in synchronous online teaching through video conferences: the instructional, managerial, technical, communicational, and social roles. Synchronous interaction between teachers and students in online learning brings "personally significant and educationally meaningful outcomes for students" (Vaughan, Cleaveland-Innes and Garrison, 2013, p. 12). Bétrancourt and Benetos (2018) emphasized that synchronous online learning can promote interaction and participation, provide structure for courses and assignments, and create opportunities for students to collaborate with other student groups. However, this mode has some disadvantages. As stated by Skylar (2009, p. 71),

"However, this type of environment requires a set date and time for meeting, and this contradicts the promise of 'anytime, anywhere' learning that online courses have traditionally promoted."

Asynchronous online learning: In this mode, teachers and students are not only separated in space but also in time, meaning that the activities of teaching and learning are temporally and spatially separated. This mode allows for flexible time investment by students, allowing them to manage their time according to their individual learning characteristics and control their learning progress (Smaldino *et al.*, 2008). According to Perveen (2016, p. 22), "Asynchronous environments provide students with readily available material in the form of audio/video lectures, handouts, articles, and PowerPoint presentations. This material is accessible anytime anywhere with an Internet connection." However, some researchers have pointed out that to ensure the smooth implementation of this mode, it is obviously important for teachers to provide clear instructions, headings, and examples for students (Delahunty, 2018). Nevertheless, this mode also has some disadvantages. Dumford and Miller (2018, p. 452) argue that the potential isolation brought about by asynchronous online self-directed learning may be one of the reasons for decreased opportunities for

collaborative learning. They conclude that while online learning seems to have some cognitive advantages, there are also important educational goals and practices, such as social collaboration and participation, that cannot simply be adapted to the online environment. They also mention that the lack of interaction and direct feedback from students in asynchronous online courses is one of the main barriers to the widespread use of online tools.

Blended online learning is an educational approach that combines online learning with traditional face-to-face classroom teaching, giving students a degree of control over time, location, and learning pace (Saboowala and Manghirmalani Mishra, 2021; Peimani and Kamalipour, 2021). By integrating synchronous and asynchronous elements, blended learning allows students to engage in real-time interaction during synchronous classes and access pre-recorded videos and course materials at their convenience through asynchronous learning, thereby enhancing engagement and fostering deep learning (Bond *et al.*, 2021). Research shows that blended learning is particularly effective in reducing cognitive load, enabling novice learners to absorb knowledge more effectively (Ashraf *et al.*, 2021; Chiu, 2021).

During the COVID-19 pandemic, the use of blended learning expanded rapidly, becoming a flexible means for the education sector to address uncertainties while further promoting students' independent learning (Bond *et al.*, 2021). Despite the numerous advantages of blended learning, challenges remain, particularly in terms of student interaction and small-group collaboration, which are especially important in disciplines that rely heavily on teamwork (Baptista *et al.*, 2021).

The successful implementation of blended learning depends on institutional support, adequate teacher training, and the effective use of technological resources (Zhang and Zhu, 2022). Studies indicate that a well-supported blended learning model can effectively enhance student satisfaction, academic performance, and sense of community, making it a widely preferred teaching model in the post-pandemic era (Means and Neisler, 2020; Agarwal *et al.*, 2021).

Synchronous and asynchronous learning each offer distinct advantages and limitations, making them suitable for different learning needs and contexts. Synchronous learning encourages real-time interaction and engagement but requires scheduled meeting times, which can limit flexibility (Dailey-Hebert, 2018). Conversely, asynchronous learning provides students with the flexibility to learn at their own pace but may lead to feelings of isolation and reduced collaboration (Dumford and Miller, 2018). To address these challenges, a combination of synchronous and asynchronous models is often recommended to enhance learning outcomes and engagement. As Xie, Liu, Bhairma, and Shim (2018) note, a blend of synchronous and asynchronous models could be well-suited to online learning, particularly for Chinese students. This approach combines the flexibility of asynchronous learning, allowing students to study at their own pace and accommodate time zone differences, with the interactive benefits of synchronous sessions, which foster real-time engagement and a sense of community.

When designing online learning environments, it is essential for educators to consider factors such as instructional goals, student preferences, available resources, and technological conditions to create an effective and responsive approach. This study will examine whether participants perceive blended learning (a combination of synchronous and asynchronous methods) as effective for developing oral language skills. Furthermore, it will explore how balancing these approaches influences student engagement and collaboration, offering valuable insights into optimizing online learning experiences for Chinese international students.

3.3.3 Interactivity in the online classroom

Interaction, a concept introduced by social psychology into the field of education, refers to the various forms of interaction and influence between individuals in a social environment. Ellis (2019) summarized the importance of specific interaction processes in a sociocultural context, emphasizing the way of learning language through participating in the processing of language experiences. In this process, individuals

achieve the expected learning outcomes by communicating intentions, concepts, and meanings with others. According to Salim (2023), interaction requires a medium, typically language, but also includes non-verbal forms such as emotions and attitudes. In the educational context, classroom interaction specifically refers to the interaction between teachers and students in the classroom, especially language interaction and English interaction. This covers activities where teachers and students communicate, discuss, ask and answer questions using language, especially in English teaching environments, where such interaction becomes a key pathway to promote the development of students' English language skills. However, virtual online learning presents unique challenges compared to traditional physical classrooms. Learners and teachers are physically separated, and the timing of communication and interaction is reduced, leading to changes in the forms of interaction.

Both synchronous and asynchronous online learning creates relatively independent and virtual learning spaces in terms of time and space. This poses challenges for interactive teaching and learning. Nonetheless, interaction plays a significant role in language teaching and learning. In English language teaching, oral proficiency requires not only knowledge output but also extensive training and activities, particularly in classroom interaction and social interaction for practice and improvement, ultimately promoting socialization (Rajendran and Yunus, 2021).

A study by Wang and Zhu (2019) explored students' attitudes towards online learning and found that students often have lower enthusiasm for classroom participation, interaction with teachers, and interaction with peers compared to traditional face-to-face courses. The phenomena mentioned above can find reference and inspiration in the studies by Garcia (2009) and Canagarajah (2013) discussed in section 3.4.3 below.

3.4 Second Language Acquisition

Language acquisition extends beyond the conscious learning of factual knowledge – it

is a skill, not simply a collection of knowledge. Chomsky, considered a founder of modern linguistics, shifted the focus of linguistic research from external structure to internal cognitive mechanisms. He viewed language as an innate cognitive ability, not just a symbolic system (Touqir, Nasir and Pervez, 2022).

Chomsky introduced key concepts like linguistic competence, universal grammar, and transformational generative grammar. He emphasized that humans are born with the potential to learn language and saw it as a reflection of the human mind, not merely a communication tool.

Observations show that children start producing their first word around 12 months of age, quickly mastering more vocabulary thereafter. From 18 to 30 months, their language learning rate increases, and they begin to learn two-word structures and sentences. This pattern indicates a natural human ability to learn language.

Chomsky's theoretical models, which include phrase structure rules, transformational rules, and morphophonemic rules, reveal the complex process of language creation (Chomsky, 1965). His contributions have not only reshaped our understanding of language's nature but also provided new frameworks and methods for linguistic research.

Additionally, linguists such as Krashen and Ellis provide valuable insights into understanding language acquisition and emphasize the importance of integrating learners' natural acquisition processes, guiding awareness, and facilitating interaction in language teaching. Swain (2006) introduces the term "languaging" to describe the process of negotiating and constructing meaning in language learning. According to Swain, "languaging" is a cognitive process where learners produce meaningful output, perceive, create, and experience life. This suggests that language learning involves deeper cognitive and affective processes, rather than mere memorization and imitation.

The rise of English as a global language began in the 17th century (Crystal, 2003). But it has increased significantly in the past 40 years as a result of globalization (as opposed to imperialism, colonisation and slavery in previous centuries). The field of English is closely related to humanities, encompassing linguistics, education, philosophy, psychology, sociology, and anthropology, making it an interdisciplinary subject (Ilić and Lopičić, 2021). When learning English, students need to not only acquire language knowledge but also understand the culture, history, and social context of English-speaking countries. This naturally connects English teaching with other disciplinary fields (Risager, 2021). Therefore, integrating English teaching with other disciplines provides students with more opportunities for practice and multiple perspectives, promoting their holistic development. In this study, the discussion of language acquisition specifically refers to English, and the learners mentioned are Chinese international students whose native language is Mandarin Chinese.

3.4.1 Krashen

In the late 1970s and early 1980s, Krashen proposed the "Monitor Hypotheses" which laid the foundation for his theory of second language acquisition. This theory consists of five basic hypotheses: the acquisition-learning hypothesis, the input hypothesis, the monitor hypothesis, the affective filter hypothesis, and the natural order hypothesis.

The acquisition-learning hypothesis, proposed in 1977, states that acquisition and learning can occur simultaneously during instructional activities. Acquisition refers to the unconscious acquisition of language by learners, similar to how they acquire their first language, while learning refers to learners consciously learning the rules and forms of the second language (Spada and Lightbown, 2019).

The input hypothesis is based on the core theory of "i+1" input, which explains how learners acquire language and develop language proficiency. "i" represents the learners' current level of language knowledge, while "i+1" represents language materials slightly above the learners' current level. When learners are exposed to

language input slightly above their current level, it facilitates language learning. Adequate and varied language input is crucial for language learning (Spada and Lightbown, 2019).

The monitor hypothesis suggests that learners need to monitor and edit their language production based on the language rules they have acquired through acquisition and learning (Schutz, 2007). According to Krashen's monitor hypothesis, individuals who acquire a language can use it fluently and effortlessly, while those who learn a language can only apply the rules of the language for self-monitoring during language production. In other words, Krashen emphasizes that only acquisition can directly promote the development of second language proficiency, stating that "language is acquired, not learned," and that learned knowledge only serves as a monitor during language output (Broad, 2020).

The affective filter hypothesis emphasizes the role of emotions in language acquisition (Krashen and Terrell, 1983). The ability of learners to effectively acquire language is influenced by their emotional state. Positive emotions can enhance language learning and production, while negative emotions can hinder language production (Wang, Wang and Shi, 2022). Motivation, personality, and emotions can affect the affective filter, which needs to be appropriately regulated to facilitate language acquisition (Krashen, 1985). Although Krashen's original publication was some time ago, the principles of his work provide valuable insights into understanding and addressing the emotional and psychological challenges faced by learners in online settings.

The natural order hypothesis suggests that when acquiring a second language, learners gradually master different aspects of the language in a certain order. This order is not arbitrary but is influenced by the inherent logic and rules of the language itself (Zafar, 2009). An important point of the natural order hypothesis is that learners' language development proceeds in stages. These stages are usually progressive, with each preceding stage forming the foundation for the next stage. For example, in oral

language acquisition, students may initially speak in single-word utterances, gradually forming sentences, and then progressing from sentences to dialogues.

In a certain online learning environment, students may experience feelings of loneliness, and helplessness, or face challenges with time management, which can lead to anxiety and negatively impact their learning outcomes (Besser, Flett and Zeigler-Hill, 2022; Mohammed *et al.*, 2022). Students who lack confidence or feel anxious may also be reluctant to actively participate in online discussions or interactions, thereby reducing their opportunities for social learning. In this context, Krashen's theory of second language acquisition offers valuable insights for studying the development of Chinese students' online oral language skills during the COVID-19 pandemic. Krashen's affective filter hypothesis highlights the role of emotions in language acquisition, suggesting that positive emotions facilitate language learning, whereas negative emotions can become obstacles. Additionally, his input hypothesis and monitor hypothesis further underscore the importance of effective input and self-monitoring in oral language development. Understanding and applying Krashen's theory allows me to better analyze and address the emotional and psychological challenges faced by Chinese students in their online oral language learning during the pandemic.

3.4.2 Ellis

Ellis (1997) described the process and outcomes of second language acquisition within the framework of pragmatics theory. The goal is to demonstrate that language acquisition reflects the way language is used. He argues against the belief that language learning is a passive process of absorbing one-way input. Instead, Ellis builds and develops Krashen's theory and emphasizes the role of consciousness in the transformative process. Additionally, he identifies language transfer errors in second language acquisition as a negative transfer from the first language. According to the perspectives of behaviourist theory, one of the main obstacles in the learning process arises from the disruption of prior knowledge. Ellis (1994) highlighted that this

disruption is particularly noticeable when learning a second language. Learners often inadvertently infuse characteristics and rules of their native language into the second language system they are studying. Ellis (1994) further explained the concept of "L1 transfer". This refers to the instance when learners integrate aspects of their native language while trying to establish a second language knowledge system.

The concept of language transfer dates to the 1950s and 1960s, during the era of behaviourism. Behaviourist psychologists then believed that language learning was predominantly through imitation and habit formation. They theorized that prior knowledge, particularly knowledge of one's native language, and any other languages learned before the target language, would influence the learning of a new language. The fundamental idea of language transfer was based on behaviourism's perspective of language learning as a process of forming habits. As such, when learning a new language, learners tend to apply the language habits they've already developed in their native language. These habits can either enable or hinder new language learning, depending on the similarities or differences between the native language and the target language. Therefore, learners must work to overcome the interference of native language habits to better grasp the characteristics and rules of the target language.

Furthermore, Ellis (1988) highlights the significant role of the environment in language acquisition. The environment provides support in terms of language input, opportunities for interaction, cultural background, as well as learning motivation and attitudes. Ellis also emphasizes the importance of teachers not only being communicative partners for learners but also receiving appropriate training to enhance their skills and draw learners' attention to language forms (Ellis, Basturkmen and Loewen, 2002).

Rod Ellis is also an advocate of Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT). In their book, Ellis *et al.*, (2020) argue that this approach encourages students to learn language through meaningful tasks, focusing on the practical use and communicative functions of language. This approach aims to improve students' communicative and practical

language skills.

In his influential article, Long (1985) detailed the innovative method of TBLT. He emphasized that TBLT centres around utilizing real, natural language materials, with students actively using the target language to complete tasks having practical and communicative value. This approach breaks away from traditional language teaching methods that rely solely on textbooks and mechanical exercises, shifting the focus to nurturing practical language skills. Long attributed the effectiveness of TBLT to the diverse learning situations it creates, which are closely related to students' daily lives, including participants in this study. This makes language learning more engaging and practical. Through task designs relevant to everyday life, TBLT provides numerous opportunities for students to practice and improve their communicative skills. In such a learning environment, students not only acquire language knowledge but also learn to communicate effectively in the real world using the language they've studied. This task-oriented teaching method, grounded in real language materials, significantly enhances students' practical language skills and promotes holistic language learning.

In the context of this research undertaken during the COVID-19 pandemic, Ellis's theory is particularly relevant and provides valuable support for studying Chinese students' online oral language skills during the COVID-19 pandemic. His emphasis on the active, cognitive process of language acquisition and the importance of the learning environment highlights the unique challenges and needs of Chinese students accessing learning from remote settings. Additionally, Ellis's insights into language transfer and TBLT underscore key factors that influence second language development, particularly in online oral skills. This theoretical foundation helps to understand and address the specific cognitive, environmental, and instructional challenges faced by Chinese students in online language learning.

3.4.3 Translanguaging

Translanguaging is a cross-linguistic practice that challenges traditional language

boundaries and classifications. It emphasizes the flexibility and malleability of language, viewing language as an inseparable whole rather than isolated units. In translanguaging, individuals can freely mix and alternate between multiple languages to achieve better communication and understanding.

Translanguaging research has gone through two stages of development. In the first stage, translanguaging was merely used as a descriptive label for specific language practices and teaching practices. It primarily focused on language use in educational settings. Related research, such as Garcia (2009), defined translanguaging as a discursive practice that forms meaning, creates experiences and increases perception by using multiple languages. She externalized the abstract concept of translanguaging into a linguistic phenomenon, a language practice that speakers use to understand everything in the world. Canagarajah (2011a, p.401) defines translanguaging as 'the ability of multilingual speakers to shuttle between languages, treating the diverse languages that form their repertoire as an integrated system'. Li (2011) detailed the practical methods of translanguaging based on the concept of superlanguage practices, with a particular focus on its application in bilingual education. In my research, I drew considerable inspiration from Canagarajah's (2013) discourse on the application of translanguaging in a globalized context. Canagarajah also underscored the value of translanguaging in fostering intercultural communication and facilitating multilingual coexistence. This offered a significant theoretical framework to evaluate traditionally monolingual teaching and communication methods.

Translanguaging strategies play a guiding role in how to more effectively use language for teaching or communication in multicultural or multilingual contexts in this study. I observed that in some instances, a monolingual teaching model could limit the growth of students' language acquisition and communication skills. Conversely, translanguaging, as a flexible and dynamic language use strategy, can aid students in comprehending and utilizing different languages, thus enabling them to effectively communicate in diverse cultures and contexts.

Secondly, learning a language is not simply about memorizing a set of codes or rules but rather learning a new way of being and doing, as language use is a process of creating, storing, retrieving, and transmitting experiences (Garcia, 2014). Garcia and Leiva (2014) argue that translanguaging goes beyond linguistic code-switching as it does not simply categorize the relationship between two languages as from A to B or from B to A. Instead, it analyzes the dynamic language use of bilingual speakers within specific contexts and understands the allocation and flow of language resources. Wei (2016) explores the application of translanguaging in English teaching at Chinese universities, analyzing its impact on students' language learning and cross-cultural communication through surveys and interviews with students and teachers. Garcia and Lin (2017) further point out that translanguaging in bilingual classrooms is a teaching mode that refers to students using two different languages alternately for language input and output. In other words, students are required to alternate between two different languages when receiving and transmitting information for language learning. Li (2022, p.1) states that:

"Translanguaging itself is a methodology offering a new conceptual framework that promotes a number of important analytical shifts: shift away from language as abstract codes to meaning- and sense-making; attend to a wider range of multi-semiotic resources whilst refusing to privilege particular modes and methods of meaning-making over others; approach translanguaging as an expansively integrated experience."

In the second stage, translanguaging research has been extended to the everyday language practices of bilingual or semi-bilingual individuals. Bilingual speakers alternate between different languages in contexts such as home and street, promoting mutual understanding among different language communities and contributing to the construction of their ideal identities. Zhang and Chan (2017) focus on posters collected in Macau and analyze the multimodal elements of multilingualism, such as colour, size, form, layout, fonts, etc., indicating that flexible multilingualism and

independent multilingualism coexist in Macau during the process of globalization. Krompák and Meyer (2018) conducted a study analyzing 300 digital photos with written signs taken in four different areas of Kleinbasel. The photos revealed how people in these areas communicate and negotiate meaning using different languages, reflecting typical cases of translanguaging, i.e., using multiple languages simultaneously in communication. Ateek (2022) shifts the focus to offline communities and argues that multilingualism and translanguaging can create inclusive translanguaging spaces, alleviate the psychological trauma of foreign refugees, and facilitate their integration into new environments.

In previous second-language classrooms, code-mixing was often labelled negatively, and if students used their native language and second language simultaneously in discussions, it was often seen as a sign of insufficient second-language proficiency. Conversely, translanguaging can effectively enhance learners' cognitive and communicative abilities (Garcia, 2009). Furthermore, translanguaging means appreciating the various language resources and cultural practices that learners bring (Pennycook, 2019), which may be the advantage of translanguaging as a translation language method, also a means of developing their English language acquisition, and a means of developing their English language acquisition for the types of international students involved in this study. With language transformation, the focus of teaching and research has shifted from teachers to learners, encouraging learners to actively and practically engage in teaching activities by utilizing all their language, cultural, and social resources.

This research explores the theory of translanguaging because it offers unique applicability to explore the development of Chinese students' online oral language skills during the COVID-19 pandemic. Compared to face-to-face classrooms, online learning often lacks immediate contextual cues, such as body language or real-time clarification, which can exacerbate language anxiety for Chinese students in English-only environments. Translanguaging allows students to draw on their full

linguistic repertoire, helping them better understand course content, express themselves more effectively, and alleviate anxiety. In online learning environments with limited interaction, this holistic approach significantly enhances student engagement and supports their mental well-being. Additionally, translanguaging takes into account students' multicultural backgrounds and encourages them to draw on their linguistic and cultural resources to better understand the learning content and the unique context in which it is being accessed. For example, Chinese students can alternate between their first language and English to understand complex concepts and express unique cultural perspectives, enhancing their language skills and intercultural communication abilities. Thus, translanguaging provides a useful framework for understanding and addressing the challenges Chinese students may face in online oral language learning.

3.5 Conclusion

This chapter delves into the various facets of learning, with a focus on online learning and its implications for second language acquisition. It begins by exploring different ways of learning, ranging from the humanistic approaches that emphasize self-realization and personal potential to the constructivist perspectives that underscore the active construction of knowledge through environmental interaction.

The chapter then transitions to the definition and types of online learning, highlighting its evolution from its early beginnings in the 1990s to its current widespread use. The various types of online learning, including synchronous, asynchronous, and blended learning, are discussed, along with their respective advantages and disadvantages. The importance of interactivity in the online classroom is emphasized, as it plays a crucial role in maintaining engagement and fostering a learning environment conducive to language acquisition.

Subsequently, the chapter delves into the intricacies of second language acquisition, drawing from theories such as Krashen's Monitor Hypotheses and Ellis's perspective

on language use and transfer. The role of environment, task-based language teaching, and the concept of translanguaging are also explored, providing a comprehensive understanding of the complexities involved in acquiring a second language.

In conclusion, while we have gained significant insights into learning, online learning, and second language acquisition, there are still many unanswered questions. One such question that remains unexplored is the specific impact of online learning on the development of oral English skills among international students, particularly those from China studying in the UK during the COVID-19 pandemic. This gap in knowledge is what I intend to focus on in my study. By delving into this unexplored area, we hope to gain a deeper understanding of the challenges and opportunities presented by online learning for second language learners, ultimately contributing to more effective and inclusive language education practices.

Chapter 4: Theoretical Framework

4.1 Introduction

This section explores the significance of key concepts, including motivation, social capital, cultural capital, and "habitus" in the context of online education and language learning among Chinese students, with a particular focus on the periods before, during, and after the COVID-19 pandemic. These concepts form the theoretical framework of this research. Topics include motivation theory, the L2 motivational self-system, Maslow's hierarchy of needs, social capital theory, Bourdieu's social capital theory, Coleman's social function perspective, Putnam's political participation and democracy, Woolcock's network-based social capital theory, cultural capital, and Bourdieu's habitus. The main aim of this research is to explore in depth the role of online learning in the context of transnational education, particularly in the development of English-speaking skills for international students. The theoretical concepts mentioned above provide a solid foundation for understanding the potential of online learning to improve the oral proficiency of Chinese international students in a transnational education environment. Finally, it is worth noting that this chapter uses these theories to study the performance of Chinese international students in online learning environments, all observations in this study were conducted online. This is primarily because, during the period of the researcher's fieldwork, all English teaching activities had shifted from traditional classrooms to online platforms due to external factors such as the global COVID-19 pandemic and the rapid development of educational technology and online platforms due to external factors such as the global COVID-19 pandemic in recent years. In recent years. This shift not only provided the researcher with a unique observational perspective but also guided this study to adapt to the new research environment in order to more accurately capture and analyze the learning dynamics and oral language development of Chinese students in an online learning environment.

Figure 4.1

4.2 Motivation Theory

The study of motivation theory has long been a focal point in educational research, particularly in the realm of second language acquisition (SLA). As Dörnyei and Ushioda (2001) note, motivation is a complex and multifaceted construct that plays a pivotal role in determining learners' success in SLA. This assertion is echoed by numerous scholars who have emphasized the importance of motivation in language learning (e.g., Gardner, 1985; Deci and Ryan, 1985). Motivation theory is crucial to understanding the online transnational education learning behaviours of Chinese international students during the pandemic. One significant question in language learning is understanding why individuals choose to learn a language. Generally, motivation is a theoretical concept employed to explain human behaviour and thought processes (Gopalan *et al.*, 2017). Initially, "motivation" was a term primarily used in psychology. There is a unanimous agreement among researchers that motivation significantly influences and guides human behaviour. As stated by Corder (1967, p. 164), "Given motivation, a human being will inevitably learn a second language if exposed to the language data." This statement highlights the significance of motivation in English language learning. Wen's (1997) research demonstrates that learning motivation directly impacts students' proficiency and progress in the target language. Drawing from the self-determination theory (SDT) paradigm (Deci and

Ryan, 1985), which posits that individuals are inherently motivated to grow, learn, and explore their environments, we can gain valuable insights into the learning behaviours of Chinese international students during the pandemic. SDT distinguishes between extrinsic and intrinsic motivation, with the latter being internally driven and associated with greater engagement and persistence in learning (Ryan and Deci, 2013).

Gardner (1985, p. 10) provides a key definition of motivation in Second Language Acquisition (SLA), stating it as "the will to learn a second language, make the necessary efforts to achieve the goal, and derive a sense of satisfaction from the process." Similarly, Hammer (1983) posits that motivation is an internal drive that inspires individuals to take specific actions. Different motivations can result in various activities. Maintaining high motivation is vital for task completion, particularly in English language learning. Gupta (2019) concurs by stating, "Motivation is considered one of the main determining factors in acquiring a second language."

Chinese international students seeking education in the UK might encounter several unique challenges before, during, and after the COVID-19 pandemic, such as language difficulties, cultural clashes, adapting to unfamiliar online learning modes, and overcoming distractions in an online learning environment. These factors can affect their learning motivation, which pertains to the reasons for their learning and the level of effort they are willing to exert. Their motivation, in turn, influences how they tackle these challenges. Understanding motivation theory can help them better manage their learning motivation (Nartiningrum and Nugroho, 2020). By engaging in self-reflection, clarifying their learning objectives, devising reasonable learning plans, and maintaining a positive attitude when facing difficulties, they can more effectively address challenges in learning and achieve better learning outcomes. For example, if they have a strong interest in the English language and Western culture, they might participate more actively in learning. Conversely, if they find online learning boring or anxiety-inducing, their motivation to learn might decrease. Compared to learning in

offline courses, more distractions can prevent students from immersing themselves in learning. This is consistent with the viewpoint proposed by Kirovska-Simjanoska (2019) in a study, which mentions that online learning largely depends on student's motivation. The learning process depends on the various distractions students face when studying at home. Therefore, students lacking motivation may need to strive harder to maintain a positive attitude toward learning and reignite their motivation by reviewing their objectives in language learning. In other words, by identifying the key factors that influence their motivation, teachers can design more targeted interventions and support strategies to address their specific needs and challenges. Moreover, by understanding how these factors interact with each other, teachers can create a more holistic and integrated approach to motivating learners in online environments.

4.2.1 L2 Motivational Self System

L2 motivation is a crucial aspect of second language acquisition and has been extensively studied by researchers worldwide. Over the years, research on L2 motivation has been conducted from various theoretical perspectives. Prior to the 1990s, most experiments and studies on L2 motivation were based on socio-psychological viewpoints (Gardner and Lambert, 1959).

In the early 20th century, researchers began to recognize the dynamic and fluctuating nature of motivation in L2 learning. They emphasized the processes involved in initiating, maintaining, and reflecting on learning behaviours. Many studies have shown that the "self" plays a dominant role in motivation and behaviour and is closely linked to personality and motivation.

Dörnyei (1998) defined motivation as "a process whereby a certain amount of instigation force arises, initiates action, and persists as long as no other force comes into play to weaken it and thereby terminate the action, or until the planned outcome has been reached."

Dörnyei's definition highlights both the goal and effort dimensions of motivation, providing a more comprehensive understanding. He also incorporates both dynamic and static perspectives, further enhancing the understanding of motivation.

Building on sociocultural achievements, Dörnyei (2005) proposed a new conceptual framework known as the L2 Motivational Self System (L2MSS). This framework consists of three selves: the Ideal L2 Self (IL2S), the Ought-to L2 Self (OL2S), and the Second Language Learning Experience (SLLE). IL2S represents individuals' aspirations and goals as language learners, OL2S refers to personal duties and responsibilities, and SLLE encompasses the learning environment and executive motivation related to direct learning experiences. IL2S and OL2S are behavioural selves, while SLLE represents a causal relationship (Dörnyei, 2005, p. 106).

Kormos, Kiddle and Csizér (2011) surveyed the learning motivation and attitudes of 202 Hungarian secondary school students. The study found that IL2S played a more significant role than OL2S in determining learners' motivation. Parental encouragement also had direct and indirect influences on students. IL2S represents the desires, longing, and hopes of language learners for themselves as language users, which can be significantly shaped by the active support, backing, and encouragement of parents. This support helps students to envision themselves as successful language learners, thereby motivating them to participate more actively in language learning. Internal factors within the classroom can influence IL2S, fostering language learning by boosting students' intrinsic motivation and active participation. These factors also impact the breadth of students' learning experiences and their involvement in language learning.

Shalan (2021) conducted a study on Saudi English learners and found close correlations between IL2S and their second language motivational behaviours, indicating the importance of IL2S as a primary motivational factor. Kim and Kim (2011) explored the relationships between IL2S, L2 learning strategies, and L2 learning behaviours in high school students from four countries. The study found

significant correlations between students' IL2S and their visual and auditory learning styles. It also identified L2 anxiety caused by OL2S as an intrinsic factor influencing learner motivation. The association between anxiety and L2 motivation suggests that IL2S can help alleviate L2 anxiety, while OL2S can contribute to anxiety (Ueki and Takeuchi, 2012).

The theoretical orientation of this study has been informed by the L2 Motivational Self System framework, proposed by Dörnyei. This framework emphasizes the role of self and recognizes that foreign language learning transcends simple communication or content mastery, asserting it as a central and defining feature of personal identity. As Dörnyei (2009, pp.216-217) suggests, language acquisition is intrinsically linked to psychological processes and is a core component in establishing one's identity. The relevance of the L2MSS framework in the context of this research is apparent. Its concentration on the learner's intrinsic motivation, self-perception, and projected self aligns profoundly with the study's objective to investigate the motivational elements affecting the English language acquisition of Chinese international students. By acknowledging the individual's self-concept and aspirations, the L2MSS framework provides a subtle understanding of student motivations and how they shape their learning journey.

Moreover, the adaptability of the L2MSS framework to different language learning contexts enhances its suitability for this study. In our increasingly globalized society, where language learners encounter a myriad of cultural and linguistic stimuli, the framework's capacity to encapsulate the intricacies of such environments is invaluable. It offers a holistic examination of how external influences, such as cultural backgrounds and learning environments, intertwine with internal motivations, thereby shaping the English-speaking proficiency of Chinese international students.

In conclusion, the incorporation of Dörnyei's L2MSS framework into this study provides a solid theoretical underpinning for the exploration of the complex nature of English language learning among Chinese international students. It supports a more

profound comprehension of the motivational interactions propelling their language learning and how these motivations interact with various contextual variables. This methodology, while not exhaustive, aims to provide valuable insights into the specific challenges and prospects encountered by this cohort in their pursuit of English-speaking mastery.

4.2.2 Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs

A crucial concept that underlies this study is Abraham Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs. This theory is pivotal in understanding the driving forces behind human motivation and behaviour. Maslow proposed a hierarchical model that outlines the progression of human needs, from the most basic to the most complex. Maslow posited that human needs as:

"It is quite true that man lives by bread alone—when there is no bread. But what happens to man's desires when there is plenty of bread and when his belly is chronically filled? At once other (and "higher") needs to emerge and these, rather than physiological hungers, dominate the organism. And when these, in turn, are satisfied, again new (and still "higher") needs to emerge and so on" (Maslow, 1943, p. 375).

As per Maslow's framework, human needs are organized into a pyramid with five distinct levels: physiological, safety, social, esteem, and self-actualization (Owens and Loomes, 2010). At the base of the pyramid are physiological needs, which are essential for survival, such as food, water, and sleep. Once these basic needs are met, individuals move upward in the hierarchy, seeking satisfaction of increasingly complex needs (Maslow, 1943).

The relevance of Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs to this study is profound, especially in the context of Chinese international students facing the challenges of studying abroad during the influenza pandemic. This theory provides a valuable framework for understanding how these students' needs evolve and how they prioritize their needs in

response to changing circumstances.

For instance, under normal study abroad circumstances, students arriving in the UK must first meet their basic physiological needs, such as finding suitable accommodation, securing food, and managing their daily lives. As they settle into their new environment, their focus shifts to safety needs, such as personal security. The pandemic exacerbated these concerns, with some students needing to overcome issues like cancelled flights preventing overseas travel, being stranded overseas without being able to see their family, and taking extra precautions to protect their health and welfare.

Furthermore, esteem needs also come into play as students strive for recognition and respect within their academic and social circles. They strive for good grades, participate in extracurricular activities, and contribute to society in meaningful ways to enhance their self-esteem and a sense of accomplishment.

Finally, at the top of Maslow's pyramid are self-actualization needs, which involve personal growth, satisfaction, and the realization of one's potential. For Chinese international students, this may involve pursuing advanced degrees, participating in research projects aligned with their interests, or engaging in cultural exchanges to broaden their horizons.

By applying Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs to this study, we can gain a deeper understanding of the challenges faced by Chinese international students and how they prioritize and navigate their needs over time. This knowledge can inform the design of more effective support systems and interventions to enhance their overall satisfaction and success during their overseas study experience. Abbas et al. (2021) applied Maslow's theory of human motivation to students' choices to study abroad. They found that the quality of education, a basic need, influenced students' decision to study in the UK. Additionally, social needs, another aspect of Maslow's hierarchy, played a role as students sought to build connections and socialize. Torabi (2020)

mentioned that self-actualization plays a significant role in language learning, facilitating the improvement of oral skills among EFL learners.

Moreover, while Maslow's theory provides a valuable lens for examining students' needs, it is important to acknowledge its limitations. As Trivedi and Mehta (2019) suggest, the theory must be complemented by other motivating factors such as expectations, experiences, and perceptions. Therefore, to provide a more comprehensive analysis, this study integrates additional theories such as Social Capital Theory, Cultural Capital Theory, and Habitus Theory. These theories offer a broader perspective on the influencing factors that shape students' experiences and outcomes, enabling a more nuanced understanding of their motivations and challenges during their study abroad journey.

4.3 Social Capital Theory

Social capital theory is a crucial and fundamental concept, focusing on the cultivation and development of a set of skills, capabilities, and abilities. The acquisition of these skills is vital as it enables individuals to effectively operate and work within their respective societies, communities, or groups. This theory is a comprehensive amalgamation of theoretical studies, perspectives, and insights from multiple disciplines including political science, economics, sociology, and other social sciences.

Over the years, many scholars such as Pierre Bourdieu, James Coleman, Robert Putnam, and Michael Woolcock, among others, have made significant contributions, shaping and refining our understanding and application of social capital. Each of these distinguished scholars brought unique and innovative perspectives, with their research, theories, and viewpoints culminating in a more comprehensive and integrated view of this study's theoretical framework, paving the way for further exploration, research, and understanding in this field.

By combining these diverse perspectives and viewpoints, my understanding of social capital theory is more comprehensive and meticulous. This understanding reveals the multiple impacts of social capital on society, individuals, and communities. Based on this, the chosen paradigm, method, or framework should be consistent with the research objectives and problems, providing a clear path for understanding.

4.3.1 Bourdieu's Perspective on Social Capital

Pierre Bourdieu's definition of social capital is a crucial cornerstone of his renowned sociological theory. In this framework, Bourdieu defines social capital as

"the aggregate of the actual or potential resources which are linked to possession of a durable network of more or less institutionalized relationships of mutual acquaintance and recognition" (Bourdieu, 1986, p. 9).

Bourdieu's concept of social capital encompasses the underlying structure of interpersonal relationships and the potential resources that can be accessed through this network. This can manifest in various ways, from direct transformations such as leveraging professional relationships to secure job opportunities, to indirect transformations such as fostering trust and reputation through active participation in social activities.

Bourdieu views social capital as a dynamic, continuously evolving process that requires ongoing investment and maintenance. He argues that individuals or groups must constantly strive to expand their social networks and deepen their relationships in order to amass more social capital and thereby gain access to a wider range of resources.

Bourdieu's theoretical framework also introduces the concepts of economic capital, cultural capital, and symbolic capital. Economic capital is institutionalized through monetary means and is often associated with property rights. Cultural capital, on the other hand, is institutionalized through educational qualifications, typically

symbolized by diplomas, degrees, and other certificates. According to Bourdieu's theory (1986), economic capital forms the basis of all other forms of capital, as it is both the cause and the effect of possessing social and cultural capital.

In his sociological analysis, Bourdieu emphasizes the role of various forms of capital, including social, economic, and cultural capital, in maintaining existing social structures. He acknowledges that these forms of capital contribute to the intergenerational reproduction of social structures. However, he also notes that high social status does not automatically or entirely benefit those born into it (Bourdieu, 2016).

The unequal distribution of social capital among different social classes or groups leads to significant differences in the opportunities available to children from different backgrounds. This is particularly evident in the processes of higher education admission and job-seeking after graduation. Bourdieu and Passeron argue that

as social rank increases, contacts outside the family also expand, but only within the same social stratum. Thus, for those at the lowest level of the social hierarchy, the subjective desire for higher education is even smaller than the objective opportunity (Bourdieu, 2006).

A key tenet of Bourdieu's understanding of social capital and educational attainment is that parents transmit their social capital to their children. This transmission provides the children with greater opportunities, enabling them to achieve higher levels of educational attainment, and ultimately contributes to the covert reproduction of social classes.

Bourdieu's analytical framework underscores the significant role of social capital in society. It highlights the profound influence of social capital in shaping individual and group dynamics. This concept is particularly relevant to my study due to its inherent potential for the acquisition and mobilization of resources, as well as for garnering

support through the establishment and maintenance of relational networks. Bourdieu sees social capital as a powerful explanatory tool for understanding social inequality and reproduction.

4.3.2 Coleman

Another prominent figure who has studied social capital from a macro perspective is Coleman.

According to Coleman (1988), social capital is "a particular kind of resource available to an actor ... Unlike other forms of capital, social capital inheres in the structure of relations between actors and among actors." Coleman argues that every individual possesses three types of capital from birth: human capital formed by genetic endowment, material capital composed of material tendencies, and social capital constituted by the social environment in which individuals live. Social capital, in a broad sense, refers to resources accumulated through relationships between people (Coleman, 1988).

Coleman's main focus of study is the educational achievement of disadvantaged students. He believes that social capital has a greater impact on individual education and is more evenly distributed than other types of capital in society, such as financial capital and human capital (Golubović and Džunić, 2013). For instance, Porras and Hoffer's study (1986), cited by Coleman (1988), revealed that the dropout rate for high school students with both parents, at most two children, and mothers with higher education expectations for their children was 8.1%. In contrast, for students from single-parent households with four children and mothers who had no expectations for their children to receive higher education, the dropout rate increased to 30.6% (Hoffer, 1986). This finding demonstrates the significant influence of family background and parental expectations on student dropout rates. Further examples that support Coleman's social capital theory, as cited by Israel, Borie, and Hartley (2001), indicate that higher parental education levels and greater family economic capital contribute to

better educational achievement. It has been observed that individuals with richer social capital tend to demonstrate better educational achievement (Adedokun, 2007). For instance, international students, due to studying in a different country, need to adjust to issues such as cultural adaptation, social isolation, economic pressure, and psychological stress (Minutillo *et al.*, 2020).

While Coleman's social capital theory has faced criticism for its failure to explain differences in individuals' possession of social capital across different social backgrounds, it remains effective in explaining differences among individuals with similar social backgrounds. Thus, the rational action theory, based on the concept of social capital, can be successfully applied when dealing with participants from similar socioeconomic backgrounds. For example, when studying the relationship between social capital and students attending private and public universities, parents' economic and cultural capital may play a more significant role than social capital.

Amidst the complexities of the global educational landscape intertwined with the COVID-19 pandemic, the present study focuses on a pivotal question: Can Chinese students actively engage with the UK's education system through online learning platforms, striving to enhance their English speaking proficiency? Drawing upon James Coleman's framework of social capital theory, we delve deeper into this trend, conceptualizing social capital not merely as a static resource or a social network structure, but rather as a dynamic force that plays a crucial role in propelling students' academic development and linguistic advancement.

For Chinese students, the economic capital possessed by their families emerges as a significant driving force in their pursuit of British international education. The investment of economic resources effectively opens the door to esteemed educational institutions in the UK, allowing them to persist in their academic journeys amidst the global challenges posed by COVID-19. Particularly in the shift towards online learning triggered by the pandemic, the financial wherewithal of families has largely determined students' access to high-quality online educational resources and essential

technological tools.

Concurrently, cultural capital occupies an indispensable position in students' academic and linguistic pursuits. The cultural backgrounds and educational experiences of parents not only establish fundamental academic and linguistic frameworks for their offspring but also subtly shape their cross-cultural communication abilities. In the emerging educational ecosystem of online learning, Chinese students confront novel academic paradigms, teaching methodologies, and linguistic environments, where the cultural capital transmitted within families emerges as a vital asset in navigating these new territories, these challenges also allow us to consider them as facing disadvantages - not just as privileged.

4.3.3 Putnam

Putnam (1995) points out that social capital consists of three components: moral obligations and norms, social values (especially trust), and social networks (especially voluntary associations). These elements promote coordination and mutually beneficial cooperation.

According to Putnam (2000), social capital can be defined as "the collective value of social networks and the inclinations that arise from these networks to do things for each other" (p. 19). Putnam suggests that the characteristics of social networks, such as trust, reciprocity, information sharing, and cooperation, are beneficial not only to individuals connected through these relationships but also to others. Putnam argues that similar to material and human capital in educational settings, social capital has the potential to enhance individual productivity and collective efficacy.

Putnam (2000) describes bonding social capital as a strong adhesive that brings people together while bridging social capital is characterized by relationships that bridge different groups. Putnam further subdivides social capital into cohesive and connected types. Cohesive social capital refers to primary groups based on close relationships

with shared attributes and a high degree of identification, such as family, relatives, friends, and neighbours. On the other hand, connected social capital refers to secondary groups based on interactions in public affairs, such as colleagues, civic organizations, or religious groups (Putnam, 2015).

Onyx and Leonard describe bonding social capital as "dense, multi-functional ties and strong localized trust" that exist within close-knit groups of people who share values, principles, and social norms, such as friends with strong relationships, families, or neighbourhood groups, and is characterized by a high level of associational density within the group (Chiu *et al.*, 2006). As the Bonding social capital emphasizes the importance of establishing strong relationships among Chinese international students, particularly those studying in the UK, is equally important. It fosters community and a sense of belonging, providing emotional and practical support. Establishing these internal networks is vital in overcoming the challenges of living and studying abroad. By forming strong internal networks, international students can find others with similar backgrounds, languages, and cultures, thus creating a small, close-knit community. This community provides an emotional safe haven, allowing students to receive support and assistance when faced with difficulties.

Bridging social capital is defined as "horizontal trust and interconnections among individuals and groups" (p. 2). Similar norms of trust and reciprocity apply, but the social relationships are weaker and exist within loose networks. Connected social capital leverages external knowledge, ideas, and resources, and can contribute to community cohesion (Russell *et al.*, 2008). The social capital theory contributes to the study of how people develop relationships and establish connections in learning networks. Putnam (2015) provides new insights into the functioning of democracy through his understanding of social capital. He argues that social capital is crucial for the maintenance and functioning of democracy, as it enables social organizations to promote cooperation, strengthen trust norms among members of social networks, enhance the efficiency of social behaviour, and ultimately serve the public interest and

ensure the stability of democracy.

According to a study by Ellison, Steinfield, and Lampe (2007), frequent use of social networking services (SNS) among university students enhanced their connections with close friends and family. This strengthened their bonding social capital. The study also found that SNS usage helped students maintain connections with high school friends and expand their social networks. This allowed them to meet various local and international friends, thereby building bridging social capital. On the contrary, it is worth noting that Jensen and Jetten's (2015) research suggests that although bonding social capital promotes the formation of student groups, it can also lead to the formation of restrictive unique norms within the group. These norms can sometimes prevent group members from establishing connections with educators, thus affecting the formation of bridging social capital with educators. This is consistent with Putnam's view that bonding social capital may limit the free actions of members due to strong internal control of social networks, showing its possible restrictiveness.

In this study, bridging social capital is primarily reflected in how it helps small groups overcome narrow worldviews, introduce external information, and facilitate the diffusion of information across multiple networks. For example, Chinese international students aspire to establish social networks and friendships with locals and students from other countries.

Many Chinese international students, upon arriving in a new cultural environment, may initially feel disoriented and isolated. However, the process of establishing social connections and friendships with local communities and peers from various countries becomes crucial in their journey towards integration and expansion of social horizons. This effort to build bridges is a manifestation of bridging social capital, which not only aids in overcoming narrow worldviews but also introduces external information and facilitates the diffusion of knowledge across diverse networks. Through these interactions, Chinese international students are exposed to new perspectives, ideas, and values, enabling them to transcend their original cultural frameworks and ways of

thinking. The cross-cultural exchange broadens their cognitive scope, enhances their cross-cultural comprehension, and fosters a more open and inclusive view of the world. Simultaneously, the significance of bonding social capital cannot be overstated. This form of social capital emphasizes the importance of establishing strong relationships within the Chinese international student community, particularly in the UK. Bonding social capital fosters a sense of community and belongingness, providing emotional and practical support to this group. For students navigating the challenges of living and studying in a foreign country, these internal networks become indispensable.

In essence, both bridging and bonding social capital play pivotal roles in the cross-cultural adaptation of Chinese international students. Bridging social capital facilitates their integration into new environments and the acquisition of external knowledge, while bonding social capital strengthens their internal support systems and fosters a sense of community. Together, these forms of social capital contribute to a richer and more fulfilling experience for Chinese international students as they navigate their academic and personal journeys abroad.

4.3.4 Woolcock

According to Woolcock (1998, p. 153), "Social capital is the information, trust, and norms that exist in a person's social networks." Woolcock (2001) expands on Putnam's concepts of bonding social capital and bridging social capital by introducing a third form called linking social capital. Linking social capital refers to alliances formed with individuals who provide access to resources, ideas, and information from outside the community and have connections to external power.

Linking social capital describes a network of norms and trust relationships that go beyond explicit, formal, or institutionalized power or authority gradients in society (Szreter and Woolcock, 2004). It is crucial because it enables individuals to access resources, ideas, and information beyond their social circles. It refers to the social

capital that connects people from different professions and is explicitly tied to power differentials. In other words, by utilizing linking social capital, individuals can access those with institutional power across social strata and leverage resources, ideas, and information outside their own groups to achieve their goals, such as engaging in extracurricular activities in British society to accumulate social capital and economic capital for future employment (e.g., international students returning to their home countries). For Chinese international students, interaction with official institutions is crucial in a foreign environment like the UK. These institutions include the UK Visa and Immigration (UKVI), educational institutions, local government departments, and healthcare systems. Contact with the UKVI is vital, as it manages and confirms students' legal residence and study qualifications. Regular communication with the UKVI ensures that students can receive updated visa and residence information promptly, preventing violations or infringement of rights due to a lack of understanding of policy changes. Registering for local medical services, such as the National Health Service (NHS), is another essential step. The NHS provides basic health insurance for residents, including international students, but they need to complete the registration process. By registering, international students can receive necessary medical assistance, crucial for their health and safety in a foreign country.

By integrating the perspectives of Bourdieu, Coleman, Putnam, and Woolcock, we can establish a theoretical framework for the role of social capital in transnational education. Social capital consists of social relationships, which are resources based on interpersonal networks. It represents a persistent social network through which actors can acquire wealth and social resources by means of their social connections. In schools, which serve as microcosms of society, the relationships between students, teachers, and staff are intricate and close. Therefore, social capital relationships are crucial in the realm of education.

In this study, social capital is defined as the sum of resources accumulated by Chinese international student communities during their experience of transnational education

in the UK. This includes relatively stable and institutionalized social relationship networks that encompass both bonding social capital with fellow Chinese students and bridging social capital with foreign students and teachers.

To fully integrate into the Western (and international) academic world, Chinese students need to go beyond bonding social capital formed with other Chinese students. They must also develop bridging social capital, which involves building relationships with individuals from other nationalities, making friends with people from diverse backgrounds in the UK, and establishing connections with various circles to gain a deeper understanding of British society. Additionally, Chinese students also need to engage with linking social capital, enabling them to fully and critically engage with the structures and power dynamics at play. During the pandemic, all courses and activities involving Chinese and British Chinese students shifted online in the context of this study. Therefore, the study applies social capital theory as a theoretical framework to examine transnational education issues for Chinese international students, exploring whether online teaching contributes to the development of social capital among international students and their ability to integrate into British society by establishing effective relationships with other groups.

4.4 Cultural Capital and Habitus

Intricately intertwined, cultural capital and social capital form the backbone of our societal structure. The term 'cultural capital' is symbolic of assets that may be tangible or intangible. These assets are vehicles that provide avenues for social mobility and elevate an individual's social standing. It is a matrix of elements such as skills, knowledge, and even music preferences. Significantly, it is not related to an individual's income, net assets, or any financial indicators. As described by Pierre Bourdieu (1997), a prominent French sociologist, and reiterated by the Cultural Learning Alliance (2019), cultural capital manifests in three forms: embodied, objectified, and institutionalized.

Embodied cultural capital is deeply ingrained and permanently resides within a person's psyche and physical being, expressed either mentally or materially. This form of cultural capital cannot be acquired through purchase or exchange. Once acquired, embodied cultural capital becomes deeply internalized and is inseparable from the individual. Examples include habits, manners, and behavioural styles that are a direct reflection of an individual's cultural capital.

On the other hand, objectified cultural capital exists in cultural goods that can be appropriated, exchanged, and inherited. These mainly include dictionaries, books, and monuments that are symbolic of a person's cultural capital. Institutionalized cultural capital, the third form, is determined by academic qualifications or diplomas and is often perceived as an institutionalized cultural state, such as diplomas or certificates. These assets are objective states that cannot be appropriated.

The empowerment that cultural capital provides individuals is significant. It enables them to achieve their aspirations, attain success, and ascend the social ladder without necessarily relying on wealth and financial capital. This concept of cultural capital is prolific in research, particularly in studies focusing on Asian students who view studying abroad as a unique strategy to set themselves apart from other graduates in their home countries, thereby gaining advantages in the increasingly competitive labour market.

A report in the Financial Times states,

"With many countries, including the US and UK, placing restrictions on working after studying, increasing numbers of Chinese graduates are studying for master's degrees abroad and then returning to China to work" (Lockett and Feng, 2019).

Chinese students place a high premium on their "suzhi" (comprehensive humanistic qualities) and strive to enhance it throughout their study abroad experience (Li, 2017).

This concept bears a striking similarity to the concept of cultural capital in the context of China. Additionally, acquiring high-value cultural capital, such as prestigious Western degrees, is impossible without the accumulation of genuine human and cultural capital. However, once successful, an individual can relatively easily acquire symbolic and political capital (Xiang and Shen, 2009, p. 521).

Moreover, Bourdieu (1977) introduced the concept of cultural reproduction theory and educational theory, suggesting that the education system plays a pivotal role in controlling the production, dissemination, and transformation of cultural capital. This transmission of cultural capital is the most covert way of passing down capital through inheritance. The education system plays a clandestine role in symbolic violence by transmitting the dominant class's culture to students through a series of teaching processes (Azaola, 2012). On the contrary, disadvantaged students who fail to meet educational standards are marginalized and excluded from the education system. For them, the adverse conditions are not economic factors, but language barriers. Some Chinese students are facing this challenge, although most participants in this study are not.

This leads us to the concept of habitus, which is "how durable schemes of perception, thought, and action resulting from the incorporation of social structures guide and generate practices" (Wacquant, 2005, p. 316). Habitus provides the foundational characteristics and practical prerequisites for the social reproduction process. It subconsciously and continuously reflects in individual actors' behaviour and drives their thoughts, perceptions, expressions, and actions. Habits developed among students from different class families become the basis for accepting and mastering information at school. Habits developed during schooling become the basis for accepting and mastering cultural industry production. In this way, the ways of thinking and acting of individual habitus are employed, reproducing the original family's class advantages based on different levels of educational resources. The education system, by recognizing the inheritance transmission of various types of

capital, contributes to the reproduction of social structures (Yin and Mu, 2020). In this study, the concept of habitus can better understand the difficulties faced by Chinese students when they first arrive in the UK for study and the reasons for their disadvantaged status (Mu, 2014). As mentioned in Chapter 2, the background introduction to the digital divide in networked use and the development of behavioural habits based on it, the digital habitus, individual internalized patterns of behaviour as thinking and action with information, digital learning and practice, for example, how Chinese students perceive the importance of the Internet in their transnational study and social life and whether they actively use the Internet to practice their English speaking skills also represents the embodiment of individual digital practice habits (Ranalli, 2013; Liu *et al.*, 2019; Zhang and Perez-Paredes, 2021).

In the context of the Internet, it is worth considering how students' habitus and capital interact to influence the patterns of social reproduction. Chinese students in the UK have a low level of cultural capital when they first arrive (e.g., starting online courses provided by UK institutions) due to significant differences in habits between them and the expected norms and values of British higher education and society (Hang and Zhang, 2023). The phenomenon of Chinese students frequently remaining silent in classrooms, as documented in prior research (for example, the study by Choi (2015) mentioned in section 2.3 regarding the Socio-cultural context of education in China), perpetuates the stereotype of them as passive learners unwilling to speak up in class (Ryan, 2010). Ha and Li (2014) point out, "Their silence in this pattern often relates to obedience, lack of critical thinking, spontaneous oral participation, sitting quietly or having no questions or answers." This phenomenon will be further explored, and attempts will be made to address the various challenges currently faced by Chinese students in the UK.

4.5 Reasons for choosing these theoretical frameworks

A comprehensive, all-inclusive, and in-depth theoretical framework has been

diligently developed by thoughtfully combining the versatile perspectives of Motivation Theory (4.5.1), Social Capital (4.5.2), and Cultural Capital and Habitus (4.5.3). This framework is meticulously designed and specifically tailored to examine the oral performance and transnational educational behaviour of Chinese international students, a group that is increasingly important in the global education landscape. The rationale for selecting this particular theoretical framework is as follows:

The first key idea is the hierarchy and dynamics of motivation. Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs, which is a widely recognized theory, elucidates the hierarchical structure of human needs, which range from fundamental physiological needs to the quest for self-actualization. Employing this framework, we can understand and decode the evolving motivations of Chinese international students in their engagement with online transnational education. Moreover, the hierarchy and dynamics inherent in this framework are also intrinsically relevant to the ongoing process of accumulating cultural capital, as students must continuously adapt, evolve and integrate themselves into a foreign culture, which can be a challenging and complex process.

The association between self-concept and motivation is the second pivotal point. The L2 Motivational Self System (L2MSS) theory, a highly relevant theory in this context, emphasizes the critical link between an individual's self-concept and their motivation to learn a language. The self-concept of Chinese international students is primarily influenced by cultural factors and the dynamics of online learning, both of which interact with their motivation to improve oral proficiency. Together, these factors have a collective impact on their learning outcomes. This theory acts as a complement to the perspective of social capital, as social capital influences the formation of learners' self-concept and motivation through the medium of social relationships.

Thirdly, the bridging role of social capital is considered. The perspectives of Bourdieu and other scholars on social capital underscore the significance of social relationships in acquiring resources and achieving academic success. For Chinese international students, social capital involves not only connections with fellow Chinese students but

also building bridges with foreign students and teachers. In online teaching environments, where face-to-face interaction is limited, social capital plays a critical, even crucial, role in establishing relationships with the broader society.

Lastly, the influence of cultural capital and habitus is explored. Cultural capital, which represents an individual's cultural competence and institutionalized cultural status, has a direct impact on students' academic performance and their ability to adapt socially. Habitus, on the other hand, refers to internalized behavioural patterns that need continuous adjustment to adapt to new social norms and cultural expectations in a transnational environment, a process that can be both challenging and transformative.

In summary, this comprehensive theoretical framework offers a holistic and encompassing explanation of the oral performance of Chinese international students in transnational education. It takes into account individual factors such as motivation and self-concept, as well as societal and cultural factors like social capital, cultural capital, and habitus. The integration of these diverse factors into a unified framework enhances our understanding of the learning experiences and needs of international students. It also provides targeted guidance for methodology, data collection, and analysis in future studies, making it a valuable tool for researchers and educators alike.

Chapter 5: Methodology

5.1 Introduction

This study is committed to a comprehensive and detailed analysis of the online learning behaviour of Chinese international students in the specific context of the pandemic. I will focus on how they find their learning paths in a digital environment, exploring various challenges they encounter in adapting to this online learning mode. At the same time, the research will also pay attention to the practical difficulties they need to cope with in their transnational life. More importantly, this study will focus on exploring the positive impact of online education on the adaptation of transnational life for Chinese international students, and its unique value in improving English speaking skills. To provide an outline of the study, this chapter first discusses the suitable research paradigm for this study - ontological and epistemological assumptions (5.2), qualitative research (5.3), before moving to present the research methods - interpretative phenomenology and ethnography (5.4), sampling - purposive sampling (5.5), research tools - classroom observation and interviews (5.6), the chapter then covers data analysis methods: field notes and MAXQDA thematic analysis (5.7), discusses the credibility and transferability of the study (5.8), and finally there is a discussion of ethical considerations (5.9), followed by a conclusion (5.10).

5.2 Ontological and Epistemological Assumptions

Numerous research textbooks recommend that researchers acknowledge their paradigm position (Mertens, 2012), asserting that defining the "trilogy" of ontology, epistemology, and methodology is crucial (Crotty, 1998).

It is important to note that ontology, traditionally considered a major branch of philosophy called metaphysics, deals with questions regarding the existence of

entities. It also examines how these entities are grouped, related in a hierarchical structure, and classified based on similarities and differences (Griswold, 1987). The ontology of constructivism involves knowledge being shaped through the interplay between the individual and their environment, rather than merely being absorbed from it. Constructivism posits that learners modify their cognitive frameworks through environmental interaction, thus generating new knowledge (Cupchik, 2001). My understanding of the nature of reality (ontology) is that reality is experienced differently by different people due to their varying perspectives. This study focuses on ontological research, aiming to understand the nature of online education issues for international students during the pandemic, common issues in online education, and their relationship to international education.

The nature of reality is a significant concern. This study requires a clear ontological position. In this study, reality is perceived as relative and constructivist, as it is observed by stakeholders within the research context of social construction. The ontological questions of education precede the epistemological questions of education. The object of educational research and the paradigms adopted in educational research originate from ontology (Norwich, 2020). Ontology focuses on the existential conditions that are intricately linked to material, social, cultural, and political settings. Therefore, the relationship between epistemology and ontology gains significant importance. In essence, understanding the connections between knowledge and the circumstances under which it is generated, as well as the interplay between facts and values, has become paramount (Ejnavarzala, 2019).

Therefore, this study primarily seeks to understand the role or potential role of online learning in developing oral English skills for Chinese students engaged in transnational education from the perspective of Chinese international students. Many variables of interest in this study are subjective or qualitative, such as Chinese students' confidence, motivation, and the formation of friendships/relationships with people from the UK and other countries (Holliman *et al.*, 2024). Qualitative research

methods excel at capturing the lived experiences, perspectives, and meanings that individuals ascribe to their social worlds (Tenny, Brannan and Brannan, 2022). This is particularly relevant when exploring complex and multifaceted phenomena such as language learning in a cross-cultural setting, where quantitative methods may oversimplify or miss nuanced understandings. Besides, studies that have employed qualitative approaches to investigate online language learning have effectively captured learners' motivations, attitudes, and challenges (Jusslin *et al.*, 2022). These studies have provided rich insights into learners' emotional and social experiences, highlighting the importance of considering these factors in understanding language learning outcomes.

Therefore, qualitative methods are well-suited for examining these concepts. Thus, this study is qualitative, interpretative, and ethnographic, allowing for an in-depth exploration of the experiences of the research subjects.

Epistemology concerns the nature of knowledge and how we understand and learn about social reality. It helps us comprehend the processes and methods of thinking, as well as the sources and limitations of human knowledge (Ejnavarzala, 2019). From an epistemological perspective, humans are social beings, and communication among humans is a social process (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017). The social nature of humans assumes the possibility and realizability of understanding language within a shared language world. Interpretative epistemology acquires knowledge by allowing individuals to express their observations, and then interprets meaning by seeking to understand their perceptions within a broader research context.

5.3 Research Paradigm

Paradigms represent a distillation of what we think about the world. Our actions in the world, including actions that we take as inquirers, cannot occur without reference to those paradigms: "We think, so do we act. (Lincoln and Guba, 1985, p.15)"

The term "research paradigm" refers to the accepted theoretical, methodological, and evaluative principles and standards of research. It is reflected in the research methods, discourse methods, and academic evaluation criteria of a discipline. The disciplinary paradigm represents the unity of content and methods within a discipline, while the research paradigm is the methodological part of the disciplinary paradigm. Guba and Lincoln (1994) provided their own interpretation of the term "paradigm" seeing it as a fundamental framework or worldview that acts as a compass for researchers. They underscored the significance of having a clear understanding of the paradigm underlying any given research, as it determines the research's objectives, driving forces, and anticipated outcomes (Guba and Lincoln, 1994, p. 116).

"It is important to note that paradigm issues are crucial, and because of this, a researcher should be clear about what paradigm informs and guides their research (Guba and Lincoln, 1994, p.116)."

This study is based on the social facts of online education during a specific pandemic period and adopts qualitative research methods to answer the overarching research question: "What role does online learning play in developing oral English skills for Chinese university students engaged in transnational education?" The following are key aspects of the research paradigm of qualitative research:

In qualitative research, the Naturalistic Paradigm is commonly used. Here, researchers document and observe phenomena as they naturally occur, without interfering with the situations of the subjects being studied (Given, 2008). This paradigm emphasizes understanding and interpretation of the research subjects based on their actual manifestations in natural environments, rather than artificially controlled experimental conditions. Unlike traditional quantitative content analysis, qualitative research cannot predefine hypotheses for hypothesis testing, as qualitative data often involve extracting and interpreting personal information with unique characteristics (Bryman and Burgess, 2002).

My study is on Interpretative Paradigms that aim to delve into and comprehend the personal experiences and interpretations of the subjects involved in the research. Researchers interact with the research subjects, collect rich data, and employ various Interpretative techniques (such as induction, deduction, and comparison) to analyze and interpret the data, revealing the internal logic and meanings of the research subjects (Denzin and Lincoln, 2000). The interpretive paradigm's ontological and epistemological foundations rest upon the belief that reality is socially constructed and relative. This means individuals can perceive and interpret the same reality differently (Hiller, 2016; Uzun, 2016). Ontologically, this paradigm suggests that there is not a single, objective reality. Instead, multiple realities are constructed through human experience and social interaction (Pascale, 2010). This perspective emphasizes that our world understanding is shaped by our experiences and the meanings we attribute to them. Consequently, reality is not a fixed entity but is continuously constructed and reconstructed through human activity (Bruscia, 2005). Epistemologically, the interpretive paradigm holds that knowledge is subjective and context-dependent. It asserts that understanding the world necessitates exploring the meanings and interpretations individuals assign to their experiences. As individuals perceive the world differently due to their social, cultural, and historical backgrounds, the knowledge they generate is inherently subjective (Pring, 2002). This paradigm prefers qualitative methods, which seek to comprehend the complexity of human behaviour and its underlying reasons, rather than reducing behaviour to rigid statistical data (Creswell, 2009). This study employs qualitative research to collect data within the naturalistic context of real online learning classrooms and participants, aiming to understand and interpret the role of online learning in developing oral English skills for Chinese university students engaged in transnational education.

In qualitative research, inductive reasoning is often utilized. This approach starts with particular instances and gradually develops more general theories and concepts by analyzing and contrasting similarities and differences across these instances (Holland *et al.*, 2010). This approach emphasizes theorizing from empirical data rather than

predefining theoretical frameworks. I believe that this method is particularly suitable for my research because it emphasizes the use of empirical data as the basis for theoretical development, rather than simply relying on predefined theoretical frameworks. Through inductive reasoning, I can deeply and meticulously understand the research topic, explore inherent patterns, themes, and relationships in empirical data, and thus promote the generation of new theories or the improvement of existing theories. This method allows me to explore and understand phenomena without imposing preconceived thoughts or theories. At the same time, the application of inductive reasoning also increases the openness and adaptability of my research. In the process of data collection and analysis, I may encounter unexpected discoveries or insights, which could challenge my initial assumptions or understanding of the topic. However, inductive reasoning encourages me to incorporate these unexpected findings into the developing theories and concepts, thereby gaining a more comprehensive and rich understanding of the research phenomena.

From a holistic perspective, qualitative research focuses on the holistic nature of the research subjects, considering not only individual characteristics and behaviour but also respecting the humanity, individuality, and social, cultural, and historical contexts in which individuals are situated. Therefore, any study involving factors such as personality, psychology, thinking, logic, motivation, desires, and intentions can be respected within qualitative research (Ushioda, 1994). In this research, I have focused on exploring the personality traits, mental health and wellbeing, and motivations of Chinese students studying online in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, aiming to explore in depth how these factors affect their online language learning behaviour. Given the complexity and subjectivity of these factors, using quantitative methods for measurement can be challenging, if not impossible. This complexity underscores the need for qualitative research methods. These methods can more accurately show how individual student differences impact their performance and success in the online learning environment, capturing the subtle variations and underlying factors behind their behaviour.

In qualitative research, methodological pluralism is commonly employed. This approach combines different research methods and tools, including but not limited to interviews and observations, to gather and process data. This approach helps reveal the complexity and diversity of the research subjects from different perspectives and levels. It is appropriate for my study, because in the online environment, I thoroughly observe and record the behaviour patterns of Chinese students, including verbal and non-verbal information like expressions and postures. The flexibility of interviews allows for a deep understanding of their individual experiences, providing lively and genuine material. Simultaneously, the interviews facilitate an in-depth dialogue with Chinese overseas students, helping to explore deep issues of cultural conflict and adaptation. By combining the subjective feelings gained from interviews with the objective behaviour recorded during observations, I can comprehensively and deeply analyze the experiences and strategies of Chinese overseas students during the pandemic from multiple perspectives.

In summary, the research paradigm of qualitative research emphasizes in-depth and detailed description and understanding of phenomena, focuses on the exploration of subjective experiences and meanings, and employs methods and techniques such as naturalism, interpretivism, inductive reasoning, holistic perspective, and methodological pluralism.

5.4 Research Methods

5.4.1 Interpretivism

Interpretivism is a research methodology positing that our understanding of reality is socially constructed, implying the absence of objective truth in the social world (Moon and Blackman, 2014). This perspective emphasizes that the meanings and interpretations of social phenomena emerge from subjective human experiences and social interactions. For instance, Pulla and Carter (2018) discuss the role of constructive hermeneutics in the scientification of social work, underscoring

interpretivism's significance in understanding social phenomena. Additionally, Tarnoki and Puentes (2019) provide a comprehensive overview of social science research frameworks and paradigms, including interpretivism, further illustrating its importance in the field.

Since the 1970s, cultural anthropologists have been significantly influenced by the interpretative approach represented by Clifford Geertz (Sullivan and Rabinow, 1979). Geertz, with his emphasis on symbols, texts, and language, initiated what is now known as 'interpretative ethnography' through his works in 1973 and 1977. His discussions on 'thick descriptions' and 'webs of significance' heralded a new era in ethnographic research (Alexander and Smith, 2011).

Anthropological interpretation revolves around constructing an understanding of events. The goal of such an interpretation is to guide people towards a deeper comprehension of the matter at hand. Geertz states:

"Believing...that man is an animal suspended in webs of significance he has spun...I take culture to be those webs, and the analysis of it to be therefore not an experimental science in search of law but an interpretative one in search of meaning. It is explication I am after, construing social expression on their surface enigmatical."
(Geertz, 1973, p.5)

Accordingly, culture is a web of meanings crafted by people, and its analysis is not the pursuit of laws through experimental science, but the quest for meaning through interpretative science. It was his view that culture is public, because "meaning is" and systems of meanings are what produce culture, because they are the collective property of a particular people (Geertz, 1973). Understanding a nation's culture involves recognizing its characteristics and commonalities. Ethnography, therefore, seeks to explain how a social group communicates and interacts. This understanding should go beyond surface observations, delving into the background and reasons for behaviour and events. Such elements should be contextualized within daily life and

correlated with individuals' words, actions, and experiences at specific times and places. Consideration should also be given to customs, social activities, behavioural patterns, and societal rules. By doing so, we can gain a deeper understanding of culture, transforming what may initially seem difficult to grasp into something easier to comprehend.

Researchers using interpretative methods study people's behaviour and the cultures they inhabit to discover the meaning and understanding behind human behaviour. They emphasize the consideration of various factors when researching a specific phenomenon in order to place social meaning or construction within a specific context (Mack, 2010). In this study, interpretative research is used to explore the role of online learning in developing oral English skills for Chinese international students engaged in transnational education. The study focuses on a specific period (the pandemic period), a specific culture (Chinese international students), and a specific social context (the UK HE context/remote UK HE context). This study can be considered an interpretative study that seeks to provide a rich understanding of Chinese students' oral English skills and transnational education through an in-depth exploration of their experiences in online learning. This approach helps reveal the importance and challenges of online learning for Chinese international students in integrating into transnational education, as well as their achievements and difficulties in developing oral English skills.

5.4.2 Ethnography

The term ethnography is derived from two roots: "ethno" meaning "a cultural group" "a nation" or "a group of people" and "graphein"- the Greek, meaning 'to write'. In anthropology, the term refers to a description of the life of a nation or a cultural group (Harrison, 2014). Researchers typically gather data through participation or in-depth interviews, with a focus on qualitative data collection (Mohajan, 2018). Ethnography is thus a qualitative research method that centres on observing and recording subjects within their cultural context, encompassing people, events, time, location, and objects.

As an active participant, my observations and experiences in the UK provided valuable firsthand insights which informed me of my study. Through daily interactions, I have found that students were often open to sharing their thoughts and feelings with me, seeing me as part of their group. This trust enabled me to gain a deeper understanding of their genuine experiences. My observation notes (see Appendix 1) me to integrate the students' perspectives with my own, leading to a comprehensive, authentic, and nuanced understanding of their experiences.

In essence, using ethnography as a method to study the Chinese international student population has offered me as the researcher a means to gain a deep understanding of their culture, values, lifestyles, social interactions, and more. Specifically, ethnographic methods can help researchers to:

Understand Cultural Differences: Chinese international students come from cultural backgrounds that differ significantly from those whose experience is of the UK education system (Spencer-Oatey and Dauber, 2019). Their values, behaviour, and communication styles may not align with mainstream UK norms. Ethnographic research can provide valuable insights into these cultural differences, revealing how they influence Chinese students' experiences in both online and offline transnational learning environments.

Explore Social Networks: Forming new social networks is essential for Chinese international students in the UK. Ethnographic methods enable a detailed understanding of their interaction patterns with local UK students, other international peers, and University staff. This can shed light on how these interactions shape their personal identities and sense of belonging. By observing interactions within digital environments, ethnographic research can reveal how online platforms (such as Zoom or Microsoft Teams) influence students' identity formation and sense of belonging. In the absence of face-to-face interactions, the online environment may alter the way international students form relationships and integrate into academic communities (Soracco, 2023). Moreover, digital spaces can either exacerbate or alleviate challenges

related to isolation, cultural differences, and social connections, offering deep insights into how virtual interactions shape personal and academic identity development (Soracco, 2023). This is particularly relevant to a study exploring issues surrounding Chinese international students, as evidenced by the responses from my participants.

Identify Challenges and Opportunities: Chinese international students in the UK face multiple challenges, including language barriers, cultural differences, and psychological stress, which may negatively impact their study abroad experience (Liu, Li and Zhang, 2022). However, these challenges are accompanied by certain opportunities, such as the potential for expanding their international perspective through cross-cultural interactions, and contributing positively to personal growth and academic progress. In the context of online language learning, particularly since the COVID-19 pandemic, new challenges have become more evident. These include technical difficulties in the online learning environment, social isolation due to the lack of face-to-face interaction, and decreased motivation stemming from insufficient self-discipline in autonomous learning. At the same time, online learning offers flexibility in scheduling, broad access to digital resources, and the reduction of geographical constraints, allowing some students to better balance academic and personal commitments. A thorough ethnographic analysis of these issues can more comprehensively identify and assess the challenges and opportunities faced by Chinese students in both traditional and online language learning environments, providing educational institutions with valuable insights for developing more practical support strategies and interventions (Jensen *et al.*, 2022). The core objective of online language learning should be to help students better adapt and enhance their learning experience, ultimately improving their overall effectiveness in this learning environment (Ayu, 2020).

Integrating interpretivism with anthropology to study the experiences of Chinese students in online language learning offers significant advantages. Interpretivism focuses on understanding individual perceptions, while anthropology emphasizes the

influence of cultural and social contexts on behaviour (Heng, 2020). These two approaches complement each other, enabling a deeper, multi-faceted understanding of Chinese students' cognitive processes and learning experiences in online language learning, while taking their cultural backgrounds into account (Miller and Horst, 2020).

In international online language learning, this approach is especially valuable. Online learning presents challenges such as the lack of face-to-face interaction, increased demands for self-discipline, and potential technical difficulties, but it also offers flexibility and access to global resources. Using an interpretive-anthropological framework, researchers can better analyze how students navigate these challenges and seize opportunities, providing valuable insights to educators aiming to improve online language learning outcomes.

Secondly, this integrated approach deepens the scope of the research. Through the lens of interpretivism, I was able to explore Chinese students' thought processes, emotional responses, and values in relation to their online learning experiences, particularly in the context of education. At the same time, anthropological methods revealed the ways in which the socio-cultural environment shaped their learning behaviour and the development and formation of their identity.

Thirdly, combining interpretivism and anthropology enabled me to highlight the diversity of perspectives. Both approaches acknowledge that people's understanding and interpretation of the same phenomenon can vary greatly. Therefore, this combined methodology allowed me to uncover the diverse viewpoints and interpretations of Chinese students in online transnational education, and to investigate how these variations impact their learning outcomes and overall experiences.

Finally, the integration of interpretivism and anthropology offers practical insights. Both methods prioritize applicability and relevance, enabling researchers to provide

targeted recommendations for students, schools, educators, and related institutions. These insights have helped me to better address the needs and challenges of Chinese students in online transnational education, ultimately with the aim of supporting their academic success and personal well-being.

5.5 Sampling

In social science research, qualitative research is highly regarded for its ability to thoroughly investigate specific situations or groups. Unlike quantitative research, which uses random sampling and large sample sizes to validate hypotheses and quantify variable relationships, qualitative research aims to understand the intricacies and dynamics of phenomena. It uncovers the profound meanings behind people's behaviour and experiences through data collection methods, such as interviews, observations, and text analysis. This study adopts qualitative research methods to gain a deeper understanding of the oral language learning of Chinese students at a university in the UK. Qualitative research typically does not employ random sampling, primarily due to its research objectives and methods (Mweshi and Sakyi, 2020). To achieve this goal, this study uses purposive sampling.

Purposive sampling, also referred to as purposeful or selective sampling, is a widely adopted method in qualitative research. This approach enables researchers to intentionally select participants who align with specific criteria based on the nature of the research questions, expected outcomes, and practical aspects of the study (Ritchie, Lewis and Elam, 2013; Oribhabor and Anyanwu, 2019). By employing purposive sampling, researchers can obtain detailed insights from individuals who possess relevant knowledge or experience needed to address the research questions, thereby fostering a more in-depth understanding of the phenomenon under investigation (Merriam and Tisdell, 2009; Creswell and Clark, 2011; Robson and McCartan, 2016). Nonetheless, purposive sampling has certain limitations. Data gathered using this method may be subject to bias due to the unique characteristics, experiences, or

motivations of the participants, which can impact the findings' reliability. Additionally, given that the research is often centred around specific cases, the generalizability of the results is likely limited (Robson and McCartan, 2016). Nevertheless, the methodological literature suggests that, with a clear acknowledgement of these limitations, purposive sampling remains a valuable tool in qualitative research, providing meaningful insights into complex phenomena.

In this study, the aim is to gain a deep understanding of the experiences of Chinese students in an online learning environment abroad and explore their unique experiences in areas such as cultural adaptation, learning challenges, language development and interaction patterns. By purposefully choosing a university in Scotland with close collaborations with several Chinese universities, I gained access to a diverse student population. These students were studying different subjects at various levels, enabling me to gather rich and in-depth information.

To achieve the research objectives, I conducted two rounds of participant recruitment, corresponding to two stages: online classroom observation and one-on-one in-depth interviews. Prior to the classroom observation stage, I contacted the lecturers of two summer online courses at different English proficiency levels at the university which was the site of this study, and obtained permission to observe the classes. In the course introduction sessions, I explained the research purpose and significance in detail to all the students and invited interested students to participate. After obtaining informed consent, I conducted multiple classroom observations, documenting students' learning behaviour, interaction patterns, and teaching methods. The observation field notes are available in Appendix 1.

The participants in the class observations in this study were from different levels of pre-university study English preparatory courses, referred to as Group A (2 participants, A1 and A2) and Group B (7 participants, B1 to B7). Group A consisted of 4 students preparing for a Master's degree, who enrolled in the course while in China and did not know each other before the course started. Group B, which consisted of 8

students in total, was made up of university lecturers from China who were preparing for a PhD at the host university in the UK. Some of them were already familiar with each other before the course began. The group included lecturers from various disciplines, with some teaching English, others teaching Chemistry, and a few working in administrative departments.

The difference in familiarity among students may have had some impact on data collection, particularly regarding oral communication performance in the online classroom. Positive peer interactions, teacher support, and strong supportive relationships are key factors in promoting learners' willingness to communicate. For example, Lee (2020) points out that these supportive dynamics not only help create a positive learning environment but also encourage learners to actively engage in language use, which is essential for language acquisition. Compared to the relative unfamiliarity among students in Group A, students in Group B, who knew each other beforehand, may have felt more comfortable during discussions, resulting in more natural and active participation. This could have led to higher levels of interaction and engagement being reflected in the data for Group B, which may not necessarily be fully applicable to less familiar groups. Therefore, caution was exercised when interpreting the data.

This difference in familiarity was also influenced by the research context. The study was conducted during the UK summer break, and the only courses available were the Business English course (Group A) and the PhD preparatory course (Group B), all of which were delivered online due to the COVID-19 pandemic. The original aim of the study was to compare the changes in oral proficiency and learning attitudes of the participants between the early stages (Group A and Group B) and the mid-stages (interviews) of their study abroad experience. To ensure diversity in the data collected, participants were selected from different academic backgrounds, professional roles, and varying levels of familiarity with each other. This included students with different

levels of English proficiency and students from various disciplines, which provided a wide range of perspectives and experiences for a more comprehensive analysis.

It was intended that these participants would successfully complete the language courses and proceed to their degree programmes in the UK. In reality, none of the participants from Group A progressed to the new semester, possibly due to a combination of factors such as personal circumstances, visa complexities, and changes in academic or career plans. In contrast, several members of Group B successfully enrolled at the same university, likely because they had clearer long-term study goals. As a result, only two participants from the classroom observation stage were retained for the one-on-one interviews: B1 (coded as P11) and B6 (coded as P14), indicating that these students participated in both the classroom observation and the interviews. The coding of the participants is as below:

The List of the participants		
Observation Group A	Observation Group B	Interview
A1	<u>B1</u>	P1
A2	B2	P2
-	B3	P3
	B4	P4
	B5	P5
	<u>B6</u>	P6

	B7	P7
		P8
	-	P9
		P10
		<u>P11</u>
		P12
		P13
		<u>P14</u>
		P15

Before conducting the interviews, I provided each participant with an overview of the study and informed them in advance that the interviews would be audio-recorded, but not videotaped. This approach was adopted to ensure data protection and anonymization, maximizing participants' privacy and the security of their information. Each interview was conducted individually online using a predetermined interview schedule guide (see Appendix 7). Based on participants' responses, additional questions were asked to explore their attitudes towards online learning, experiences in transnational learning, and oral performance in more depth. To help interviewees overcome communication barriers and express their ideas more smoothly, a flexible language interview strategy was employed.

Cortazzi, Pilcher and Jin (2011) highlight the multiple benefits of conducting interviews in participants' native language. They argue that this approach typically enables participants to be more open, relaxed, and expressive, ultimately yielding

richer or more accurate information. This viewpoint underscores the importance of language in the interview process, especially for gathering in-depth and detailed information. Conducting interviews in participants' mother tongue helps to eliminate language barriers, allowing them to express their thoughts and feelings more freely. Each participant was given the option to choose the language of the interview (English or Mandarin Chinese) according to their preference and proficiency.

To achieve systematic and ethical data collection, participants were recruited in two stages: the first stage involved students observed in the classroom (two students, P11 and P14), and the second stage involved contacting Chinese students from various academic levels and programs through the university's email system (13 participants, P1 to P10, P12, P13 and P15). I specifically sought participants who had attended live online classes during the COVID-19 pandemic. Students who expressed interest were provided with detailed information about the study, including the research background, objectives, interview process, expected duration, participants' rights, and privacy protection measures. Participants were free to decide whether to participate, with no consequences for refusal. Relevant interview participant information documents are listed in Appendix 10.

In qualitative research, adherence to key ethical practices is essential. Researchers are expected to ensure informed consent, maintain confidentiality and privacy, follow the principle of beneficence, and demonstrate honesty and integrity throughout the research process (Kang and Hwang, 2021). After obtaining informed consent, the interview language was adjusted according to participants' preferences. An outline of interview questions was also provided beforehand (see Appendix 7), which enhanced transparency and allowed participants to better prepare for the topics that would be covered.

All interviews were conducted via online platforms such as Zoom in consideration of COVID-19 health and safety protocols, to minimize transmission risk and ensure the safety of participants and the researcher. Each interview lasted approximately 20

minutes to one hour, with the duration adjusted based on participants' engagement and the depth of discussion. Researchers are expected to adhere to ethical standards, including honesty, integrity, accountability, transparency, and compliance with professional norms (Wiest, 1989). These principles emphasize the responsibility of researchers to implement safeguards that protect participants from potential harm, such as psychological or physical discomfort, social harm, or threats to their safety (Kang and Hwang, 2021). In compliance with the University's ethical requirements and to ensure data accuracy, all interviews were recorded with participants' permission and supplemented with my detailed interview notes (available in Appendix 2). During the interviews, I used non-leading questions and avoided subjective guidance as much as possible to ensure the authenticity and objectivity of the data.

As a certified translator, my qualifications equip me to provide accurate and reliable translations. I have a firm grasp of both the source and target languages, which includes sensitivity to subtle cultural nuances, essential for maintaining authenticity and precision. Additionally, as a researcher, my background and academic focus inevitably influence my translation approach. My comprehension of the subject matter enables me to interpret interviewee statements more deeply, resulting in translations that are both faithful and contextually accurate. However, I recognize that my role as a researcher can introduce potential biases. To mitigate this, I strive to remain objective and impartial in the translation process, strictly refraining from incorporating personal interpretations or assumptions. This careful balance allows me to faithfully represent the participants' true intentions, maintaining the accuracy, objectivity, and reliability of the data by adhering to rigorous translation practices.

It is also essential to note that translation involves more than mere linguistic conversion; it requires attention to semantic, contextual, and cultural fidelity (Li, 2022). As Ryan (2020) explains, literal translation, or direct translation, is often used to ensure the precision of translated material, as this method emphasizes adherence to

the structural and linguistic specifics of the original text, preserving its meaning without additions, omissions, or changes. Lomaka (2017) supports this viewpoint, noting that literal translation aims to maintain the exact contextual meaning of the source without any alterations. However, Ryan (2020) also points out that while literal translation prioritizes accuracy, it may sometimes produce expressions that seem awkward or unnatural in the target language. This can occur when a direct translation does not account for the linguistic conventions and cultural differences of the target language or when there is a lack of equivalence between specific words or phrases in both languages.

The majority of the interviews were conducted in Chinese, as participants felt it allowed them to express their views more comprehensively. The total duration of the interviews was 5 hours and 34 minutes, averaging approximately 26 minutes per interview. Following the interviews, the contents were transcribed and translated into English (see Appendix 2) for participants to review and confirm the accuracy of the content. The transcriptions were then securely stored in a Word document on an encrypted computer to ensure data protection and confidentiality.

The rationale for recruiting participants in two stages, conducting research in two phases, and the benefits this approach brought to the study are detailed in the following section, Research Instruments (5.6).

5.6 Research Instruments

As a PhD student, I occupied the role of an "insider" in my research due to my in-depth understanding of the lived experiences and challenges faced by Chinese international students. This insider status allowed me to gain participants' trust more easily and facilitated access to the research field. According to Kanuha (2000), participants are often more willing to share their experiences when they perceive that the researcher shares a common understanding with them. However, being an insider also presents challenges, such as the risk of bias or over-identification with

participants, which may compromise the objectivity of the research (Asselin, 2003). To address these concerns, I implemented strategies such as reflexivity, regularly reflecting on my position within the research context

At the same time, I also held an "outsider" status in relation to my participants, as I did not know them personally or have specific knowledge of their individual circumstances prior to the study. According to Fay (1996), outsiders can maintain a more objective perspective, though they may face difficulties in gaining trust and accessing deeper data from participants.

The concept of the "space between" proposed by Aoki (1996) and Kanuha (2000), challenges the traditional binary distinction between insider and outsider roles. Researchers often inhabit a middle ground, neither fully insider nor fully outsider, and this space provides a unique vantage point. This dual status allows researchers to benefit from both roles: insiders can leverage shared identity to gain deeper insights, while outsiders may offer fresh perspectives that insiders might overlook.

As Dwyer and Buckle (2009) note, the "space between" disrupts the binary division of roles in qualitative research, recognizing the complexity of researchers' identities. Newman and Benz (1998) further argue that similarity and difference coexist in the research process, rather than being mutually exclusive. This duality enabled me to maintain objectivity while also gaining a deeper understanding of my participants' backgrounds and experiences.

5.6.1 Insider Research - Online Observation

In the field of ethnographic research, the identity positioning of the researcher, whether as an insider or outsider of the research field, has a significant impact on the research process. The researcher, as a participant observer or listener, is at the heart of the research and needs to reflexively consider how their position inside and outside the research field shapes their research results (Paechter, 2013). Traditional views

regard ethnographic researchers as external observers, entering different cultures and capturing their core characteristics through participant observation. However, in the past thirty years, research perspectives have gradually shifted to situations where researchers are part of the research group, which has sparked discussions about researchers conducting research as insiders, outsiders, or a combination of both (Eppley, 2006). Insiders, due to their close connection with the research field, can familiarize themselves with the field quickly and are more likely to identify and understand patterns in culture and personal meaning (Stephenson and Greer, 1981). One of the research advantages of insiders is that they easily gain acceptance from research participants (Dwyer and Buckle, 2009), especially in environments with similar backgrounds and races. The researcher's membership promotes the establishment of acceptance and trust between them and the participants (Dwyer and Buckle, 2009). In contrast, for outsiders, integrating into the research group and building a trusting relationship may be a more challenging and time-consuming process.

In the first phase of this study, a non-participatory, ethnographic, insider research classroom observation method was used. I acted as a complete observer. A complete observer adopts an open attitude, minimizes their influence on the classroom environment as much as possible, and accepts all possibilities of the observed phenomena. From the interpretivism perspective, observers should actively immerse themselves in the observation environment. They should also maintain critical introspection about potential biases and expectations. This is to ensure that these preconceived notions do not influence the behaviour or attitudes of the students or teachers in the classroom; strive to capture all important activities occurring in the online classroom, including teacher-student interaction, student participation, use of technology, etc.; and meticulously record the observed phenomena. The aim was to gain a deep understanding of the classroom culture, interaction patterns, and other aspects by observing teaching activities and student behaviour. This method

emphasizes my deep involvement and observation of the classroom to obtain authentic and comprehensive data.

The observations were focused on two different levels of online English preparatory courses offered by a Scottish university in 2021 (specific details will be discussed in Chapter 6). The students participating in these two courses were Chinese international students receiving remote online education from the UK while located in China, engaging in transnational education through online learning.

The objective was to observe and compare the authentic behaviour of participants in their online classrooms. By selecting two groups of courses with different English proficiency levels, the aim was to conduct a comparative investigation and discover more comprehensive issues in online classrooms. The observation period was from July to August 2021.

Observation is one of the fundamental ways for humans to understand the world around them and an important tool for scientific research. Observation is not just about perceiving things but also depends on the observer's perspective (Chen, Wang and Xie, 2011). Field observation can be classified in various ways, such as participant observation and non-participant observation, covert observation and overt observation, static observation and dynamic observation, structured observation and unstructured observation, exploratory observation and validation observation, long-term observation and short-term observation, and other forms (Chen, 2000). Observation is used as a research method in two different ways - structured and unstructured (Pretzlik, 1994). In empirical research, structured observation is a discrete activity aimed at recording physical and verbal behaviour. The observation schedule is predetermined using a classification system based on known theories. On the other hand, unstructured observation is used to understand and interpret cultural behaviour. Observers using the unstructured approach usually enter the field without preconceived concepts of discrete behaviour they might observe (Mulhall, 2003). Before entering the online classroom observation, I did not set specific

expectations or behaviour categories. I was just an open observer, ready to record any cultural behaviour or social interaction that might occur among the Chinese international students. Next, I entered the online classroom, observing their communication methods, language used, and expressed emotions. I recorded any interesting or important phenomena observed. This could include specific teacher-student dialogues, group discussions among students, and textual information in the Chatbox. After the observation ended, I conducted an interpretative analysis of the recorded phenomena. I attempted to understand the cultural significance, social rules, or emotional expression behind the observed behaviour.

Ethnographic classroom observation differs from traditional classroom observation. Traditional classroom observation is often conducted by external observers who use preset observation tools or scales to record and analyze specific aspects of the classroom. Ethnographic classroom observation, on the other hand, places more emphasis on the subjective experience and in-depth understanding of I. It focuses on grasping the overall situation of the classroom and conducting in-depth exploration. An insider researcher shares characteristics with the participants, such as gender, ethnicity, or culture, while an outsider researcher does not share these same characteristics (Mercer, 2007). Insider research refers to research conducted by individuals who have direct access to and experience of the culture or context being studied. Adler and Adler (1994) argued that insiders are more familiar with the group being studied and the issues faced by that group. Bonner and Tolhurst (2002) suggested three advantages of being an insider researcher. First, an insider can better understand the research problem. Second, they do not disrupt the flow of internal social interactions within the system. Finally, they can obtain authentic data from participants because they can establish good relationships with them.

As an insider researcher, it is essential to fully immerse oneself in teaching activities and observe student performance. I am qualified to be an insider researcher for several reasons. Firstly, my diverse educational background includes four years of

undergraduate education in China, traditional postgraduate education in the UK, as well as online and offline doctoral education in the UK. This allows me to examine research questions from a cross-cultural perspective and conduct comparative analyses of online learning experiences under different educational systems. Secondly, I experienced online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic, giving me a deep understanding of the topic and insights into the challenges faced by research subjects in similar contexts and their coping strategies. Additionally, I share the identity of Chinese international students with the research subjects, and we have the same Chinese cultural background. This cultural resonance helps me gain a deeper understanding of their values, attitudes towards learning, and behavioural patterns.

Through multiple observations of the research subjects' online courses, I have collected a wealth of research data. To ensure ethical considerations, the classroom observations were recorded in the form of field notes instead of audio or video recordings (see Appendix 1).

Field notes are utilized by researchers to observe and record their dense involvement in the lives of others (Emmerson, Fretz and Shaw, 2011). Their primary purpose is to objectively and comprehensively document what transpires, as many details may be forgotten throughout the study. Recording is crucial in qualitative observation as it involves transforming phenomena into words and capturing factual content. After each observation, I standardized the format of the observation records, recorded the observed data, and saved it in a Word document for subsequent analysis. These field notes also served as a foundation and guide for designing interview questions.

5.6.2 Ethnographic Online Semi-Structured In-depth Interview

Interviews are a crucial method of data collection in qualitative research and serve as a complementary approach to the initial phase of the study. The research focuses on Chinese international students who engaged in online learning at a university in Scotland, either in the UK or in China, during the year 2021. The participants include

undergraduate, master's, and doctoral students, providing a comprehensive perspective from different academic levels. The interviews took place between September and October 2021. At this time, the Chinese students had completed the language preparatory courses in the UK, and passed the International English Language Testing System (IELTS) exam with a score of 6, an English Language proficiency test developed and run by the British Council in partnership with IDP Education and Cambridge Assessment English, and started their formal degree programs in the UK (Read, 2022).

For this research, semi-structured one-to-one interviews were conducted. This approach allowed for a certain level of control over the interview structure while also providing flexibility to adapt the process and content based on the actual situation. Thirteen open-ended interview questions were designed based on the data obtained from the first phase of classroom observations. These questions aimed to elicit participants' insights on adapting to the British education system, cultural differences, and language barriers during the pandemic. The interviews were conducted online, either in Chinese or English depending on the participants' preferences, to facilitate comfortable expression of their thoughts in the chosen language. Each interview took place in a one-to-one online format and lasted between 30 to 60 minutes. The interviews were transcribed verbatim, and the transcripts were sent back to the interviewees for content confirmation before entering the data analysis process.

Interviews are widely used in qualitative research as they provide valuable insights into individuals' perspectives, understandings, and experiences of specific phenomena (Ryan, Coughlan and Cronin, 2009). Unlike surveys, interviews offer a more flexible approach, allowing participants to express their viewpoints in their own language and concepts (Kendall, 2008). Furthermore, interviews provide an opportunity to capture students' subjective accounts of their online learning experiences, complementing the data obtained through online observations, such as participants' thoughts, emotions, and physical states.

As a form of conversation, interviews differ from everyday conversations in that they have specific purposes and rules, with unequal power dynamics between the interviewer and the interviewee (Merriam, 2009). The interviewer determines the content, style, type, and duration of the conversation (Bernard, 1988). Moreover, interviews are collaborative processes in which both parties mutually construct "facts" and "actions". Thus, interviews are not an "objective" process of learning from each other but a subjective process of mutual exploration, interaction, and coordination (Chen, 2000). This study employed a semi-structured interview approach, which is more flexible and informal, resembling a free-flowing conversation. The primary goal was to gather as much useful information as possible through semi-structured interviews.

Compared to traditional face-to-face interviews, online interviews offer significant flexibility and adaptability, particularly when geographical constraints prevent in-person meetings. In the context of this study, the COVID-19 restrictions made face-to-face interactions impossible, making online interviews an effective and practical solution to ensure the study could proceed without compromising participant safety or data collection quality. With travel restrictions in place, face-to-face interviews became impractical, and online interviews emerged as the only viable alternative, enabling qualitative research such as this research to continue.

The primary advantage of online interviews lies in their flexibility in terms of time and location, as they can be arranged at the convenience of both parties without logistical concerns (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2002). Remote interviews also save travel costs and facilitate interaction across different geographical locations and time zones (King, Horrocks and Brooks, 2018; Hewson, 2007). Additionally, the online environment enables participants to participate in interviews in familiar settings, such as their homes, reducing the anxiety of speaking with strangers and leading to more candid responses (Lo Iacono, Symonds and Brown, 2016).

However, online interviews also have limitations. The primary issue is the difficulty in capturing non-verbal cues, such as body language and facial expressions, which typically provide emotional depth in face-to-face interviews. Additionally, technical issues such as unstable internet connections can disrupt the interview process and affect data collection (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018; King, Horrocks and Brooks, 2018). Another potential limitation is the inability to ensure that all participants conduct the interviews in an appropriate environment, which may lead to distractions or background noise, thereby affecting the quality of the data collected. As discussed in Chapter 7, some students attended online classes from locations such as taxis or shopping centres.

In conclusion, despite certain limitations, online interviews offer an effective alternative for conducting research under pandemic-related restrictions and were therefore selected as the preferred method for this study. While challenges exist, by addressing these issues appropriately, researchers can still gather valuable insights under different conditions, demonstrating the adaptability of research methodologies.

This study conducted interviews with Chinese international students who studied in the UK or participated in online courses from China. The aim was to gain insights into their experiences of online learning abroad/at home and compare them with their experiences in China. The interview responses revealed the students' academic growth during their study abroad and demonstrated their attitudes towards oral English skills, self-awareness, and social integration in a cross-cultural environment. These insights contributed to a comprehensive understanding of the role of online learning in developing oral English skills for Chinese university students engaged in transnational education. The findings from the interviews also helped identify issues and improvement directions for the online learning experience.

5.6.3 Key Advantages of the Two-Stage Research Design

In Biesta's (2012) work, he explores the sequential combination in mixed research methods, a research design model where "one method follows another". In this design, one method is typically employed first, and based on its results, another method is designed or implemented. Biesta emphasizes a model in which qualitative research is conducted first, followed by quantitative research. The aim is to use qualitative data (e.g., interviews, observations) to gain a deep understanding of the research phenomenon, form hypotheses or research frameworks, and then use quantitative methods (e.g., questionnaires, tests) to validate or further explore these hypotheses.

My own study, drawing on Biesta's results, adopts a sequential combination of "qualitative analysis followed by quantitative analysis", which significantly contributes to the depth and trustworthiness of the research. Firstly, classroom observations in the initial stage provided a foundational understanding of the online learning environment and any interaction patterns that emerged among the Chinese participants, though these patterns were generally limited, as online learning tends to be less conducive to interactive engagement. This macro-level observation revealed classroom dynamics, teaching methods, and the challenges students faced in real-time online settings. By observing participants in real online learning environments, I was able to identify a series of key issues, such as communication barriers, differences in students' oral participation, and technical problems they experienced. These observations not only provided valuable insights for answering the research questions but also directly influenced the design of the interview questions for the next phase. For example, classroom observations revealed that students participated in online classes from different locations, leading to the design of the question: "Where do you usually take online classes—at home, in the office, or somewhere else? How do you think your physical location affects your online study?" Furthermore, although issues such as slow response times during online activities by the students and lecturers, and challenges related to screen sharing, arose during class, no students pointed them out, prompting the interview question: "Compared with face-to-face classes, what responsibilities do you think students should take in online courses?" Additionally,

the observation that some students used Chinese when communicating with teachers and peers led to the question: "What do you think about using Chinese during class this phenomenon?" These specific examples illustrate how the first stage directly led to the second, ensuring that the interview questions were more targeted and relevant to observed learning behaviour.

Secondly, classroom observations served as an important resource for designing interview questions for the second phase of the data collection for this study. The observations offered a broad contextual foundation, ensuring that the interview questions were more precise, targeted, and relevant. The context encompasses the overall learning environment, as well as the behaviours and patterns observed during the online classes.

This approach enabled me, as the researcher, to explore in-depth topics such as language barriers, peer interaction, and cultural adaptation. By tailoring the interview questions where possible based on the participant's behaviour during the classroom observations, the interviews generated more meaningful and insightful discussions, ensuring that the interview questions probed into the experiences and perspectives identified in the first stage.

Thirdly, one-to-one semi-structured interviews enabled personalized and detailed exploration of the participants' learning experiences in this unique context. While the classroom observations in this study provided a broad overview of general trends, the interviews allowed participants to elaborate on the specific challenges they faced, both in terms of learning and their personal perspectives within this learning context. The combination of observational data and personalized interviews ensured that the research was able to capture both the general patterns of student behaviour and the nuanced experiences of each participant. The interviews were able not only to support the participants in providing deeper personal insights but also to offer opportunities to validate or expand upon the findings from the first stage, further strengthening the rationale for the two-stage research design.

This two-phase research design, therefore, combined macro-level observations with micro-level individual interviews, significantly enhancing the credibility and reliability of the study. It enabled me to conduct multidimensional and multi-level analyses, ensuring that I gained a comprehensive understanding of the research topic while providing a more robust framework for exploring the complexity of participants' perspectives on students' online learning experiences. By combining the macro perspective from classroom observations with the micro perspective from interviews, the study was able comprehensively to explore students' online learning experiences.

However, it is important to acknowledge the potential limitations of this two-stage design. First, relying on online platforms for research, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic, presented certain challenges, such as the time zone difference between China and the UK is 7 hours during daylight saving time and 8 hours during standard time; technological limitations, and participant availability, all of which affected the scheduling and smooth execution of data collection. To address these challenges, flexible interview arrangements were adopted to ensure that each participant could take part at times which were suitable to them. Despite these limitations, I was able to ensure that the research design maintained rigour and comprehensiveness through flexible adjustments, ensuring an in-depth investigation into students' online learning experiences.

5.6.4 Designing Interview Questions Based on Key Observations

In studies on teachers' pedagogical content knowledge, researchers often combine classroom observations with interviews to capture teaching practices and explore the decision-making processes behind them. Barendsen and Henze (2019) utilized classroom observations to document teachers' instructional methods and followed up with interviews to delve deeper into the rationale for their pedagogical choices. This approach not only highlighted what teachers did in the classroom but also uncovered the reasoning behind their instructional strategies, offering a more

comprehensive understanding of teaching practices. This study adopted a similar methodological framework for data collection and analysis.

Based on the analysis and summary of classroom observations from Group A and Group B, several key observation themes emerged: online course arrangement of teaching components and teacher feedback, the impact of technology and environment, student engagement, and the relationship between first language interference and oral proficiency. Using these themes, 13 interview questions (attached as Appendix 7) were generated to further explore how online learning influenced the development of oral English skills in Chinese university students engaged in transnational education. I demonstrate, below, how the key observation themes informed the design of these interview questions:

5.6.4.1 Observation Theme: Course Arrangement and Teacher Feedback

The observations highlighted how course structure and teacher feedback significantly impacted students' oral proficiency. Through thoughtful course design and targeted feedback, students had opportunities to use and practise their spoken English, which was critical to improving their skills. As previously noted, the classroom learning experiences of Chinese students often limited their opportunities for engaging in oral discussions. Traditional cultural factors in China, such as the concept of "face" contributed to students' reluctance to speak up during class, I was aware, as a Chinese student, that they may be anxious about fearing making mistakes that could lead to embarrassment. Therefore, interview questions were crafted to explore students' perceptions of course design and teacher feedback.

Question 2: Please tell me about your online learning experiences with UWS.

(This question provided insight into the overall impact of course structure and teacher feedback on students' learning experiences.)

Question 5: What did you think were the benefits of taking online classes? Please be specific.

In what ways were online courses helpful during your transnational period of study at UWS?

(This explored how the online course format supported students' language learning in a cross-border context.)

In order to gather participants' reflections on their experiences in pre-English course language programmes (or pre-doctoral programmes), I asked the following question.

Question 8: How do you feel about the current arrangement of online programmes for international students at the beginning of their studies?

(This question delved into students' feedback on the initial course arrangements and how well these facilitated their transition to online learning.)

Question 12: Did you think online courses would satisfy your experience transitioning to studying in the UK?

(This question assessed whether online courses effectively supported students in preparing for their transition to studying abroad.)

5.6.4.2 Observation Theme: The Impact of Technology and Environment

The observations revealed that technology issues (such as unstable internet) and learning environments (such as studying at home or other inappropriate places) significantly impacted students' ability to participate and engage in oral communication. Questions were designed to explore how these factors affected students' learning experiences and language practice.

Question 3: Where did you usually take online classes—at home, in the office, or somewhere else?

What did you think about the physical location during your online study?

Were there any ways in which your physical location affected your ability to study online?

(These questions investigated how students' learning environments influenced their participation and performance in online classes.)

Question 6: What challenges did you face in taking online courses in China/UK?

How did you overcome them?

Did you ever encounter technical problems in online courses? If yes, please give examples.

How did you think this kind of problem affected you?

(These questions explored how students navigated technological challenges and how these impacted their engagement.)

Question 7: In what ways did online courses provide you with a good opportunity to practise speaking? Why?

How often did you have to use spoken English in class?

(This question aimed to understand whether students had sufficient opportunities to practise speaking English in online courses, despite technological or environmental limitations.)

Question 9: Compared with campus-based classes, what responsibilities do you think students should take in online courses?

(This question assessed how students perceived their responsibilities in managing challenges related to technology and environment in online learning.)

5.6.4.3 Observation Theme: Student Engagement and the Relationship Between First Language Interference and Oral Proficiency

The observations indicated that student engagement and the use of first language (Chinese) during class discussions affected oral proficiency development. Students who actively participated showed better oral proficiency, while those relying on their first language showed slower progress. Interview questions were designed to explore student engagement, language use, and learning preferences.

Question 4: What did you think were the differences between online and campus-based classes? Why?

Did you prefer online classes or campus-based classes?

Which learning mode did you think would be more effective for you?

(This question helped assess students' preferences for learning modes and how these preferences might affect their ability to develop oral proficiency.)

Question 10: Please share your communication experience with teachers and classmates during the online course.

In my first stage of observation for this research, I observed some online lessons, and I noticed that some students spoke Chinese to the teachers and other students during the lessons. What did you think about this phenomenon?

(This question explored students' thoughts on the use of their first language during English-speaking courses and its impact on language acquisition.)

Question 11: What kind of class mode did you think was more suitable for you—online, offline, or a combination of online and offline? Why?

(This question helped to determine which learning format students found most effective for improving their oral English proficiency.)

5.6.4.4 Observation Theme: Personal Background and Other Insights

Understanding students' personal backgrounds and additional comments about their online learning experiences helped contextualize their responses and offered a more comprehensive picture of their learning challenges and needs.

Question 1: Please tell me something about yourself and your academic/professional background.

(This introductory question provided background information to better understand the student's learning context.)

Question 13: Was there any aspect of your online study experience during the transitional period from China to the UK that you would like to comment on that we have not covered today?

(This open-ended question allowed students to express additional thoughts or concerns that may not have been addressed in the previous questions.)

The interview questions were developed based on key themes that emerged from the fieldnotes I made during observations of Group A and Group B, ensuring a focused exploration of the role of online learning in developing students' oral English skills. The questions addressed several critical aspects, including the way in which the online learning course was delivered, teacher feedback, technology and environment, student engagement, first language interference, and personal background. This approach aimed to provide comprehensive insights into students' experiences and the challenges they faced in an online language learning setting.

5.7 Data Analysis

In this study, thematic analysis (TA) functioned as a flexible and robust qualitative research tool, essential for systematically identifying, analyzing, and interpreting patterns or themes within the dataset. The foundational nature of TA allows it to operate independently of specific theoretical frameworks, making it adaptable across diverse research paradigms and disciplines. This versatility is why TA has been widely used in fields like psychology, education, and health research, providing a nuanced yet structured description of qualitative data (Braun and Clarke, 2006).

TA's flexibility accommodates both inductive (data-driven) and deductive (theory-driven) approaches. In inductive analysis, themes are allowed to emerge organically from the data, particularly beneficial when exploring under-researched topics. Deductive analysis, however, is directed by pre-existing frameworks, enabling researchers to investigate data through a particular lens. Many studies, including this one, combine these approaches to capture the data's richness comprehensively (Braun and Clarke, 2013). Moreover, TA is applicable across varied research designs, sample sizes, and data collection methods, from small case studies (Cedervall and Åberg, 2010) to extensive datasets (Mooney-Somers, Perz and Ussher, 2008).

Researchers such as Xu and Zammit (2020) underscore that TA supports systematic data analysis while documenting the research process transparently. Nowell *et al.*, (2017) highlight that using a structured coding framework enhances credibility and rigour by providing clear evidence trails. In this study, the TA's adaptability was fundamental for the in-depth exploration of participants' perspectives, offering a richer understanding of their experiences and motivations.

Despite TA's strengths, it has limitations. The flexibility of TA can lead to inconsistent application, risking arbitrary theme selection and superficial analysis (Antaki *et al.*, 2002). To avoid these pitfalls, researchers must clearly define their methodological choices, theoretical assumptions, and coding decisions to enhance the analysis's transparency, credibility, and replicability (Holloway and Todres, 2003). Additionally, a common misconception is that themes naturally "emerge" from the

data. Braun and Clarke (2006) emphasize that the researcher plays an active role in interpreting and choosing themes, which should align with the research questions and theoretical frameworks rather than appearing passively. Without acknowledging this interpretive role, analyses risk becoming vague and lacking depth, necessitating a reflective approach for meaningful theme extraction (Taylor and Ussher, 2001).

While TA's flexibility is beneficial, it may not suit all qualitative research designs, especially those that require strict adherence to theoretical frameworks, such as grounded theory or discourse analysis (McDonald and O'Callaghan, 2008). However, for this study, TA's flexibility proved invaluable in capturing the nuanced responses of participants in semi-structured online interviews.

Thematic analysis is rooted in deconstructing data into smaller, meaningful units and organizing these into broader themes aligned with the research questions. As described by Braun and Clarke (2006), TA facilitates systematic organization and in-depth interpretation of data. Holloway and Todres (2003) affirm that "the matizing meanings" is central to qualitative research methodologies, marking TA as an essential tool in this domain.

The thematic analysis process typically follows several coding stages. Initial open coding involves identifying meaningful concepts, phrases, or sections of text. In the next stage, selective coding, these concepts are grouped into broader themes. The final stage, theoretical coding, connects the data to existing theories or generates new insights, providing a structured understanding of the data. This multi-stage approach enhances data clarity and deepens the analysis.

The TA method employed in this study closely aligns with the approach by Brown and John (2022) in their research on a Doctoral Induction Programme at a Scottish university. Adopting Yin's (2015) five-phase cycle—compiling, disassembling, reassembling, interpreting, and concluding—this approach allows emergent themes to shape the analysis. Bazeley (2009) advocates for this recursive method as it enables a

flexible exploration of participants' experiences and identities. Following this model, this study systematically analyzed the interview and classroom observation data, providing insights into participants' oral learning and communication experiences in online education settings for international students.

By identifying subtle patterns within the data, this research illuminates the complexities of participants' oral learning and communicative experiences in online educational settings. The thematic analysis finding working grid (see Appendix 8) served as a critical tool in this process, facilitating a structured and organized approach to theme identification. This framework allowed for systematic categorization of codes and themes, providing transparency in theme development and ensuring the rigour and validity of the analysis.

5.7.1 Analyzing data from Online Observations

The online observation conducted in the first phase is crucial for understanding the background of this study and identifying the challenges faced by Chinese students in developing oral English skills. Through this observation process, I explored the core difficulties that Chinese students encounter in online English language learning during the COVID-19 pandemic. The classroom serves as the primary setting for observing participants' learning attitudes, oral application abilities, and interaction. I documented not only the participants' speaking, interaction, and problem-solving strategies in detail but also paid special attention to their cooperation and communication with teachers and classmates.

The analysis of the field notes I made during classroom observations was conducted through a systematic and meticulous process. The following steps were undertaken to ensure thorough and rigorous analysis:

I commenced by thoroughly reviewing all field notes to ensure a comprehensive and accurate understanding of the recorded information. I highlighted key observation

findings, such as specific learning behaviour, recurring interaction patterns, and notable events or turning points relevant to the research questions. These included student participation, teacher questioning strategies, technical issues, first language interference, and behaviour across different learning environments. Specific occurrences, such as students' English proficiency, technical disruptions, and the use of their first language to facilitate understanding, were extracted for further analysis.

To conduct a deeper analysis, I systematically assigned initial codes to each observed behaviour or phenomenon based on the study's objectives. For example, frequent use of first language was coded as 'the role of L1' and technical problems were categorized under 'technical issues.' By applying consistent codes, I was able to group related behaviour and phenomena, identifying emerging patterns across the field notes. Recurring observations highlighted differences in student English proficiency and varying levels of classroom participation motivation. These were grouped under broader categories such as 'student English proficiency' and 'classroom participation motivation.' I also noted the influence of teacher feedback and questioning strategies on student engagement, which informed the development of related themes.

After consolidating the codes, I categorized them into six overarching themes (themes as below), that encapsulated the key phenomena and challenges students faced during online learning. These themes offered a comprehensive understanding of the dynamics of student engagement, as well as the complexities and challenges inherent in online education.

Observation themes	
1	Student English Proficiency and Teacher Questioning

	Strategies	
2	Student Motivation in Classroom Participation and Oral Expression	
3	Advantages and Challenges of Chinese Online Learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Relationship between Online Learning Tools and Learning Efficiency and Interaction ● Issues with Reading in Online Learning ● Location of Online Learning
4	Technical Issues	
5	The Role of L1 in Online Learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Unconscious/Subconscious Use of L1 ● Conscious use of L1
6	Informal/Peer Learning	

Throughout the analysis process, I maintained a reflective and critical thinking approach, considering possible biases, limitations of the research, and the reliability and significance of the analysis results in a broader context.

5.7.2 Analyzing data from Semi-structured Online Interviews

Through in-depth interviews, a substantial amount of data was collected. Thematic analysis was applied to the qualitative data collected via semi-structured online interviews, using MAXQDA software to ensure a systematic and rigorous analysis process.

MAXQDA, a well-known qualitative data analysis tool, offers a range of tools for coding and categorizing data, identifying patterns, and creating visual representations of the findings. The thematic analysis began by importing the interview transcripts into MAXQDA, where meaningful concepts and sections were identified. These were then grouped into larger categories during selective coding. MAXQDA's "code system" helps organize categories and subcategories effectively, with constant comparisons between data segments and established categories to ensure consistency and distinction. In the final stage, theoretical coding links the coded data to existing theories or develops new theoretical explanations. MAXQDA's "memos" function was used to document theoretical reflections and compare them with the coded data, ensuring that the evolving theories sufficiently explained the data.

In the process of analyzing the interview data from 15 participants, I began by systematically reviewing the transcripts of each interview. I initially identified key aspects related to the participants' experiences with online learning, which were then organized into specific codes. The initial coding process involved the creation of several key categories such as academic background, models and processes (e.g., class mode preference and teaching process), attitudes and motivation for online classes, online class participation issues, learning environment, data collection, experiments, and exam-related experiences.

After this stage of coding, I refined and grouped similar codes, leading to more focused thematic categories. For instance, the benefits of online learning emerged from discussions on satisfactory and positive views, rich learning resources, ease of self-study, low-pressure adaptation, and flexible study processes, which were ultimately categorized under one broader theme. Additionally, codes related to

language use (such as oral proficiency, oral English practice, and L1 usage) as well as social and transnational experiences (which involved aspects like school department, education and cultural differences, transnational learning, informal learning, part-time jobs, and internships) were identified and grouped accordingly.

Once the codes were sufficiently categorized, I then synthesized them into broader themes to encapsulate the key findings of the interviews. Ultimately, eight major themes were formed:

Online Interview themes		
1	Advantages of Online Learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Flexibility and Safety in Online Learning ● Enhancing Teaching with Digital Features
2	Student Feedback on Blended Learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Interaction, and Enhanced Learning Outcomes ● Choices and time management challenges
3	Challenges of Institution-led Online Learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Challenges for Teaching Quality ● Issues Around Interaction, Cultural and Social Capital in Online Learning
4	Evaluation of Institution-directed Online Learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Mental Health and Social Challenges in Online Learning ● Impact of Study Environment on Learners'

		<p>Focus</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Self-directed Learning and Attendance Issues in Online Learning <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Time Management Challenges ◆ Motivation and Discipline in Online Learning ● Ensuring Network Stability and Technical Literacy in Online Learning
5	Autonomy in Online Learning and Blended Learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Benefits and Challenges of Video and Recording Features ● Benefits and Challenges of the Subtitle Feature ● Enhancing Learner Autonomy in Online Learning
6	Motivation for Online Oral Expression	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Motivation for Learners' Oral Expression and Shifts Towards Independent Learning ● Educational and Cultural Influences on Oral Expression ● Factors Influencing Motivation for Oral Expression

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Differences in academic disciplines ◆ Emotions, Confidence, and Stress Factors in Online Oral Participation ◆ Cultural Background and the Role of Social Capital in Communication Preferences ● Participation and pseudo-participation ● Balancing Silent and Oral Communication: The Dual Role of the Chatbox in Online Learning
7	Use of L1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Conscious Use of L1 ◆ Attitudes of students towards Using of L1 ◆ Attitudes of lecturers towards Using of L1 ● Unconscious Use of L1
8	Further Challenges of Online Learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Issues Regarding the Security of Assessments in Online Presentations ● Network Restrictions and Time Zone Challenges Affecting Oral Participation

5.8 Reliability and Transferability

Lincoln and Guba (1985) suggest four interconnected principles for assessing trustworthiness: credibility, which ensures the interpretation is genuine and findings accurately reflect participants' views; audibility, allowing for verification of the research process; confirmability, ensuring the research findings are reliable and can be replicated; and transferability, facilitating the application of research findings to other contexts.

Reliability is an important consideration in qualitative research as it refers to the consistency and stability of research findings. A study is considered reliable if it can produce the same or similar conclusions under the same or similar conditions. To enhance the reliability of this study, I employed triangulation by comparing data from observation field notes and interview scripts. This ensured the stability and consistency of the results (Lincoln and Guba, 1985; Merriam, 1998).

Triangulation is a method used to test the credibility of qualitative research. Its purpose is to verify conclusions by using data or personnel from multiple sources, thereby obtaining the maximum truthfulness of the research findings (Chen, 2000). In this study, multiple sources of data were collected, including classroom observations and interviews, and different data were cross validated. I sought to understand the same issue from different perspectives and contexts and compared the results. I also paid attention to both verbal and non-verbal behaviour of the participants to judge the consistency of the data they provided. Additionally, the coding was discussed and revised multiple times throughout the research process, resulting in the final coding of this study.

Transferability in qualitative research refers to the extent to which research findings, interpretations, and conclusions can be applied or transferred to similar backgrounds or settings. To establish transferability, researchers need to provide detailed and rich descriptions of their research activities, hypotheses, and the background of the

research being conducted. This includes comprehensive descriptions of research design, data collection methods, analysis techniques, and Interpretative frameworks used to understand the data. By providing a comprehensive description of the research process, researchers enable readers to assess the potential applicability of the findings to their own backgrounds.

As Lincoln and Guba (1985) pointed out, the goal of transferability in qualitative research is not to make generalizable assertions, but to provide enough detail for readers to assess the potential applicability of the findings to their own backgrounds.

This study documented detailed research design and methodology. The selection of appropriate research design and methodology is crucial to ensure the transferability of the research. Furthermore, Guba and Lincoln (1985) recommended a technique for establishing transferability in qualitative research, which involves providing "thick descriptions" of phenomena. Thick description means that researchers provide detailed descriptions of experiences and information gathered during the data collection process. In this study, I strived to objectively and accurately record the reality in classroom observation notes and interview transcripts, which helps readers understand the context in which the research findings were derived and increases the transferability of the research results.

5.9 Ethical Considerations

Britton (2020), Smith and Smith (2018), and Thomas (2022) emphasized the importance of adhering to ethical standards in research, especially when it involves the rights and interests of individuals affected by the research subject. In studies involving human subjects, obtaining ethical approval is essential to ensure the protection of participants from physical and mental harm, as well as to safeguard their safety and rights. Before collecting data for this study, I submitted an application to the university and obtained ethical approval from the research ethics committee (Appendix 9). The application process involved sending relevant

documents to the participants of the classroom observations and interviews and obtaining their signatures. These documents included a participant information sheet (see Appendix 3 and 4) and a research informed consent form (see Appendix 5 and 6).

After obtaining ethical approval from the university, I communicated the research information to the participants using a mixed-method approach, sending them bilingual (Chinese-English) research introductions electronically. This was done to ensure that Chinese students fully understood the research content, familiarized themselves with the research process, and addressed any limitations in their English proficiency. This bilingual approach provided participants with the opportunity to fully comprehend the research information and subsequently sign the informed consent form.

In this study, I followed the five ethical principles proposed by Hammersley and Traianou (2012): minimizing harm, respecting autonomy, protecting privacy, providing reciprocity, and treating participants fairly.

Autonomy and informed consent of participants: Before the study commenced, it was ensured that each participant fully understood the purpose, methods, potential risks, and their rights in the research. This ensured that they voluntarily participated in the study with full informed consent. To protect the privacy of participants, several measures were taken. For instance, in the data collection process, which involved one-on-one interviews and internal observation records, I ensured the removal of any personally identifiable information from the records. This step is crucial as it guarantees the non-disclosure of participants' identities, thus avoiding harm to them. During the internal observation stage, I only observed those participants who signed the consent form, and the behaviour of other participants who did not sign the consent form was not recorded. During the interview process, I respected the autonomy of each participant and encouraged them to voluntarily share their study abroad experiences. This ensured that participants were not coerced into sharing information. Additionally, I emphasized the right of the interviewees to withdraw at any time

before the interview began. This is an important ethical consideration as it ensures that participants are fully aware of their rights and can make decisions about their participation in the study. Close attention was also paid to the emotions of the participants during the interview, and the interviews were conducted after negotiation and completion. This is because participants should not be subjected to any undue pressure or discomfort during the research process. As a recognition of the participants' contributions, I provided each participant with a detailed research report and a summary of the findings. This helps them understand the research findings and their significance and provides them with references for their learning and development.

Regarding the equal protection of rights, confidentiality of the participants was ensured by storing to ensure the confidentiality of participants, their personal information, such as names and contact information, was stored separately from interview records and written records. All documents related to this study, including draft versions of the thesis, observation records, interview records, etc., were stored in electronic (restricted) secure folders on password-protected devices, which only I and my supervisor could access for necessary analysis and research work.

Through these measures, I ensured strict adherence to ethical standards in the research, fully protecting the rights of the participants. This not only enhances the reliability and effectiveness of the research but also establishes trust and cooperation with the participants. These practices are crucial in promoting responsible and ethical research and provide valuable references for future academic research.

5.10 Conclusion

In this chapter on methodology, the main focus is on the series of methods, tools, and their theoretical foundations and application methods used in the research process. Here is a summary of the content:

Firstly, the chapter elaborates on the research paradigm, including naturalism, interpretivism, and inductive reasoning. These paradigms provide the theoretical foundation and guiding ideas for the entire research, determining the direction and focus of the research. Then, the ontological and epistemological assumptions of the research are introduced. The ontological assumptions mainly explore the way knowledge is formed, i.e., how knowledge is constructed through the interaction between the individual and his/her environment. The epistemological assumptions focus on how we understand and recognize social reality, emphasizing the social construction of knowledge or reality understanding. These assumptions provide a basis for the choice of research methods and data analysis.

In the research methods section, the focus is on online observation and semi-structured in-depth interviews. Online observation allows researchers to gain an in-depth understanding of students' real behaviour and interaction in the online learning environment, while semi-structured in-depth interviews can capture students' profound views and feelings about online learning experiences and the development of oral skills. Regarding sample selection, the chapter describes the process of using purposive sampling methods to ensure that the selected participants meet the research purpose and requirements, thereby increasing the representativeness and effectiveness of the research.

Furthermore, the research tools, including the internal researcher's online observation and semi-structured in-depth interview guidelines, are introduced. These tools provide specific methods and guidance for data collection, ensuring the accuracy and reliability of the data.

In the data analysis section, the chapter provides a detailed explanation of the application of qualitative survey methods, including data collection, coding, classification, and interpretation. Through comparative analysis of online observation and interview data, researchers can gain a deep understanding of the impact of online learning on students' development of oral English skills.

Finally, the chapter also emphasizes the reliability and transferability of the research. By providing detailed and rich descriptions and ensuring the ethics of the research, researchers strive to ensure the accuracy and applicability of the research results, making them extendable to other similar situations or groups. The data results from this chapter will be important for comprehending the role or potential role of online learning in developing oral English skills for Chinese students engaged in transnational education. These findings will be further discussed in Chapters 6 and 7.

Chapter 6: Findings from Online Classes Observation

6.1 Introduction

This comprehensive study is centred on the active involvement of Chinese students in transnational online learning. Breaking down the research into two distinct parts, this chapter is dedicated to the presentation of findings derived from the first part. The initial part of the research required an in-depth observation of online class sessions, providing a unique perspective into the world of remote learning.

The observations, carried out meticulously in the year 2021, took place during the height of the global COVID-19 pandemic. The setting for these observations was a large university in the west of Scotland, UK. As the pandemic enforced extraordinary circumstances, leading to the widespread shutdown of physical campuses worldwide, it compelled educational institutions to transition towards the medium of online learning. Therefore, the focal point of my observations naturally gravitated towards online courses.

The prevailing circumstances at the time rendered face-to-face teaching impossible, thus restricting the research's scope to traditional classroom teaching interaction. However, this unique situation offered a silver lining in the form of an unprecedented opportunity to explore the real-world impacts of online teaching in a comprehensive manner. During the pandemic, educational institutions, including universities, showcased their adaptability by swiftly modifying their teaching modes to ensure the seamless continuation of courses online for Chinese students. This swift transition enabled students to maintain their educational journey in China without any delay in their academic progress, even before they set foot on their formal campus in the UK.

The participants of this study were enrolled in two levels of English preparatory courses, aptly named Group A and Group B. Group A consisted of pre-Masters students, and Group B consisted of pre-PhD students. In this chapter, I will delve

deeper into aspects pertaining to the observation process, the participants, and the structure of the courses. Furthermore, I will present my findings from this part of the study in a detailed manner.

In this study, my role was that of a non-participant observer, observing two online class groups. This method proved beneficial as it allowed me to collect valuable data without disturbing the flow of class discussions or activities, thereby maintaining the natural progression of the class. Prior to the commencement of the observation process, I ensured to explain my research objectives in detail to all students in both groups to foster transparency and a clear understanding of the research's purpose. Moreover, I encouraged students who were open to participating more actively in the research by signing participant information forms and consent forms.

In Group A, two students (identified as A1 and A2) willingly agreed to participate by completing the necessary documentation. Their agreement signified their consent to utilize their data in subsequent analyses, primarily focusing on their interactions and contributions within the online classroom environment. Similarly, in Group B, seven students (identified as B1, B2, B3, B4, B5, B6, and B7) volunteered their participation and signed the informed consent forms. Their active participation facilitated an in-depth study of their behaviour, interactions, and responses during observed classroom conversations.

It is essential to underscore that while all students participating in the classroom conversations were under observation, only those who explicitly agreed by signing the consent forms were included in special analyses related to participant behaviour. This approach is in line with ethical research practices, guaranteeing the privacy and protection of all students while enabling focused research on pre-selected participants. For each group, three online classroom observations were conducted to gain a comprehensive understanding of the online learning environment and student engagement. This methodology facilitated a thorough study of the dynamics of the online classroom, offering invaluable insights into student engagement, interaction

patterns, and overall classroom effectiveness.

Another crucial aspect that warrants mention is that no audio, video, or screenshots were recorded during the observation to adhere to ethical standards. Instead, my focus was on observing and recording participants' verbal interactions, their active participation in classroom activities, and their identification of phenomena in the online learning environment. The contents of these observations were meticulously recorded in handwritten field notes, then transferred to an electronic format and saved as a Word document on the researcher's encrypted computer. These materials will be used for data analysis in this chapter and further discussed in Chapter 8.

Students from Group A and Group B participated in online courses offered by a research-focused university. Notably, there were differences in English proficiency levels between the two groups. The selection of two groups with varying levels of English proficiency for observation was aimed at collecting more meaningful data.

Group A: Pre-intermediate English Preparatory Course (Master's level)

Group A was comprised of students who had registered for a foundational Business English online course, offered by the university. The central objective of this course was to enhance and develop critical business English skills. These skills span a diverse range of areas, listening, speaking, reading, and writing. The composition of this group was quite small, comprising only four students. Despite their basic understanding and grasp of the English language, their proficiency levels, as indicated by their IELTS scores, were not up to the mark. These scores varied from 5 to 5.5, which was lower than the minimum requirement of 6 as stipulated by the UK Visas and Immigration. Given this situation, it was quite possible that these students might face significant language barriers, particularly when dealing with more intricate topics during the online classes. The class sessions that were observed for this analysis were scheduled from 1:30 PM to 3:30 PM according to UK time, which would be 8:30 PM to 10:30 PM as per Beijing time. In the course of these observations, particular

attention was paid to two participants, referred to as A1 and A2.

Group B: Advanced English Preparatory Course (PhD level)

Group B focused on the university's PhD admission programme and aimed to enhance students' research skills for PhD studies. The course content covered topics such as research skills, academic writing, presentation skills for PhD candidates, and critical reading. Group B consisted of eight students, mostly university teachers in China. Their English proficiency met the English language entry requirements for international students (IELTS scores 6 or above), indicating a higher level of proficiency compared to Group A, but they did not all meet the university's requirement of 6.5 for PhD study. The observed class sessions were scheduled from 9:00 AM to 12:00 PM UK time during standard time and from 9:15 AM to 12:00 PM UK time for the third session. These corresponded to 5:00 PM to 8:00 PM and 5:15 PM to 8:15 PM Beijing time, respectively. In this study, the online teaching behaviours of the entire class were comprehensively observed and recorded. However, only seven students, identified as B1, B2, B3, B4, B5, B6, and B7, had voluntarily agreed to be directly involved in the data collection process and to have their interactions and responses specifically analyzed. The observation and data collection were conducted in strict adherence to ethical guidelines, ensuring the privacy, confidentiality, and informed consent of all participants.

The observations of Groups A and B contribute to understanding the role of online learning in developing Chinese university students' oral English proficiency and transnational learning. A further aim of this part of the study was to collect data that could inform the areas to focus on in part of the Interview. The observations provide a comprehensive picture of how students participate in transnational online classroom environments and offer a comparative analysis of their experiences compared to traditional campus-based learning. The data collected and the subsequent findings from this study will be systematically presented in the following subsections, adhering to the sequential order of the analytical steps undertaken.

6.2 Student English Proficiency and Teacher Questioning Strategies

This chapter has a specific purpose in mind. It aims to present a comprehensive picture of the raw field notes that have been collected meticulously throughout the observation research process. It also intends to conduct a thorough and detailed data analysis that pertains specifically to the two distinct groups' Student English Proficiency and Teacher Questioning Strategies. The primary objective of this chapter extends beyond merely identifying these strategies. The focus is not just to understand what these strategies are but to explore their interconnections and associations. This is done to understand their impact and influence on student proficiency in English. The aim here is not merely to understand these strategies in isolation, but to comprehend the interplay between them and how it impacts overall student performance. By doing so, I hoped to provide valuable insights and observations that can contribute significantly to the field of study. Through a detailed examination and analysis of the collected data, I aimed to provide a comprehensive understanding of the subject matter and contribute to its future development.

Observations in Group A

This was an online learning class led by the teacher. The teacher started the new lesson and asked some simple questions related to the topic, to which students only needed to answer 'yes' or 'no'.

When the teacher began teaching in English, it was observed that some Chinese students looked confused and seemed to not understand.

Observations in Group B

This was an online learning class with the teacher as a guide, focusing more on student-centred approaches and encouraging student participation. During the introduction of the new lesson, the teacher used keyword prompts to guide students to

answer questions using complex sentences. The teacher continued with further questioning, using language to encourage student thinking. Then, each student provided an oral definition of the learned concepts based on their understanding. Finally, the teacher guided all students to summarise the key points of the class.

The above observations suggest that students' oral English proficiency affects the difficulty and complexity of the teacher's questions. In Group A, the teacher asked simple 'yes' or 'no' questions, indicating that students' oral proficiency may be weaker and they may find it challenging to answer more complex questions. Nevertheless, the teacher continued to pose new questions to stimulate student thinking, encourage their oral responses, and provide practice. This phenomenon reflects the communicative nature of teaching emphasised by Stevick (1990) in humanistic learning, where teachers should facilitate students' oral language learning through controlled classroom interactions. Additionally, teachers adjust their instructional techniques based on students' proficiency levels to ensure active participation and understanding of the taught concepts (Argüelles and Anderson, 2007). The observed classroom interactions in Group A and Group B had distinct impacts on the overall learning environment and student engagement in the online setting.

In Group A, the limited nature of interaction, consisting primarily of simple yes/no questions, had a noticeable effect on classroom dynamics. This approach resulted in a largely passive learning environment where students were not encouraged to think critically or express their understanding beyond basic affirmations. When students lack meaningful interaction in the classroom, they often find it difficult to actively engage in class discussions or to delve deeply into the course content. This lack of engagement in online classes can hinder their cognitive development and affect their learning outcomes. Furthermore, the inability of students to effectively participate in interactions can generate a sense of powerlessness, negatively impacting the overall classroom atmosphere and leading to more passive roles for them in the classroom. This situation can trigger a harmful cycle: the absence of participation makes it

challenging for students to engage in in-depth discussions, which in turn reduces their motivation to participate, ultimately affecting their cognitive development and deep understanding of the learning material.

On the other hand, in Group B, the intentional use of student-centred strategies and keyword prompts to elicit complex responses had a significant positive impact on classroom interaction. This approach fostered a more interactive and dynamic learning environment where students were encouraged to actively engage with the material and each other. The subsequent oral definitions and summaries further enhanced this interactive process, enabling students to consolidate their knowledge, make connections between concepts, and receive immediate feedback from their peers and the instructor.

The contrast between these two groups underscores the importance of intentional classroom interaction strategies in online lessons. The limited interaction in Group A likely had a negative impact on student engagement and learning outcomes, while the more interactive approach in Group B promoted active learning and deeper comprehension. This analysis emphasizes that teachers need to carefully consider the impact of their classroom interaction strategies on student learning outcomes. They should design online courses that encourage meaningful interaction, stimulate student motivation, cultivate students' social capital, and promote active participation through intentional teaching practices. A core part of this approach is for teachers to fully consider students' English language proficiency levels, adjust teaching strategies accordingly, and ensure that students of different English levels have the opportunity to deeply participate and benefit from the provided educational experience.

This phenomenon reflects the constructivist learning theory emphasized by Piaget (1978), where the teacher's guiding role should gradually decrease, eventually allowing students to learn and think independently. Additionally, this phenomenon also aligns with the input hypothesis proposed by Krashen (1985), which states that if learners receive input slightly beyond their current level, it will promote language

learning.

As mentioned earlier, Group A students had lower oral proficiency compared to Group B students; the teacher in Group A specifically targeted oral proficiency and attempted to develop it openly, while the learning in Group B was focused by the instructor more on content (research skills, academic writing, etc.) rather than solely on students' oral proficiency. By comparing the analysis of Groups A and B, it can also be observed that Group B students had significantly higher participation and learning outcomes than Group A. Due to their higher level of English proficiency, the students in Group B were better able to benefit from the online classes, as evidenced by their use of more complex sentences when answering questions, indicating a deeper comprehension of the course material. Additionally, Group B students made a higher number of voluntary contributions and participated in discussions for a longer duration, suggesting greater interest and willingness to actively engage in classroom interactions.

In conclusion, students' oral English proficiency influences the difficulty and complexity of the questions posed by teachers. The teacher's questioning techniques are also important in classroom teaching as they can stimulate student thinking and participation, thereby promoting learning. Furthermore, in Group A, A2 had more active participation in the classroom compared to A1, which may be due to the teacher asking more questions to A2. The teacher likely had valid reasons for asking A2 more questions. They may have assessed A2's learning progress or identified areas needing improvement and thought that extra questions would provide useful practice and reinforcement. Alternatively, they may have noticed specific gaps in A2's understanding and used targeted questioning to address these issues. In both instances, the teacher's increased focus on A2 was probably meant to enhance the student's learning, not due to personal preference or bias. While A1 might not have shown the same level of engagement or responsiveness to questions as A2, leading the teacher to focus more on students who clearly benefit from direct interaction. Alternatively, the

teacher may believe that A1 has a preference for independent learning, and thus affords them a certain level of respect. Teachers need to be mindful of their biases and provide opportunities for each student to participate in classroom activities as much as possible (Samuels, 2018). Additionally, this section highlights the importance of teachers observing and recording student performance in order to more accurately assess their learning progress and potential needs, ultimately ensuring a positive transnational learning experience for Chinese international students.

6.3 Student Motivation in Classroom Participation and Oral Expression

Observations in Group A

Student A1 displayed low interaction in the classroom and rarely volunteered to answer the teacher's questions. In contrast, Student A2 demonstrated higher participation, answering questions more frequently and actively engaging in classroom interactions.

In the classroom, when the teacher asks a question, research indicates a trend where certain students appear more likely to wait for the teacher to call on them before answering a question, instead of proactively raising their hands. During group activities, it has been observed that some students, including those from Chinese backgrounds, may prefer to listen to the group leader's direction rather than volunteer their own ideas and suggestions.

At the end of the course, when the teacher announced that the English course was about to end and there were no plans for the following week, some Chinese students showed confusion as they might not have fully understood what the teacher meant. In this situation, the Chinese students did not take the initiative to ask the teacher questions or seek clarification, but chose to remain silent. This further reduced their opportunities to communicate with the teacher in class.

Observations in Group B

Students B1, B2, B3, B4, B5, B6 and B7 all answered the teacher's questions, providing opportunities for oral practice. B1, B2, B3 and B5 answered questions relatively more frequently in the classroom. During the communication, B2 and B3 displayed some language barriers. They attempted to express their thoughts in English, but often struggled to communicate fluently due to vocabulary or grammatical limitations.

B4 took the initiative to raise his hand and share his opinion. His in-depth and well-organised presentation demonstrated not only his level of understanding of the material but also, his active participation in classroom communication. This was also the case with B7, who was fluent in oral English and used more complex lexis and more low-frequency vocabulary.

In the group discussion session, students B1 and B2 communicated fluently in English with smooth dialogue and actively participated in the discussion. However, in their group, there was another Chinese student, B6, who spoke less throughout the discussion and listened most of the time.

Through observation, it can be seen that there are significant intra-group and inter-group differences in student engagement and interaction during class. In Group A, Student A1 showed low participation and rarely responded to the teacher's questions, while Student A2 displayed higher activity levels, answering questions and actively participating in class interactions multiple times. In contrast, students in Group B had overall higher engagement, with all students answering the teacher's questions at least once, gaining opportunities for oral practice. However, it is worth noting that within Group B, the performances of Students B1, B2, B3, and B5 stood out as they responded more actively to the teacher and participated more frequently than other students. This analysis reveals the uneven phenomenon of student engagement, indicating that within the same learning environment, student

participation can vary due to individual differences. For those students who are less proactive in classroom participation, the reasons can be referenced from the study by Rachel Zhou, Knoke, and Sakamoto (2005). This research found that Chinese students commonly reported low levels of classroom participation during the early stages of their studies in Canadian academic institutions, typically only participating when directly asked to answer questions or give presentations. Many students described their role in the classroom as "listeners" or "observers" finding it difficult to actively engage in classroom discussions. However, this "passivity" and silence in the classroom were not what they desired. In fact, they often felt uneasy and frustrated due to their inability to participate more in classroom discussions. Therefore, the data from this study reflect the individual differences among students, as well as the necessity for teachers to pay attention to each student's classroom participation.

In examining the performance of students B1, B2 and B6 within the context of group discussions, it is evident that notable disparities exist in terms of participation levels and communication proficiencies. Specifically, B1 and B2 have demonstrated remarkable fluency in English, coupled with a keen engagement in collaborative dialogue. Their capacity to articulate ideas seamlessly and engage dynamically with peers indicated a solid mastery of linguistic skills and confidence in expressing their viewpoints. Consequently, this level of engagement serves to enhance the overall vitality and cognitive depth of the group discussions.

However, a contrasting trend was observed in B6's participation patterns. B6 tended to have fewer verbal contributions, often assuming a more passive, receptive role within the group. While this behaviour may be attributed to various factors, it could potentially signal challenges in English proficiency or a lack of self-assurance when communicating in the target language. Additionally, it is plausible that cultural nuances may be influencing B6's participation style, possibly leading to a more reserved or cautious approach in collective discussions. It is imperative to emphasize that these observed differences do not inherently suggest inferiority in terms of B6's

cognitive abilities or knowledge base relative to B1 and B2. Instead, they highlight areas where targeted support and encouragement could significantly bolster B6's active engagement in future discussions. Online learning typically requires students to be more autonomous and actively engaged. Those inclined towards active participation, may excel in self-directed learning, adapt well to the independent learning environment, and find it easier to communicate and interact with other students or instructors through online platforms. However, some learners may struggle to participate due to various factors such as language proficiency, lack of confidence, or cultural differences. This could lead to them gaining fewer learning experiences or even feeling marginalized in online learning settings. In contrast, traditional classroom environments often provide more direct encouragement or pressure for students to participate actively. However, such encouragement and pressure may be lacking or less evident in online settings. Nevertheless, this does not imply that introverted or passive students cannot benefit from online learning. On the contrary, this learning environment may offer them a relatively low-pressure atmosphere, allowing them to participate and learn more comfortably. The key lies in providing appropriate support and encouragement to all students to ensure they can fully engage and benefit from learning. Customized approaches may be necessary to assist those who feel uncomfortable or marginalized in online environments, ensuring their integration and success.

To analyze the classroom oral expression motivation of participants in Groups A and B, I will refer to the L2MSS (Second Language Motivation Self System) theory mentioned earlier in 4.2.1, as well as the habitus theory mentioned in 4.4.

According to the L2MSS theory, students' motivation in language learning may be influenced by three dimensions: ideal L2 self, ought-to L2 self, and L2 learning experience. Based on the observed results, active participants in Group A and Group B may have strong "ideal L2 self" images, meaning they may have clear visions of their future selves using a second language, and these visions could provide a strong

motivation for them to actively participate in class. Moreover, their active participation may be related to their "ought-to L2 self", indicating they may feel a responsibility or obligation to reach a certain language level or meet specific language use expectations, which could have driven their learning engagement. Active participation might reflect these students' positive experiences in language learning, which could include effective teaching methods, a supportive learning environment, or good interactions with classmates and teachers, all of which could enhance their motivation to learn. Their displayed interests and goal-orientation might be vital components of their language learning motivation, thereby inspiring their active performance in class. It is worth noting that motivation is a dynamic concept that can change with variations in the learning environment, personal development stages, and external factors.

In contrast to the more engaged students, those who are less active in Group A and Group B might exhibit weaker motivation in one or more aspects of the L2MSS. However, it would be premature to attribute their lack of participation solely to a poorly defined L2MSS. There could be various reasons for their inactivity, such as a lower proficiency level in English, shyness, poor sleep quality, or even concerns about their appearance. While it is possible that their motivation may be affected by unclear goals or negative learning experiences related to second language learning, I cannot definitively conclude this based on the available data alone. Therefore, I must exercise caution in making assumptions about their motivational profiles and consider a broader range of potential factors.

From the perspective of habitus theory, student learning behaviour does not exist in isolation but is deeply influenced by past experiences and behaviour patterns. For those students in Group A and Group B who are active, they may have formed a habit of actively participating in classroom interaction over a long period of learning. This habit not only makes them more confident in class and willing to express their views, but it also further enhances their enthusiasm and motivation for learning. This positive

cycle makes them more calm and confident when facing new learning challenges.

However, for those students in Group A and Group B who are relatively less active, the situation may be just the opposite. They may have formed negative learning habits for various reasons (such as lack of confidence, lack of interest in learning content, fear of making mistakes, etc.). This habitus not only affects their class participation but may also weaken their learning motivation and confidence, causing them to fall into a vicious cycle of learning. It should be noted that while the habitus theory provides us with a perspective to explain the differences in student learning behaviour, it is not the only explanation.

6.4 Advantages and Challenges of Chinese Online Learning

6.4.1 Relationship between Online Learning Tools and Learning Efficiency and Interaction

Observations in Group A

In the classroom, the teacher asked students to download two files from the university Moodle site and gave them 10-15 minutes to read them on their own. During the reading time, almost all students turned off their cameras. Students independently accessed the websites to browse and download course reading materials and watch videos. In this process, it was not possible to directly observe the participation of the Chinese students.

After the teacher assigns online learning tasks, students often just browse the relevant materials on their own and rarely take the initiative to ask questions and share ideas with the teacher and other students. Their interaction with the teacher and other students is very limited.

In sections where expressing their own opinions is required, A1 would choose to express in text form through the Chatbox, rather than verbally.

Observations of Group B

The teacher instructed students to summarize their thoughts and input them into the Chatbox, allowing all students to view the responses.

After students finished reading the materials on the screen, the teacher asked them to use the electronic hand-raising function. Once all students raised their virtual hands, the teacher invited them to answer questions in a specific order.

After explaining the key points, the teacher encouraged students to use [Menti.com], an interactive website for real-time bullet voting. Students uploaded their answers to the website through the link shared by the teacher, and the website immediately displayed their responses.

When B3 encountered unfamiliar words while reading English in class, B3 used the computer's read-aloud function to get the correct pronunciation. This function not only helped B3 quickly grasp the pronunciation of new words but also improved his learning efficiency.

Student B7 prepared a presentation PowerPoint before participating in the online class and presented it to the entire class during the session. The presentation was engaging and interactive, featuring videos and images. Both the teacher and classmates provided positive feedback on the creativity and effectiveness of the presentation.

Achieving effective interaction between teachers and students, as well as among students in an online environment, is challenging. This is due to the loss or reduction of many non-verbal cues, such as facial expressions, body language, and tone of voice, typically present in traditional face-to-face communication. In Group A, despite the use of online learning systems and related websites for learning support, there was no evidence of real-time classroom interaction via online technology. This suggests a missed opportunity to establish close and effective communication. Although effective online learning tools, like university Moodle sites, can provide a rich array

of learning resources and convenient management features to aid students in studying more efficiently. The teacher asked students to download files from university Moodle sites and read them independently, but most students turned off their cameras during this time. This reflects, to some extent, that in an online learning environment, due to the lack of face-to-face communication and real-time supervision, students might be more easily distracted or lose interest. Turning off the camera could be a signal of the students' lack of active participation, indicating that they might not be fully engaged in reading the materials. Tobi, Osman, Bakar and Othman (2021) pointed out that in Google Meet classrooms, only a few students would turn on their cameras to greet the teacher when joining the class, then turn off their cameras when the course began. Sederevičiūtė-Pačiauskienė, Valantinaitė and Asakavičiūtė (2022) suggested in their research that teachers should explain the reasons for recommending the use of cameras in synchronous classroom sessions, and maintain transparency on how to enhance the learning experience with the use of cameras. They believe that encouraging students to use cameras in synchronous remote classrooms is vitally important for freshmen who are still cultivating learning habits and social networks.

In contrast, Group B experienced a positive impact from technology on classroom interaction. This could indicate that teachers and students used online tools more effectively for real-time communication, collaboration, and feedback. As a result, they created a more intimate and interactive learning environment. For example, the use of the Chatbox function encouraged active thinking and written expression of opinions, facilitating textual communication and discussion among students. The electronic hand-raising function allowed the teacher to easily monitor each student's progress in reading, improving classroom efficiency. The use of an interactive website made classroom interaction more dynamic and interesting, increasing student participation in online learning.

Based on the comparison between Groups A and B, it can be inferred that teachers design interactive activities based on students' English proficiency levels. Group B,

with higher English proficiency, fully utilized online technology to enhance classroom interaction. This suggests that online learning may be more effective for higher-level groups, as it can be more student-centred and cater to individualized needs. On the other hand, Group A students may benefit more from offline classroom instruction to improve their English proficiency, as teachers can employ different questioning techniques and motivate student participation more effectively.

The tendency of students, like A1, to express themselves in text within the Chatbox can be attributed to several factors. Firstly, A1's preference for written communication could stem from a history of using social media and instant messaging tools, resulting in less participation in face-to-face verbal interactions. This long-term practice has formed A1's habit of writing to express opinions. Secondly, written communication offers advantages such as convenience, precision, and the ability to edit, which aligns with A1's habits and reinforces their preference for this medium. When expressing opinions, A1 is likely to opt for a method that ensures accuracy and effectiveness. Another factor might be social anxiety or lack of confidence. Verbal communication requires instant responses, which can be stressful. If A1 has faced setbacks or negative feedback in past verbal interactions, they may prefer the safer option of written communication. Lastly, A1's educational experiences could also play a role. If their education emphasized written over verbal expression, they may be more comfortable organizing and expressing their thoughts in writing. This familiarity with written communication could lead A1 to favour it when sharing opinions.

In conclusion, observations of Groups A and B demonstrate that online learning tools offer several advantages, including:

Rich interactive features: Online learning tools such as Chatbox and electronic hand-raising encourage active thinking and expression of opinions, facilitating communication and discussion among students and between students and teachers. This interactivity not only makes the learning process more dynamic and interesting, but also enhances student engagement and learning outcomes. Interactive websites

such as [Menti.com] and other tools increase the visibility of learning topics, making knowledge presentations more three-dimensional and vivid. This presentation style stimulates students' interest and curiosity, enhancing their engagement in learning.

Personalized learning experience: Online learning tools, such as Chatbox for sharing and chatting, menti.com, and the vast array of internet learning resources to evaluate students' oral English proficiency.

Convenience and flexibility: Students have the convenience of accessing online learning platforms at any time and from any location, allowing them to watch videos, listen to audio, and access materials for previewing and reviewing. However, it is important to note that while the ability to study from anywhere is advantageous, if not used appropriately or regulated, it may pose obstacles to real-time online learning. This issue will be further discussed in detail in section 6.4.3 Location of Online Learning.

Diverse learning resources: Online learning platforms provide abundant electronic learning materials that students can download and use without additional costs. These resources not only enrich students' learning content, but also broaden their knowledge horizons.

6.4.2 Issues with Reading in Online Learning

Observations in Group A

The teacher shared PowerPoint slides and e-textbooks with small font sizes on the screen. As an observer, I found it necessary to enlarge the e-screen on my computer to see the full content. This may have been a challenge for students as well. However, none of the students proactively addressed this issue.

Observations in Group B

When the teacher shared PowerPoint slides on the online learning platform, the shared content was not fully visible on the screen. Some content was blocked, but the teacher may not have been aware that the slides were not fully visible and continued with the lecture. However, none of the students in the class proactively pointed out this issue.

In my observation of both Group A and Group B, I identified several issues related to the display of electronic learning materials. These included problems such as small font sizes and incomplete content display. These issues, while seemingly insignificant, may have posed substantial challenges for students in terms of readability, thereby potentially affecting their learning effectiveness. It is worth noting that traditional printed materials often have the advantage of facilitating focused attention, promoting deep thinking, and enhancing learning. However, electronic learning materials, despite their convenience and ability to present a wide range of content, can inadvertently create obstacles for students. These obstacles can range from minor inconveniences, like small font sizes on the screen, to major hindrances, such as the lack of clarity and completeness of shared content. These factors can negatively impact students' learning efficiency, motivation, and overall focus.

When confronted with the issue of poorly displayed text in an online classroom setting, the majority of students from both groups opted to endure the difficulties rather than actively communicate their concerns to the teacher. This phenomenon was particularly noticeable among Chinese students, whose reactions to such problems may be influenced by the distinctive principles of their cultural habitus.

From the perspective of Chinese cultural habits, it is mentioned in Section 2.3 on the Socio-cultural context of education in China that Chinese people are influenced by the "rites" in Confucian thought and have a sense of respect for their teachers. Therefore, students' reluctance to speak or ask questions in online classrooms can be attributed to their deep-seated respect for teachers and obedience to authority. In Chinese culture, teachers are held in high esteem, and seen as the disseminators of knowledge and symbols of authority. This high level of respect for teachers often comes with an

inherent sense of obligation to heed their instructions, which may deter students from taking the initiative to ask questions or provide feedback. Moreover, as highlighted in section 2.3 the concept of "face," referring to an individual's social dignity and reputation, plays a pivotal role in influencing student behaviour in Chinese culture. In a society where "face" holds significant value, students may harbour concerns that asking questions or drawing attention to issues could potentially lead to discomfort for the teacher or reflect negatively on their own perceived level of knowledge, thereby causing damage to both their own and the teacher's "face." This fear of "losing face" can consequently result in students choosing to remain silent, even when encountering difficulties with electronic learning materials.

In conclusion, while electronic learning materials provide convenience and a wealth of information, they also present certain display issues that could potentially impede students' reading abilities and overall learning effectiveness. Furthermore, the Chinese cultural norms of respecting teachers and the concept of "face" may impact students' propensity to actively participate and ask questions in class. Therefore, in order to enhance learning outcomes in an online environment, both teachers and students must be aware of these issues and strive to find effective solutions.

6.4.3 Location of Online Learning

Observations in Group A

During the scheduled class time from 1:30 PM to 3:30 PM UK time, Student A1 logged into the online class using a mobile phone at 2:56 PM. Background noises from a Chinese shopping mall could be heard during the class. When answering questions, A1 opened the front camera and microphone on their phone. However, after answering the question, A1 turned off the camera and microphone and did not participate further in the class. It can be inferred that A1 was participating in the online class from outside the shopping mall using their mobile phone.

Student A2 occasionally had the sound of a crying child in the background when answering the teacher's questions. The child would occasionally appear in front of A2's camera, and their voice could also be heard from A2's microphone during group discussions. It can be inferred that A2 was participating in the online class from home in the presence of while also performing childcare duties.

Observations in Group B

Participants B1, B2, B3, B4, B5, B6 and B7 were observed participating in the online class from their homes or offices, using a computer with a webcam. They all turned on their microphone when answering questions. There were no instances of children or other individuals interfering during the entire class.

By comparing the observation records of Group A and Group B, I can understand more deeply that one of the advantages often attributed to online learning is its flexibility, allowing students to study at different times and places. However, when I examine this flexibility in the actual learning environment, I may find that it is not always an advantage and may even bring a series of problems and challenges. As mentioned in 6.3 Student Motivation in Classroom Participation and Oral Expression, A1's class participation is weaker than A2's. This may be because A1 takes classes on his phone in the mall, facing more distractions than A2, who, although occasionally disturbed by a child in her learning environment, at least remains indoors, in front of her class electronic device. Meanwhile, students in Group B did not suffer from many external disturbances, so there were more students actively participating in class interactions.

From the perspective of the learning environment, Ellis (as cited in Section 3.4.2) emphasizes the importance of the environment in second language acquisition. In Group A, while the students enjoyed the flexibility of online learning, their learning environment appeared to be noisier and less stable compared to Group B. As observed in the classroom, A1 took the class on their phone in a shopping mall, and got

distracted by the surrounding noise; A2, studying at home, also got distracted by a child present, which likewise affected their learning. In contrast, Group B students studied in quiet homes or offices, which likely enabled them to maintain focus and a higher level of learning efficiency. And there seems to be a correlation between accessing the class with no distractions and being able to engage fully with the lesson.

In terms of learning motivation, the SLL2 perspective in the L2MSS theory (as mentioned in Section 4.2.1) suggests that executive motivation related to the learning environment and direct learning experiences can influence language learning. In Group A, students appeared to have less ability to focus attitude on online courses, potentially due to a lack of favourable learning environments and full preparation and engagement with the course. This attitude may weaken their learning motivation and subsequently affect their classroom integration. In contrast, Group B students seemed to value online courses more, actively creating conducive learning environments and fully participating in classroom interactions, indicating a stronger motivation and engagement in learning.

The interrelation between the learning environment and learning motivation should not be overlooked. A noisy and unstable learning environment may lower students' learning motivation, while a quiet and comfortable learning environment may enhance it. Additionally, students' learning attitudes and habitus can also influence their utilization of the learning environment and learning outcomes. Therefore, while online learning provides flexibility in terms of time and location, this flexibility may not always be an advantage. Without proper environmental and motivational support, this flexibility can lead to suboptimal learning outcomes for students. This calls for more thoughtful consideration and guidance from schools and instructors in promoting online learning.

6.5 Technical Issues

During the online classes in both Group A and Group B, several common technical

issues were observed:

The teacher's computer had slow response times and experienced lagging.

There were malfunctions when the teacher shared files on the screen, preventing successful sharing.

Both students and the teacher experienced slow internet loading speeds, resulting in asynchronous audio and video with noticeable delays.

Students' microphones malfunctioned, causing their voices to be inaudible.

When the teacher played videos, the video could be seen, but the audio was lost.

Observations in Group B

During a group discussion, B5 and B6 were placed together. B6's computer microphone had no sound. To complete the discussion, B5 and B6 used WeChat voice calls on their mobile phones. With their flexible and quick response, the group discussion was successfully conducted.

In the subsequent rearrangement of the group discussion, B1, B2, and B6 were placed in the same group. Since B6's microphone still did not work, B1 and B2 communicated orally in English, while B6 participated in the discussion by typing in English in the Chatbox.

As mentioned in Section 3.2.3 self-directed learning, the observed technical issues frequently interrupted the smooth flow of online classes and had an adverse impact on students' learning experiences. However, Group B students demonstrated the characteristics of self-directed learning mentioned in Section 3.2.3. This includes actively engaging in the learning process, thinking critically, solving problems, continuously improving their learning abilities, and having to navigate their own way of achieving the task. B6 actively dealt with the microphone issue and sought

alternative solutions, reflecting the principle of active student participation in the self-directed theory. It is worth mentioning that, although the students were in an online learning setting, they still managed to accomplish the task successfully. However, had they been attending offline classes, they would not have encountered this particular challenge in the first place.

Furthermore, the influence of technology on social interaction should be considered. Technical issues negatively affected students' learning experiences and interactions. When audio and video were asynchronous or students' microphones malfunctioned, real-time social interactions were hindered. In the online learning environment, real-time social interaction is crucial for building and maintaining the bonding social capital among Chinese students, as proposed by Putnam (as cited in Section 4.3.3). The proactive attitude of B5 and B6 also demonstrated their efforts to maintain their bonding social capital even in the face of technological challenges.

However, these issues also provide insights for educational institutions and technology providers. While students can cope with technical issues through self-directed learning, educational institutions and technology providers have a responsibility to provide stable technical environments to support students' online learning.

6.6 The Role of L1 in Online Learning

The term "first language" (L1) encompasses a person's earliest linguistic experiences and represents the initial stages of language development. Typically, this refers to the language spoken by primary caregivers within the home environment, serving as the foundation for all subsequent language learning. This acquisition process is remarkable for its naturalness; it occurs spontaneously and intuitively, rather than through formal or explicit instruction (Thompson, 2017).

For Chinese students embarking on their educational journey in the UK, the influence

of their L1 - Chinese - is particularly significant. Prior to their arrival in the UK, these students have been immersed in a predominantly Chinese-speaking environment, where Chinese language and culture have shaped their communication patterns and cognitive processes. As such, the Chinese serve as their primary linguistic reference point, influencing their approach to learning and expressing themselves in the English language.

6.6.1 Unconscious/Subconscious Use of L1

Observation Record of Group A:

A1 unconsciously or subconsciously answered the teacher's questions in Chinese, then realized and switched back to English.

To clarify how it was ascertained that A1 and A2 thought they were speaking English even though they were speaking Chinese, consider this additional information: Upon returning to the main classroom after the unsupervised discussions, A1 and A2 continued their conversation in Chinese without realizing the language switch. When the teacher approached them, they attempted to communicate in what they believed was English, but it was evident from their tone and the words used that they were still speaking Chinese.

Observation Record of Group B:

Group B did not demonstrate significant issues with unconscious switching between Chinese and English. However, B3 consistently made mistakes when using pronouns such as "he/she" while answering the teacher's questions. Despite understanding the difference between the two pronouns in English, B3 seemed to struggle with their correct usage.

To further illustrate this point, A1 and A2 switch between Chinese and English unconsciously or subconsciously during classroom interactions. Consider the situation

where A1 and A2 continued their conversation in Chinese after returning to the main classroom from unsupervised discussions. When approached by the teacher, they attempted to communicate in what they believed was English. However, it was apparent from their tone, choice of words, and sentence structure that they were still speaking in their native language. This implies they may not have been aware of the shift in language, believing they were communicating in English. Such an occurrence highlights the profound influence their mother tongue has on acquiring a second language, exemplifying the concept of Translanguaging as described in Section 3.4.3.

The confusion observed in Group A between their native language and English can be attributed to various factors. Firstly, their lower oral proficiency in English may have contributed to their reliance on their native language when facing difficulties in expression. Secondly, the influence of their native language on second language acquisition (English) may have been more significant, leading to unconscious or subconscious switches between the two languages. Lastly, their tendency to revert to their native language when encountering the limitations of their English proficiency suggests a certain level of dependence on their native language for communication.

The role of conscious and subconscious processes in second language acquisition has been a contentious issue in applied linguistics. Some theorists, such as Krashen (1982, 1985), have distinguished between "acquisition" and "learning" by using the terms "conscious" and "subconscious". In this context, the observed phenomenon in Group A aligns with the concept of enhanced translanguaging theory discussed in section 3.4.3. This theory suggests that learners may use elements from their native language to facilitate communication and learning in a second language environment.

The influence of the native language on second language acquisition is also evident in Group B's performance. Specifically, B3's confusion between "he/she" may stem from phonetic characteristics in their native language (Chinese). In Chinese, the pronouns "他" (tā) and "她" (tā) have the same pronunciation, which could explain the difficulties B3 encountered when distinguishing these words in English. Zheng's (2018)

research further supports this finding by identifying frequent incorrect use of "he/she" by L1 Chinese students in spoken English, suggesting that they are not genuinely confused about gender but are more likely influenced by their native language.

It is worth noting that these language phenomena, whether occurring in online or physical classrooms, are common and related to cross-linguistic interactions resulting from L1 switching. The online learning environment may exacerbate these issues as certain social and linguistic cues, such as facial expressions and body language, may be reduced in face-to-face communication. As a result, learners may rely more heavily on their native language to compensate for these missing cues, leading to increased instances of language alternation and confusion. To mitigate these challenges, teachers and educators should be aware of the potential for language transfer and provide support and guidance to help learners navigate the complexities of second language acquisition.

6.6.2 Conscious use of L1

Observation record of Group A

In the group discussion session, although the teacher emphasised the need to communicate in English, A1 still tended to communicate with their group members in Chinese or simply remained silent.

During class, when A1 couldn't understand English words or grammar spoken by the teacher, A1 would ask other students in Chinese. Other students would then translate the answers into Chinese to help A1 better understand the knowledge points.

Observation record of Group B

In group discussions, B3 occasionally used Chinese (possibly consciously) because B3, not being an English major teacher, had limited fluency in spoken English. B3 used Chinese to express ideas, while the other two students still responded in English

to B3's words.

Through the observation of these two groups of students, it is evident that the students are aware that they are using L1 expressions, and their classmates who communicate with them also use L1 expressions. Chinese students of Groups A and B tend to use Mandarin to aid in understanding the knowledge taught by the teacher. In Group A, students had lower English oral proficiency, and the influence of their native language on their second language acquisition (English) was more significant. This resulted in more frequent confusion between their native language and English. For example, when A1 encounters English words or grammar that they don't understand, they choose to seek help from other students in Mandarin. This behaviour demonstrates that learners perceived easier or more effective means of communication, their native language, when faced with language barriers. Classmates assist A1 in Mandarin, effectively using the native language as a bridge to help A1 better understand and grasp the knowledge points in the target language. This cross-linguistic collaborative learning helps A1 immediately solve problems. However, if they rely heavily on Chinese translation, this arguably inhibits any substantial progress in English. While cross-linguistic collaboration can be beneficial, over-reliance on the native language as a crutch can hinder the development of independent English language skills. Translation can provide a quick fix at the moment, but it may not foster the deep understanding and long-term retention of English concepts and structures that are essential for fluency and proficiency.

Group B students had a higher level of English oral proficiency, but some students still used their native language in oral communication. L1 can help them understand and remember the learning content. For example, B3 occasionally used Chinese in group discussions, especially when feeling limited in English expression. This indicates that learners flexibly switch between two or more languages based on communication needs and their language abilities to ensure accurate information transmission. When B3 used Chinese expressions, the other students still responded in

English. This multilingual interaction may help B3 establish a connection between their native language and the target language, thereby promoting their English learning.

Behan, Turnbull, and Spek (1997) primarily explored the impact of the use of the first language (L1) on the learning outcomes when learning a second language (L2). Through a study on French immersion students, they found that even in environments requiring the use of L2 (French), students would unconsciously use L1 (English) for communication and task completion. They concluded that 'L1 use can both support and enhance L2 development, functioning simultaneously as an effective tool for dealing with cognitively demanding content' (p. 41).

In summary, students' use of their native language in the classroom may be conscious or subconscious, depending on their language abilities and communication needs. In any case, this behaviour should be seen as part of language learning strategies rather than mere reliance on their native language. The studies of Cook (1999) and Swain and Lapkin (2000) further emphasize the importance of the flexible use of multiple languages in different contexts. For students at the beginner level, the use of the first language can serve as a means of motivation and reducing frustration. Eldridge's view (1996) suggests that limiting the use of the native language to increase the time spent using the target language may not always be effective. In fact, recent research has shown that the use of the native language can facilitate language learning, especially when learning complex or abstract concepts. The observation results show that Chinese students tend to use their native language to assist in understanding when faced with comprehension difficulties. This behaviour may be related to their learning habitus and classroom environment, and it may also reflect their understanding of the relationship between their native language and the target language. As outlined in section 3.4.3, the Translanguaging theory offers a valuable perspective on student learning behaviours within multilingual settings. The evidence gathered from this study indicates that the dynamic application of both native and target languages in

educational contexts serves more as a beneficial learning approach than merely an impediment or distraction from mastering the target language.

6.7 Informal/Peer Learning

In the course of observing Group B, a significant and noteworthy event transpired that merits further, meticulous examination. This event occurred during the third session when, due to unforeseen personal circumstances, the instructor was tardy for a duration of 15 minutes. This unintentional delay not only presented an unexpected opportunity for the students, but also served as a valuable lesson in peer interaction and self-directed learning.

In the absence of a designated waiting area set up by the teacher, the participants found themselves logged into the primary online classroom unsupervised. Interestingly, this brief unsupervised period, far from resulting in chaos or confusion, turned out to be a fertile ground for spontaneous interaction among the students, showcasing their ability to adapt and make the most of the situation. They discussed their daily life situations and helped each other with problems encountered in completing assignments. This informal Chinese communication not only enhanced understanding and connection between classmates, but also helped them better understand each other's learning progress and confusion.

This interaction fostered a sense of community and belongingness that is often conspicuously lacking in online learning environments. The use of their native language for informal chats not only facilitated communication but also broke down barriers and eased insecurities, allowing for a more relaxed and open exchange of ideas and experiences. Such interactions are commonplace in traditional, face-to-face classrooms but are sadly lacking in many online settings.

In typical online classrooms where a virtual waiting room is implemented, students are generally restricted to viewing a reminder box until the teacher initiates the

session. While this maintains order and structure, reflecting a positive aspect of online learning, it also unintentionally deprives students of the opportunity to engage in informal communication before and after classes. Therefore, it becomes paramount to create informal online spaces that can replicate the physical environment of informal/peer learning. By eliminating the waiting room and allowing students to enter the virtual classroom early, they can engage in productive conversations with their peers. This fosters a learning atmosphere akin to that of a traditional classroom, allowing students to make the most of their time while waiting for the formal class session to begin.

Putnam's bonding social capital theory, as discussed in section 4.3.3, underscores the significance of strong social ties and trust in promoting community and social development. Viewing Group B students as a community, although the teacher was absent, the students decided to enter the online classroom and communicate in their native language. These students are not only classmates but also colleagues in a real-world society on a regular. Viewing Group B students as a community, it is worth noting that they actively participated in pre-class discussions in the online classroom, communicating in their native language, even in the absence of the teacher. These students are not only classmates in the online classroom, but also colleagues in daily life. This observation is in line with Putnam's social capital theory, which emphasizes the importance of strong social connections and trust in promoting community and social development. The behaviour exhibited by Group B students reflects the influence of pre-existing bonding social capital in their interactions, they had existing connections with each other, and also developed and deepened their connections through pre-class interactions and shared anxieties.

Moreover, the students' interaction reflects the trust-building aspect of social capital. Their willingness to freely communicate in Chinese during the unsupervised time signifies a high level of trust among them. In environments characterized by trust, individuals are more inclined to share personal information and experiences,

confident that their disclosures will be respected and safeguarded. The establishment of trust further enhances community cohesion, motivating students to actively participate in classroom discussions, share ideas, and collaboratively solve problems.

This positive learning atmosphere fosters improved academic outcomes and promotes holistic student development, thereby enhancing the overall quality of the educational experience. It is worth noting that in traditional, face-to-face classrooms, student-to-student communication arises organically. However, in online settings, this type of interaction is often limited or even absent.

The spontaneous pre-class communication observed among Group B students serves as a valuable supplement to this deficiency. By eliminating the waiting room and affording students the opportunity to engage in informal communication before class, online platforms can provide a more authentic and engaging learning experience. By simulating the informal learning environment of a physical classroom, online spaces can foster stronger social connections and trust among students, paving the way for more effective and collaborative learning experiences.

In conclusion, the observation of Group B highlights the importance of informal learning and peer interaction in online education. It suggests that future designs of online classrooms and platform development should prioritize the creation of informal learning spaces that encourage spontaneous communication and collaboration among students. Such features will not only foster a more positive and engaging learning environment but will also contribute significantly to the development of bonding social capital among students, regardless of their nationality or cultural background.

6.8 Conclusion

In this chapter, I have explored the effects of online learning within a specific context on a group of online learning, utilizing multiple theories to analyze and interpret the data gathered. Our exploration has centred on how students' proficiency in oral

English impacts teacher questioning strategies, classroom participation, and their motivation to express themselves orally in an online setting. Furthermore, I have delved into the advantages and challenges unique to Chinese online learning. This comprehensive analysis has encompassed various factors such as the relationship between online learning tools and learning efficiency, the level of interaction achieved in virtual classrooms, reading comprehension issues, and the logistical concerns related to class locations. Additionally, I have dedicated a section to discussing the significant role played by the native language (L1) in the online learning process. We have distinguished between unconscious and conscious use of the native language, emphasizing its potential to aid students' comprehension and retention of new knowledge. Moreover, we have highlighted how the strategic use of L1 can enhance students' efficiency and engagement in online learning environments. Lastly, this chapter has underscored the critical importance of informal learning and peer-to-peer learning in online education. Informal learning contributes significantly to the development of bonding social capital, fostering trust and camaraderie among students. This, in turn, strengthens the cohesion of the learning community, making students more inclined to collaborate, share knowledge, and support each other's academic journeys.

In conclusion, the findings presented in this chapter offer valuable insights into the potential and challenges of online learning, particularly in the context of oral English proficiency and transnational education. These insights not only contribute to a richer understanding of online learning but also pave the way for further critical examination and discussion in the subsequent chapter. As we progress in our exploration of online learning, it is evident that this mode of education presents unique opportunities and challenges that must be carefully considered to ensure optimal learning outcomes for all students.

Chapter 7: Findings from Online Interview

7.1 Introduction

The previous chapter presented the findings from the first part of the research. This chapter discloses the results from the second part, which involves interviews with Chinese international students. These interviews were conducted after the classroom observations and took place during COVID-19 in 2021, as discussed in Chapter 5.

This study selected participants from a specific geographical area, all from the same university in Scotland, which aligns with those chosen for classroom observation (Group A). Unlike Group A, where all students participated in online courses within China during the COVID-19 pandemic, Group B's students engaged in online learning from varied locations. Some students, during interviews, revealed that they attended online courses from China. Some of these students began their online classes in China and later moved to the UK to continue, while others were already in face-to-face courses in the UK before the COVID-19 pandemic and chose to remain there for their online studies post-pandemic. This geographical diversity among participants enriches the research, providing insights into how various learning environments and locations affect students' experiences and outcomes during the COVID-19 pandemic. To ensure the diversity and comprehensiveness of the data, 15 students were selected for the interviews, including 5 bachelor students, 5 master students, and 5 doctoral students (specific subjects are shown in Appendix 10). Some of the participants completed their undergraduate/master's degrees in China. Then they came to the UK for graduate or doctoral studies. By selecting five students from each academic level and specifically choosing individuals from fields such as education, business, and engineering, the study aims to comprehensively cover and understand the impact of academic maturity on the online learning experience. This method takes into account that a student's disciplinary background may affect the way they engage with online learning. By exploring how these different fields adapt to the unique needs and

challenges of online learning, the study is dedicated to investigating the diversity and complexity of online learning experiences from a multidisciplinary perspective.

7.2 Advantages of Online Learning

7.2.1 Flexibility and Safety in Online Learning

The COVID-19 pandemic presented unprecedented challenges to the traditional delivery of learning, accelerating the adoption and implementation of online courses. As discussed in Chapter 2, online learning emerged as a practical and effective response to the global health crisis. By overcoming geographical limitations, this mode of education allowed international students from China and other countries to participate in UK-based courses remotely. Similarly, students within the UK could continue their studies without attending campus, thus mitigating many of the restrictions imposed by the pandemic on in-person learning.

By April 2022, when interviews were conducted for this study, the benefits of online education had become evident. Online courses provided a secure learning environment, effectively minimizing the risk of virus transmission through face-to-face contact. This advantage was particularly critical during the pandemic, which necessitated social distancing and reduced international travel. For Chinese international students, staying in China to attend UK courses online significantly lowered the risk of exposure to the virus. This not only enhanced their sense of safety but also fulfilled essential physiological and safety needs, enabling them to focus on their studies without undue health-related concerns. Participant 13 highlighted that increased travel costs, infection risks, and potential medical expenses, which discouraged many students from travelling to the UK, corroborated by data from HESA (2022). The shift to remote learning also reduced expenses related to travel and visas, making UK education more accessible to international students during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Participants in this study expressed a broad appreciation for the security provided by online learning. For instance, Participant 14 stated, "I believe that every student can benefit from online courses during the COVID-19 pandemic." Participant 7 shared, "For me, it is safer to go out less." while Participant 13 remarked, "Online learning is a reasonable choice in response to government requirements for social distancing and avoiding cross-infection policies." These views underscore the widespread recognition of online education as a practical and safe alternative during a global health crisis.

Online courses offer students unparalleled flexibility and convenience. Participant 13 noted, "Online courses are very convenient and give me more free time, I can review and revise anytime, and that's a big advantage." The ability to study without commuting enabled students to manage their time more effectively, fostering a proactive approach to learning. This aligns with Jehanghir, Ishaq and Akbar's (2024) perspective, which emphasizes the importance of learner autonomy in the educational process. Similarly, Participants 12 and 4 appreciated the elimination of commuting, which gave them greater control over their schedules and studies.

The flexibility of online learning also supported students in balancing multiple commitments. Participant 14, for example, managed both academic and work responsibilities while attending online courses, citing the adaptability of online education as a key enabler. This reflects the broader finding that a flexible learning environment promotes self-directed learning (SDL), as noted by Asino and Pulay (2019). The capacity to tailor learning schedules and access resources at one's own pace empowered students to take charge of their educational journey.

The development of online learning has significantly expanded students' access to global resources and academic opportunities. Participant 13 observed, "If you want to study across countries, online learning is the most effective way. Especially during the COVID-19 pandemic, it is almost impossible to attend classes in person due to the geographical distance between China and the UK." Many participants highlighted the

ability to engage with international academic events and conferences as a key benefit. For instance, Participant 13 actively participated in online academic conferences, enhancing his research through exposure to diverse perspectives and resources. He shared, "When exploring content pertinent to my research topic, I frequently utilize online resources...Participating in these lectures has significantly enhanced my research."

The immediacy and accessibility of online courses also facilitated the development of SDL skills, which are critical for success in online learning environments (Morris and Rohs, 2021). By enabling students to manage their time efficiently and take greater control of their learning processes, online education supports both immediate academic needs and long-term skills development.

While the rapid expansion of online learning was initially a response to the COVID-19 pandemic, participants recognized its potential to reshape cross-border education in the future. Participant 11 noted, "As an international student, it is more appropriate for me to stay in China and take online courses in the current situation. Therefore, I prefer online learning." He acknowledged the necessity of online education during the pandemic but also saw it as a harbinger of future trends in international education. Similarly, Participant 14 emphasized how the flexibility of online learning allowed him to adapt to various demands, underscoring its value beyond the immediate crisis.

Students also distinguished between Emergency Remote Learning and structured online education, recognizing the latter's potential for its long-term integration into academic programmes. The pandemic catalyzed innovations in online learning, demonstrating its capacity to overcome geographical barriers and enhance access to quality education. This dual role, as an emergency response and a viable long-term model, positions online learning as a transformative force in international education (Skledar Matijević, 2022).

The rapid development of online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic has had a profound impact on Chinese international students and their learning. By providing a safe, flexible, and accessible learning environment, it addressed immediate challenges while paving the way for long-term innovations in education. Participants in this study highlighted the numerous advantages of online learning, including enhanced safety, time efficiency, and access to global resources. As the educational landscape continues to evolve, the insights gained from this period of rapid adaptation offer valuable lessons for the future of international education.

7.2.2 Enhancing Teaching with Digital Features

The hand-raising feature in online classrooms provides students with more opportunities to practise and, therefore, enhance their listening and speaking, aligning with theories of interactivity that emphasize active engagement.

Wu (2021) examined the interaction between students, tutors, and peers following the implementation of an online learning platform, indicating that learners preferred interactive features like emoticons and the "raise hand" function to engage with their tutors. In this context, as noted by Participant 12, students in online classrooms benefit from the flexibility of signalling their wish to speak or ask questions through the virtual "raise hand" function, bypassing the need to wait for face-to-face interactions typical in physical classrooms. Salim (2023) emphasizes that non-verbal communication can have a significant impact on interactions through facial expressions, tone of voice, and gestures. In online classrooms, the expression of these non-verbal cues is somewhat limited. However, the virtual "raise hand" function provides a supplementary form of non-verbal communication. This function simplifies the process, allowing students to signal their intent to speak or ask questions by merely clicking a button, directly conveying their intention to the teacher. This method is both efficient and clear, aligning with Salim's notion of communication being "simple and understandable." Additionally, it reduces the emotional burden on students who might otherwise feel anxious in face-to-face

interactions, making it particularly beneficial for those less comfortable with in-person communication.

Furthermore, this interactivity resonates with Krashen's Comprehensible Input Hypothesis (Spada and Lightbown, 2019), which suggests that language acquisition is enhanced when learners are exposed to comprehensible input at a slightly advanced level. The hand-raising feature encourages students to engage with input that is contextually rich and interactive, enabling them to practise the language in ways that are both comprehensible and responsive to their linguistic and technological skill levels. Garza (2021, p. 297) reinforces this idea, highlighting that learners can virtually "raise their hands" on platforms like Zoom, effectively signalling questions or comments. This approach promotes inclusivity and equity while providing students with a clear and comprehensible means of participation. Together, these features enhance the interactive nature of online classrooms, supporting both equitable engagement and language acquisition through structured, inclusive participation.

Participant 14 highlighted another benefit of online courses, which is the real-time recommendation and demonstration of online learning resources by lecturers. They explained,

"Lecturers recommend online learning resources in class, such as websites, and show us how to access them in real-time through screen sharing. It is easy for us to understand at a glance. During Zoom classes, lecturers also share website links or articles (PDF, Doc) in the Chatbox, and we can open them immediately. This digital learning method is very convenient and timely."

Furthermore, online platforms allow lecturers to quickly share materials with students, enabling immediate access without any waiting time. Participant 15 mentioned the convenience of lecturers using the Chatbox function to share "real-time links or articles." This feature not only streamlines and improves resource distribution but also becomes particularly important in virtual classrooms, where students cannot

immediately access physical materials like in physical classrooms. These applications of digital features not only enhance teaching efficiency but also enrich students' learning experience.

7.3 Student Feedback on Blended Learning

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, many higher education institutions, including those in this study, have implemented various teaching modes for students: fully online, fully offline, or a hybrid of both. Let's explore the advantages and disadvantages of this emerging learning model together.

7.3.1 Interaction, and Enhanced Learning Outcomes

Several students, such as Participant 1, highlighted the flexibility of their courses, stating, "Most of my courses are conducted online, but I also have the option to attend classes on campus because the offline content is synchronous." This dual modality enables students to select the learning approach that best suits their individual needs and schedules, thereby enhancing learning efficiency. This flexibility aligns closely with the characteristics of synchronous online learning, as discussed by Lin and Sun (2024). They emphasize that synchronous online learning leverages virtual classrooms to facilitate one-on-one or one-to-many real-time teaching. This mode can provide students with feedback and interactive opportunities when available, fostering a deeper understanding and practical application of knowledge. By integrating synchronous and face-to-face options, students can benefit from the real-time engagement of synchronous learning while also enjoying the freedom to tailor their educational experience to their preferences and goals.

Saboowala and Manghirmalani Mishra (2021) and Peimani and Kamalipour (2021) emphasize that blended learning combines online and face-to-face teaching, offering students flexibility in terms of time, location, and learning pace. This flexibility is particularly evident in lecturer-student interactions. For instance, Participant 6

explained, "If the tutor is not on campus, we choose online communication; if they are at the school, we communicate face-to-face." This adaptability ensures that both students and lecturers can choose the most convenient and effective mode of communication based on their circumstances, further enhancing the learning experience.

Participant 12 shared,

"I think online teaching is more efficient for certain content. Our courses are often divided into two parts: pure theory and experiments. I can preview the theory part on my own, while the experiments require on-campus operations. Although experiments can also be done online, I believe that operating them that way would be more complex and time-consuming."

Participant 3 has a positive attitude towards blended learning: "I like blended courses because they are flexible. I enjoy taking online classes at home with a relaxed mood, but I also like occasionally going to school to meet lecturers and classmates." This model not only enhances interaction among students and between students and lecturers but also improves learning outcomes.

In summary, blended learning has garnered widespread praise from students for its flexibility and interactivity. This innovative approach not only caters to the personalized learning needs of students but also significantly enhances their learning efficiency and outcomes. However, it is important to acknowledge that this model, like any other, presents its own unique challenges and areas that require continuous effort, improvement, and optimization in practice.

7.3.2 Choices and time management challenges

In some situations, students may not have the autonomy to choose between online or offline courses. De Silva (2023) applied Maslow's theory of human motivation to analyze students' decisions to study abroad, emphasizing that the quality of

education—a fundamental need—played a key role in their choice to study in the UK. However, a lack of autonomy in educational settings can hinder the fulfilment of students' hierarchical needs, impacting their overall motivation and satisfaction. Participant 4 highlighted this challenge, expressing frustration about the inability to choose between online and offline learning modes, particularly as a student living far from the UK campus. They noted:

"We must follow the lecturer's instructions. I once asked if I could choose online courses due to the long distance but was told that as a full-time student, I do not have that choice."

This lack of flexibility not only limits students' ability to manage logistical challenges but also undermines their sense of autonomy, a key psychological need in Maslow's framework. Without autonomy, students may struggle to maintain motivation and satisfaction, both of which are essential for their academic and personal development.

Participant 10 expressed difficulties with time management in blended learning:

"I once took a course where the online part was from 10 am to 11 am, followed immediately by the offline class from 11 am to 12 pm. This arrangement was not reasonable for me. If I took online classes at home, I had to rush to the school without much buffer time in between." This challenge relates to Maslow's physiological and safety needs, as poor scheduling creates physical and mental strain, limiting students' ability to concentrate on academic goals.

This theme delves into two primary challenges students face in a blended learning environment. Firstly, there is the issue of impractical scheduling of online and offline classes. Particularly when the arrangement of online and offline courses are closely linked, without sufficient buffer time for students to transition from one setting to another. In such scenarios, students often find themselves rushing from their home's

online learning environment to campus for in-person classes within a short span, undoubtedly adding significant stress to their lives.

Secondly, in some instances, students are compelled to attend on-campus classes and are unable to choose online learning based on their personal circumstances and preferences. This restriction on choice in a blended learning environment could undermine students' sense of autonomy, as they cannot freely choose the learning environment and methods that suit them best. This could potentially lead to a decrease in their learning efficiency and interest.

Following Maslow's hierarchy of needs (4.2.2), when basic needs (such as physiological needs and a sense of security) are not met, it is challenging for individuals to pursue higher-level needs. In a blended learning environment, the pressing time schedules and lack of choice may cause students to feel anxious and insecure. These fundamental emotional needs are not adequately met, thus affecting the motivation of students to pursue higher-level learning objectives, which is not conducive to their learning and growth.

7.4 Challenges of Institution-led Online Learning

7.4.1 Challenges for Teaching Quality

The sudden transition from face-to-face to online learning due to the COVID-19 pandemic, referred to in Chapter 3 as ERT, posed significant challenges for lecturers and students in adaptation to the new mode of delivery, particularly impacting teaching quality. During this shift, educational institutions were under pressure to quickly implement online learning, which exposed essential issues, especially for Chinese international students who encountered inconsistent teaching quality, limited lecturer experience in online education, and a lack of diverse online teaching methods.

Participant 9 recalled,

"At that time, we had just transitioned from offline campus courses to online courses, with only a few class hours left. The lecturers simply provided us with PPTs. Due to the sudden outbreak of Covid-19, everyone was at a loss, and the lecturers did not really consider how to improve online teaching."

This reliance on presentation slides highlights a key limitation of ERL, consistent with findings by Barbour *et al.*, (2020), who described ERL as a stopgap solution often implemented without the interactive elements typical of pre-planned online learning. Many lecturers, unprepared for the sudden shift to online education, struggled to recreate the engagement and collaboration that are hallmarks of face-to-face learning. For participants in this study, the result for the participants in this study was a passive learning experience with minimal engagement, which was especially challenging in subjects requiring hands-on participation, such as Engineering.

Students also faced additional challenges in adapting to this unfamiliar online environment. Participant 5 described their initial confusion and technical difficulties, saying,

"When I first started taking courses online in March 2020, I was still quite confused because it was my first time to take courses online. I first experienced not being able to access the online classroom through the link. Then I emailed my lecturer and asked my classmates to find out how to access the online classroom. After that, I slowly became familiar with it."

In subjects like Engineering, the limitations of ERL became even more evident. Participant 5 further explained:

"The challenge may be that some of our courses will have experiments. The lecturer can only do that by doing the experiment herself/himself and other lecturers help to record it and then put the video on the online platform. The process is not as familiar

as if we were doing it ourselves, so that's a (challenge)."

These adjustments highlight how technical barriers and the immediate response required from university lecturers led to limited preparation for delivering online education, as also noted by Bozkurt and Sharma (2020). Lecturers' lack of experience with digital platforms often resulted in content delivery that lacked interactivity, reducing opportunities for meaningful engagement. Participant 9 further commented:

"At that time, we were forced to transition from traditional offline courses to online learning, but it seemed like the lecturers were not adequately prepared. Many times, we only received PPTs without substantial interaction and discussions."

These accounts are consistent with observations by Ferri, Grifoni, and Guzzo (2020), who found that ERL exposed significant inequalities in preparation and highlighted lecturers' struggle to provide effective learning experiences. Additionally, the absence of interactive elements likely contributed to a decline in student motivation and emotional engagement (Lawanto *et al.*, 2022).

In conclusion, although the rapid shift to online learning was necessary to ensure educational continuity, it revealed essential gaps in teaching quality and adaptability (Hayat *et al.*, 2021; Lassoued *et al.*, 2020). The limited prior experience of both students and university lecturers, along with technical challenges, impacted the effectiveness of online courses.

7.4.2 Issues around Interaction, Cultural and Social Capital in Online Learning

In addition to challenges with teaching quality, the online format limited essential opportunities for interaction, social capital development, and opportunities for learners to “access the target culture, which is vital to international students’ academic and social experience. The lack of face-to-face engagement hindered some students’ ability to build connections, both within their academic environment and the broader social context, which affected their access to the target culture and the development of

oral proficiency. As Putnam (2015) highlights, social capital—formed through trust and cooperation within networks—is essential for effective social functioning. In the online learning context, reduced interpersonal interaction restricts students' opportunities to build this social capital, potentially weakening their sense of connection and support within the academic community.

Participant 7 highlighted the reduction in interactive opportunities, saying,

"At the beginning, we were not accustomed to online learning. We had not been exposed to online courses before. After the transition, the lecturers mainly taught based on PPTs, lacking oral interaction and discussions."

This one-way teaching method restricted real-time feedback and oral practice, particularly essential in language courses. As a result, students had limited opportunities for active engagement, real-time feedback, and skills development, which are essential for language acquisition development of the language skills which are essential for a sense of involvement in the learning process. Participant 7 further explained,

"During online learning, we rarely had opportunities for oral practice and face-to-face interaction. Most of the time, the lecturers were lecturing, and we were listening." This approach limited students' oral development and hindered the accumulation of social capital in their social networks.

The restricted format thus limited the development of social capital, access to and involvement in the social and academic areas. In traditional face-to-face environments, students build "bonding social capital" (Bourdieu, 1986) through interactions with peers and lecturers, fostering a supportive learning community. Participant 6 noted,

"There is not much difference between the online and offline class content in terms of the school's curriculum for the initial period of study abroad. However, I think it is possible that students will have a better experience in the offline classes, and they will

be able to communicate with the lecturer face to face and be more involved in the class. However, online students can only listen to the lecturer's lessons in the accommodation by themselves, so they may communicate with the lecturer about the course content or discuss problems with their classmates, which makes the experience of studying in the UK not particularly good."

This sentiment reflects how the online format limited meaningful engagement, making it difficult for students to form a strong sense of community.

Furthermore, the lack of in-person interactions hindered the development of "linking social capital" (Szreter and Woolcock, 2004) which involves connections across diverse cultural and social backgrounds. These broader interactions are essential for cultural engagement and cross-cultural understanding, helping students access the host society. Participant 6 highlighted the importance of this type of interaction, stating,

"When studying abroad in the UK, participating in local courses and activities helped me quickly integrate into the local society, and my oral proficiency also improved significantly. However, it seems that the current online courses cannot provide such opportunities."

This limited exposure to local culture affected students' opportunities to build social networks and gain new perspectives, which are essential for personal and professional growth. Students widely believed that face-to-face participation in local cultural activities was irreplaceable, with online learning posing a significant challenge for those seeking to improve their oral proficiency and access and exchange social and cultural interests (Bailey *et al.*, 2022).

In the context of social capital, bonding social capital refers to the strong, inward-looking ties within homogeneous groups that share similar backgrounds, values, or identities (Ceci, Masciarelli and Poledrini, 2020). In the offline setting,

students could actively engage in classroom discussions and group activities, forming strong relationships with their peers and lecturers. These connections provide emotional and instrumental support, essential for navigating the challenges of studying abroad (Ceci, Masciarelli and Poledrini, 2020). Linking social capital, on the other hand, includes weaker, outward-looking ties with individuals or groups from different backgrounds. Through these ties, students gain new ideas, perspectives, and opportunities, facilitating cross-cultural competencies crucial for their growth (Ceci, Masciarelli and Poledrini, 2020).

In conclusion, the restricted interaction and limited cultural integration in online learning environments presented substantial challenges for Chinese international students (Brown *et al.*, 2022). This theme highlights the importance of incorporating interactive elements and facilitating cultural engagement in online learning.

7.5 Evaluation of Institution-directed Online Learning

7.5.1 Mental Health and Social Challenges in Online Learning

Extended periods of online learning can lead to feelings of social isolation and a lack of genuine interpersonal interaction among students, negatively impacting their mental health, learning-related emotions, and motivation (see Section 3.3.3). In the participants' statements, students' psychological states demonstrate a range of complex characteristics. Some students might thrive in this environment, actively interacting with the course material and classmates, while others may struggle, experiencing emotional volatility, feelings of loneliness, and even immense psychological pressure. Decreased motivation due to boredom and loneliness: For example,

Participant 9 mentioned that: "We feel that after going to the UK being bored in the dormitory and taking online classes for most of the year, it looks like we hadn't one abroad. This may also be related to the age of the student, for example, if the student

has just arrived abroad, his motivation and mood will be affected if he does not feel very good about studying abroad."

This lack of motivation and negative emotions can significantly impact their overall experience.

Lack of social interaction and mental health issues: The limited social interaction provided by online learning environments can make students feel lonely, anxious, and depressed. Participant 15 points out that "Everyone becomes more isolated and then more vulnerable and less resistant to frustration."

The discrepancy between reality and expectations: The online learning experience during the COVID-19 pandemic differs greatly from the expectations of Chinese students. Participant 15 and Participant 8 compare their current experiences with their pre-pandemic expectations and emphasize that the psychological experience of students during online learning is very different.

Participant 15 was attending an online class in China and recalled that:

"The psychological experience for students can vary greatly. In the past, before the pandemic, Chinese students studying in the UK had a positive impression and a fulfilling experience. However, if I had come to study during the Covid-19 pandemic, I would have missed out on many of the joys of studying abroad. If I had faced any minor difficulties or challenges, I would have been confined to my room, attending online classes all the time. I believe this would have resulted in a very negative psychological experience after completing my studies."

The lack of face-to-face communication and interaction can lead to negative psychological experiences.

These psychological pressures not only affect students' mental health but also hinder their social capital development and motivation, making them more reluctant to

communicate with others. Although some students have found ways to cope with the negative effects of online learning, such as the mention of pets by Participant 6, which may help students who study online every day, not every student has the conditions to have pets due to limitations in accommodation, economic factors, or personal preferences.

However, not all students believe that studying at home will have a negative impact on their mental well-being. Participant 4 mentioned that they enjoy studying at home because "I feel more confident when studying at home. I don't like meeting a lot of people. But if I go to campus, I feel very nervous and stressed." Similarly, Participant 10 also believes that studying in the home environment is more relaxing and helps them achieve better academic performance and improve learning efficiency. This indicates that while online learning presents challenges for most students, for some students, it may be a more comfortable and effective way of learning.

7.5.2 Impact of Study Environment on Learners' Focus

Regarding the impact of studying at home (i.e., physical study location) on students' levels of attention, students provided various feedback. Participant 9 mentioned that studying alone at home decreases their study focus due to the lack of companionship for studying. Participant 3 stated, "I find that studying in the library or open learning spaces is more effective than at home. Such environments help me stay more focused." Similarly, Participant 6 also believed, "Offline courses are more suitable for me because I can concentrate better in a physical classroom." They generally perceived lower efficiency in studying at home, which easily led to a lack of concentration.

In addition to the location of the study, external factors are also considered as a cause of attention distraction. For example, Participant 2 noted, "My room is not tidy, and my desk is messy, with only space for a computer and a screen. This environment has some impact on my learning efficiency."

Participant 3 also admitted, "When studying at home, I easily get distracted, always thinking about playing games or what to eat after class." Participant 6 expressed, "When taking online classes at home, I tend to relax more and sometimes get distracted by using my phone."

Some participants believe that public study areas such as libraries and quiet offices are more conducive to learning because these places help enhance focus. Participant 3 said, "In an open study room, I think less about things unrelated to studying and can concentrate better." Participant 11 also stated, "At home, a comfortable environment may make me lazy. I prefer studying in the office because it doesn't allow me to lie down and rest." This may be related to the study atmosphere in these locations.

However, for others, the noisy environment in public places can distract their attention and negatively affect their learning efficiency. Participant 4 shared her experience of studying online courses while working part-time: "Sometimes my course conflicts with work hours, making it hard for me to concentrate. It is challenging for me to listen to lectures while working."

This situation is completely different from the experience of being distracted at home. Additionally, although one may not expect (or even desire) students to attend classes while working, this student seems to consider it feasible. This is an issue worth the attention of schools, lecturers, and online course platforms, which will be further discussed in Chapter 8 on how to avoid such behaviour that seems to contradict class requirements.

Participant 2 pointed out, "The physical location of students is important. If they take online classes in public places, they may be surrounded by noise, which affects the quality of listening." Participant 13 also shares a similar view, "Taking classes in a noisy environment will definitely affect learning outcomes. Moreover, in a noisy setting, students may be reluctant to turn on their microphones for oral expression."

In conclusion, students' learning environment and physical location have a significant impact on their level of attention.

7.5.3 Self-directed Learning and Attendance Issues in Online Learning

In the online learning environment, self-discipline has become a significant issue. Participant 7 noted that "online courses tend to decrease students' self-discipline," and Participant 9 mentioned a "negative impact on my learning efficiency." Some students log in but turn off their cameras, potentially engaging in unrelated activities like playing games (Participant 2), while others might even attend class from their beds (Participant 10). This highlights a challenge for Self-directed Learning, as online settings require students to be more self-motivated and disciplined, without the structure of a physical classroom in order to succeed academically.

Assignment Submission and Participation: Participant 12 reflects that some students "seem less engaged in online assignments, and there are cases of assignments not being submitted."

7.5.3.1 Time Management Challenges

Time management is an issue for students taking online classes, particularly for those joining from different time zones. Both Participant 7 and Participant 10 refer to a common problem, noting, "It is easier to be late for morning classes. If you don't wake up on time, you'll miss the class." Participant 6 also highlights that some students struggle with attentiveness due to early start times, explaining, "Some students only open their computers and enter the online classroom during class time, but they are actually still sleeping because the class starts too early."

Participants' struggles with punctuality and attentiveness in morning online classes, as noted by Participants 7, 10, and 6, highlight gaps in self-directed learning (SDL) skills, particularly in time management and focus. Morris and Rohs (2021) and Karatas and Arpaci (2021) underscore that effective SDL is crucial for online learning success, as

students who actively manage their schedules and strategies perform better. However, as Godwin-Jones (2019) suggests, practical guidance and tools, such as time management workshops or automated reminders, are essential to help students develop these skills and maintain engagement, addressing challenges like late arrivals and inattentiveness during early classes.

Furthermore, for students located in China but enrolled in UK courses, managing class schedules can be particularly challenging due to time zone changes. When the UK switches from Greenwich Mean Time (GMT) to British Summer Time (BST) in late March, the time difference with China shifts from eight hours to seven hours. This means that a UK class beginning at 9 a.m. will start at 4 p.m. China time during winter (GMT) but shift to 5 p.m. China time during summer (BST). While this one-hour shift may seem minor, it requires students in China to adjust their schedules, often resulting in later study sessions and potentially impacting their daily routines, sleep, and focus. In contrast, students who remain in the UK are unaffected by this time zone shift, as their schedules align directly with the local time. However, punctuality and maintaining alertness for morning classes remain common challenges across locations, as online learning requires disciplined time management in home environments that often lack the structured atmosphere of in-person classes.

7.5.3.2 Motivation and Discipline in Online Learning

Online learning environments often pose challenges to students' motivation and self-discipline. Participant 4 states, "Everyone is hidden behind their computers and phones. I feel like I have become lazy, and that's the main reason why I lose interest in anything." This reflects a broader challenge in online education, where the absence of face-to-face engagement can diminish learners, leading to disengagement. This aligns with the findings of Morris and Rohs (2021), who emphasized the role of self-directed learning (SDL) in maintaining motivation in online contexts. Karatas and Arpaci (2021) further suggest that SDL is critical for sustaining engagement in virtual learning, as learners must actively manage their own learning process to succeed. The

analysis of the lack of motivation to participate in online courses will be presented in section 7.7.

A key feature in online learning platforms is attendance tracking tools. This functionality allows university lecturers to effectively monitor students' progress and provide timely feedback. One of the critical features of online learning platforms is attendance tracking, which enables lecturers to monitor students' progress and provide timely, personalized feedback. As Participant 10 states, this tool "allows lecturers to have a clear understanding of each student's situation" and provide targeted feedback. However, some participants point out that even if students log in to the learning platform and are shown as "online," they may actually be sleeping, dealing with personal matters, or engaging in other non-learning activities.

To address these shortcomings, participants suggested implementing measures to promote discipline and active participation. Participant 5 suggests, "Students should follow the same rules in online classes as they do in offline classes, as this helps maintain discipline in online classrooms." Participant 2 noted "Based on my experience, students shouldn't keep their cameras off for the entire class or half of the class without interacting with the lecturer." Such feedback echoes the findings of Lian et al. (2021), who emphasized that lack of direct supervision in online learning can lead to reduced engagement and inefficiency.

7.5.4 Ensuring Network Stability and Technical Literacy in Online Learning

Online courses offer students a wealth of learning resources, but these resources can become inaccessible if students lack the necessary digital skills and IT literacy. The absence of these skills can present technical challenges for students, affecting their participation and learning outcomes in online courses.

During previous observations of online classrooms, both students and lecturers frequently encountered network and device issues. To gain a deeper understanding of

this problem, I explored the topic of access to technology in interviews with students. While some students (such as Participant 4 and Participant 12) had stable home networks that ensured the quality of their online classes, other students faced a variety of challenges. Ferri, Grifoni and Guzzo (2020) emphasize that ERL exposed significant technological inequalities, particularly affecting students in under-resourced areas. This aligns with the experiences of students like Participant 12, who struggled with audio-visual synchronization and unstable networks, compounding difficulties for students whose first language is not English during listening exercises.

Not only do students face technical problems, but lecturers also encounter challenges. Participant 4 described a situation where a lecturer missed multiple classes due to device issues, which not only affected the course's progress but also reduced students' interest in the subject. Device issues are not limited to unstable networks. Participant 6's supervisor experienced disconnection during the opening seminar due to network problems, Participant 15's headphones malfunctioned during class, and Participant 3's computer automatically shut down due to overheating. The instances shared by Participant 6 and Participant 15 reflect Lawanto et al's. (2022) findings on unstructured and poorly designed online interactions, which increase anxiety and reduce motivation. Similarly, Participant 3's computer overheating emphasizes the need for proper device functionality, as technical failures undermine the continuity of learning.

Despite these challenges, some students have taken proactive measures. Participant 11 suggests using a computer or laptop for classes as screen size affects reading efficiency. To ensure a good online class experience, Participant 12 even uses two computers. These strategies align with Yang's (2023) emphasis on the flexibility of ERL to enable students to adapt and continue learning despite disruptions. Additionally, Participant 4 emphasizes the importance of testing devices before class to reduce the likelihood of technical issues. Several students (Participant 2, Participant

5, and Participant 6) mentioned that in the online class environment, both lecturers and students may be unaware of issues with screen sharing or microphones. Therefore, they stress the importance of timely communication between lecturers and students. Participant 6 further suggests, "If students encounter any problems during online classes, they should promptly inform the lecturer, as this will improve the quality of online classes." These students' experiences demonstrate that by taking appropriate measures, the impact of network and device issues on online learning can be minimized.

Participant 5 and Participant 12 mentioned that the university did not provide training on the functionality of the online platform, leaving students to figure out the features on their own. This lack of guidance makes it difficult for students to fully engage in online classrooms and effectively utilize online resources. Bozkurt and Sharma (2020) assert that ERL, as a rapid response, often neglects foundational elements like lecturer and student preparedness. This lack of guidance can impair students' ability to fully engage in online learning, limiting the benefits of digital tools and resources.

In conclusion, stable networks and devices are key factors in ensuring the smooth progress of online learning. Students should take active measures to address these challenges, and schools should provide necessary technical support and training to help students overcome technical issues and fully utilize online resources. Through communication and collaboration between lecturers and students, the effectiveness and quality of online learning can be maximized.

7.6 Autonomy in Online Learning and Blended Learning

7.6.1 Benefits and Challenges of Video and Recording Features

Students generally find the video recording feature very helpful in their learning. For example, Participant 3 said, "I would review the videos recorded during online classes as study materials to better prepare for exams." This indicates that the video recording

feature assists students in reviewing and preparing for exams. Participant 5 mentioned, "I usually don't use it, but if there's a topic I don't understand well, I would still use it." Participant 8 also expressed appreciation for the ability to watch class videos multiple times, demonstrating the flexibility and repeatability of the video recording feature. In situations where there is a conflict between the lecturer's availability and class time, as mentioned by Participant 4, "If the lecturer didn't have time for online classes, they would pre-record the lecture content and upload it to the school website for students to download and watch on their own." The recorded content serves as supplementary material. Participant 9 mentioned, "If I have any doubts, I can pause the learning video and search for information on the website to deepen my understanding of that specific topic." This shows that the pause function of videos helps in better understanding the content. In comparison to offline courses, Participant 10 pointed out, "I cannot review videos of offline lectures, and with the passage of time, sometimes information is forgotten." On the other hand, online courses can be recorded and learned anytime, anywhere, as mentioned by Participant 13, "One more convenient thing is that online courses can be recorded at any time and any place, so students can review them anytime, which is a great advantage."

However, excessive reliance on recordings may also lead to issues. Participant 12 mentioned, "Some students turn off their camera and microphone during online classes and do other things like playing games, working, or shopping, and then rely on the recorded video or audio to catch up. Although the classroom content is recorded, the synchronous interaction between lecturers and students, and among students, as well as group discussions, cannot be made up. Missing out on these opportunities will result in less practice in speaking." This suggests that over-reliance on videos may cause students to miss out on real-time interaction and speaking practice opportunities.

Students generally consider electronic notes to be an important tool in online learning platforms. For example, Participant 15 states, "What you see in online meetings and

seminars can be easily recorded, and then easily copied and saved, generating electronic notes." This is a significant advantage as it allows students to review materials at their own pace and retain information more effectively. Additionally, it makes it easier for students to revisit materials when preparing for exams or assignments.

The video recording feature in online courses exemplifies the strengths of asynchronous learning in blended environments, as highlighted by Bond *et al.*, (2021). It enables students to engage at their own pace, enhance understanding, and revisit material as needed. However, excessive reliance on recordings can undermine synchronous interactions, reducing opportunities for real-time engagement and skills development. A well-balanced approach to blended learning, integrating the strengths of both synchronous and asynchronous methods, is essential for fostering deep learning and maximizing educational outcomes.

7.6.2 Benefits and Challenges of the Subtitle Feature

According to the data, students may face challenges in understanding online course content due to lecturers' diverse accents (such as Scottish or Indian accents) and the lack of non-verbal cues typically available in face-to-face communication, such as eye contact and body language. As noted in Section 2.5.2, and as Zhang (2020) points out, Chinese students may find it challenging to fully understand lecturers' accents, which is further supported by Participant 3:

"Because of the lecturer's accent, like a Scottish or Indian accent, and the lack of intuitive feedback like eye contact, I often find it difficult to understand online content." Similarly, Participant 8 expressed, "Sometimes, the lecturers' English accents are not very standard, which makes it hard for us to fully understand what they are saying."

The subtitle feature offers a critical solution by providing real-time textual support during online lectures, allowing students to process the spoken content more effectively. Participant 3 specifically mentioned, "Subtitles are very helpful in understanding what the lecturer specifically said in lectures or tutorials." This aligns with findings from Krashen's (1985) Input Hypothesis, which emphasizes that comprehensible input slightly above the learner's current level facilitates language acquisition. Subtitles can help students bridge the gap between their current understanding and the lecture content, particularly when faced with unfamiliar accents or unclear pronunciations.

Although subtitles contribute to the understanding of online content, some students pointed out that online reading materials require more time to browse and understand compared to traditional offline classrooms. Participant 12 believes, "Online reading materials require more time, while offline classrooms allow for direct browsing and note-taking."; Participant 8 added, "Subtitles can help us Chinese students better understand some lecturers' non-standard English accents." The use of subtitles in online courses can indeed assist Chinese students in better-comprehending lecturers' non-standard English accents or unclear pronunciations. However, the impact of subtitles on oral English skills is a nuanced issue.

Despite these advantages, the reliance on subtitles raises concerns about their impact on oral English skills and listening comprehension (Ng, 2024). While subtitles provide immediate support, they can reduce the cognitive effort required to process spoken language, as Participant 11 pointed out, "If I always rely on subtitles to understand course content, I may miss opportunities to exercise my listening and speaking abilities." Ellis (1997) highlights the importance of active engagement and consciousness in the language acquisition process, which may be diminished when students overly depend on subtitles. Additionally, if the automatically generated subtitle content is inaccurate, it may lead to misunderstandings or confusion (Koh, 2022).

In conclusion, the subtitle function is a valuable tool in the online learning environment, for all students whose first language is not English. It can help them better understand and participate in courses in cross-cultural learning. However, to maximize its benefits and avoid potential risks, students should use this function moderately and combine it with other learning strategies to ensure a comprehensive and effective learning experience.

7.6.3 Enhancing Learner Autonomy in Online Learning

During my research, I found that students generally believe that online classrooms demand a higher level of autonomy in learning. For instance, Participant 3 noted, "Online classrooms can enhance self-control because I am forced to learn independently without the supervision and participation of lecturers and classmates." This aligns with the Self-Determination Theory (SDT) by Deci and Ryan (1985), which emphasizes the importance of autonomy as a core component of intrinsic motivation. When learners feel they have control over their educational process, they are more likely to engage deeply with the material and sustain their motivation over time.

Similarly, Participant 1 noted, "When participating in online courses, students need to learn more independently, as online courses may require students to listen and learn actively." These perspectives underscore the critical role of self-discipline and self-driven abilities in online learning.

Participant 14 added, "PhD students, in particular, need self-study skills", further emphasizing the importance of Self-directed Learning (Godwin-Jones, 2019), particularly at advanced educational stages where independent learning skills are essential for success.

One of the unique advantages of online learning is the ability to fully leverage the abundant resources available on the internet. Participant 14 specifically mentioned

that his online course was conducted entirely online, without any campus-based classes, which made him more reliant on online resources. They stated, "Apart from the online course modules, I believe we can also access other valuable information from the internet, which can supplement non-real-time classroom learning." This flexibility enables learners to tailor their educational content to align with their interests and learning objectives, fostering intrinsic motivation as described in Ryan and Deci's (2000) work on SDT.

The internet provides not only a wealth of learning resources such as websites, documents, and online tools, but also helps students gain a deeper understanding of course content and broaden their knowledge horizons (Smith *et al.*, 2014). For example, Participant 6 emphasized the help of Internet resources in his learning process:

"There are various learning resources available on the internet, such as a large number of electronic literature, instructional videos, and more. Sometimes, I also utilize the internet to search for information related to my research topics and participate in online seminars that interest me."

These resources are particularly valuable for students who are new to a country and face language challenges. Participant 9 shared how he overcame language barriers using online resources: "All Chinese students face language barriers when they first come to the UK, even if their IELTS scores are good, their academic English may not be. So, when I first came to the UK, I would search for instructional videos related to my major on YouTube and watch them repeatedly." This practice supports Krashen's (1985) Input Hypothesis, which posits that exposure to comprehensible input slightly above one's current level is critical for language acquisition.

Furthermore, the Internet facilitates academic exchanges. Participant 9 mentioned,

"I often participate in online seminars organized by the university, where I listen to other students introducing their research. We are usually busy with our own research, and it is difficult to gather in one physical location. Online academic seminars solve this problem." This aligns with Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs (1943), particularly the esteem and self-actualization levels.

This online interaction function gives students a convenient learning channel and fast access to the latest knowledge, an advantage over traditional offline courses. As Participant 1 and Participant 4 noted:

"In real-time online classes, when I encounter something, I don't understand, I can immediately search for the answer in the browser."

This instant access to information enhances learning efficiency and encourages students' autonomy and problem-solving skills. Besides, online classes offer a wider space for in-depth discussions. Tools like Chatbox and forums enable students to interact with classmates and lecturers from different backgrounds, promoting knowledge sharing and cultivating essential thinking skills and global perspectives. However, the benefits of traditional offline classrooms, such as face-to-face communication, real-time feedback, and rich body language exchanges, are hard to replicate online.

Lastly, Participant 8 emphasized the role of the Internet in improving language skills:

"At the beginning, I wasn't accustomed to the British accent and couldn't fully understand what they were saying. In my spare time, I would go to YouTube every day to find some videos to practise English and help improve my listening skills. I believe learning English is a process from difficult to easy." This example illustrates the interplay between extrinsic motivation (to succeed academically) and intrinsic motivation (a desire to improve linguistic competence). The gradual progression from "difficult to easy" in mastering English reflects the dynamic nature of motivation

outlined in Dörnyei's (1998) definition, which highlights the sustained effort required to achieve learning goals.

In conclusion, the internet provides abundant resources for online learning, potentially enhancing students' educational outcomes, expanding their knowledge base, promoting academic exchanges, and improving language skills. In this framework, "internet" includes not only online courses provided by educational institutions but also a wealth of resources for independent learning, serving as a valuable resource for students, even if their courses do not have online components. Students can freely explore a vast amount of information, interactive tools, and educational platforms, enriching their traditional classroom experience, diving deeper into personal interests, and better fostering and improving their self-learning abilities. Students are not just passive receivers of information; they become active participants in their educational development, utilizing online resources to fill their knowledge gaps, explore new areas of interest, and connect with content that aligns with their learning goals.

7.7 Motivation for Online Oral Expression

7.7.1 Motivation for Learners' Oral Expression and Shifts Towards Independent Learning

The Ideal L2 Self (IL2S), a key part of Dörnyei's (2005) L2 Motivational Self System (L2MSS, as discussed in Section 4.2.1), represents students' aspirations to use a second language (English) fluently. While the IL2S focuses on personal goals, the Ought-to L2 Self (OL2S), driven by external expectations, often motivates initial engagement, particularly in oral expression. Additionally, Group Discussions and the Second Language Learning Experience (SLLE) foster motivation through meaningful and interactive learning, supporting both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation.

Enthusiasm for oral expression plays a crucial role in the use of spoken language. Some students demonstrate high levels of enthusiasm for participating in online

classroom discussions. They willingly engage in communication with lecturers and classmates, actively practising their oral skills. For example,

Participant 3 states,

"I have online communication with the teaching and tutoring staff every week, and the lecturer provides me with opportunities for oral communication. Even online, we still understand each other and express our opinions." Participant 3 highlights weekly online interactions with teaching staff, emphasizing the role of such opportunities in fostering oral practice. This reflects the IL2S (Dörnyei, 2005) as a vision of oneself as a confident communicator in English, driving participation.

Similarly, Participant 14 expresses a positive attitude, saying, "I actually participate in oral discussions quite often in online classes." Participant 4 believes that actively practising oral skills contributes to personal development, stating, "I will try to speak English in online classes and continue to improve my oral proficiency." These examples reflect the efforts students make to develop their oral English skills. Participant 14's positive attitude toward frequent discussions indicates that their IL2S is well-developed, as they envision themselves as fluent English speakers.

Furthermore, English oral skills serve as a means for students to acquire knowledge and information. Through group discussions, students can exchange ideas, culture, and knowledge, achieving a comprehensive integration of these aspects. Participant 3 shares their experience, saying, "I have a lot of opinions on this, and other group members agree with my ideas. So, I think it was a successful conversation, and I also learned a lot from other international students." As Dörnyei (2009) noted, language learning is deeply connected to psychological processes and identity formation. The collaborative and interactive nature of group discussions helps students integrate language learning into their self-concept, reinforcing their motivation.

Over time, students' motivation for oral expression may change, aligning with the dynamic nature of motivation in the L2MSS theory. Initially, students may be driven by novelty and external expectations (the "should L2 self") to actively participate. However, as time progresses, their focus may shift towards the experience and feelings during the learning process (L2 learning experiences). Participant 7 describes the change in their motivation for oral expression when they first started and after a period of time.

Participant 7 states,

"At the beginning of online classes, I was very proactive and answered whatever the lecturer asked. If I didn't know how to express myself clearly, I would use translation software and then communicate with the lecturer. But after a while, I rarely initiated communication. Because some questions can be answered in the pre-reading materials provided by the lecturer, I just read them myself."

The findings align with Kim and Kim (2011), who observed that IL2S is closely linked to specific learning strategies and behaviours. Participant 7's shift toward independent learning, characterized by a preference for solving problems autonomously, may reduce direct communication and interaction, potentially impacting motivation for oral expression. However, reduced real-time interaction does not necessarily diminish oral expression ability. Students can continue to enhance their skills through online discussions, group projects, and other collaborative activities. In conclusion, while independent learning may alter a student's approach, it does not inherently weaken their motivation for oral expression, as IL2S remains a key driving force in their language learning journey.

7.7.2 Educational and Cultural Influences on Oral Expression

In the context of studying abroad, students often face differences in culture and education systems that may significantly impact on their oral language skills and

classroom participation. These differences can be reflected not only in teaching methods and academic requirements but also in the ways students are encouraged to communicate and engage in class. Through interviews with students, it is clear how contrasts between the Chinese and UK education systems influence the development of oral English skills among Chinese students.

Firstly, structural differences in the Chinese and UK education systems can shape how students develop oral proficiency (Wei, 2022). According to Participant 1,

"I believe that the education systems in China and the UK are different. In the UK classroom, lecturers may pay more attention to each student's own ideas and encourage them to express their own opinions. In China, there are more people in the classroom, and the lecturer may not be able to ask every student, so students have relatively fewer opportunities for oral expression."

This highlights how smaller UK class sizes and a focus on individual expression can foster oral participation, potentially enhancing students' critical thinking and communication skills. In contrast, larger class sizes in China may offer fewer opportunities for verbal expression, which can affect students' comfort and proficiency in speaking over time.

Differences in teaching approaches also can play a key role. Participant 6 noted, "UK classrooms generally revolve around students, while many Chinese classrooms revolve around lecturers, where lecturers lecture and students listen." Such differences mean that new students may need time to adjust to the more interactive format of UK classrooms, which require greater verbal engagement. However, students often find that preparatory English courses do not fully prepare them for the oral demands of the UK system. For example, Participant 2 shared that the knowledge taught in language classes is "not particularly difficult," and the sudden requirement of giving a speech posed a challenge for him. Participant 2 noted

"This indicates that preparatory courses should give more emphasis to academic oral and presentation skills training as pre-English courses to better help Chinese students adapt to the academic environment in the UK."

In addition to educational approaches, cultural differences may influence the development of oral language skills. Participant 3 emphasized the importance of using appropriate English vocabulary to express emotions and avoid cultural misunderstandings, which is essential in cross-cultural interactions. For many, language preparatory courses play an essential role in building confidence for verbal communication. Participant 11 found the academic writing and presentation training particularly helpful.

However, some students, like Participant 2, felt that the preparatory language course was "not as difficult as the IELTS preparation courses in China" and more focused on "an inspiring way of learning" though it mainly focused on basic vocabulary and learning objectives. They found the transition challenging, noting that "after the five-week language class, the lecturer asked us to write a 1,000-word essay straight away," which felt like a significant leap in difficulty given the simplicity of prior exercises. From Participant 2's perspective, "the course may be designed to transition students 'from Chinese to English education' and to 'slowly transform students from bottom English thinking to pure English thinking.'" However, they felt that at their age, "some of the habits of mind may have been fixed long ago," and that what is needed is more targeted training in academic English.

In summary, the data from my participants suggests that differences in education systems and cultural expectations significantly impact the development of oral language skills for Chinese students. Students felt that, to better support their verbal proficiency, educational practices should focus on building cross-cultural communication skills and creating targeted academic English programmes that prioritize speaking and oral engagement. They believed that enhancing these programmes would help them transition more smoothly into the interactive and

discussion-based environment of UK academic life.

7.7.3 Factors Influencing Motivation for Oral Expression

In addition to students' motivation and emotions, several other factors can impact their oral expression.

7.7.3.1 Differences in Academic Disciplines

In discussing the varying importance of English oral proficiency across disciplines, Participant 10 from the School of Computer Science, notes that their field does not demand a high level of spoken English. As a result, they seldom engage in group discussions, whether in online or on-campus courses. Conversely, Participant 2's course places a stronger emphasis on developing English oral skills. Participant 2 explains that online courses have provided a learning experience comparable to or even better than face-to-face teaching. They actively participate in group discussions, share opinions, and receive feedback from classmates, which makes them feel genuinely involved in the class.

This contrast highlights the role of Dörnyei's (2009) L2MSS in shaping language learning behaviours. Participant 2's active engagement in oral discussions can be linked to their "ideal L2 self," which represents their aspiration to become a proficient English speaker. This vision likely motivates them to take full advantage of online platforms for interaction and feedback, aligning with Dörnyei and Kubanyiova's (2014) emphasis on the importance of building vivid, future-oriented self-images in language learning contexts.

For Participant 15, a Biology PhD student, oral proficiency holds minimal relevance to their academic research; as a result, their spoken English has not significantly improved even after pursuing a doctoral degree in the UK. This case reflects the diminished role of the "ought-to L2 self"—the external obligations or pressures to use spoken English in their field. According to Dörnyei (2005), when the "ought-to L2

self" does not align with the individual's goals or immediate environment, the motivational drive can wane, as evidenced by Participant 15's minimal emphasis on oral skills in their discipline.

In contrast, other participants highlight the essential role of English oral skills in their international education experience. For instance, Participant 4 emphasized their personal commitment to improving spoken English for self-development and to benefit others, stating, "I will try and am still trying my best to speak English, just for my own benefit to improve myself and to improve others." This aligns with Dörnyei's (1994) notion that intrinsic motivation, fuelled by self-improvement and personal fulfilment, can be a powerful force in language learning. Such self-determined motivation underpins Participant 4's sustained effort to develop their English skills, reflecting a proactive engagement with their "ideal L2 self."

Participant 1 also noted the importance of using English, especially in classes in which there is a diversity of learners: "I think most of the students in the class are from different countries, so I think it is better to speak English so that everyone understands." This example demonstrates the motivational role of social context, as described by Dörnyei (2001), where the learning environment fosters a sense of responsibility and inclusion, prompting learners to use the target language actively.

Several participants see English communication as essential to fully participating in UK-based education. Participant 12 commented, "I think that since students choose to come to the UK, it is important to communicate in English in class as much as possible." Likewise, Participant 13 emphasized, "Because we are now being educated in a UK university, we still have to speak English in class. Speaking Chinese is not conducive to the lecturers' teaching and the student's understanding, including learning, and I think we should avoid using Chinese in this situation." Participant 14 added, "I actually have quite a lot of discussions in class," underscoring the interactive aspect of their academic experience.

The immediate environment, including peer interactions and institutional expectations, shapes these participants' motivation to prioritise English use. Dörnyei and Ushioda (2001) emphasised that such contextual factors can reinforce the learner's engagement by creating opportunities to connect their current self with their envisioned future self as proficient English communicators.

These perspectives illustrate how the need for English oral proficiency varies across disciplines and individual approaches to international study, with some students prioritizing its development as a core part of their educational experience.

7.7.3.2 Emotions, Confidence, and Stress Factors in Online Oral Participation

Participant 2 noted that online classes can provide a more forgiving environment for students who may not feel at their best emotionally. He shared, "But if a student is not in a good mood and doesn't want to talk, then the online class is more friendly." This statement reflects the role of affective factors in motivation, as proposed by Krashen's (1985) Affective Filter Hypothesis, which emphasizes that emotions such as stress and anxiety can either facilitate or hinder language learning.

Confidence in the subject matter also appears to influence participation levels. Participant 4 pointed out a common issue in online courses, stating, "Mostly we just silence and we don't talk. Everyone dislikes to talk in my courses. We wait for people to talk, but then nobody talks, so we just silence, don't talk for the whole time." This passivity suggests a lack of intrinsic motivation and self-efficacy, as defined by Deci and Ryan (1985) in their SDT. This passive environment suggests that students may lack the confidence to express themselves, often preferring to remain silent and wait for others to initiate conversation. Such behaviour highlights a need for strategies within online classrooms to encourage active participation and help students build confidence in sharing their ideas.

In comparison, Participant 3 believes that the stress level is significantly reduced in offline courses, particularly regarding verbal expression. He stated, "Offline courses are more interactive and more interesting. Lecturers can ask questions, and you can talk directly to the lecturers without a screen. It is less stressful." This highlights the importance of face-to-face interaction, where non-verbal cues such as facial expressions and body language play a vital role in reducing communication barriers. According to Maslow's (1943) framework, offline settings better fulfil students' needs for social interaction and belonging, creating a supportive space for verbal expression.

Overall, these insights indicate that online learning environments could benefit from strategies designed to foster an inclusive and supportive atmosphere. By helping students feel comfortable sharing ideas and asking questions, educators can promote engagement, reduce stress, and improve the overall effectiveness of online participation (Brown *et al.*, 2022).

7.7.3.3 Cultural Background and the Role of Social Capital in Communication Preferences

Chinese students often gravitate towards communicating within their own cultural circles, creating a sense of cultural comfort and familiarity. This tendency can be seen in Participant 1's approach, who stated, "I don't actively participate in discussions, but if the lecturer directly asks me a question, then I will respond." This passive attitude reflects a reliance on bonding social capital, where individuals derive strength and support from similar others within their own cultural group.

Contrastingly, Participant 2 exhibits a different behaviour, actively seeking to engage in cross-cultural environments. He said, "I regularly take the initiative to answer questions and add energy to the classroom, even during group discussions." This proactive stance demonstrates a utilization of bridging social capital, where individuals cultivate relationships and connections with those outside their immediate cultural circle, fostering diversity and broader perspectives.

The contrast between these two participants highlights the importance of balancing bonding and bridging social capital in online learning environments. While it is comfortable and reassuring to rely on one's own cultural group, actively seeking cross-cultural interactions can lead to richer learning experiences and a deeper understanding of diverse perspectives.

7.7.4 Participation and Pseudo-participation

The term "pseudo-participation" in an online classroom, as I define it, refers to students who have technically fulfilled the formality of participating in class activities (such as logging into the online classroom with their electronic accounts) but are not genuinely engaged in the learning process. This includes behaviours like turning off their cameras and not actively participating in class interactions, indicative of a lack of deep thinking and substantial learning. The emergence of pseudo-participation is closely related to the unique environment of online classrooms. The anonymity of online classrooms can easily lead to a relaxed mentality among some students, and the lack of face-to-face interaction may decrease their motivation to learn and level of engagement. Additionally, the absence of real-time supervision and feedback from lecturers may lead students to lower their standards for themselves, making pseudo-participation more likely.

In English learning environments, many students in the research believe that campus classrooms provide a superior experience for participation and immersion. Face-to-face communication is seen by most students as the preferred method for language learning. Many students believe that campus classrooms are more conducive to Participant and immersive English learning, and they prefer face-to-face communication. As an example of task-based learning, this emphasises real-authentic communication as a core element of language learning (Prahbu, 1990; Van den Branden, 2016). Participants highlighted the advantages of offline learning environments for facilitating these real-world interactions.

Participant 9 said, "I believe I can better converse in English face-to-face"; Participant 2 emphasized the role of a rich language environment in developing speaking skills. "In offline environments, you may experience higher levels of engagement and immersion. Interacting well and learning effectively become easier."

As Participant 9 emphasized, face-to-face communication in offline settings fosters greater engagement and immersion, aligning with TBLT's (Ellis *et al.*, 2020) focus on goal-oriented tasks that mimic authentic conversational contexts. The offline environment allows learners to experience more natural and meaningful exchanges, thus improving their fluency. Furthermore, this observation ties closely to Bourdieu's (1977) concept of embodied cultural capital, where the skills, behaviours, and interactional competencies that students acquire through direct, face-to-face engagement reflect deeply internalised forms of cultural knowledge. For Chinese students, participating in physical classrooms not only enhances language proficiency but also enriches their embodied cultural capital by internalising communication norms and social behaviours prevalent in Western educational settings.

As pointed out by Participant 10, "Offline, I can interpret meaning based on the other person's body movements, which heavily relies on eye contact and gestures." Participant 10 noted the importance of non-verbal cues like eye contact and gestures in offline interactions. These cues enhance communication, making it easier to interpret meaning and fostering deeper engagement, consistent with TBLT's (Ellis 2003; Long 2015) emphasis on using real language to solve real problems.

Participant 6 also agrees, stating that a tangible classroom environment is more conducive to communication and expressing ideas. They stated that,

"In offline classrooms, students have more opportunities to interact face-to-face with lecturers and classmates. If they encounter unclear concepts, they can directly approach people around them for clarification."

Such non-verbal elements also contribute to the habitus of students. According to Wacquant (2005, p. 316), habitus encompasses the durable, internalised patterns of thought, perception, and action shaped by social and cultural structures. The ability to interpret body language and gestures is part of the habitus that students develop through repeated offline interactions, which may not be adequately cultivated in online classrooms. This reinforces the disparity between offline and online learning environments in shaping effective communicative practices.

Participant 8 also feels that their involvement in online classes is primarily limited to passively watching the screen, with fewer opportunities for active engagement than in classroom-based learning. They further explained, "The difference is the level of communication. I think offline it is a bit more direct; you can feel the emotions of the lecturer and students more directly. Online, it is probably just talking to a screen, and people can only focus on listening and speaking." Participant 6 also points out the lack of face-to-face interaction in online classrooms, which reduces the learning experience for Chinese students in the UK and limits their exposure to British culture. It is worth noting that Participant 8 defines their relationship with the instructor as similar to an online friendship, with limited face-to-face communication. This lack of meaningful interaction reflects the challenges of acquiring cultural capital in online environments. As Bourdieu (1997) notes, embodied cultural capital is typically acquired through immersive, face-to-face interactions, which are difficult to replicate in virtual settings. Consequently, Chinese students in online classrooms may struggle to fully internalise the communicative norms of British higher education.

"Initially, it was difficult for me to adapt, especially in a virtual environment where I couldn't establish a genuine face-to-face connection with the lecturer, as if we were just online acquaintances. (Participant 8)" This observation aligns with Wacquant's (2005) concept of habitus, for Participant 8, the absence of face-to-face interaction hampers the development of a habitus that aligns with the norms and expectations of

the UK educational system, thereby affecting their ability to build meaningful academic relationships.

For doctoral students without fixed classes, online learning greatly reduces opportunities for interaction with others. Participant 13 and Participant 15 point out that their communication with mentors and classmates is very limited. However, informal learning in online classrooms poses more challenges. Participant 4 and Participant 5 noted that after transitioning to online classrooms, Chinese students had fewer opportunities for communication with foreign classmates. Participant 4 believes, "I think physical classrooms are more suitable for international students. You can have them interact more with local students to overcome their fear of speaking, both before and after class." This challenge is closely tied to the development of bridging social capital, as described by Putnam (2000). Bridging social capital facilitates connections across diverse groups, enabling Chinese students to interact with local and international peers and gain exposure to new perspectives. However, the lack of informal, spontaneous interactions in online classrooms restricts these opportunities, limiting their ability to develop broader social networks.

Participant 2 shared an unpleasant experience in an online class: during a group discussion, a classmate turned off their microphone and camera, hindering communication. They believe this is disrespectful to other group members. Participant 2 states, "Based on my experience, students shouldn't keep their cameras off for the entire class or half of the class without interacting with the lecturer. It is like the lecturer is performing a monologue." They believe that such behaviour disrupts the interactivity and sense of participation in the classroom. The phenomenon of pseudo-participation not only affects the collaborative nature of learning but also diminishes the potential for social and cultural capital acquisition. Bourdieu (1986) argues that social capital relies on active participation in relational networks; thus, passive behaviours in online settings undermine students' ability to build and leverage these networks for academic and personal growth.

Participant 4 shares that their courses often organize online group discussions. Participant 13 mentions that in online academic conferences, there is usually a Q&A session at the end, providing participants with opportunities for oral interaction. "After the presentation, the speaker provides a final Q&A session. It is a chance to participate and I practice my speaking skills during this time." Participant 14 believes that staying in touch with classmates through chat applications is still feasible. Participant 8, studying in the UK during the pandemic, actively seeks opportunities to participate in British society and create opportunities for oral practice. These examples highlight the potential for online environments to foster linking social capital, as Woolcock (1998) describes. By participating in structured discussions, academic conferences, and extracurricular activities, students can access external networks and resources, bridging the gap between their immediate academic communities and broader professional or social networks.

In conclusion, students from different majors have varied experiences with online courses. While some courses successfully promote students' English-speaking skills, others fall short. This indicates that there is room for improvement in online learning environments in terms of providing effective participation and support for language learning.

7.7.5 Balancing Silent and Oral Communication: The Dual Role of the Chatbox in Online Learning

The Chatbox functionality has become an essential communication tool in online learning environments. This feature is particularly valuable for introverted or shy students, including many students from Asian countries. In a traditional face-to-face classroom, these students may feel anxious about speaking fluently or making mistakes. The Chatbox provides a safe space for them to express their thoughts through written text, allowing them to participate more actively in classroom discussions. As Rogers (1960s) highlights in his humanistic approach, self-directed learning fosters confidence and autonomy, and Chatbox enables students to engage at

their comfort level. Similarly, Maslow's (1943) hierarchy of needs emphasizes the importance of a supportive environment in addressing emotional and cognitive barriers, which the Chatbox can help to mitigate.

Participant 2 agrees, stating,

"The Chatbox feature greatly facilitates communication among shy students. In online courses, shy Chinese or other Asian students can share their viewpoints through the Chatbox, eliminating the need for oral expression and significantly reducing their pressure."

Moreover, modern computer and mobile phone input methods, including spell-check and auto-correct features, further support learning by alleviating pressure on writing and minimizing errors. This reflects Vygotsky's (1978) scaffolding theory, where tools reduce cognitive load, enabling students to focus on meaningful interaction.

However, as with any tool, the Chatbox functionality comes with its advantages and disadvantages. On one hand, it offers a vital communication channel for shy students, facilitating their participation in a less intimidating manner. On the other hand, an excessive reliance on this text-based communication mode can lead to negative consequences, particularly for Chinese students. A significant concern is that over-dependence on this mode might hinder the development of speaking skills, as noted by Bruner (1960), who emphasized the importance of verbal interaction for cultivating critical thinking and problem-solving skills.

Participant 1 highlighted, "We often just type and discuss in the application without anyone speaking." indicating a preference for typing over verbal interaction. Similarly, Participant 15 observed, "We just type and send messages, and very few people choose to communicate through voice or video," further underscoring the tendency to avoid using speaking as a means of communication. Stevick (1996) underscores that balanced lecturer control and student agency are essential for effective learning;

over-reliance on text-based communication could limit students' ability to develop oral proficiency.

Furthermore, Participant 10 shared his experience of asking questions to classmates by typing messages via the Chatbox in class. "Sometimes we ask each other questions, but we do it through sending text messages via the Chatbox. This method is convenient, but you don't need to speak orally, just send a text message." While this form of communication promotes learning to some extent, it deprives students of the opportunity to practice their speaking skills.

The integration of the Chatbox feature into online learning environments introduces a pivotal dimension to education. This tool facilitates self-expression and inclusivity, aligning with humanistic principles such as Moskowitz's (1978) emphasis on autonomy and Williams and Burden's (1997) view of collaborative learning environments. However, educators must strike a balance, ensuring the Chatbox complements rather than replaces verbal communication. Speaking cultivates listening comprehension, pronunciation, and impromptu thinking—skills that text-based tools alone cannot nurture.

By integrating task-based activities (Ellis, 2000; Van den Branden, 2016) that require both written and spoken participation, educators can enhance fluency and accuracy, achieving the balanced interaction emphasized by Constructivist Learning Theory. The objective should be to ensure the Chatbox serves as a supportive tool, fostering confidence and engagement while promoting oral proficiency. Adopting this balanced approach can help students develop holistically in online learning environments, bridging the gap between text-based and spoken communication.

7.8 Use of L1

7.8.1 Conscious Use of L1

7.8.1.1 Attitudes of students towards Using L1

When discussing the attitudes of Chinese students towards using L1 (their first language, i.e., Chinese) in different contexts, we can analyze it from the perspective of translanguaging theory (Garcia, 2009; Canagarajah, 2011; Li, 2018). The translanguaging theory (which I detailed in section 3.4.3) suggests that language users flexibly select and utilize different language resources based on social environments and task demands. This choice is not only based on the practicality of the language itself but also closely related to the language users' identity, cultural background, and social practices.

In this study, most participants believed that using L1 in informal contexts is understandable because it facilitates more effective communication. For example, Participant 3 said, "If they occasionally speak Chinese, I think it is acceptable. When Chinese people communicate with each other, speaking Chinese is a simpler way without barriers. Communication is effective." This resonates with Garcia and Lin's (2017) argument that translanguaging strategies enable bilingual or multilingual speakers to address specific communicative challenges.

P6 also expressed,

"For Chinese students, especially in the early stages of studying in the UK, their language logic is not flexible enough to switch between Chinese and English. Therefore, lecturers and students should understand them more and not rush them." This aligns with Garcia and Lin's (2017) observation that translanguaging is an effective strategy to address specific communicative needs in bilingual or multilingual contexts. In informal contexts, using L1 may help convey meaning more directly and accurately, reducing the possibility of misunderstandings and facilitating smoother interaction (Wei, 2023).

However, using L1 in academic settings is more complex. Some participants believed that occasionally using L1 in group work is acceptable and even beneficial because it helps improve communication efficiency. This viewpoint reflects the practical considerations of language choice in translanguaging theory (Canagarajah, 2013). However, Participant 13 also expressed concerns that excessive reliance on L1 may hinder English learning. He said, "Using Chinese means that English speaking practice cannot be relatively strengthened. Because using Chinese in meetings and discussions is not conducive to English speaking practice." This aligns with Krashen's (1985) Input Hypothesis, which highlights the importance of exposure to comprehensible L2 input for language acquisition. Over-reliance on L1 could reduce opportunities for meaningful L2 interaction, thereby hindering fluency development.

It is consistent with the findings of the Tai and Chen (2023) study, which identified reasons why Chinese students use their first language for communication, including fear of making mistakes, lack of confidence in English skills, and unfamiliarity with English technical terms. This may be related to the educational experiences Chinese students have had for a long time, where they are afraid of making mistakes and failing.

Furthermore, some students mentioned that using L1 in the classroom may be due to Chinese students' limited fluency in speaking or their inability to think in English. This viewpoint reveals the cognitive and metalinguistic aspects of language use, which are also important aspects of interest in translanguaging theory. The research analysis by Ossa Parra and Proctor (2021) found that translingual teaching aids students in language analysis. The study suggests that translingual teaching not only enhances students' metalinguistic awareness and cognitive involvement but also allows them to position themselves as professional linguists.

At the same time, concerns about using L1 leading to discrimination or disrespect reflect sociocultural factors in language use. Participant 15 pointed out, "But if there are people from other countries in the group discussion on my subject course,

speaking Chinese would exclude non-Chinese students from the discussion, which I think is very bad and very racist." Participant 4 believed, "I think it is a bit impolite to speak Chinese in public." Translanguaging theory emphasizes the close connection between language choice and identity and social relationships (Garcia and Leiva, 2014). In this case, using L1 may be seen as excluding or disrespecting Chinese speakers who do not have English as their first language, which can lead to social conflicts and negative evaluations. Zhang and Chan's (2017) analysis of multilingual communication in Macau supports this view, showing how language practices can both build community and unintentionally exclude others if not carefully managed.

In conclusion, the use of L1 by Chinese students in different contexts can be analyzed from various perspectives of translanguaging theory. This theoretical framework not only explains why students choose to use L1 but also reveals the sociocultural, cognitive, and practical considerations behind this choice. In future education and language policies, more attention should be paid to how to balance the use of different languages to meet students' communicative needs and promote their multilingual development.

7.8.1.2 Attitudes of Lecturers Towards Using L1

According to the L2MSS (as cited in Section 4.2.1) theory (Dörnyei, 2005), lecturers' attitudes towards students' use of L1 (Chinese) can be influenced by various motivational factors. L2MSS theory emphasizes that learners' motivation comes not only from external pressure or rewards but also from internal self-identity and interest in the target language culture. Therefore, lecturers' attitudes may reflect their views on learners' self-identity and language learning goals.

Some participants responded that their lecturers have a tolerant attitude towards students' use of Chinese, allowing them to communicate in Chinese in informal settings. This attitude may stem from the lecturers' understanding that using the mother tongue can help students communicate more effectively, alleviate language

anxiety, and promote their social interaction in an academic environment. This corresponds to the concept of the "ideal L2 self" in L2MSS (Dörnyei, 2005), where learners aspire to become their ideal selves through mastery of the target language. In this case, lecturers may believe that using Chinese helps students express themselves better and achieve self-identity. For example, Participant 2 shared that some lecturers allow students to communicate in Chinese, which they find friendly.

Participant 2 further added, "English is the language of the classroom, and lecturers want to create more opportunities for students to practice English." lecturers may believe that to improve students' English proficiency, it is necessary to create an all-English learning environment. This viewpoint reflects the concept of the "ought-to L2 self" in L2MSS (Dörnyei, 2005), where learners feel the need to master the target language to meet external expectations or requirements. In this case, lecturers may consider restricting the use of Chinese as necessary to ensure that students can achieve the expected level of English.

It is worth noting that some students mix Chinese and English when communicating with their supervisors, especially when the supervisors are also Chinese. Participant 14 mixes Chinese and English when meeting with their supervisor because the supervisor is Chinese. This highlights the importance of adaptability in language use, especially in multicultural environments. Additionally, Participant 6 believes that using Chinese in communication with Chinese lecturers may be more efficient, while using English may be more appropriate when communicating with British supervisors.

Participant 6 said,

"When I communicate with my first supervisor, we choose to discuss in Chinese so that he can better understand the problems I encounter in my research. This means that there will be no communication barriers between me and my supervisor."

This situation indicates that language use is flexible and can be adjusted based on communicative needs and social environments. This is related to the concept of "language learning experience" in L2MSS, where learners adjust their learning strategies and language use based on past experiences and current environments.

In summary, lecturers' attitudes towards students' use of L1 may be influenced by various motivational factors, including their views on learners' self-identity and language learning goals. In educational practice, the interview findings suggest that considering individual differences and language learning needs of students to develop appropriate teaching strategies and language use rules. Likewise, students need to adapt their language use based on their learning goals and social environments.

7.8.2 Unconscious Use of L1

The phenomenon of unconsciously using one's mother tongue (Chinese) while expressing oneself in the second language (L2) has been a topic of interest in language acquisition and second language acquisition research. This study observed that some students unconsciously use their mother tongue, Chinese, while expressing themselves in English.

When discussing the phenomenon of students unconsciously using their first language (L1, Chinese) while using the second language (L2), we can analyze it from the perspective of translanguaging theory. Translanguaging theory emphasizes that language users flexibly select and utilize different language resources based on communicative needs, identity, and social practices. This language use is not limited to within a single language but may involve the interweaving use of multiple languages.

Firstly, for English non-native speakers, unconsciously using their L1 as a coping strategy when facing difficulties in expressing themselves or needing quick responses

in L2 is a natural response. This is because their L1 is deeply ingrained in their language system and becomes an instinctive reaction.

As Participant 9 stated,

"When communicating in English, sometimes I find it difficult to respond quickly, even if I understand the course materials. I unconsciously use my mother tongue because, for me, it is easier to express my thoughts."

This phenomenon aligns with the concept of flexible use of language resources in translinguaging theory. Martin et al. (2006) found that to effectively complete teaching tasks, lecturers and students spontaneously switch between English and Gujarati. This flexible use of language resources within these schools did not provoke any concerns or inquiries among those involved, instead, the schools were recognized as secure environments where students could freely express their multilingual identities (Martin *et al.*, 2006). In this case, students are not simply switching from one language to another but bridging between the two languages to meet current communicative needs.

Secondly, it is worth noting that not only students but also non-native English-speaking lecturers may experience similar situations of unconsciously using their L1. This further confirms the influence of identity and social practices on language choice, as emphasized in translinguaging theory. Participant 12 mentioned, "My supervisor is Italian and sometimes unconsciously uses Italian words. This is because his mind reflects Italian thoughts at that moment. Similarly, if a student blurts out one or two words in their mother tongue, it should be considered normal." Both lecturers and students may encounter vocabulary or structural difficulties when using L2, and in such cases, they may rely on L1 to fill the gaps and ensure smooth communication.

Furthermore, translanguaging theory also emphasizes the cognitive and metalinguistic aspects of language use. When students struggle to find appropriate L2 expressions, they may resort to using L1 to describe or explain concepts. This phenomenon reflects students' cognitive strategies when dealing with complex language tasks. By using L1, they can convey meaning more accurately and reduce cognitive burden.

To sum up, the phenomenon of students unconsciously using L1 while using L2 can be reasonably explained from the perspective of translanguaging theory. This phenomenon not only reveals the flexibility and diversity in language use but also emphasizes the role of identity, social practices, and cognitive strategies in language choice. In future research on second language acquisition, more attention should be paid to the phenomenon of translanguaging to gain a more comprehensive understanding of learners' needs and challenges.

7.9 Further Challenges of Online Learning

7.9.1 Issues Regarding the Security of Assessments in Online Presentations

As education transitions to online modes, maintaining fairness in assessment, particularly in oral presentations, becomes a challenging issue. The unique characteristics of online environments can undermine traditional assessment methods, occasionally raising ethical and reputational concerns. Bozkurt and Sharma (2020) highlight that emergency remote teaching, implemented during the COVID-19 pandemic, exposed significant challenges in maintaining equitable assessment conditions, particularly due to variations in students' access to reliable technology and internet infrastructure. These disparities create unequal opportunities for students to perform to their full potential, affecting the overall fairness of assessments.

In traditional, in-person settings, exam supervision is direct, with proctors monitoring the room in real-time to ensure adherence to exam rules. This supervision reduces cheating risks and ensures fairness. Participant 3 remarked, "Every university

prohibits cheating in offline courses," underscoring the value of fairness in traditional settings. However, the online format introduces new complexities. As Participant 2 elaborated, "Some students prepare speeches before oral exams, read them off outside the view of the camera, and thus score high marks in the exam." Without real-time proctoring, online assessments may allow for cheating, particularly in oral presentations where students might read pre-prepared texts, hindering the authenticity of their spoken skills assessment. As Lassoued et al. (2020) emphasize, the lack of uniform policies and clear guidelines in online learning environments contributes to the uneven application of assessment methods, further exacerbating issues of parity and fairness.

This shift to online assessments has led to inconsistencies across different courses and departments. Some educators or institutions may allow reference materials during presentations, while others attempt to uphold traditional, stricter protocols, leading to varied assessment standards. Such discrepancies affect the consistency of oral language skill evaluations, impacting students' grades and the perceived fairness of assessments.

Additionally, internet instability poses a notable challenge. In a physical exam, candidates experience the same environmental factors, but in online settings, internet reliability varies. For students in regions with poor connectivity, interruptions during live oral assessments can impact their ability to complete assignments on time, directly affecting scores and grades. Participant 5, for example, experienced a network interruption while submitting an audio file, resulting in a delayed submission. Bozkurt and Sharma (2020) argue that such technological barriers disproportionately disadvantage students from under-resourced regions, creating unequal conditions that can undermine the validity of assessments.

7.9.2 Network Restrictions and Time Zone Challenges Affecting Oral Participation

For Chinese students, network restrictions and time zone differences present significant challenges to developing oral language skills in online courses. These issues impact students' engagement and complicate opportunities to practice speaking skills effectively. The recent COVID-19 pandemic has only intensified these difficulties, especially for those in doctoral research.

For instance, Participant 15 experienced difficulties with oral data collection due to restrictions on face-to-face interaction. "The outbreak disrupted my data collection plan. I had intended to visit companies in person, but now I can only conduct interviews through phone or WeChat. This method makes it difficult to establish trust with the interviewees and fails to capture subtle non-verbal communication." In-person interviews would have provided richer, more natural data collection for Participant 15's study. However, moving to phone and WeChat interactions created a less engaging environment, limiting non-verbal communication and trust-building, which are essential for gathering quality spoken data. The pandemic has underscored the need for flexibility in research methods to preserve the accuracy of data involving verbal interaction (Liu and Shirley, 2021).

In addition to the challenges posed by remote interaction, network restrictions in China complicate students' access to resources essential for improving oral skills. Students often face barriers to accessing platforms like Google, YouTube, or educational sites with oral practice tools. Some students use Virtual Private Networks (VPNs) to bypass these restrictions, yet this presents additional issues. Participant 3 noted, "When studying in China, the Wi-Fi is usually stable, but occasionally I need to use a VPN. In reality, I don't have a legal VPN solution, so it really bothers me." The need for unauthorized VPNs poses both legal and technical challenges for students, affecting their ability to access English-speaking resources. Furthermore, unauthorized VPN use is risky and unreliable, as such services can be shut down, disrupting learning. This ongoing challenge suggests a need for universities to consider secure, ethical solutions that can enhance access to oral practice resources.

Time zone differences also significantly impact students' ability to practice and participate in real-time spoken activities (Yang, 2022). When Chinese students join online courses based in countries like the UK, the time difference, coupled with daylight-saving adjustments, can make it difficult for them to engage effectively. Scheduling misalignments disrupt circadian rhythms and can diminish oral participation during live sessions. Students may miss out on real-time language practice, potentially impacting oral fluency and confidence.

In conclusion, network restrictions and time zone challenges present barriers to Chinese students' development of oral language skills and access to quality resources. Addressing these challenges will require creative strategies from students and support from educational institutions, ensuring that online learning environments promote equal access to spoken language practice and support the development of verbal proficiency.

7.10 Conclusion

This chapter has explored the multifaceted experiences of Chinese international students in online learning, addressing both advantages (e.g., safety, flexibility, and access to resources) and challenges (e.g., interaction limitations, mental health, and assessment fairness). These findings underscore the need for tailored strategies to optimize online learning environments, with a focus on balancing autonomy, interaction, and support systems.

The next chapter will engage in a comprehensive analysis, leveraging data from this and preceding chapters to align the findings more directly with the research questions, with a particular emphasis on oral English proficiency. Recognizing the broad spectrum of issues raised by participants, the core aim will be to employ this data in addressing the research questions. This will highlight the importance of identifying and examining effective strategies to improve oral English skills within online learning environments.

Chapter 8: Discussion

8.1 Introduction

The core aim of this study is to explore "What is the role of online learning in improving the English-speaking skills of Chinese university students?" This broad issue has necessitated an in-depth investigation into various aspects of online learning within the context of language acquisition. Based on this, the research further proposed four specific research questions (detailed below). By analysing data collected through classroom observations (Chapter 6) and interviews (Chapter 7) with Chinese international students at a Scottish university, and in conjunction with relevant literature, this paper provides a thorough analysis and discussion of these data. This chapter not only offers conclusive statements but also presents the results of an analysis of the data from the findings, explored in relation to the literature examined in Chapter 3.

8.2 Findings in Relation to the Research Questions

8.2.1 Question 1: What do Chinese international students understand by online learning and how do they engage with it?

8.2.1.1 Classification of Online Learning

Online learning saw rapid changes during the pandemic, driven by the necessity for Emergency Remote Teaching (ERT). Synchronous online learning, asynchronous online learning, and blended online learning, which had existed prior to the pandemic, were widely adopted and adapted to meet the evolving demands of remote education during the COVID-19 pandemic. These types of learning have distinct characteristics, catering to different students' learning needs and preferences.

(1) Synchronous Online Learning and Asynchronous Online Learning

This research question focuses on Chinese international students' understanding of online learning, revealing that participants categorise online learning into synchronous and asynchronous types. Synchronous online learning facilitates instant interaction through online platforms, breaking down physical barriers and enabling students to participate in learning from home or elsewhere via mobile devices or personal computers. Features of synchronous online learning include real-time uploading and downloading, subtitles, recording functions, and chat boxes, making the learning process more interactive and engaging (Yan *et al.*, 2021; Almahasees, Mohsen and Amin, 2021).

In contrast, asynchronous online learning allows students to study according to their own schedules, with course content typically delivered through recorded videos, reading materials, and discussion forums. This mode offers high flexibility, suitable for students who need to arrange their study time independently. However, the interactivity of asynchronous learning is relatively lower, and students may lack immediate feedback and real-time communication with teachers and peers (Peimani and Kamalipour, 2021). The study found that asynchronous learning not only facilitated students' integration into the international educational environment but also laid a solid foundation for their future academic and professional development, helping them acquire the skills and knowledge necessary to succeed in a globalised world (Alzlan *et al.*, 2020).

Nevertheless, this flexibility also presented the participants of this study with challenges. Students who lack self-discipline and self-management skills may not fully utilise the conveniences of online learning, leading to uneven learning efficiency (Yang, Zeng and Xu, 2022). For example, some participants turn off their cameras and microphones during online classes to avoid participation, which negatively impacts learning outcomes. This indicates a misunderstanding among participants regarding the conceptualisation of online learning, failing to fully recognise the importance of interaction and participation in online learning in this study.

(2) Blended Online Learning

Blended online learning combines the advantages of both synchronous and asynchronous learning, potentially, providing a more flexible and diverse learning experience. Most Chinese international students who were participants in this study have given positive evaluations of blended learning, appreciating its high flexibility, which allowed them to choose between online or face-to-face learning based on personal needs and schedules. For instance, Participant 6 stated, "If the tutor is not on campus, we choose to communicate online; if the tutor is on campus, we communicate face-to-face." (Participant 6). This dual modality not only enhances learning efficiency but also strengthens interactions between students, teachers, and peers (Gao *et al.*, 2024).

Real-time interaction and feedback in online learning environments are essential for students' learning outcomes (Ellis, 1988). Blended learning, by combining online and offline interaction methods, partially alleviates the lack of interaction inherent in purely online learning. For example, Participant 6 noted, "If the tutor is not on campus, we choose to communicate online; if the tutor is on campus, we communicate face-to-face." (Participant 6). This flexible mode of interaction enhances students' ability to understand and apply knowledge (Lin and Sun, 2024). However, despite the improvement in interactivity to some extent, blended learning still requires further optimisation to meet the needs of different disciplines and learning stages (Saboowala and Manghirmalani Mishra, 2021).

However, it is evident from participant responses in this study, that blended learning also introduces challenges related to time management and choice limitations. Participant 4 expressed dissatisfaction with the restrictions on choice: "If the lecturer requires us to attend on-campus classes, I do not have the right to choose online courses." This lack of autonomy can undermine participants' self-direction, affecting

their learning motivation and satisfaction. Additionally, Participant 10 referred to difficulties with time management: "The online part was from 10 am to 11 am, immediately followed by an on-campus class from 11 am to 12 pm. This arrangement was unreasonable for me."

8.2.1.2 Misconceptions of Online Learning Among Chinese International Students

Online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic, as an emerging educational model, offered many conveniences but also led to certain conceptual misunderstandings, particularly within the Chinese international student community.

The study identified that some participants demonstrated inappropriate behaviours during online learning. For example, in classroom observation data 6.3, Student A1 attended online classes while shopping, reflecting their difficulty in maintaining focus and discipline in the online learning environment. Similarly, Student A2 perceived online learning as a casual and flexible mode of study, leading to poor management of their study time and space. Furthermore, presented in interview data 7.5.3, some participants logged in but turned off their cameras, potentially engaging in unrelated activities like playing games (Participant 2), while others even attended class from their beds (Participant 10). This contrasts sharply with the strict discipline of traditional classroom learning in China, where physical presence and direct supervision naturally reinforce students' concentration and engagement. The content related to this theme and its connection to speaking skills will be addressed in a discussion of the fourth research question.

8.2.2 Question 2: How did Chinese international students adapt to the rapid development in online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic, and how did this affect them?

Through the analysis presented in Chapters 6 and 7, it is evident that Chinese

international students adapted effectively to the rapid development of online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic through various strategies. These strategies not only addressed immediate challenges but also met their long-term educational needs.

Firstly, the use of interactive tools and platforms significantly enhanced classroom engagement and learning efficiency. Participants frequently utilised chatbox functions, electronic hand-raising, and interactive websites like Menti.com to conduct real-time Q and A sessions and polls. For instance, Participant 12 noted that using the electronic hand-raising feature made him more confident in participating in class discussions, thereby improving his language proficiency. These tools encouraged active participation, aligning with the work of Bernard et al. (2011), who emphasised the importance of interaction in online learning for improving student engagement and outcomes.

Personalised teaching by instructors played an essential role in helping students adapt to online learning. By designing learning activities tailored to the student's English proficiency levels, lecturers were able to assist students in better understanding course content. Participant 12 noted that lectures designed different activities based on their English levels, which helped him comprehend the course material more effectively. This personalised approach aligns with the work of Artino (2008), who highlighted the motivational impact of interaction and personalised learning in education, and also corresponds to the research conducted by Ellis et al. (2020) on the principles of Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT).

Online platforms enabled the participants of this study to access course materials anytime and anywhere, helping them balance academic responsibilities with personal or professional obligations. Participant 13 pointed out that online courses were very convenient, giving her more free time to review and revise materials as needed, which she considered a significant advantage. This flexibility aligns with the research of the work of Deci and Ryan's (2000) Self-Determination Theory, which emphasises the role of autonomy in enhancing intrinsic motivation. Additionally, the online learning

environment fostered the development of self-directed learning skills such as time management and self-motivation. Participant 14 mentioned that she could attend online courses while balancing the demands of her job, which was very important to her. This perspective is supported by Zimmerman and Schunk (2012), who stressed the importance of self-regulated learning in online education.

Global academic participation was another significant advantage brought by online learning. Participants were able to use online platforms to attend international academic conferences and engage in transnational research collaborations. Participant 13 shared that she participated in several international academic conferences online, which exposed her to different perspectives and resources, greatly benefiting her research. This opportunity to engage in international education and academic activities without relocating reshaped students' academic and professional trajectories, aligning with the findings from the work of Ho and Crookall (1995), who highlighted how meaningful learning environments enhance global connectivity and outcomes.

Additionally, online learning improved Participants' safety and well-being by reducing health risks and lowering the potential economic burdens associated with travel, visas, and accommodation. Participant 7 indicated that reducing outings from home was safer for him, supporting Hedge's (2001) assertion on the importance of safety in fostering learner well-being. The flexibility of online learning also reduces potential commuting time, allowing students to dedicate more time to their studies and personal growth. Participant 4 commented that not having to commute gave her more time to focus on her studies.

This transformation in learning reflects broader changes in educational practices that emerged during the pandemic. Mullen, Giralt, and Murray (2023) argue that the "new normal" in education represents a fundamental transformation rather than a return to pre-pandemic methods. This paradigm shift emphasises blended learning, where online and face-to-face teaching are integrated as standard practice. Furthermore, it underscores the importance of cultivating digital literacy among educators, enabling

them to effectively utilise digital tools and adapt to evolving technological demands. This forward-thinking approach aligns with the need for adaptable and resilient education systems that can address both current and future challenges in a technology-driven world.

In conclusion, by leveraging the advantages of online learning, this group of participants adapted effectively to the rapid development of online education during the COVID-19 pandemic. However, while online learning offered numerous benefits, it also posed significant challenges that will be discussed in the following section.

8.2.3 Question 3: What are the challenges faced by Chinese students while participating in online learning?

8.2.3.1 Technical and Equipment Issues

Technical and equipment problems significantly impacted this group of participants' online learning experiences. Unstable network connections and poor equipment quality hindered their participation in online courses and adversely affected learning outcomes. For example, Participant 12 noted that unstable internet connectivity led to audio and video desynchronisation, which affected his ability to practise listening skills. This aligns with the work of Ferri et al. (2020), who pointed out that the rapid shift to online teaching exposed technological inequalities, potentially influencing students' learning experiences.

Additionally, a lack of digital skills limited some participants' ability to fully utilise online learning platforms. Participant 5 noted that the university did not provide training on the online platform, requiring students to explore functions of the technology on their own, which affected their learning effectiveness. This reflects the concept of digital habitus (Liu *et al.*, 2019; Zhang and Perez-Paredes, 2021), explaining why some participants struggle to operate online learning platforms proficiently without systematic training.

For participants in this study incomplete content display due to small fonts on shared screens affected readability and increased learning difficulty. Participant 12 stated that their device did not display everything completely, which affected their learning efficiency. Technical communication was also a concern; participants often lacked proactive communication when encountering technical difficulties, leading to learning interruptions. Participant 5 described initial technical troubles, explaining that they could not join the class via the link initially and had to resolve the issue through emails and assistance from classmates. Social capital theory emphasises the importance of social networks and resource access in overcoming such technical access issues (Coleman, 1988). Participant 5's experience illustrates the essential role of social capital in online learning environments.

8.2.3.2 Learning Environment and Distractions

The learning environment and distractions posed significant challenges. External noise and interference made it difficult for participants in this study to concentrate, affecting learning efficiency. Participant 2 noted that their room was cluttered and only had a computer on the desk, which affected their learning efficiency. Inconsistent learning conditions impacted some participants' ability to focus and fully engage in learning. Participant 3 responded that when studying at home, he became distracted easily, often thinking about playing games or eating after class.

Family responsibilities often added to the pressure on participants, with some participants needing to balance caregiving duties, affecting their focus and efficiency. Participant 4 described a conflict between work and study, stating that sometimes class time conflicted with work hours, making it hard to concentrate on lectures. These factors not only impacted students' physiological and safety needs (Maslow, 1943) but also interacted with their habitus, influencing learning behaviours and efficiency (Bourdieu, 1997; Wacquant, 2005). The combination of environmental distractions and personal responsibilities therefore led, for some participants, to challenges in maintaining concentration in online learning environments.

8.2.3.3 Motivation and Self-discipline

Motivation and self-discipline are essential for success in online learning but were often lacking for some participants. The absence of interaction and a sense of participation in online environments reduced some participants' motivation. Participant 4 pointed out that everyone was hidden behind computers and phones, which made them feel lazy and was the main reason they lost interest in anything. The observation that "Everyone is hidden behind their computers and phones." reflects the lack of social interaction and immediacy, which can lead to feelings of detachment and lethargy. This aligns with Dörnyei's (2005) L2 Motivational Self System (L2MSS), as it demonstrates how the disruption of self-concept—through reduced interaction and accountability—negatively impacts intrinsic motivation.

Self-discipline dependence was another challenge, as some participants struggled to maintain progress without a structured environment. Participant 7 mentioned that online courses often reduce students' self-discipline, which negatively affects their learning efficiency. Time management difficulties, especially for participants learning across time zones, further impacted daily routines and efficiency. Participant 6 described the challenges brought by time zone differences, explaining that after the UK adjusted to daylight saving time, the class time in China became 5 p.m., disrupting their daily routine. Maslow's (1943) hierarchy of needs further explains that unfulfilled higher-level needs can lead to motivation deficits, affecting students' learning engagement and efficiency. For Participant 6, the disruption of their routine may have impacted higher-level needs, such as self-esteem and a sense of control, which are essential for maintaining focus and active participation in learning.

8.2.3.4 Mental Health and Social Isolation

The participants made it clear that long-term online learning can lead to feelings of loneliness and social isolation, reducing real interactions with classmates and teachers, and impacting psychological well-being. Participant 15 noted that online learning in

her experience makes everyone more isolated and psychologically more vulnerable. Participant 8 responded that long-term studying online at home makes them feel a lot of pressure.

The experiences of Participants 8 and 15 can be effectively analyzed through the lens of social capital theory, which emphasizes the importance of social networks and interactions in fostering a sense of belonging and support (Putnam, 2000; Woolcock, 2001). For some participants in this study, the lack of physical interaction with classmates and lectures eroded their social capital, leaving them feeling disconnected and unsupported. Building stronger networks, even within the context of online learning, could mitigate these challenges by providing emotional and academic support. Maslow's (1943) hierarchy of needs further contextualizes these experiences by highlighting how unmet social needs—such as belongingness and connection—can affect mental health and motivation. The absence of regular interpersonal interactions deprives these participants of opportunities to meet these fundamental psychological needs, thereby exacerbating participants' feelings of isolation and stress.

8.2.3.5 Social Environment and Cultural Understanding

The lack of emotional connection experienced by some participants in online environments affected, for some participants the establishment of supportive learning communities and impacted learning experiences. Participant 7 emphasised the lack of face-to-face interaction which is affecting learning enthusiasm. This issue can be viewed through the theories of cultural capital and habitus. Bourdieu (1989) posits that the accumulation of cultural capital and adaptation of habitus are essential for students' emotional connections and social capital construction in a new cultural environment. For Participant 7, the lack of direct interaction with peers and lecturers may have impeded their ability to acquire cultural capital, such as nuanced communication skills, shared cultural understanding, and academic norms that typically come from in-person engagement.

Moreover, social capital theory (Putnam, 2015; Bourdieu 1989) underscores that establishing strong social networks and emotional connections helps students better integrate into society, improving learning experiences and outcomes. The challenges highlighted by Participant 7 reflect the need for strategies to foster emotional connections and social capital in online learning settings.

8.2.4 Question 4: In what ways does participation of Chinese international students in online learning affect their oral proficiency?

8.2.4.1 Enhancement Through Active Participation

Active engagement in online classes—such as speaking clearly, asking questions, and participating in discussions—played an essential role in enhancing oral proficiency among some participants by providing increased practice opportunities and building their confidence. Regular interactions in discussions and QandA sessions enable participants to apply language skills in real-time, thereby enhancing fluency and comprehension. For example, Participant 3 stated that he had online communication with the teaching and tutoring staff every week, and the lecturer provided opportunities for oral communication. Similarly, Participant 14 mentioned that they actually participated in oral discussions quite often in online classes. These consistent engagements facilitated repeated practice, which is essential for language acquisition (Krashen, 1985). Moreover, actively participating in online classes fosters self-confidence, a critical factor in language learning. Participant 4 remarked that they tried to speak English in online classes and continued to improve their oral proficiency, while Participant 2 shared that participating in group discussions made them feel genuinely involved, enhancing their confidence in speaking. Dörnyei's L2 Motivational Self System (L2MSS) posits that a strong Ideal L2 Self motivates students to engage actively in language use by envisioning themselves as proficient speakers, while positive Second Language Learning Experiences (SLLE), as experienced by Participants 3, 4, and 14, can reinforce this motivation, leading to sustained active participation, such as experienced by participants 3, 4 and 14.

Additionally, according to Maslow (1943), active engagement fulfils higher-level psychological needs such as esteem and self-actualisation, with participation providing recognition and a sense of achievement that propels personal growth and enhances motivation for language learning, in this way, participants in this study may have enhanced their own well-being.

8.2.4.2 Impact of Passive Behavior on Learning Outcomes

Passive participation in online learning can significantly impede the development of oral proficiency by limiting practice opportunities and reducing motivation (Dörnyei, 2005). When learners are passively involved, such as merely listening without engaging, they have fewer chances to practise speaking, which can hamper the development of their oral skills. For instance, Participant 8 noted that their involvement was restricted to passively watching the screen, stating that offline environments are more direct, allowing emotional involvement in the learning' often experienced by the lecturer and students to be felt more directly. Participant 8 also noted that "Online, it is probably just talking to a screen, and people can only focus on listening and speaking." Additionally, reduced motivation often leads to a decline in participation, as seen from the experience of Participant 7, who mentioned that at the beginning of online classes, he was very proactive. However, after a while, they rarely initiated communication because some questions could be answered in the pre-reading materials provided by the lecturer, leading him to read the materials themselves. Dörnyei's L2 Motivational Self System (L2MSS) suggests that a weak Ideal L2 Self or heightened L2 anxiety associated with the Ought-to L2 Self can result in passive behaviour, while Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs highlights that unmet social needs like belongingness and esteem can prevent students from fully engaging. As is clear, above, from Participant 7's discussion without meaningful interaction, students may not reach the higher levels of motivation necessary for effective language development.

8.2.4.3 Impact of L1 Use and Translanguaging Practices

The use of the first language (L1) in online learning environments can present both supportive and detrimental effects on English (L2) oral proficiency (Dörnyei, 2009). Over-reliance on L1, such as Chinese, during online classes, can limit immersion in English and reduce opportunities for language practice. For example, Participant A1 observed that when unable to understand English instructions, she would ask peers in Chinese, while Participant 13 emphasised that speaking Chinese in a UK university setting in general, is not conducive to the lecturers' teaching and the students' understanding, advocating for the avoidance of Chinese in such situations. Conversely, as Canagarajah (2013) strategic translanguaging—the fluid use of multiple languages—can aid in comprehending complex concepts; as Participant 3 noted, the occasional use of Chinese during online courses, particularly in peer discussions for knowledge exchange, can make communication more effective. However, excessive use of L1 may hinder L2 proficiency and lead to social exclusion, with Participant 15 warning that speaking Chinese would exclude non-Chinese students from the discussion, labelling it as ‘very bad and very racist’. According to Translanguaging Theory by García and Wei (2014), while translanguaging can support understanding, maintaining a balance is essential to prevent dependence on L1, which may impede L2 immersion and proficiency. Therefore, educators should guide students to use L1 judiciously to support learning without compromising the development of English proficiency. This connection illustrates how Participant 3’s practical use of L1 in peer discussions reflects a real-world application of translanguaging, emphasizing the need for intentional and guided integration of L1 in educational settings.

8.2.4.4 Cultural and Educational Adjustments

Cultural norms and educational backgrounds significantly influence students' participation levels in online learning, thereby affecting their oral proficiency. Differences in educational practices between China and the UK appeared, from the experience of the participants, to impact their willingness to actively engage in online

classes. For instance, Participant 1 observed that in the UK classroom, lecturers may pay more attention to each student's own ideas, whereas in China, students have relatively fewer opportunities for oral expression. Additionally, Participant 6 noted that UK classrooms generally revolve around students, while many Chinese classrooms revolve around lecturers. Furthermore, cultural tendencies to avoid public mistakes, rooted in Confucian values that emphasise respect for authority, humility, and harmony (Choi and Han, 2023), may reduce students' willingness to speak up in English, hindering oral practice. The concept of "saving face" can cause students to avoid speaking to prevent potential embarrassment, both online and during 'in-person' classes (Liu, 2021). However, it is essential to recognise individual differences within cultural groups, as not all Chinese students are passive; some actively seek engagement. Participant 4 suggested that increasing interaction with local students could help overcome their fear of speaking, highlighting the diversity within cultural groups. Furthermore, Participant 15 expressed concerns about inclusivity, stating that speaking Chinese could exclude non-Chinese students during online classes, which they consider very bad and very racist, underscoring the importance of creating a supportive and inclusive online learning environment that encourages active participation from all students.

8.2.4.5 Technological Influences

In the experience of participants for this study technology significantly shaped participation dynamics and, consequently, oral proficiency development. Online platforms often favour written communication over oral participation, thereby limiting opportunities for speaking practice. For instance, Participant 2 noted that the chat box feature greatly facilitated communication among shy students, eliminating the need for oral expression, while Participant 1 mentioned that they often just type and discuss an issue via the Chatbox without anyone speaking. Participant 15 observed that very few people chose to communicate through voice or video. Additionally, technical barriers such as network interruptions seemed to further discourage oral participation by

creating frustration and undermining the fairness of oral assessments. Participant 5 reported that network interruptions affected the submission of audio files. These factors collectively imply that an overreliance on text communication diminished the opportunities for speaking, negatively impacting oral proficiency. To address these challenges, it is essential to provide robust technical support and encourage the use of audio and video features during online learning, thereby enhancing oral engagement and mitigating technical issues.

8.2.4.6 Emotional Factors

Emotional factors play a significant role in influencing students' participation levels and language acquisition (Krashen, 1985). Emotions and psychological states, such as anxiety, can either be alleviated or exacerbated in online settings, thereby affecting students' willingness to engage orally. For example, Participant 3 preferred offline classes, stating that offline courses are more interactive and less stressful, while Participant 2 noted that if a student is not in a good mood and does not want to talk, the online class is more friendly. Additionally, students' emotional well-being seemed to impact directly their readiness to participate in oral activities, as illustrated by Participant 7, who experienced decreased communication, stating that after a while, they rarely initiated communication and instead just read the pre-class learning materials themselves. Dörnyei's L2 Motivational Self System (L2MSS) suggests that high levels of L2 anxiety can negatively impact motivation to participate, whereas positive emotional experiences enhance motivation and encourage active engagement. The reluctance of Participant 7 to actively participate may be explained by the negative emotional factors they encountered, which likely discouraged them from seeking interaction and contributing to discussions. Moreover, Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs (Maslow, 1943) indicates that anxiety affects basic psychological needs, and when students feel insecure or stressed, their ability to focus on higher-level needs such as esteem and self-actualisation diminishes, thereby hindering language development.

8.2.5 Conclusion

This chapter has effectively addressed four key questions concerning online language learning through the responses of the participants in this study. Firstly, the chapter addresses the first question by analysing how participants categorise online learning models—synchronous, asynchronous, and hybrid learning—and their respective advantages and challenges. Secondly, in response to the second question, it explores the adaptation strategies employed by participants, such as the use of interactive tools and personalised teaching methods, and how these strategies can enhance language proficiency and academic engagement. Thirdly, it identifies challenges including technological equipment issues, distractions in the learning environment, lack of motivation and self-discipline, mental health concerns, and social isolation. Finally, it focuses on the differing impacts of active participation versus passive behaviour on the improvement of speaking skills, and examines the role of first language and cultural adjustment in language development.

Through the discussion of these issues, this chapter analyses the essential role of online learning in enhancing the English-speaking abilities of Chinese international students at Scottish universities, as experienced and evidenced by the participants in this study revealing its potential to promote language acquisition and academic success. The concluding chapter synthesises these insights, integrates the research outcomes, and proposes directions for future studies, highlighting the importance of optimising online learning environments to support language acquisition and academic success in a globalised educational landscape.

Chapter 9: Conclusion

9.1 Introduction

The motivation for this research stems from my personal learning experiences and profound insights into education. During my four years of undergraduate study, I delved deeply into domestic education theory in China. Then, during an internship in Indonesia, I felt for the first time the importance of cultural differences and spoken English in working and living in a foreign country. This experience made me realize the importance of improving spoken English skills for international students. In my final year of university, I began to understand the process of studying abroad and prepared for the IELTS language exam. Later, I was fortunate to pursue a Master's degree in the UK, experiencing the academic atmosphere of British campuses and critical teaching methods firsthand. In the UK, I actively participated in various club activities, experienced local society and culture in depth, and visited many European countries. These experiences not only enriched my life experience but also significantly improved my spoken English skills.

Furthermore, after graduating from my master's, I worked in the international department of a university in Beijing, closely interacting with many Chinese students preparing to study abroad. I witnessed their anxiety and confusion when facing the challenge of spoken English and personally experienced the joy and sense of accomplishment in helping them overcome difficulties. This work experience made me more deeply aware of the unique challenges and issues facing Chinese students in improving their spoken English skills.

Especially after the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020, a profound change occurred in the global higher education sector, and the importance of online learning became increasingly prominent. During my doctoral studies, I personally experienced various stages before and after the COVID-19 pandemic outbreak, global lockdown,

and recovery, experiencing in-depth the development and challenges of online education. I noticed that while online learning provides Chinese students with more learning opportunities and resources, it also brings new challenges and potential problems. How to fully utilize the advantages of online learning and improve the spoken English skills of Chinese students under such circumstances became a problem I urgently wanted to solve.

Therefore, I decided to conduct this research, aiming to explore more suitable English-speaking learning methods and strategies for Chinese students by analyzing in depth the features and advantages of online learning platforms and combining the actual needs and characteristics of Chinese students. Through this research, I hope to provide suggestions for ways in which Chinese students can have a better, more efficient English-speaking learning experience, help them adapt better to the demands of online learning, and realize their dreams of studying abroad. I firmly believe that through these efforts, Chinese students can gradually overcome the limitations of online learning in improving spoken English levels, providing a more solid language foundation for their academic journey.

Thus, this research aims to provide profound insights and analysis into the role of online learning in enhancing the English-speaking abilities of Chinese international students. To reiterate, this study adopted a qualitative analysis approach from the unique perspective of Chinese international students. It extensively explores observation records and interview texts to comprehensively evaluate the effects of online learning and its impact on the English-speaking skills and learning experiences of Chinese international students in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic. Building on previous research findings, this study tentatively constructs a multidimensional and comprehensive analytical framework to delve deeper into various factors influencing the improvement of English-speaking proficiency through online learning.

This framework incorporates important theoretical elements such as learning motivation, social capital, cultural capital, and learning habits. Firstly, Motivation

Theory focuses on the source of an individual's motivation during the learning process. Within this framework, the L2 Motivational Self System and Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs are key theories explaining the motivation for individual learning. The L2 Motivational Self System emphasizes the complexity of self-identity and motivation in second language learning, while Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs provides a more general framework of human needs to explain the basis of motivation. Next, social capital theory focuses on the interactions of individuals in social networks and how these interactions affect the learning process and outcomes.

Theories by Bourdieu, Coleman, Putnam, and Woolcock, respectively, explore the role of social capital in learning from different perspectives. These theories emphasize the importance of social networks, trust, norms, and resources in promoting the learning process. Lastly, the concepts of cultural capital and Habitus shift the focus to the role of culture and habit in learning. Cultural Capital emphasizes the value of cultural resources and knowledge in learning, while Habitus describes how these resources and knowledge impact learning through an individual's daily habits and practices. Combining these theories and concepts into a theoretical framework helps us to understand the learning process more comprehensively.

Motivation theory provides the basis for learning motivation, social capital theory reveals the impact of social interaction on learning, and cultural capital and habitus emphasize the role of culture and habit in shaping learning experiences. These different theories and concepts interweave within the framework, forming a complex and comprehensive learning theory framework, providing a more in-depth and comprehensive perspective to explore the phenomenon of online language learning for this study.

To ensure the depth and relevance of the research, a specific UK university was chosen as the research object, and through meticulous observations, the main challenges faced by Chinese international students in online learning environments are revealed. Additionally, through semi-structured interviews, efforts were made to

understand the level of online learning participation among Chinese international student populations, the diverse influencing factors of online language learning, and the development of their oral communication skills in daily life and academic contexts. This study also attempted to explore the complex interaction between online education and the enhancement of English-speaking abilities. In the final stage of the research, the core objectives of the study are reviewed, and the data analysis process is detailed as much as possible in order to provide clear and comprehensive answers to the research questions. Furthermore, I attempt to provide some possible directions and recommendations for future related research. Of course, this study is also aware of its limitations, constraints, and potential areas for future research, and hopes that these findings can provide inspiration and assistance to subsequent researchers.

9.2 Overview of the Research

Chapter 1 introduces the study, focusing on the experiences of Chinese international students in online language learning. It outlines the core principles, research objectives, key research questions, and the methodological approach adopted in this research. In addition, the chapter emphasizes the significance of the study and provides an overview of its structure towards the end.

Chapter 2 explores the development of educational technology and the significance of online language learning. It provides an overview of the historical development of online learning and examines the role of various platforms in facilitating language acquisition. The COVID-19 pandemic accelerated the growth of online learning and introduced the concept of Emergency Remote Teaching. However, it also exposed several challenges, such as issues in Chinese online learning policies, resource imbalances, and reduced learning efficiency. This chapter further discusses the insufficient preparedness of some universities (both in China and the UK) for online education during the COVID-19 pandemic, as well as the motivation and challenges students faced.

Chapter 3 offers a comprehensive literature review related to this study, addressing learning theories, online learning, and its impact on second language acquisition (SLA). Starting with a review of humanistic and constructivist approaches, it highlights the importance of individual potential and interaction with the environment in knowledge construction. The chapter then delves into the definitions, types, and evolution of online learning, including synchronous, asynchronous, and blended learning, while analyzing their respective advantages and disadvantages. It particularly emphasizes the significance of interaction in online classrooms, which is essential for maintaining learner engagement and fostering a conducive environment for language learning. Additionally, this chapter provides an in-depth analysis of SLA theories, drawing on Krashen's and Ellis's frameworks. It also discusses environmental factors, task-based language teaching, and translanguaging, offering rich perspectives on SLA. Despite the thorough exploration, challenges remain in the fields of learning, online learning, and SLA, paving the way for further research.

Chapter 4 focuses on the theoretical and conceptual framework underpinning the study. It incorporates several key theoretical perspectives and concepts that guide the research. Notably, the chapter introduces motivation theory, with particular attention to Dornyei's L2 Motivational Self System, which highlights the role of the individual self in SLA and the interplay between external influences and internal motivation. Furthermore, social capital theory is integrated into the framework, examining how resources derived from social relationships impact online learning experiences. Concepts of cultural capital and habitus are also discussed. Together, these theories provide a systematic guide for understanding the mechanisms of the research questions.

Chapter 5 details the ethnographic research methodology used in this study, including the paradigms of naturalism, interpretivism, and inductive reasoning. The research tools employed include online observation and semi-structured interviews. The purposeful sampling method ensures the representativeness of participants. This

chapter is designed to ensure the accuracy of research data, using qualitative methods to analyze data while also addressing ethical considerations. This methodology lays the groundwork for the subsequent analysis of the development of oral English skills in online language learning.

Chapters 6 and 7 focus on the presentation of observational and interview data, respectively. By showcasing the findings from the observational research and interviews, these chapters reveal both the strengths and weaknesses of online learning in developing Chinese university students' language skills, particularly their oral proficiency. These chapters also discuss the differences in oral language requirements across various disciplines and highlight the insufficient emphasis some lecturers place on oral communication skills in their instruction.

Chapter 8 provides a comprehensive discussion of four research questions related to Chinese international students' experiences with online language learning. It evaluates the significance and challenges of online learning, students' understanding of it, and their learning experiences. This chapter also explores the challenges faced in oral communication during online learning, offering a basis for potential solutions.

Chapter 9 presents recommendations for improving English oral skills through online learning. These include the effective use of online resources, fostering interactive strategies within learning communities, and developing autonomous learning skills and cross-cultural communication abilities.

9.3 Evaluating the Research

This study delved into the multidimensional aspects of online learning and the experiences of Chinese students studying in the UK, particularly focusing on how online learning impacts the development of Oral English language skills among these students. I designed four research questions and employed qualitative research methods to comprehensively explore the advantages, disadvantages, challenges, and

new requirements of online learning in terms of student self-management and the development of communication skills with other learners, from various backgrounds. It also revealed the differences in oral communication requirements in English across different disciplines and highlighted the insufficient emphasis placed by some university lecturers on developing Chinese students' oral communication skills.

The findings of the study indicate that despite some limitations, given the unique circumstances of the COVID-19 pandemic, this research holds practical value. It provides essential insights into the experience of participants in this study from the same university, deepening participant's understanding of the experiences of Chinese students during the COVID-19 pandemic. More importantly, these insights can help inform and shape better educational practices in the post-pandemic era. The study has raised awareness of the lack of emphasis on peer learning among Chinese students compared to their domestic and international counterparts in the context of online learning, prompting a re-evaluation of how online learning can better serve Chinese students. These conclusions have important implications for educators and administrators in improving online learning environments and refining online education strategies.

This research design employed a qualitative methodology, utilizing techniques widely recognized in the field of educational research, and incorporates a comprehensive approach to data collection as well as an in-depth process for data analysis. The conclusion section not only summarizes the advantages, disadvantages, and challenges of online learning but also presents a series of practical recommendations for optimizing learning outcomes. These recommendations hold significant value for educational practitioners and policymakers, as they can be directly applied to improve current online learning environments and enhance online education programmes.

In summary, through in-depth exploration and research, this study not only investigated the two main types of online learning, real-time and asynchronous, and revealed their respective advantages and challenges in improving the English oral

skills of Chinese students, but also uncovered issues that students face in understanding and adapting to the online learning environment, such as the misuse of learning time and space and the evasion of classroom discussion. But there were also positives associated with both of these: the study emphasized the importance of equipment and networks in online oral language learning and proposed innovative strategies that combine technological tools with teaching methods. These findings not only deepen understanding of online learning but also provide valuable practical guidance to lecturers and universities for optimizing the online learning environment and improving educational quality.

To collect data from human subjects, documenting their real-life experiences and emotions, is something that quantitative research cannot achieve. Future research in this area can compare learning experiences in different environments, recruit students from various universities to analyze commonalities and differences among Chinese students, continue to deepen the understanding of online education, and optimize the online language learning experience for international students.

9.4 Contributions

9.4.1 Methodological Contributions

This study makes significant contributions to the methodological field by exploring the dynamics of online language learning for Chinese international students. It systematically reviews motivation theories such as the L2 Motivational Self System (Gardner and Lambert, 1959; Dörnyei, 1998, 2005, 2009; Ueki and Takeuchi, 2012) and Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs (Maslow, 1943; Owens and Loomes, 2010; Abbas *et al.*, 2021; Torabi, 2020), as well as related theories such as social capital (Bourdieu, 1986; Coleman, 1988; Putnam, 1995; Woolcock, 1998), cultural capital and habitus theory (Bourdieu, 1997; Wacquant, 2005). These theoretical frameworks provide solid support for understanding the development of online interactive oral skills and issues associated with Chinese students' adaptation to online learning during the COVID-19

pandemic. The study's innovative and flexible methodology can enhance research approaches in related fields, particularly in the context of online language education.

Secondly, the methodological strength of this study lies in its combination of classroom observation and interviews, two qualitative research techniques that complement each other. This approach provides a comprehensive understanding of the complexities of online language learning. Classroom observations offer direct insights into real-time interactions and teaching practices, capturing the nuances of online learning environments. This first-hand data collected a rich perspective on the challenges and dynamics of language acquisition. In addition, interviews offer an in-depth exploration of students' subjective experiences, motivations, and perspectives on online learning (Ryan, Coughlan and Cronin, 2009). Together, these methods create a balanced view that integrates both objective observations and subjective insights, providing a thorough analysis of the students' experiences.

Lastly, the methodological contributions of this study have implications for future research. Its approach to research design, data collection, and analysis offers valuable insights for scholars in linguistics, education, and sociology. For example, the integration of theoretical frameworks with empirical data collection ensures the academic rigour of the study. Utilizing multiple data sources enhances the reliability and trustworthiness of findings, while qualitative data analysis methods provide deeper insights into the data. These methodological practices contribute to the development of rigorous research standards and can offer guidance for future studies in online language learning.

9.4.2 Theoretical Contributions

This study makes several important theoretical contributions by advancing the understanding of online language learning, particularly in the context of Chinese international students. First, it helps me to better understand the challenges which students face in developing their English-speaking skills through online learning

during the COVID-19 pandemic. By comparing online education with traditional campus-based learning, the study highlights the strengths and weaknesses of online methods for language acquisition, offering new insights into how different learning environments impact spoken English proficiency.

Secondly, the study introduces new theoretical perspectives and analytical frameworks for understanding online language learning. Through an in-depth analysis of students' experiences, it systematically reveals the advantages, limitations, and evolving needs within online education, especially in relation to student motivation and engagement. These insights provide a supplement to certain traditional views in language acquisition theories, providing empirical evidence to support more dynamic and practical frameworks for understanding online language learning. The study emphasizes the role of digital interaction, the adaptation to virtual learning environments, and the impact of technology on language development.

Importantly, the theoretical contributions of this study are closely connected to practice. Identifying the actual needs and challenges of Chinese students in online language learning, offers a theoretical foundation for educational institutions and policymakers to enhance the quality of online language teaching. These insights not only enrich academic discourse but also provide practical guidelines for improving the design and implementation of online language education programmes.

9.4.3 Practical Contributions

This study offers several practical contributions that are directly applicable to enhancing online language learning experiences:

Enhanced Understanding of Learning Modes: The study provides a discussion of synchronous and asynchronous online learning modes in Chapter 8 and their impact on the development of English-speaking skills. It identifies the strengths and challenges of each mode, offering practical recommendations for educators on how to

design language courses that maximize student engagement and oral proficiency. These insights are valuable for developing targeted teaching strategies that optimize the use of online learning tools for language practice.

Recommendations for Course Design and Learning Platforms: By analyzing the factors that influence students' success in online language learning—such as participants' prior experience of learning, internet accessibility, platform design, and teaching methods—the study provides practical suggestions for improving online language courses. For instance, it highlights the importance of incorporating interactive elements, real-time feedback mechanisms, and opportunities for spoken practice in online platforms to better support language acquisition.

Strategies for Enhancing Student Engagement: The study emphasizes the need for students to develop self-discipline and effective time management skills for the online learning environment. It offers strategies such as maintaining a distraction-free study space, using task management tools, and actively participating in online discussions to improve speaking skills. These recommendations aim to help students take greater control of their learning process and maximize the benefits of online language education.

Guidance for Educational Institutions: The study provides actionable recommendations for universities and educators to support Chinese students in their language learning journey. It suggests that institutions enhance their technical infrastructure, design more engaging and flexible course schedules, and offer targeted support services to address the specific challenges of online language learning. This includes providing training for lecturers to effectively use digital tools that facilitate spoken language practice and creating opportunities for peer interaction and collaborative learning.

Development of Digital Learning Resources: The study also recommends improvements for online learning platforms, such as the integration of AI-powered

speaking tools and role-playing simulations that offer personalized feedback. These digital resources can provide more engaging and effective ways for students to practice speaking skills, making language learning more interactive and adaptive to individual needs.

In conclusion, this study makes meaningful contributions across methodological, theoretical, and practical domains, focusing on the complexities and potential of online language learning for Chinese international students. By providing a detailed understanding of both the challenges and opportunities within this context, the study offers a solid foundation for improving the effectiveness of online language education. Its insights into learning behaviours, motivational dynamics, and digital teaching tools pave the way for more inclusive and effective approaches to language acquisition in an increasingly digital world. Through its findings, the study aims to explore the development of authentic oral language skills and support the development of high-quality online language education that meets the needs of Chinese students, enabling them to achieve their academic and personal language learning goals.

9.5 Limitations

In exploring the impact of online education on Chinese students' English-speaking development at UK universities, this study has reached meaningful conclusions and formulated practical recommendations. However, several limitations have emerged, highlighting the study's scope and suggesting avenues for future research.

One significant constraint involves the data collection process. Due to limitations in time, resources, and access, this study focused on a relatively small sample size of Chinese students. While this allowed for a deep, qualitative analysis, it restricts the generalizability of findings to broader student populations. Furthermore, there was a lack of continuity in participant engagement: Group A students, observed during initial sessions, did not advance to formal degree programmes, while only a subset of Group B participants remained involved in follow-up interviews. This gap in

longitudinal data limits the study's insight into the progression of students' language skills over time and hampers a more consistent analysis of their development.

Additionally, contextual differences in classroom observations introduced interpretive challenges in the interpretation of the data collected. Group A participants did not know each other prior to the course, while Group B students shared pre-existing knowledge and relationships as colleagues in China. This disparity likely influenced the students' level of interaction and sense of comfort within each group, affecting the dynamics of online participation. These differences challenge the comparability of data and restrict the study's findings to student groups with similar backgrounds, making broader generalizations difficult.

The scope of research focus was another limitation, as the study emphasized the English-speaking skills of Chinese students in an online context. Although this focus facilitated in-depth analysis of their unique challenges, it limited the broader applicability of findings to other academic skills such as writing and reading comprehension. Additionally, the study did not explore the distinct language needs across various academic disciplines, which likely require tailored approaches for optimal language development. Expanding future research to include diverse academic skills and examine their interactions within online learning environments could yield a more holistic understanding of online education's impact.

Moreover, the study's analytical perspective predominantly reflects the students' experiences and challenges in online learning. While this learner-centred approach offers valuable insights, it overlooks the perspectives of online platform operators, institutional administrators, and educators. Including these viewpoints could provide a more balanced understanding of online language education, yielding strategies that support students, educators, and institutions alike.

The methodological constraints imposed by the COVID-19 pandemic also affected the study. All data collection activities, including classroom observations and interviews,

were conducted online, which posed unique challenges. Unstable internet connections occasionally disrupted classroom sessions, potentially affecting data accuracy. Likewise, online interviews can limit the nuanced understanding typical of face-to-face interactions, potentially limiting the richness of responses and impacting the overall quality of data.

Finally, conducting this research entirely online introduced specific challenges to participant engagement and data consistency. Variations in internet quality among participants affected engagement in online classes and interviews, while the reliance on digital communication may have limited the depth of expression and non-verbal cues, which are often more accessible in person. These limitations underscore the need for flexible methodologies that accommodate technological disparities and enhance the depth of data collection in digital research environments.

In conclusion, while this study offers valuable insights into the development of English-speaking skills through online language learning for Chinese students, these limitations underscore areas where future research could expand. Addressing issues such as sample size, participant continuity, and incorporating multiple perspectives will provide a more comprehensive understanding of online education's complexities. Overcoming these limitations can deepen our understanding of online language learning, improving its design and effectiveness for diverse student populations.

9.6 Recommendations

This section provides comprehensive recommendations for students, educators, universities, and online learning platforms, addressing the unique challenges faced by Chinese students in online and blended learning environments. These strategies focus on promoting engagement, enhancing language skills, ensuring assessment fairness, fostering cross-cultural understanding, and supporting Learners' mental health and self-discipline.

9.6.1 Recommendations for Students

To effectively leverage online language learning opportunities, Chinese students are encouraged to participate in online cultural exchange events and English conversation clubs. Activities like virtual tours, workshops, and discussion groups offer practical contexts for spoken English practice, helping to improve pronunciation, fluency, and confidence. Students should also maximize social media and educational platforms, such as YouTube or educational channels, which provide exposure to authentic language. Selecting high-quality content aligned with learning goals and proficiency levels will enrich the learning experience. Self-discipline is essential for online learning success, and students should create distraction-free study environments, set achievable goals, and use digital planners to stay organized. Engaging in peer learning through group discussions, study groups, or language exchanges offers valuable speaking practice within a supportive community. Additionally, following Translanguaging theory (Garcia, 2009; Canagarajah, 2013; Li, 2016; Li, 2022; Liu and Fang, 2022; Ateek, 2022; Pennycook, 2019), students might use their first language strategically in complex discussions to facilitate comprehension, gradually transitioning to English to build language confidence and proficiency (Kendall, 2008). University resources, such as online tutoring, language coaching, and writing workshops, provide valuable personalized support to help students overcome language challenges and remain motivated.

9.6.2 Recommendations for University Lecturers

And lecturers play a critical role in fostering engaging online environments. To support Chinese students' language development, lecturers should integrate structured real-time speaking activities, such as role-playing, debates, and situational dialogues, which encourage active verbal participation. Creating an inclusive classroom atmosphere that values mistakes as part of the learning process can build confidence and encourage students to take risks in their oral expression. Technology tools, like Zoom breakout rooms, Mentimeter, and live quizzes, can enhance engagement and

may make sessions dynamic and interactive, reducing the tendency of some students to disengage during online classes. Lecturers can also leverage translanguaging techniques to ease students into complex topics using L1 when necessary, then gradually shift to English as students gain comfort. This approach can help to build a solid English foundation while managing anxiety related to language use. Additionally, asynchronous options, such as recorded lectures and flexible participation times, can address time zone challenges, helping students from different regions to stay engaged.

9.6.3 Recommendations for Universities

Universities should enhance online language course quality by integrating diverse speaking opportunities, such as conversation practice sessions, pronunciation workshops, and real-time speaking clubs. These activities offer interactive environments where students can practise language skills actively and supportively. Mental health and psychological support services, including regular counselling, peer support networks, and virtual campus activities, are also vital in helping to mitigate the isolation and stress often associated with online learning. Universities should provide dedicated technical support and platform training to address technical issues swiftly and ensure students can navigate online resources effectively. Recognizing time zone differences, institutions should offer flexible scheduling options, including recorded lectures, to enable remote students to manage their studies better. Peer interaction and support networks, such as online study groups and discussion forums, can create a sense of community and provide students with consistent opportunities to practise English and exchange feedback.

9.6.4 Recommendations for Online Learning Platforms

Online learning platforms can enhance language development by implementing AI-powered speaking tools that analyze students' pronunciation and grammar in real time, offering specific feedback. Interactive features like role-playing simulations enable students to practise language skills in various real-life scenarios, providing a

safe environment for skill application before authentic use. Progress tracking and feedback mechanisms can show improvements in fluency, pronunciation, and participation, helping students monitor their development and set new goals. Additionally, offering flexible learning options, including asynchronous recordings and customizable schedules, helps students adapt to different time zones and personal commitments.

9.6.5 Recommendations for Blended Learning and Supporting Self-Discipline

For a more effective blended learning experience, universities should provide students, especially those living far from campus, with the option to choose online course formats where possible. Optimizing scheduling with a 15-30 minute buffer between online and in-person classes helps alleviate potential stress such as transition stress and enhances the overall learning experience. Time management tools within learning platforms, along with camera use and attendance tracking policies, can support student engagement in online classes and promote the development of self-discipline, which is essential for academic success in digital learning environments.

These recommendations collectively establish a structured framework for students, educators, universities, and online platforms to collaboratively enhance the online learning experience for Chinese students. By prioritizing self-regulation, intercultural exchange, psychological support, and interactive digital tools, these strategies aim to promote meaningful engagement, uphold assessment integrity, and foster robust language development. Such an integrative approach not only facilitates academic growth but also supports students' holistic personal development in digital and hybrid learning environments.

9.7 Academic and Personal Growth: Reflections and Gains in the Research Process

In the process of conducting this in-depth research, I have not only gained rich

academic knowledge but also experienced significant personal growth. The multidimensional exploration in this study has provided me with a deeper understanding of higher education, students, lecturers, platforms, and myself.

Firstly, through the practical application of methodologies, I have realized the importance of specific research methods such as data analysis, statistical software utilization, and literature review. Through data analysis, I have learned how to extract key information from large datasets and apply statistical software for quantitative analysis. Additionally, during the literature review, I have deepened my understanding of existing knowledge and discovered new research perspectives and questions. These skills have not only been immensely helpful in this study but will also play a significant role in my future academic career.

Secondly, through interactions with participants, I have gained a richer understanding of the experiences of students studying abroad. In this process, I have played the role of not only a researcher but also, to some extent, a teacher and a student. The interaction with participants has made me realize that education is about guidance and inspiration, and learning is a process of continuous exploration and discovery. These experiences have not only influenced my understanding of education and learning but have also made me contemplate how to apply these understandings to my personal and professional development.

During the research process, I have also engaged with online education platforms. While these platforms provide convenience for students, they also present challenges and limitations. For example, how to maintain student engagement and provide effective feedback are issues that require further thought and solutions. These experiences have made me pay more attention to the application and development of technology in education and have sparked my thinking about future directions in higher education or technological improvements.

Furthermore, this research has provided me with significant insights into the gains

from cross-cultural communication. Through interactions with participants from different countries, I have not only learned about their cultural backgrounds and individual conceptual differences but also learned how to utilize communication strategies to establish effective communication. These insights have enriched my personal life and have made me more confident and professional in my work from an international perspective.

As a researcher, I have undergone significant transformation and development in this study. I have not only learned how to independently design and implement a rigorous research project but also learned how to analyze and interpret data from multiple dimensions and perspectives. Importantly, this research has clarified my research direction and interests, laying a solid foundation for my future academic career. Additionally, this research experience has inspired my thinking about future research directions. I will continue to monitor the development trends and challenges in the fields of transnational education and online education and explore more effective solutions using new research methods and technological approaches.

Throughout this journey, my academic experience has been profoundly shaped by my time in the UK, spanning the pre-pandemic, pandemic, and post-pandemic periods from 2019 to 2022. Over three years of not returning to my home country, I faced long stretches of solitude, often spending time in my apartment with my cat, Leo, and occasionally with the company of friends. This period was marked by moments of loneliness, anxiety, and depression. However, it also became a time of growth and resilience. Reflecting on those challenges, I take pride in my ability to navigate through them and emerge stronger and more self-assured.

Overall, this research has not only brought significant gains and growth in my academic journey but also provided deep reflections and progress on a personal level. I believe that this research experience and its outcomes will have positive impacts on my future and will also provide valuable insights and references for understanding online education for Chinese students in the context of transnational education and

oral communication education.

9.8 Future Research

9.8.1 Expanding the Scope of Inquiry in Online Language Learning

To enhance the rigour and applicability of future research in the field of online language learning, it is essential to broaden the scope of inquiry beyond the current limitations. This approach should emphasize inclusivity and diversity, offering a more holistic understanding of how online learning can support the development of students' oral language skills.

Future studies should aim to include a larger and more diverse sample, covering a broader range of student groups from various age brackets, educational levels, and institutions. This includes participants from different regions, backgrounds, and learning stages. Expanding the sample diversity will help ensure that research findings are more representative and generalizable. By including data from underrepresented groups and students with varying proficiency levels, researchers can gain a richer understanding of the factors influencing the development of oral language skills through online learning. This will contribute to the identification of general trends as well as unique challenges faced by different student populations.

To fully understand the potential of online language learning, research should extend beyond higher education environments. Investigating the impact of online learning on oral language skills in primary schools, secondary schools, and specialized language training institutions can provide a more comprehensive view of language acquisition across various developmental stages. Such research would allow for a deeper understanding of how online tools and platforms influence language skills at different stages of the learning process, leading to more targeted recommendations for different age groups and educational contexts.

9.8.2 Incorporating Lecturer Perspectives in Online Language Learning Research

Lecturers play a pivotal role in the success of online language learning, particularly in guiding students' development of oral language skills. Including lecturers' insights can enrich understanding of the online teaching process and the challenges it entails, specifically:

Future research should involve structured interviews with lecturers who are actively engaged in online language learning and teaching. Such interviews could yield valuable qualitative data about lecturers' strategies, challenges, and successes in promoting oral language skills through virtual platforms. By understanding the specific techniques that lecturers find effective, as well as the hurdles they face, researchers can better identify key areas for improvement in online language teaching.

Quantitative surveys can complement interviews by collecting data from a broader range of lecturers. These surveys should be designed to gather information about teaching practices, the availability and effectiveness of online resources, and the support structures provided by institutions. Analyzing this data will help researchers gain a broader perspective on how lecturers adapt their methods for online language instruction and what additional support might be needed to enhance their effectiveness.

Organizing workshops, webinars, and discussion forums focused on online language teaching can foster collaboration among educators. These forums can serve as platforms for sharing innovative practices, discussing challenges, and exploring solutions for teaching oral language skills online. Such professional exchanges could not only contribute to improving teaching quality but also provide researchers with new data and insights into best practices in the field.

9.8.3 Long-term and Tech Strategies for Online Speaking Skills

To advance the understanding of oral language skill development in online language learning, future research should prioritize longitudinal studies, student engagement, and the role of technology in fostering effective spoken language practice. Longitudinal research is essential to capture how students' oral language skills evolve over time in online learning environments, from early preparatory stages through to advanced levels in formal academic programmes. By tracking students' progress, researchers can identify which online learning features have a lasting impact on students' speaking abilities and highlight areas where additional support may be needed to reinforce oral proficiency at different educational stages.

Research should also address specific methods that encourage real-time spoken interaction, such as integrating structured speaking opportunities, promoting active verbal participation, and providing real-time feedback. These activities can help students become more confident speakers while engaging them directly with learning material. Moreover, studies that focus on the effectiveness of live speaking practice, as opposed to asynchronous learning, will be valuable in evaluating how direct interaction impacts pronunciation, fluency, and confidence in spoken language skills.

With rapid technological advancements, future studies should examine how various online platforms and tools, particularly those equipped with AI, can support spoken language development. Research should focus on evaluating the effectiveness of features like real-time pronunciation correction, adaptive feedback on grammar and syntax, and conversational AI tutors, as these innovations offer personalized and engaging ways to practice speaking. Examining how students interact with these tools will provide insights into optimizing AI-driven language learning experiences that cater to individual learner needs.

Finally, technical challenges, such as unstable internet connections or limited access to digital resources, can significantly impact students' learning experiences. Investigating solutions to these issues—such as bandwidth optimization, improved platform design, and the inclusion of offline learning resources—will be essential to

ensure all students can benefit from stable and accessible online learning environments for speaking practice.

In conclusion, future research in online language learning should concentrate on developing and refining methods to support and develop spoken language skills. By focusing on longitudinal progress, real-time interactive activities, the impact of advanced technologies, and overcoming technical barriers, researchers can contribute to more effective, engaging, and accessible strategies for oral language development in online learning settings.

9.9 Conclusion

This study focuses on Chinese international students and explores the effects of online learning on improving English-speaking abilities. Using a qualitative analysis approach, it constructs a comprehensive analytical framework encompassing key elements such as learning motivation, social capital, cultural capital, and learning habits.

The research findings show that online learning can positively influence the development of English-speaking proficiency among Chinese international students. However, the study also identifies challenges, such as learners' difficulties in maintaining engagement and adapting to virtual learning environments. These insights suggest new directions for future research, including comparing learning experiences across different educational settings and refining the design and implementation of online language learning environments.

Additionally, this study fills theoretical gaps in the field of online language learning, offering innovative analytical frameworks and theoretical insights. It provides practical, targeted recommendations for educators to enhance online language instruction. These findings contribute to improving the quality and effectiveness of online education, fostering more effective learning strategies and providing a

foundation for future advancements in online language learning.

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Appendices

Appendix 1 Online Observations Field note - A and B Examples

Observations Journal

Observation is the process of collecting field notes by observing the people and places of the research site. This method of data collection offers an opportunity to record information related to the actual behaviours of individuals in the research site (Creswell, 2012). Based on the reading and summary of Creswell (2012), observation in qualitative research involves the systematic process of collecting data by observing individuals and their environments within the research site. Creswell outlines several key steps that guide the observation process:

- Choose an observation site that will help you best understand the central phenomenon.
- Look around and enter the site slowly; Take limited notes, at least initially.
- Decide who or what to observe, when to observe, and for how long of the observation.
- Identify your role as an observer.
- Make multiple observations to understand best of the site and individuals
- Design some recording methods during observation
- What information will you record during your observation
- Record descriptive and reflective field comments
- Allow yourself to be known, but remain unobtrusive
- Slowly withdraw from the site after observation

The HNC Pre-MBA Business English online course (Group A) was chosen for observation. The course covers Business English skills such as listening, speaking, reading, and writing. The students have an elementary level of English proficiency, which can be compared to an IELTS score below 6.0, indicating they are still developing their ability to communicate effectively in English, especially in a business context. There are a total of five students in Group A.

After the researcher explained the purpose and details of the study to the students, a total of four students were enrolled in the course. They came from different cities in China and did not know each other before joining. Two of them ultimately signed the university's Participant Information Sheet and Consent Form, agreeing to be observed.

Table 1 Overview of Group A Participants

Participants	Gender	Status	Oral English Language Proficiency during the online class
A1	F	The students did not know each other before the course.	2
A2	M		1

Table 2 Field notes from Group A's observations-1

<p>Setting: Microsoft Teams online class Role of Researcher: Observer Time: 1.30pm-3.30pm Date:27-09-2021</p>
<p>Descriptive Field Notes</p> <p>1. Review At the beginning of class, the teacher gives feedback on the problems in each student's homework and asks the students to correct them, and then asks the students to send the revised homework to the chat box.</p> <p>2. New lesson The teacher asks questions about the learning content, and all students answer. Then the teacher asks questions one to one, and students answer one to one. At this time, everyone communicates in English.</p> <p>3. Next, the teacher-led the students to do listening exercises. After the listening played, check the answers. A2 actively answers the questions. The teacher asks "Do I need to play the listening again?" but no one answered.</p> <p>4. The teacher divided the class into two groups and asked the students to discuss and share their answers in English with other members in the 'break room'. The teacher emphasized that "Students must discuss in English". At this stage, participants check their answers in English, but A1 unconscious use L1 (Chinese). Other students will also repeat the grammar to A1 in Chinese to help her better understand.</p> <p>5. In class, when A1 cannot understand the English words the teacher says, A1 will ask other students in Chinese.</p>
<p>Reflective Field Notes</p> <p>1. Internet speed problem: Audio and video are out of sync due to the network speed delay during the teaching. The display fonts of PPT and electronic textbooks are small type fonts. Sometimes students need to enlarge them by themselves.</p> <p>2. Equipment problem: The PPT flashed back during the teacher's teaching, and the file opening speed sometimes is slow- whether the teacher was using a personal computer or a school laptop.</p> <p>3. Environmental issues: The online classroom environment: When students attend class at home, there are sometimes children's voices in the background sound. This means the students are studying from home, with significant distractions from the lesson going on around them.</p>

Pointers
A student is late and enters the class without knowing where the listening is going.

Table 2 Field notes from Group A's observations-2

<p>Setting: Team online class Role of Researcher: Observer Time: 1.30pm-3.30pm Date:28-09-2021</p>
<p>Descriptive Field Notes</p> <p>1. Four students participated in this class. The teacher teaches the new lesson, and asks simple questions (teacher-led learning), that students only need to answer “YES OR NO”. A2 always actively answers the questions raised by the teacher. Compared with other students, the teacher also prefers to take the initiative to ask A2. A2 is a more active student in the class. Therefore, even if he does not know how to answer some questions in English, he will try to answer Yes/no or use body language.</p> <p>2. During the class, when the teacher asks a question, all the students turn on the microphone to answer the question together. The background sound will be a little noisy, and there will be a phenomenon that you can't hear what everyone is saying.</p> <p>3. Next, the students were arranged to discuss in their ‘break room’. At this stage, A1 and A2 use a mixture of Chinese and English language expressions to exchange answers and discuss learning content with other students to complete the tasks arranged by the teacher.</p> <p>After returning to the main class, the two participants still unconsciously spoke Chinese (they genuinely spoke Chinese and thought they were speaking English), and the teacher could not understand what they were saying.</p> <p>4. At the end of the class, the student asked: "What is the study plan for the next week?", the teacher said: "The English course is about to end, there will be no arrangements for next week." But other students said that there would be specialized courses next week. Students are some confusion about what is happening with this class and the future arrangement of online courses.</p>
<p>Reflective Field Notes</p> <p>1. Internet speed problem: In the group discussion, the students will be systematically arranged into group 1 and group 2, but the researcher is not grouped smoothly due to network problems.</p> <p>2. Equipment problem: Today's class is another teacher. During the class, the teacher's computer was sluggish, and the files crashed.</p> <p>3. The online classroom environment: During group discussion, the voice of children will be heard from students' microphones.</p> <p>4. Electronic materials for class</p>

<p>Teachers and students use electronic textbooks and PowerPoint, whether everyone has become accustomed to this way of learning.</p> <p>5. The advantages of online courses</p> <p>A. For a class with a small number of students in the classroom, the teacher can observe the real-time dynamics of all students through a display page of Teams (this tells the teacher which students are talking, and who they are talking to), which is conducive to the teacher to better grasp the learning situation than in a physical classroom.</p> <p>Students all attend the classes in China from 8.30 pm-10.30 pm (China time). Everyone has classes at home. Online classes can solve the problems of space and time in the UK and China. It certainly allows lessons to take place that couldn't happen without this technology.</p>
<p>Pointers</p>
<p>One student did not turn on his camera or join in the class discussion, so he could not be observed.</p>

Table 2 Field notes from Group A's observations-3

<p>Setting: Team online class Role of Researcher: Observer Time: 1.30pm-3.30pm Date:27-09-2021</p>
<p>Descriptive Field Notes</p> <p>1. This is a review class. Only A2 and another student entered the class at 1.30 pm, and the teacher took the classmates to review and do questions.</p> <p>2. At 2.50 pm, the third classmate entered the class, but just hung up in the classroom and did not participate in the class discussion.</p> <p>3. At 2.56 pm, A1 enters the class, but the background sound can be heard. It shows that she uses her mobile phone to log in to Teams outside (supermarket).</p> <p>It was until 3.15 pm that A1 returned home; at this time, A1 switched to the computer to log in to TEAMS, formally enter the classroom to learn, and communicate with classmates.</p>
<p>Reflective Field Notes</p> <p>The Teams software can be used on these different devices, such as on a computer terminal, a mobile terminal and an iPad. According to A1's participation in the classroom today, we can observe that online class provides no environmental restrictions for students to attend classes, and students can participate in the classroom anywhere. However, It seems that it is also very easy for them to NOT participate in the online class- e.g. the student who joins at 2.50.</p>
<p>Pointers</p>
<p>It is a review lesson, not every student attends the class on time.</p>

Observations Journal- Group B

The purpose of this observation is to collect data and to establish a clearer understanding of the Chinese students' study experiences during the transition period (from being domestic students in China to international students in the UK). As a result, these observations can help me better design effective interview questions.

The doctoral Induction Programme (DIP) as Group B at UWS was chosen for the following observations(1, 2 and 3). The teaching content is based on Doctoral Research Skills, Writing for PhD Study, Doctoral Presentation Skills and Reading for Critical Understanding. The students are at an advanced level in English. In addition, these students are also university teachers in China. There are a total of 8 students in Group B. After I explained the research purpose and detail to the students, 7 of them signed UWS Participant Information Sheet and Consent Form and agreed to be observed. I made three observations, taught by three different teachers or whose classes had different contents.

Table 1 Overview of Group B Participants

Participants	Status	Last Level Of Education
B1	University Teacher of the same university	Pre Doctoral
B2	University Teacher of the same university	Pre Doctoral
B3	University Teacher of the same university	Pre Doctoral
B4	University Teacher of the same university	Pre Doctoral
B5	University Teacher of the same university	Pre Doctoral
B6	University Teacher of the same university	Pre Doctoral
B7	University Teacher of the same university	Pre Doctoral

Table 2 Field notes from Group B's observations-1

Setting: Zoom online class Role of Researcher: Observer Time: 9.00 am -12.00 am Date:02-11-2021
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<p>Descriptive Field Notes</p> <p>1. Review The teacher gave feedback on the completion of the homework and pointed out the problems that students had in the assignment. Teacher prompted students with keywords and guided students to use complex sentences to answer questions. When discussing the vocabulary they learned last class, the teacher asked every student to share their understanding.</p> <p>2. New lesson Next, the teacher asked the students to think about the theme (Plagiarism) of the new lesson and assigned the reading materials. When the students finish reading the material on the screen, the teacher asks the students to use the "Raise Hand" function of ZOOM. After all the students raised their virtual hands, students answered the questions in order.</p> <p>3. Group discussion The teacher divided every 2/3 students into three groups and asked the students to share their views on "Plagiarism" with the group members. During the period, the teacher used the "Chatbox" function to send discussion topics and to all the students, and everyone has received the message on the screen. The group I observed was composed of B1 and B5. During the discussion, B1's poor network affected the start time of the group discussion. The two students communicate fluently in English, asking questions and answering in English to each other. It is worth noting that B1 uses Chinese to explain 'relevant proper nouns' to facilitate the understanding of B5. During the group discussion, the teacher entered each group to monitor. In my group, the teacher came in and monitored twice.</p> <p>4. Back in the primary Zoom classroom, the teacher asked the representatives of the three groups (B2, B1 and B3) to share their views. B5 combined the experience to supplement her/his opinions on Plagiarism, and the students communicated fluently in English. At the same time, the teacher continued to ask questions in-depth, using words to encourage students to think, and finally led to the definition of Plagiarism.</p> <p>5. The teacher shared the screen and sent reading files in the Chatbox for students to download and read. The teacher assigned 8 minutes for reading exercises and asked students 'Once you have completed the notes for the key points, please raise your hand'. Finally, the teacher guided the students to summarize the key points of the lesson. When B1 does not know how to express himself in English, other students will help him answer questions in English. And concludes the class after students' active discussion.</p>
<p>Reflective Field Notes</p> <p>1. Flexible use of online course platform functions is conducive to improving classroom teaching and learning efficiency. In addition to PPT, Moodle, web pages, video websites, and interactive websites can also be used in the online classroom.</p> <p>2. Writing the requirements of group discussion on the PPT and sending the discussion topics to each group is helpful for students to understand what the teacher means.</p>

<p>3. The students took online classes at home or in their offices, but there were no interruptions from children or others.</p> <p>4. B5, B3 was forgetting to turn on the microphone when answering a question. The teacher reminded them to open the microphone to answer questions, but they didn't realize it themselves. This is different from the actual classroom.</p>
<p>Pointers</p> <p>The UK changed the British Winter Time of 2021 on 31 October, when the time difference between the UK and China from 7 became 8 hours. But the class start time in the university has not changed. This means that students' start time for classes (Beijing time) has changed from 4-7 pm to 5-8 pm.</p>

Table 2 Field notes from Group B's observations-2

<p>Setting: Zoom online class Role of Researcher: Observer Time: 9.00 am -12.00 am Date:03-11-2021</p>
<p>Descriptive Field Notes</p> <p>1. First of all, the teacher introduces the topic of the class, explains the requirements for discussion, and divides the students into three groups with 2-3 members per group.</p> <p>2. In the group discussion, students B2 and B7 communicated fluently in English and had a smooth conversation. They actively participated in the discussion.</p> <p>3. Back in the primary Zoom classroom, the teacher asked the students to summarize the ideas discussed, and put the ideas into the Chatbox to send to all the students.</p> <p>4. Once again, the teacher arranged for the students to have a group discussion according to the teaching content. B1 and B5 first communicated with each other about their daily life in Chinese, and then discussed in English. Then back to the main Zoom class, the teacher asked each student to share their views and typed them into the PPT.</p> <p>5. The teacher asked the students to download two files from UWS Moodle and leave them 10-15 minutes to read them by themselves. During the reading time, almost all students turned off the camera. Then the teacher explained the meaning of proper nouns to the students.</p> <p>6. Next, when listening practice. The teacher sent the video to the students, and students listened to it by themselves. After listening, students have a group discussion. During the discussion, B3 used 'He/She' incorrectly, although the student understands the difference between he and she, B3 still makes slip, I guess this is due to the influence of L1's mother tongue. In Chinese, "he, she and it" are all pronounced the same "Tā", while does not need to be distinguished in oral Chinese.</p> <p>7. Finally, the teacher guided the students to summarize the lesson's key points and concluded the class after students' active discussion.</p>
<p>Reflective Field Notes</p>

<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Due to the inconvenient working environment at home, the teacher took classes in the school office instead, but the equipment in the school office was old and not suitable for online classes. The video is not particularly sharp, and the microphone is low in sound. 2. When the teacher shows PPT, the shared screen display is incomplete. Part of the content is blocked out, presumably the teacher wasn't aware that the powerpoint wasn't fully visible. However no one in the class pointed out the problem. 3. During the group discussion, the two students put the microphone on. When B2 speaks, B7's microphone echoes back, so it's worth considering the impact of these technical issues on overall lesson quality. 4. In addition to PPT, Moodle, web pages, video websites, and interactive websites can also be used in the online classroom.
Pointers
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. B6 entered the classroom at 9.36 am (have asked for leave in advance) 2. Only 1/3 of B6's head can be seen through the camera, so we can assume she is present. But maybe it's difficult to know if she is fully engaged with the lesson.

Table 2 Field notes from Group B's observations-3

Setting: Zoom online class Role of Researcher: Observer Time: 9.15 am -12.00 am Date:05-11-2021
Descriptive Field Notes
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Since the usual class time is at 9.00 am (but the actual class time is 9.15 am, most students enter the classroom at 9:00. There is no waiting room, so students share their daily routines and discuss assignments in Chinese. 2. The teacher came into the classroom and greeted the students. B2, B3 and B5 shared their opinions fluently in spoken English. The teacher explained the knowledge and used 'Menti.com' to increase interaction. Students sent their answers to Menti.com through the link shared by the teacher, and then Meti.com vividly presented their answers. 3. In a group discussion, B5 and B6 are paired up. B6's microphone has no sound. The teacher is not in breakout room, in order to successfully complete the discussion, so B5 and B6 decided to communicated through the Wechat audio call. When the teacher monitored the group, B5 explained the reason why B6's voices were heard through the microphone of B5. With the flexibility of the two students, the discussion was successfully completed. 4. Next, the teacher rearranged the group members. B1, B2 and B6 were divided into one group. Since the microphone of B6 still couldn't work. B1 and B2 communicated with each other in English, while B6 typed in the Chatbox in English. In the communication process, B1 occasionally used Chinese (maybe subconsciously, because B1 not very fluent in spoken English, his English is limited to express his ideas, therefore, he often use Chinese to express his ideas), while the other two

<p>students would still answer in English.</p> <p>5. The teacher asked the students about their understanding of the reading material. B2, B4, B5 and B7 actively participated in class discussions, B4 took the initiative to raise his hand and share his opinion. His in-depth and well-organised presentation demonstrated not only his level of understanding of the material but also his active participation in classroom communication. Especially B7, who was fluent in oral English and used more complex lexis and more low-frequency vocabulary.</p> <p>6. Finally, the teacher used a questionnaire to allow students to choose their own reading assignment, giving them the option to select between Article A or Article B, thereby granting them autonomy in deciding their assignment.</p>
<p>Reflective Field Notes</p> <p>1. There no 'Waiting Room' for the actual class, By canceling the waiting room, students enter the virtual classroom and communicate with other students, which is similar to the actual class. If the teacher sets the waiting room, the student can only face the reminder box of Zoom until the teacher clicks to start the class. 'Waiting Room' because there is a lack of communication between students before and after class. Therefore, teachers can consider to cancel the 'Waiting Room' to give students an environment to discuss before the class starts.</p> <p>2. In a group discussion, B6's microphone has no sound, it affects the communication efficiency of group discussion</p> <p>3. In addition to PPT, Moodle, web pages, video websites, and interactive websites can also be used in the online classroom. In this class, the teacher uses 'Menti.com' to increase classroom interaction.</p> <p>4. Students and teachers need to be able to flexibly deal with the equipment problems in class, such as the failure of the B6 microphone, without the help of a teacher, B6 did not give up participating in classroom interaction, she find the solutions to using Wechat call and typing in the Chatbox, to participate in group discussion.</p>
<p>Pointers</p> <p>B6 did not turn on the camera, so B6's level of engagement cannot be observed.</p>

Appendix 2 Online Interview Transcription and Coding examples

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Participant 1

Interviewer: Hello and welcome to this study. Let me start by introducing my research, which is exploring the role of online learning in the development of English speaking skills and how it can be used to facilitate Chinese students' transnational educational experiences at UK universities. Today's interview is anonymous and voluntary, you can ask questions at any time, and we can stop the interview at any time if you feel pressured during the process. If you wish to withdraw from the study afterwards, you can also contact me at any time and withdraw at any time. Then, if you're ready, we'll start the interview.

Participant 1: Okay.

Interviewer: Can you tell me about your subject and which faculty you belong to at UWS?

Participant 1: My subject is Business Administration, so it belong to a business school.

Interviewer: And what grade are you in?

Participant 1: I am now in my third year.

Interviewer: Do you have to do your fourth year after your third year? Or do you apply directly to a master's degree?

Participant 1: I'm still thinking about it.

Interviewer: Okay, I understand. And what year did you start at UWS?

Participant 1: I am enrolled from 2019 but I gap a year in the middle.

Interviewer: OK so for 2019 you are taking offline courses?

Participant 1: Yes.

Interviewer: So when did you go back to the UWS?

Participant 1: I am starting again in 2021.

Interviewer: So you've already started online courses in 2021?

Participant 1: Yes.

Interviewer: Okay. So can you share your experience with the online course at UWS?

Participant 1: Most of my courses are conducted online, but I also have the option to attend classes on campus because the offline content is synchronous.

Interviewer: I understand. It's been a combination of online and offline since you started back at UWS in 2021, right?

Participant 1: Yes.

Interviewer: And do you prefer to go to school or take courses online?

Participant 1: Although I think offline courses are more interesting, but for me, it's better to go online, I guess.

Interviewer: Why?

Participant 1: I feel safer in online courses.

Interviewer: And where do you take your courses online? Is it at home, or somewhere else?

Participant 1: In the school accommodation.

Interviewer: And do you think that the actual location of participation in the online courses affects your ability to learn?

Participant 1: I don't think so. It is acceptable for me to have online courses at home.

Interviewer: Okay, so what do you think is the difference between an online course and an on-campus course?

Participant 1: I think that online courses may require students to listen to the lectures themselves and take the initiative to learn. In campus courses, students can communicate with the teacher and ask questions directly if they don't know something. But with online courses, it may not be as convenient.

Interviewer: I understand. So the online class you're talking about is the equivalent of the teacher taking the class offline while she has a live stream? And does she record them?

Participant 1: It's live class. This may depends on teacher, but some students may ask the teacher to record it. Or students can record themselves.

Interviewer: Do you prefer online or offline?

Participant 1: I like to be online.

Interviewer: Apart from the security reasons you just mentioned. Do you think there are other reasons why you think it's better to be online?

Participant 1: I might be able to look up information. For example, if I don't understand something in an online class, I can look it up immediately, but in an offline class, I can't look it up immediately and I'll be nervous if I had to answer questions.

Interviewer: And what do you use to find information?

Participant 1: Use a computer, use an iPad to go to an online class and use a computer to look up information.

Interviewer: Is it on a website or is there software like this to help you learn?

Participant 1: Yes.

Interviewer: Can you give me an example?

Participant 1: For example, In real-time online classes, when I encounter something I don't understand, I can immediately search for the answer in the browser.

Interviewer: I understand. Which do you think is more effective for you, the online or offline mode of learning?

Participant 1: I think there are advantages for both, but I'm more of an online person.

Interviewer: OK So for you, actually what you experienced in 2019 years was offline, and then when you came back it was a combination of online and offline. How do you feel that now that you're back at UWS for the second time and you've changed to an online course, how does that help you in your transitional learning from Chinese education to British education?

Participant 1: I believe that the education systems in China and the UK are different. In the UK classroom, lecturers may pay more attention to each student's own ideas and encourage them to express their own opinions. In China, there are more people in the classroom, and the lecturer may not be able to ask every student, so students have relatively fewer opportunities for oral expression.

Interviewer: You didn't do your undergraduate studies in China, did you?

Participant 1: I did, but I was in a special situation, I didn't really do an undergraduate degree, I did a foundation course or something like that.

Interviewer: I see, and what challenges do you find when you are in the online courses at UWS?

Participant 1: No challenge.

Interviewer: The online course, because you took it in the UK, right? So you don't have the problem of time difference.

Participant 1: Yes.

Interviewer: Have you encountered any other problems? Like technical problems or something like that.

Participant 1: Sometimes the teacher has an accent and I can't understand a bit of it.

Interviewer: I understand. Did you have any problems with the network or computer equipment or anything like that?

Participant 1: I haven't encountered any problem of these, the teachers are quite well prepared.

Interviewer: I understand. In the online course, do you go and participate in class discussions? How often do you think you speak English in class?

Participant 1: I don't actively participate in discussions, but if the lecturer directly asks me a question, then I will respond.

Interviewer: I understand. And do you think that online courses can provide you with the opportunity to practice speaking?

Participant 1: I think it can offer, but it depends on whether the teacher wants me to answer the questions or not.

Interviewer: So for you, if the teacher asks a question you will answer it?

Participant 1: Yes. I get to practice speaking English when I answer questions.

Interviewer: Do you have group discussions? Do you discuss with other students during group discussions?

Participant 1: We have group discussions, but I don't really participate in them, I might ask what part I'm responsible for, or if I have a question I'll ask the group. I might ask what part I am responsible for, or if I have a question I will ask the group. We often just type and discuss in the application without anyone speaking

Interviewer: I see. So everyone doesn't just have a voice discussion in the group? Or is it just that for you, you don't really like to communicate in oral English?

Participant 1: In some courses, the teacher organises a group discussion and arranges for students to answer a certain question, with the microphone on. But in my case, it depends on whether I will answer the question or not, and I will only participate if I know the answer.

Interviewer: Okay, because I've been to observe some online courses before, and there are some Chinese students who might speak Chinese to the teacher and the students during the class, what kind of perspective does this have for you?

Participant 1: I would speak Chinese to the teacher, so if the teacher is from China, that might be fine. I think most of the students in the class are from different countries, so I think it's better to speak English so that everyone understands.

Interviewer: I understand. And are there any other Chinese students in your class?

Participant 1: Yes, but the teachers basically assigned us to different groups, and there were very few Chinese students in the same group.

Interviewer: I see, so it's the teachers who deliberately put students from different countries into groups, right?

Participant 1: Yes. It's like this, the teacher probably just wants us to practise speaking.

Interviewer: And what responsibilities do you think students should take in online courses?

Participant 1: When participating in online courses, students need to learn more independently, as online courses may require students to listen and learn actively.

Interviewer: Is there anything else?

Participant 1: No.

Interviewer: I see. So how do you feel about the current arrangement of online programmes for international students at the beginning of their studies?

Participant 1: I think it's adequate and there are a lot of tutoring sessions that have been changed to offline now.

Interviewer: I understand. So what would be a better model for you to take courses? Online and offline or a combination of online and offline? Why?

Participant 1: I think you can combine online and offline because I think it might be better to have a part online and part offline learning for the students and teachers.

Interviewer: I see. Is there anything else you'd like to add to our interview today about the online learning experience during the transition from China to the UK?

Participant 1: No more.

Interviewer: Ok, thanks for your participation, thanks.

Participant 1: You're welcome.

Participant 4

Interviewer: Welcome you participate in this research, so my topic is An exploration of the role of online education in developing oral English skills to facilitate the transnational education experiences of Chinese students progressing to University study in the UK, so today's interview is voluntary. And you should feel free to ask any questions during the interview. And if you feel nervous or anything cause you stress, we can stop this interview immediately. So if you are ready, we can start our interview now.

Participant 4: Ok.

Interviewer: OK, so first question is could you please tell me yourself and your academic background, you don't need mention your name?

Participant 4: Ok, so I am a fourth year student based on HR at UWS.

Interviewer: Yeah, so sorry could you repeat your subject?

Participant 4: That is HRM, human resource management.

Interviewer: Ok. Which year are you studying?

Participant 4: I am in the fourth year, the last year of my bachelor study.

Interviewer: OK, so when have you start your study at UWS?

Participant 4: Oh, it's back to 2018.

Interviewer: OK, so you started your bachelor degree since 2018 and till now.

Participant 4: Yes.

Interviewer: Ok . And please tell me about your online learning experiences at UWS?

Participant 4: Oh, online courses started like 2 years ago. And basically all the courses are going online. They're like no campus and courses.

Interviewer: Yes.

Participant 4: It kind surprise I guess at the beginning.

Interviewer: Yeah, so could you please introduce your online courses more details?

Participant 4: what do you mean online?

Interviewer: Yeah, I mean because you changed the offline to online and what courses looks like? Where is the difference between the online and offline?

Participant 4: Obviously online one is fully focus on remotely all the module and information is online. On campus and is more like you physically attended class and I think online one is more convenient compared to the offline courses.

Interviewer: I see. So can you tell me why do you think online is more convenient?

Participant 4: Because I'm located in Aberdeen, not in paisley. So basically on the online courses more like. As I said convenient for me because I don't have to travel all the way down there. I can just take the online courses and in my house. I don't have to buy a ticket to the paisley. It takes me more than 3 hours travel from where I located to Paisley. That is why online is more convenient for me.

Interviewer: Ok thanks. So where do you like take online courses at home or other some else place?

Participant 4: At home. Mainly at home

Interviewer: OK, so anything else place?

Participant 4: No.

Interviewer: Ok. And do you think the physical location will affect your study or not?

Participant 4: Yes, I think it does affect.

Interviewer: Can you tell me why?

Participant 4: I guess. Depends on the environment, you might get distracted.

Interviewer: Ok, I understand so you mean the distracted what what that mean?

Participant 4: This location. I feel more confident when studying at home. I don't like meeting a lot of people. But if I go to campus, I feel very nervous and stressed.

Interviewer: Yeah, I see.

Participant 4: So when I am at home, it can just make my study more easily.

Interviewer: Ok, so do you prefer online courses or the campus based courses?

Participant 4: I mean for the fourth year student obviously on the campus courses are more better. But, personally, I like online courses because, like according to my life, online courses it's like much better than the campus courses.

Interviewer: Yeah, I see.

Participant 4: If the lecturer requires us to attend on-campus classes, I do not have the right to choose online courses. We must follow the lecturer's instructions. I once asked if I could choose online courses due to the long distance but was told that as a full-time student, I do not have that choice.

Interviewer: Oh, I see. So you mean whether online or offline. It actually depends on the lecture on the school.

Participant 4: Yes, yeah, mostly.

Interviewer: OK. I understand so for you personally you think online is much better for you, because you feel more confident and you don't need to go to school anymore and it can save your time? And I guess it will save your money as well.

Participant 4: Yeah, but obviously as a fourth year students studying last year of the undergraduate study it's good to attend Class on the campus, because the students can get more concentrated and that's what I am presently preferred. But again, it is really far away for me to travel from Aberdeen to down there and then the lectures requiring you to go to the class on campus. Before, I once emailed to my lecture, said, Can I attend online courses because I located quite far away from Paisley? But my lectures replied, that because you are enrolled as the full time student so that's not appropriate. I mean he forced me to go. He didn't give me many choices, but like yeah, he said to me: 'you have to go on campus now, not online. Because you don't have any like reasonable reason.'

Interviewer: I see. So what do you think are the benefits of taking online courses?

Participant 4: There are quite a lot of benefits. Yes, you can search a few sources when the lecture ask you to bring the questions. If you don't know the answer, ok, just Googled it and find the answer.

Interviewer: Yeah, anything else.

Participant 4: It is very creative teaching. You want to see how is the lecture going on if the courses like 2 hours or during the tutorial can take online courses, it is never had it before. Looks like new for us.

Participant 4: I think there's quite a few drawbacks too.

Interviewer: OK, I see. Like what?

Participant 4: People can't concentrate. It is hard to focus on what the teacher said. It for the 2 hours courses. Seems like everyone can be lack of practice. They are completely silent when they put into the breakout room.

Interviewer: I see.

Interviewer: So what's the challenge for you have you faced any challenges during the online courses.

Participant 4: Again, too hard to focus, hard to concentrate like what I said. You just want to do something else like play your phone or others during the 2 hours class. It is a really big challenge. Less concentrate. Another one is because I have a part time job. Sometimes my course conflicts with work hours, making it hard for me to concentrate. It's challenging for me to listen to lectures while working.

Interviewer: Ok. So if you do online courses. I guess you can still take participate through your phone.

Participant 4: Yeah, you can going to the lecture by phone. But you won't be able to listen to what they say during the work, it is too hard for you to focus.

Interviewer: I know. So how did you overcome this problems?

Participant 4: Try not to work. Attend the courses or sometimes like go on to my phone and then work while I have my courses. But I don't have any class now. It was just like the first 3 months in January, February and March were quite hard for me to handle it. During that time, I have quite a lot courses, but I'm working and now it's fine. I don't have many class, I just have a essay to submit. But, normally I'm just adjusting my working hours, then go to the class and go on to the Zoom or Teams during that time.

Interviewer: Got it.

Interviewer: So have you ever encountered technological problems during online?

Participant 4: Not really, because I got quite stable Wi-Fi. But they are quite a lot students are complaining about their Wi-Fi is not working or very low speed. All my friends had this kind of problem before.

Interviewer: I see.

Participant 4: And one interesting to mention that but. It's about one lecture. Back to last time, she suppose to give us a lecture for 2 hours. Every time she's got the technical problems and everybody was trying to help her to fix it. But then somehow she just missed the class, left

the class or finished the class. Every single time she tried to teach on there, there should have some technical problems appear. And she don't come back, after she fix it or I don't think she can fix it. Whatever, she just finished class and leave everyone there to wait for her.

Interviewer: So what can you learn after that?

Participant 4: Nothing. Because. It happens every single week when she tried to teach us and there's some kind of issue is coming up. But maybe for the first half an hour, she's really trying to teach us something, but after that again there are some problems happen, and she's just coming forward to say anything else.

Interviewer: So will she send some PDF or some reading materials or videos to you?

Participant 4: She's got send some video, pictures. And she's sending it on moudle. But then she's also trying to play it when we in the lecture but I think pointless.

Interviewer: Ok. Will that effect to your study for this for this subject?

Participant 4: Yeah definitely. Everyone just don't want to attend her courses anymore.

Interviewer: Yeah, I see. And after that did you get a good score for this subject.

Participant 4: I would say it's a decent score. Yeah, it is a really good score. So it is not a big problem.

Interviewer: OK, I see. So do you think that online courses can provide you with a good opportunity to practice your speaking?

Participant 4: I think it depends, I will try to speak English in online classes and continue to improve my oral proficiency.

Interviewer: Why?

Participant 4: Is just too shy to say I guess. Or sometimes, I just didn't catch what the teacher is asking me.

Interviewer: Yes.

Participant 4: I just tried to like not to answer anything in the class.

Interviewer: Ok, so do you have group discussion during online class?

Participant 4: Yeah, every single time when I have my courses online. Because the lecture will put you into a breakout room. So basically there are quite a lot students in the breakout room. You have to discuss the articles or a sectional issues. Actually the leture give you some kind of issues that you have to discovered in the group. That does happen every time when I have my on courses, especially with my program leader, she very like discussion every single time.

Interviewer: yeah, when the discussion group will you join the discussion and will everybody is sharing an speaking English in that time?

Participant 4: Mostly we just silence and we don't talk. Everyone dislike to talk in my courses. We waiting for the people to talk, but then nobody's talk so we just silence just don't talk for the whole time.

Interviewer: I see. So will you talk with your classmates before or after the class?

Participant 4: I will do that in my first year. I will try and am still trying my best to speak English, just for my own benefit to improve myself and to improve others. But not now.

Interviewer: So why you can did it at first year why is changed.

Participant 4: I think it's because I have experiences. Everyone is hidden behind their computers and phones. I feel like I have become lazy, and that's the main reason why I lose interest in anything. But on the actual class, we have to meet then we should do something.

Interviewer: Yeah, you mean for the physics class, you can meet your classmates so it's more easier to talk.

Participant 4: Yeah, because. For example, first years I have quiet like scheduled private meet every single week. So normally, we do meet up with my classmate to discuss the materials for the class. Then, the online courses begin we hardly do that. Even though the lecture to requires you to prepare something beforehand, but we just let it go.

Interviewer: I see. How do you feel about the current arrangement of online programmes for international students at the beginning of their studies?

Participant 4: Personally, I think physical classrooms are more suitable for international students. You can have them interact more with local students to overcome their fear of speaking, both before and after class. The online courses for them. Maybe I think they like not enough.

Interviewer: So why do you think for the for the international student physical class more essentially?

Participant 4: Like I said, it gives them more interactions with the local students with their classmates to practice their English or their shortages. I just think physical class better for every single

one including me.

Interviewer: Ok. So compare with the offline courses. What do you think for the responsibilities for students should take in the online courses?

Participant 4: I guess it's just saying that so online courses. Like prepare beforehand attended class online. Make sure your technical issues are sorted. And that kind of thing they need to prepare.

Interviewer: Yep, anything else.

Participant 4: Engagement I guess. Each of the class.

Interviewer: Ok, I see. In my previous observation and I notice that some students they speak Chinese to the teachers and other students during the class. So what do you think about this?

Participant 4: I'm not sure. So normally people will think if you are in the English environment is should speak English, with people that surrounded you.

Participant 4: And then I think it little bit not polite to speak other languages. But now I think it just fine. cause it not cause anything. I'm not really sure about this.

Interviewer: I mean I guess you mean if the student who has stay at English environment an everybody speak English. So you should speak English as well, because I think it is a bit impolite to speak Chinese in public. But if the students who staying with the Chinese group, so you think if they speak Chinese that's still fine.

Participant 4: Yeah. But isn't like if you're in the English environment even though there are Chinese students around you. And you know you should trying your best to encourage yourself to speak English, not just for you, but for other people that surround you. Or for the lectures or the whole class.

Participant 4: I'm don't like speaking Chinese when I am in the English environment. Even though you are in the English environment and you're surrounded by your Chinese classmates. And then I will try and still trying my best to speak English, just for myself benefit to improve myself and to improve others so.

Interviewer: Ok, I understand now.

Participant 4: Yeah, like I don't have any offence their. I'm just saying like just better to speak English to practice more.

Interviewer: So for you what kind of class model is most suitable, online, offline or the combination of online and offline.

Participant 4: I definitely prefer offline one, cause after like a year on the online class, I am tired of it. I want to go back to courses on campus. And I think. It is much better to have Physical class rather than remotely ones. Just like. If you more engaged with the class and speak up more, you don't want just sit there like silence for the whole time.

Interviewer: Yeah, I understand. Today's we are talking about the online study and also especially for the some international students, who are experiences during the transnational period from China to the UK? I think it's not actually it's not a big issue for you, but do think any other comments that we haven't mentioned today do you want talk more?

Participant 4: I think we covered quite a lot areas today.

Interviewer: OK. Thank you for your Participant 4:. So now we finish the interview.

Participant 4: Thank you.

Participant 7

Interviewer: Hello and thank you for taking part in this study. Let me start then with a brief introduction to my topic. My research topic is about An exploration of the role of online education in developing oral English skills to facilitate the transnational education experiences of Chinese students progressing to university study in the UK. Our interview today is voluntary and anonymous, so you can ask questions at any time. If you feel nervous or pressured during the interview, we can end it at any time. You can also withdraw from the study at any time if you wish to do so afterwards. So if you are ready, we will start today's interview.

Interviewer: So first of all, could you please tell us about your academic and professional background and when you enrolled at UWS?

Participant 7: I am from the School of Education and my undergraduate background is in childhood studies. I am studying Early Education for my Masters.

Interviewer: I see, so did you do both your undergraduate and postgraduate studies at UWS? And what year did you start your undergraduate studies?

Participant 7: Yes. Both at UWS. My undergraduate degree is in September 2020.

Interviewer: And had it been converted to an online course?

Participant 7: Yes.

Interviewer: Can you tell us about your online learning experience at UWS? Both your undergraduate and your postgraduate studies.

Participant 7: At the beginning, we were not accustomed to online learning. We had not been exposed to online courses before. After the transition, the lecturers mainly taught based on PPTs, lacking oral interaction and discussions. Compared to offline classes, online classes are much less interactive, and we basically listen to the teacher's lectures, then we take notes on the key points and study on our own. It was the beginning of the Covid-19. So the online classes were not very well arranged at the beginning. The online learning experience of the master's degree was a little more conversational, and then there were more topics to discuss.

Interviewer: I understand. Do you do your online classes at home or do you do them elsewhere?

Participant 7: Internet classes in the school accommodation.

Interviewer: So you're taking classes online in a school accommodation in the UK?

Participant 7: Yes.

Interviewer: I understand. So where do you think you'll be taking your classes online? Does the physical location make any difference to you?

Participant 7: For me, it is safer to go out less. Then I don't have much interest in online classes, so this affects my ability to learn online and overall I don't think online learning is good.

Interviewer: I see, so you prefer to be able to learn at campus, in the classroom, right?

Participant 7: Right. I think offline course would be better.

Interviewer: I understand. And what do you think is the difference between an online course and offline course?

Participant 7: The biggest difference between online and offline courses is the interactivity, the interaction with classmates and teachers, which is lacking. Another thing is that online courses tend to decrease students' self-discipline among students.

Interviewer: I see, so how effective do you think you would be on a campus course?

Participant 7: The level of interest is higher in comparison to online classes. The interest in learning is stronger and there is more interaction with the teacher.

Interviewer: And what do you think are the benefits of online classes?

Participant 7: The online classes were designed to reduce the impact of the Covid-19. The only benefit I see is a reduced risk of infection. The impact of the spread of the Covid-19 is reduced. It protects the health of the students and the teachers, nothing else, that's the only benefit.

Interviewer: As you were enrolled in 2020, it would have been a time when you were just transitioning from your education in China to the UK, and you were just in time for the online courses. How do you think the online courses offered by UWS have helped you in your transnational studies?

Participant 7: The online classes were not particularly helpful for me, because I took them in my

accommodation in the UK. But if the students are still in China, it is very helpful for them to study across the border because it breaks the physical gap.

Interviewer: I understand.

Interviewer: Did you encounter any challenges or difficulties during your time studying online in the UK?

Participant 7: Challenges and difficulties. One is the impact of hardware, such as the internet, which sometimes makes me difficult to log on to online courses. Another is that self-discipline decreases. I occasionally miss the time of my online classes, sometimes I miss half an hour of class or 15 minutes late. It's easier to be late for morning classes. If you don't wake up on time, you'll miss the class. I also occasionally let my mind wander during class. This is also a difficulty with self-discipline.

Interviewer: Understand, when you say you missed a lesson or missed a 15 minute or half hour lesson, what do you think is the reason for this?

Participant 7: Sometimes I ignore that it's time for class. For example, in some courses, students are informed by email 15 minutes in advance, but sometimes I don't get it in time and I may miss some of the emails, which causes me to forget the class time.

Interviewer: I understand.

Participant 7: The individual teacher will send us an email to remind each student, there is 5 minutes left before class starts, and then I see the email so I can be on time for class.

Interviewer: I understand. And what do you think about the issues you've just mentioned, and how do you think they've affected your studies?

Participant 7: For my studies, I may have to go back to the lesson videos repeatedly. The repetition will take up some of my time.

Interviewer: So do teachers offer live online streaming and video recordings of your classes? Could you go into a bit more detail? Did the school offer that when you were an undergraduate?

Participant 7: For undergraduate courses, some teachers offer two types of classes. For postgraduate courses, all teachers offer the two options of offering students either live or recorded lessons.

Interviewer: I understand.

Interviewer: As you mentioned earlier, online courses can lead to a lack of communication. Do you think there are any aspects of online courses that provide you with the opportunity to practice speaking?

Participant 7: During online learning, we rarely had opportunities for oral practice and face-to-face interaction. Most of the time, the lecturers were lecturing, and we were listening. Other teachers will ask questions at the end of the lesson, which will reduce communication if students are reluctant to ask questions. Most teachers also give us the opportunity to ask questions in the middle of the lesson. But I don't answer frequently.

Interviewer: And do you have group discussions or anything like that?

Participant 7: Yes.

Interviewer: And do you get to practice oral English during the group discussions?

Interviewer: It was good practice for oral English. But I don't talk much, because the teacher asks questions and we usually finish the discussion within 5-8 minutes, basically we don't talk after the discussion, but the teacher leaves a lot of time for us.

Interviewer: So what does everyone do for the rest of the group discussion?

Participant 7: Students are less communicative, they stay silent and wait.

Interviewer: How often do you interact with your teachers and classmates during the online classes?

Participant 7: At the beginning of online classes, I was very proactive and answered whatever the lecturer asked. If I didn't know how to express myself clearly, I would use translation software and then communicate with the lecturer. But after a while, I rarely initiated communication. Because some questions can be answered in the pre-reading materials provided by the lecturer, I just read them myself.

Interviewer: I understand. Because I've been to observe some classes before and I've noticed that there are some students who may speak Chinese to the teacher and the students during the class. What do you think of this phenomenon?

Participant 7: I think this is a very normal phenomenon. I don't think it's inappropriate because nowadays there's a lot of diversity in languages and students from different countries are in the same classroom and then it's a normal scene for them to speak their own language.

Interviewer: And do you think the Chinese students in your class will discuss with each other in

Chinese?

Participant 7: We often have discussions in Chinese.

Interviewer: I understand. But do you think discussing in Chinese will help you learn in class?

Participant 7: I think it helps because discussing in Chinese makes us more efficient in solving problems. Yes, we can understand the knowledge better.

Interviewer: I see. How do you feel about the current arrangement of online programmes for international students at the beginning of their studies?

Participant 7: Online courses I feel average, but generally still satisfied, because there has been no large-scale online courses collapse phenomenon.

Interviewer: I see. So what you mean by average, can you tell us a bit more about what you think is the average point?

Participant 7: Most of the lessons are taught by the teacher, and then there is less interaction. If the lecturer didn't have time for online classes, they would pre-record the lecture content and upload it to the school website for students to download and watch on their own.

Interviewer: I understand. What responsibilities do you think students should have in online classes as opposed to offline classes?

Participant 7: In online courses, students should take the initiative to complete the tasks assigned by the teacher. Because this is more important, there are fewer opportunities for communication in online classes, and if the tasks set by the teacher are not completed on time, it will affect the quality of subsequent online classes and will have a negative impact on their own learning.

Interviewer: I understand. So which mode of class do you think would be better for you? Because UWS is now offer for live or recorded online, as well as offline classes. Which do you prefer?

Participant 7: I prefer offline courses.

Interviewer: And when did UWS start offering offline courses?

Participant 7: The offline courses started in the second semester of my Master's degree.

Interviewer: All of them?

Participant 7: Individual courses.

Interviewer: I understand. So for you, even though it's a combination of online and offline, would you still prefer to have all your courses offline?

Participant 7: I would have preferred an offline course if the Covid-19 had improved. But in its current situation, it's safer to go online.

Interviewer: Is there anything else you'd like to add to what we've discussed today about your online learning experience during the transition from China to the UK?

Participant 7: No.

Interviewer: OK, thank you for your participation.

Participant 7: Bye.

Participant 10

Interviewer: Hello and thank you for taking part in this study. Let me start then with a brief introduction to my topic. My research topic is about An exploration of the role of online education in developing oral English skills to facilitate the transnational education experiences of Chinese students progressing to university study in the UK. Our interview today is voluntary and anonymous, so you can ask questions at any time. If you feel nervous or pressured during the interview, we can end it at any time. You can also withdraw from the study at any time if you wish to do so afterwards. So if you are ready, we will start today's interview.

Participant 10: Ok, I'm ready.

Interviewer: Okay, first of all, could you please tell us about your professional and academic background? You don't need to say your name.

Participant 10: I studied Computer Networking at UWS, and I did my third and final year at UWS.

Interviewer: What year did you enter?

Participant 10: The entry year is 2019. I will be a third year student from 2019 to 2020 and then a final year from 2020 to 2021.

Interviewer: I see, so your subject belong to the School of Computing, right?

Participant 10: Yes, it is belongs to the School of Computing.

Interviewer: I understand. So according to your enrolment schedule, would you have been taking offline classes in 2019 and then switched to online in 2020?

Participant 10: Yes.

Interviewer: Can you share your experience of taking online courses in your subject after the school switched to online courses in 2020?

Participant 10: I think it was in April 2020 that the school started online, which were conducted in the form of online classes, and remote experiments were conducted by connecting to the school's computers.

Interviewer: I understand, but how do your teachers teach? What is the difference in the process of the class compared to offline?

Participant 10: The process of the lesson is much simpler, we don't have to go to the classroom, we just turn on our computers, log on to the Zoom and we are ready for the lesson. Then the teacher gives us a lecture and we follow the lecture.

Interviewer: So when you were talking about doing experiments, do all the students connect to the university server and do the experiments at the same time?

Participant 10: Our experiment time will still be separated. Basically, each subject has its own slot, and there is a fixed time to connect to the school's lab computer, and then after that time, we can't use it anymore. In fact, as long as theoretically no one is using it, the students can use it, which is actually quite convenient.

Interviewer: And where did you take your online classes? And did you have any internet problems at home when you were taking online classes or doing experiments?

Participant 10: I haven't really encountered this problem, and I feel like my internet is always fine. If it's a problem with the internet, it's usually the home network that's not working, but it's not likely to be the school lab network, which is fine. And the online platform had a tracking tool, which allowed lecturers to have a clear understanding of each student's situation.'

Interviewer: I understand, so do you think the physical location of the online classes had any impact on your study?

Participant 10: Impact, I think it's good. It's quite relaxing to have online classes at home, I don't have to go out. For example, I don't do online classes in libraries and other places, I think it's good to study at home of the online class.

Interviewer: I understand that you can take classes online from home, and then like you said one of the advantages is the convenience of not having to go out. Are there any other advantages?

Participant 10: Also I am more relaxed at home and my mind is more active. So for me, if I have an active mind, I can do experiments or complete other tasks more efficiently.

Interviewer: I understand. So for you, you taking an offline class for 2019 and an online class for 2020. Do you think any difference between online and offline?

Participant 10: The difference is that one is online and the other is offline.

Interviewer: What are the changes in the curriculum or your participation in the classroom or your interaction with other students?

Participant 10: Offline, I don't think we have much interaction in our offline classes. Even when it's offline, if it's just a class, the students will listen to the teacher, and then teacher will demonstrate the steps us. In the online classes, the teacher also demonstrates and teaches to the students, and the students listen. In terms of communication, I don't think there is much communication on my class. Sometimes we ask each other questions, but we do it through sending text messages via the Chatbox. This method is convenient, but you don't need to speak orally, just send a text message.

Participant 10: If it's a lab class, there may be some communication between students, but it's not much different between online and offline. Offline, I can interpret meaning based on the other person's body movements, which heavily relies on eye contact and gestures. If it's an online lab class, then you don't know the status of the teacher, I don't know if he's online or not, so I may not be able to seek help from the teacher in time. Therefore, I prefer offline lab class.

Interviewer: Ok. So to summarise, the lab class are better offline. And then all the other courses in your subject are basically the same online and offline.

Participant 10: Yes. The other thing is that maybe online, the teacher will give us a video recording of the lesson and we can watch it back afterwards. I cannot review videos of offline lectures, and with the passage of time, sometimes information is forgotten.

Interviewer: I understand. How do you feel about the current arrangement of online programmes for international students at the beginning of their studies?

Participant 10: I don't really know about this one.

Interviewer: No problem. So do you do your online classes in your home in the UK?

Participant 10: For the online classes I took at accommodation in the UK.

Interviewer: And did you have any challenges when you were online in the UK?

Participant 10: The challenge, may be that I can't get up in the morning.

Interviewer: Don't you have this problem with offline classes?

Participant 10: For offline classes, I might push myself, but for online classes, it doesn't matter. I can just open my phone and log in, and I can take the class in bed, so I don't want to get up.

Interviewer: I understand. And will you be able to overcome this problem?

Participant 10: No intention to overcome. Maybe I got up late 10 to 20 minutes, and missed a bit of what the teacher was saying. Basically, if the class in the morning, I will probably join in halfway through the lesson. There is a re-watch of the course, so I can just catch up on the points I missed, it's not a big loss.

Interviewer: I understand. So with the online courses, are there many opportunities for you to practice speaking English for your major?

Participant 10: There are not many opportunities to practise speaking, because in class, it is mainly the teacher who talks. In lab classes, students may have to ask the teacher questions and need to practise speaking. Students need to understand what technical difficulties they have encountered and how to explain this to the teacher, which requires them to practise their English skills.

Interviewer: Okay. And how often do you speak English in class?

Participant 10: If it's just a class, I basically don't have the opportunity to speak English, but in labs, I occasionally ask the teacher questions, maybe once or twice in labs.

Interviewer: And do you have group discussions?

Participant 10: No group discussion.

Interviewer: Yes, and did you have the opportunity to interact with the other students in the class?

Participant 10: Sometimes people ask each other questions, but we all send messages. It's just a typing kind of thing, you don't communicate verbally, you just send a text message to ask.

Interviewer: Ok. What responsibilities do you think students should take in online classes?

Participant 10: What are the responsibilities? I don't really know what that means.

Interviewer: For example, in an offline course, the student's responsibilities might be: to be on time, not to be late for class, and so on. What responsibilities do you think students should have in an online course?

Participant 10: I think, because it's at university level, from the school's point of view, student probably

just need to attend every Zoom class because the platform records attendance. But for the individual student, they may need to take care of their own business and be more self-controlled.

Interviewer: I understand, because I have observed some online courses before, and I found that some students would speak Chinese to the teacher or other students during the class, how do you feel about this phenomenon?

Participant 10: Speak Chinese with teacher, is the teacher Chinese too?

Interviewer: It doesn't have to be Chinese either.

Participant 10: I haven't come across this one.

Interviewer: How do you understand the phenomenon of speaking Chinese with students?

Participant 10: I think it depends on the individual, if we can understand each other, it may be more efficient to communicate in Chinese. When we do group work, if all the members are Chinese, it doesn't really matter if it's in Chinese or English as long as we can achieve our goal, as long as we can finish the work.

Interviewer: Which model of classes is more suitable for you, online, offline or combination of online and offline?

Participant 10: I think I can do it online for regular classes. For labs, I can go offline. For courses that require hands-on work, I think I can get more direct help from the teacher offline.

Interviewer: I understand. And then finally, I'd like to ask again if the online courses offered by UWS are adequate for your experience of studying in the UK, especially during this transition period that you're in?

Participant 10: I think the online course is quite good. I haven't had any problems with the teacher not responding to my questions, because I've encountered situations where even though the labs are online, the teacher's help is quite timely. Personally, I think the content of the course is quite good, but I think it would be better if it was offline at the beginning of transnational education.

Interviewer: Yes. I see. So is there anything else you'd like to add to our conversation today?

Participant 10: I also think the combination of online and offline, I think one thing to consider with this model is the time it takes for students to commute between home and school. I once took a course where the online part was from 10 am to 11 am, followed immediately by the offline class from 11 am to 12 pm. This arrangement was not reasonable for me. If I took online classes at home, I had to rush to the school without much buffer time in between. The school did not take this into account when scheduling this course.

Interviewer: I understand.

Participant 10: That's it.

Interviewer: Okay, well thank you for the interview today. If you have any further questions, we'll be in touch. Thank you.

Participant 10: Yes, thank you.

Participant 13

Interviewer: Hello and thank you for taking part in this study. Let me start then with a brief introduction to my topic. My research topic is about An exploration of the role of online education in developing oral English skills to facilitate the transnational education experiences of Chinese students progressing to university study in the UK. Our interview today is voluntary and anonymous, so you can ask questions at any time. If you feel nervous or pressured during the interview, we can end it at any time. You can also withdraw from the study at any time if you wish to do so afterwards. So if you are ready, we will start today's interview.

Participant 13: Ok.

Interviewer: Okay, so first of all, please tell us about your academic subject and the school you're coming from, and when you started.

Participant 13: I am currently in my second year of PhD at UWS, I having entered in 2019, with a year interrupted in my studies. My subject is Accounting, and I am in School of Business. This is my current status.

Interviewer: Okay. And where did you study before?

Participant 13: My master study also at UWS for one academic year from 2018 to 2019.

Interviewer: OK, I understand. So for you, that means you've experienced UWS offline classes as well as online classes. So can you share your experience of learning from the online classes at UWS?

Participant 13: Actually, I haven't taken any online classes, because master classes in 2018-2019 are generally offline. It's only since the Covid-19 in early 2020 that UWS has been taking online classes. I was already a PhD student at the time, so I basically just met with my supervisor for meetings and would study online. So basically, I was using the Zoom to meet with my supervisor.

Interviewer: How long do you and your supervisor meet on Zoom? What kind of content do you discuss?

Participant 13: Each meeting usually lasts about half an hour. The main questions we discuss are how my research is going and what I can do afterwards, what I can add to it and what I can improve on if I'm not doing well. Basically, 90% of the discussion is about what I'm working on now.

Interviewer: I see. And do you have any other online learning experiences?

Participant 13: For example, I attend conferences and other online learning sessions, seminars that are related to my subject. When exploring content pertinent to my research topic, I frequently utilize online resources. At the beginning of 2022, I took part in two of online seminars with Zoom, which lasted about 2-3 hours. Participating in these lectures has significantly enhanced my research. One more convenient thing is that online courses can be recorded at any time and any place, so students can review them anytime, which is a great advantage.

Interviewer: What department organised those seminars you attended?

Participant 13: I forget the department, I was looking for something related to my research topic online. Some lectures, I think it was by Chinese scholars, some organized by the University of Glasgow.

Interviewer: I see, and was this information provided to you by UWS?

Participant 13: My supervisor gave it to me and recommended it to me at the meeting.

Interviewer: I see.

Interviewer: Do you meet with your supervisor online?

Participant 13: Yes.

Interviewer: I see, so it's some additional seminars given to you by your supervisor. And where do you usually do your online classes? Is it somewhere else or at home?

Participant 13: If I can catch up I am at home.

Interviewer: And are you at home in China or in the UK?

Participant 13: Currently in the UK.

Interviewer: And what did you just say about not being able to catch up?

Participant 13: Sometimes I can't back home in time, so I just attend the online seminars wherever, like outside, but basically this rarely happens, 99% of the time I'm at home.

Interviewer: I understand. So do you think that if you were outside, this physical location would affect your actual online learning efficiency?

Participant 13: Definitely. If I am outside in a library or a coffee shop, which are more suitable places to study, I definitely can be more efficient, but taking classes in a noisy environment will definitely affect learning outcomes. Moreover, in a noisy setting, students may be reluctant to turn on their microphones for oral expression.

Interviewer: I understand. Do you ever get disturbed by members of the family or other things when you're at home for online classes?

Participant 13: Personally, I haven't been disturbed so far, because I live in a quiet area and have my own room, so I don't seem to have been disturbed so far.

Interviewer: OK, I understand. And what do you think is the difference between the online classes and offline classes?

Participant 13: First of all, the first thing that is more obvious is that offline classes the communication between people is more intuitive, and then people will raise any problems in time to solve them. Sometimes online gives me the intuitive feeling that it is not as interactive as offline. The second point is that online classes are more flexible and free. So for those who have a long commute, online classes are more convenient.

Interviewer: I see, so which one do you prefer?

Participant 13: For me at the moment, in this Covid-19 environment, I am leaning towards the online classes.

Interviewer: I understand. So do you feel that the online classes have had an impact on your learning outcomes or your learning status?

Participant 13: I think the main thing is that I'm doing a PhD now, unlike my previous master studies where there weren't too many classes, which amounted to almost nothing. For me, the difference between the two is not that big, but Online courses are very convenient and give me more free time, I can review and revise anytime, and that's a big advantage.

Interviewer: I see. Can you tell us what you think are the benefits of taking classes online? Apart from the freedom that you mentioned just now.

Participant 13: And then the second point is that it don't need to commute, directly where the internet is better and I can always go online for classes.

Interviewer: Okay.

Participant 13: Yes.

Interviewer: Do you think that the online classes that UWS offers now will help you in your overall studies and even in your transnational studies?

Participant 13: It definitely helps. If you want to study across countries, online learning is the most effective way. Especially during the COVID-19 pandemic, it's almost impossible to attend classes in person due to the geographical distance between China and the UK. It can also involve some cultural influences.

Interviewer: Do you think you can get a better feel for the local culture in the UK and so on in the online classes?

Participant 13: On the classes, if the class is online it definitely suffers in terms of culture. It is not face-to-face, because you and your classmates are separated by a screen, and in some cases only your name is displayed on the screen. The microphone is not on or the camera is not on, so it's not as involved as offline. And then at home, you definitely don't feel the UK culture as much, so I do think this is a big influence.

Interviewer: I see. And did you encounter any challenges when you were doing the online classes? For example, some technical problems or some other problems.

Participant 13: I haven't encountered any for the time being, as most of the classes are almost always held at home in a stable wireless environment. My teacher has never missed a lesson, and I have attended on time, so I have not encountered any unforeseen circumstances.

Interviewer: So like the computer or did there was a crash on the device or something?

Participant 13: No, basically it will be charged up and all ready to go in advance, so being prepared in advance will avoid some problems.

Interviewer: Yes, definitely. So the next question is, do you think that online classes can provide you with the opportunity to practice speaking?

Participant 13: First of all, it is can, because the teacher sometimes asks me questions. Secondly, it's not just online classes that offer it, it's mainly up to the students themselves. If you are active in answering questions, then you will definitely work on your speaking. If you are more

introverted and don't want to answer questions actively, you will have less chance to practice speaking.

Interviewer: I see, so if you're meeting one-on-one with a supervisor, you should have a lot of opportunities to speak.

Participant 13: Yes, basically, because most of the one-to-one interface is a two-person conversation.

Interviewer: So you mentioned that you went to some conferences, did you have the opportunity to practice speaking at these conferences?

Participant 13: Basically, I attend these sessions on a PPT presentation. After the presentation, the speaker provides a final Q&A session. It's a chance to participate and I practice my speaking skills during this time.

Interviewer: I see, and how often do you speak English in class or conference?

Participant 13: In the classroom, because my supervisor is Chinese, we have a mix of Chinese and English. And then I don't have a systematic schedule of classes at the moment. So this question is a little bit not suitable for me.

Interviewer: I understand. So how do you feel about Chinese students taking online classes at UWS at the moment ?

Participant 13: I think it is reasonable. Firstly, online learning is a reasonable choice in response to government requirements for social distancing and avoiding cross-infection policies. Secondly, there are times when Chinese students don't have international flights, sometimes it's a matter of airfare, and some students take classes at home and it's more convenient for them to have online classes.

Interviewer: I understand. How do you feel about the current arrangement of online programmes for international students at the beginning of their studies?

Participant 13: I'm not sure how to answer this, because I don't personally feel how the online classes are set up and how they are delivered to Chinese students. For me, the difference between the two is not that big, but Online courses are very convenient and give me more free time, I can review and revise anytime, and that's a big advantage.

Interviewer: I understand, what do you think of some of the online courses offered by the UWS to support PhD students?

Participant 13: Various online methods such as Zoom and other video methods are more convenient, I am very happy with the current format of online classes.

Interviewer: OK, I understand. So what do you think is the responsibility of the student as opposed to in this offline classes?

Participant 13: First of all, it is the student's responsibility to be on time for class. The second thing is to try to maintain a positive attitude during the online classes, to ask questions, to participate and to review the class. I think it is important for students to be positive about these things.

Interviewer: I understand. So if students encounter some difficulties or challenges during the online classes, they should be a bit more positive, right?

Participant 13: First of all, if you are experiencing difficulties online, you can seek help from the relevant school department. Most school department will be able to solve the problems. But if can't, I'm actively trying to find other ways to solve them, so I know that they can be solved.

Interviewer: So there was a lot of communication between you and the teacher in the online class, as you mentioned. Do you interact with other students?

Participant 13: Rarely, I basically interacted with a few PhD students in the same year. The main reason for this is that there is no class for us, so everyone meets with their supervisors on a one-to-one basis, and there is not the same atmosphere as normal class, so there are not as many opportunities to meet with fellow students.

Interviewer: Before I concentrated I observed some online classes and I noticed that there might be some students who speak Chinese to the teacher and students during the lessons. What do you think of this phenomenon?

Participant 13: Because we are now being educated in a UK university, we still have to speak English in class. Using Chinese means that English speaking practice cannot be relatively strengthened. Because using Chinese in meetings and discussions is not conducive to English speaking practice.

Interviewer: So, like you just mentioned, your meetings with your supervisor were also in both English and Chinese. What do you think of that? How does this mode of communication work for

you?

Participant 13: This mode of communication is definitely more convenient and efficient as Chinese is the mother tongue for me and my supervisor. At the same time, there is also a disadvantage that the speaking practice cannot be relatively strengthened. Because in the meetings and discussions, this is actually not conducive to the practice of spoken English.

Interviewer: Like you say it's not good for speaking practice, is it good for your overall knowledge or for the advancement of your research?

Participant 13: It is definitely beneficial. Because some of the research progress or research directions are definitely still mostly spoken in English. Because some things are really difficult to translate into Chinese, people are still more used to thinking in English.

Interviewer: I understand. So which part is it in Chinese?

Participant 13: We actually speak in a mix of English and Chinese. But most of my professional knowledge or things related to my research are in English. Sometimes we speak in Chinese, so we can more understand.

Interviewer: OK. I understand. If there are some words in English that you don't understand or you can't express, then you will use Chinese to assist?

Participant 13: Mostly not, because the research I'm doing is still mainly about English. Sometimes I don't know how to translate the English into Chinese, but it's easier to understand it when it's said in English.

Interviewer: OK understand. So for you, which of the three models is more suitable for you now that UWS is online, offline, and a combination of online and offline classes?

Participant 13: Right now it's the online classes that are more suitable because I live far away campus, and then online is more convenient.

Interviewer: OK, I understand. So apart from what we've discussed today, is there anything else you'd like to add about your online learning experience during the transition from China to the UK?

Participant 13: No.

Interviewer: Okay, well thank you for the interview, that's it for today.

Participant 13: Yes, thank you.

Appendix 3 Participant Information Sheet - for online observation

School of Education and Social Science

参与者信息表

探讨在线学习在发展英语口语技能方面的作用

如何运用在线学习促进中国学生在英国大学学习的跨国教育经验

你被邀请参加一项研究。在你决定之前，最重要的是你要理解为什么要做这项研究，以及它将涉及哪些内容。如果您愿意，请您花时间仔细阅读以下信息并与其他人讨论。如果您有什么不清楚的内容，或者您需要更多的信息，请与我联系。你是否想要更多的信息。请花点时间来决定您是否愿意参加本次研究。

本项研究的目的是什么？

本研究主要目的为探讨在新冠肺炎后的全球社会中，在线学习对从事跨国教育的中国大学生的英语口语技能的发展和作用。

我的数据收集将分为两个研究阶段，第一个阶段：“内部研究”（课堂观察），第二个阶段：访谈。

您现在参与的是本研究的第一个阶段（课堂观察），我会将您的课堂真实情况记录在观察日志中，但我不会对您的课程进行任何音频或视频录制。该阶段的研究目的为收集数据，并更清楚地了解中国学生在过渡时期（从中国学生向英国留学生身份过渡）的学习经历。此外，通过对大家的课堂观察可以帮助我更好地设计第二阶段的采访问题。

为什么我会被选中？

您被选中参加这项研究是因为您是在UWS的中国留学生，并且您正在参与UWS的在线英语暑期课程。

我一定要参加吗？

本研究是否参加由您个人决定。如果您决定参加，您会收到这张信息表，并被要求签署这份同意书。

我只会观察签署了此表格学生的表现，并在我的观察日志中记录您的学习行为。如果您不同意参加本次研究，您的课堂表现和行为将不会被观察和记录。

如果我参加了会怎么样？

我作为一名内部研究员，我将会通过观察您的真实课堂情况，比如观察您与老师和同学的英语口语互动，在观察期间，您将像往常一样继续上课，我会做一些记录，您不需要做任何其它事情。在我的毕业论文中，关于您的所有课堂互动都是以匿名的形式记录。

参加有哪些可能的好处？

这是本研究的第一阶段。您在观察期间的表现将有助于我们探索如何更好的利用在线学习提高中国大学生英语口语能力，并为我的第二阶段的采访问题设计提供很好的信息帮助。我的研究结果有助于改善您在从中国向英国留学过渡期的学习质量。

参加本项目有哪些可能的坏处和风险？

参与这项研究并没有真正的风险，但是您可能会因为我的观察而感到不舒服（比如害羞或焦虑）。

我会在观察期间保持安静，绝不拍照、截图或记录您的个人信息。

数据保护隐私声明

Data Protection Privacy Notice

The data controller for this project will be University of the West of Scotland (UWS). The UWS Data Protection Office provides oversight of UWS activities involving the processing of personal data and can be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. UWS's Data Protection Officer is Emma Cockrow and can be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk.

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<https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/data-protection-reform/overview-of-the-gdpr/individuals-rights/>

Right to Withdraw

If you decide to take part you are still free to withdraw at any time up to one month after completing the study without giving a reason, your contributions during the class will not be recorded, and your data will not use for this research, I will delete all records of you.

The information that you provide me with will be kept for up to 10 years to allow for potential publication from the thesis at a future date. You are free to contact me and withdraw your data.

What will happen to the results of the research study?

The findings from this study will be included in my Ph.D dissertation and may be published in the form of a report or article.

Who has reviewed the study?

ESS Ethics Committee

Contact for further information

If you require any further information please contact:

Researcher:

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High Street,

Paisley,

PA1 2BE

UK

Research Supervisor:

Dr Steve Brown

University of the West of Scotland,

High Street,

Paisley,

PA1 2BE

UK

Thank you for taking part in this study.

Participant Information Sheet

An exploration of the role of online education in developing oral English skills to facilitate the transnational education experiences of Chinese students progressing to university study in the UK

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Please ask me if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part.

What is the purpose of this study?

The main purpose of this study is to explore the role of **online learning** in developing the **oral English skills** of Chinese university students who are engaging in **transnational education** in a post- Covid-19 global society.

My data collection is divided into two research stages: 'Insider research' (class observation) and interviews. This is the **first stage** of the study (class observation), I will record your observations in a journal but I will not make any audio or visual recordings of the lessons you observe. Therefore the purpose for this first stage is to collect data and to gather a more clear idea of the Chinese student's study experiences during the transition period (to being students both in the China and UK).

Furthermore, these observations can help me better design effective interview questions.

Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen to take part in this study because you are Chinese International students in UWS, and you are taking online English courses at UWS.

Do I have to take part?

It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you do decide to take part you will be given this information sheet to keep and be asked to sign a consent form.

I will only observe the performance of the students who signed this form and record their learning behavior via Observation Journal. The performance and behavior of those who did not sign the form will not be observed and recorded.

What will happen to me if I take part?

As an insider researcher, I plan to do some preliminary "insider research", to observe your class performance, such as your oral interaction with teachers and classmates. During the observation, you will continue your class as normal, I will make some notes for the class, you don't have to do anything. In my dissertation about you classroom interactions will not contain any information that could be used to identify them.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

This is the first stage of the study. Your participation during the observation will help me to explore the role of online learning in developing the oral English skills of Chinese university student and to design effective interview questions for my second interview stage. My findings can help improve the quality of provision for international students transitioning towards studying in the UK.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

There are no real risks to participating in this study, but you may feel uncomfortable (like shy or anxious) because of my observation. I will keep quiet while observing and never take photos, screenshots or record your personal information.

西苏格兰大学(UWS)为本项目的数据控制者。UWS数据保护办公室对涉及个人数据处理的UWS活动进行监督，UWS的数据保护官员是Emma Cockrow，您可以通过与dataprotection@uws.ac.uk联系，了解相关内容。

如果您对如何处理您的个人数据感到担忧，请首先通过dataprotection@uws.ac.uk联系UWS的工作人员。如果您仍然不满意，您可以联系信息专员办公室(ICO)。联系详情和数据主体权利详情可在ICO网站上查阅：<https://ico.org.uk/for-organizations/data-protection-reform/overview-the-gdpr/personal-rights/>

退出研究的权力

如果您决定参加，您仍然可以在完成本研究一个月后的任何时候退出，而无需给出理由，您在课堂上的表现将不会被记录，您的数据也不会用于本次研究，您的所有数据都会被删除。

您提供给我的研究数据将会被保存10年，以便将来发表论文所用。如有任何疑虑，您可以随时与我联系。

这项研究的结果会怎么样？

这项研究的结果将被纳入我的博士论文，并可能以报告或文章的形式发表。

谁审查了这项研究？

UWS 教育与社会科学学院道德委员会

如果您需要更多信息，请联系：

研究员：

刘婧

苏格兰西部大学，

高街，

佩斯利，

PA1 2BE

英国

研究主管：

史蒂夫·布朗博士

苏格兰西部大学，

高街，

佩斯利，

PA1 2BE

英国

感谢您参与本次研究。

Appendix 4 Participant Information Sheet - for interview

School of Education and Social Science

Participant Information Sheet-Interview

An exploration of the role of online education in developing oral English skills to facilitate the transnational education experiences of Chinese students progressing to university study in the UK

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Please ask me if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part.

What is the purpose of this study?

The purpose of this study is to explore the role of **online learning** in developing the **oral English skills** of Chinese university students who are engaging in **transnational education** in a post- Covid-19 global society.

Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen to take part in this study because you are a Chinese International student in UWS, and you are taking the courses at UWS.

Do I have to take part?

No, participation is entirely voluntary. If you decide to take part, you will be given this information sheet to keep and sign a consent form. You have the right to withdraw without giving a reason and without prejudice. You don't have to answer questions you don't want to without giving reasons; You can withdraw from the study at any time, and interviews will be terminated if you indicate that you would prefer this.

What will happen to me if I take part?

You will be invited to participate in an online semi-structured interview with me. During this interview, I will discuss with you the differences and similarities between online learning and campus-based learning, how online courses affect you (both positively and negatively), and your oral practice during the courses (online and campus-based). The interview should take less than one hour.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

Your opinions will help us explore the role of online learning in developing the oral English skills of Chinese university students. You have the opportunity to reflect on your online study experience, and your oral English learning behaviour. You can better understand your motivations for studying abroad. Our conversation may help you to better participate in online learning and help you better integrate into UK education and life in the UK.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

I do not expect there are any disadvantages or risks to you. I will minimize any possibility before the research process. I will never take photos, screenshots or record your personal information. However, Audio or text recordings are taken during the interview. These recordings will be stored securely, and that any information that could be used to identify participants will not be included in the study.

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如果您对如何处理您的个人数据感到担忧,请首先通过dataprotection@uws.ac.uk联系UWS的工作人员。如果您仍然不满意,您可以联系信息专员办公室(ICO)。联系详情和数据主体权利详情可在ICO网站上查阅: <https://ico.org.uk/for-organizations/data-protection-reform/overview-the-gdpr/personal-rights/>

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UWS 教育与社会科学学院道德委员会

如果您需要更多信息,请联系:

研究员:

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苏格兰西部大学,

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佩斯利,

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英国

研究主管:

史蒂夫·布朗博士

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探讨在线学习在发展英语口语技能方面的作用，

如何运用在线学习促进中国学生在英国大学学习的跨国教育经验

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我一定要参加吗？

本研究是否参与完全是自愿的。如果您决定参加，您将获得此信息表，并被要求签署这份同意书。您有权在不提供理由和不带偏见的情况下退出。您可以无理由拒绝回答您不想回答的问题；您可以随时退出研究，如果您表示意愿，采访将被终止。

如果我参加了会怎么样？

您将被邀请参与与我的在线半结构化访谈。在这次采访中，我将与您讨论在线学习和线下学习之间的差异和相似之处，在线学习对您的影响（好处和挑战），以及您在在线课程中的口语练习情况。面试时间会少于一小时。

参加有哪些可能的益处？

您的观点将有助于我们探索如何更好的利用在线学习提高中国大学生英语口语能力。您有机会思考您的在线学习经历和您的英语口语学习行为。您可以更了解您出国留学的动机。我们的对话可能帮助您更好地参与在线学习，帮助您更好地融入英国教育和英国生活。

参加本项目有哪些可能的坏处和风险？

我不认为对您有任何不利或风险。在研究过程之前，我会尽量减少任何风险的可能性。我绝不会拍照、截图或记录您的个人信息。但是，在采访过程中我会进行音频和文字转录。这些录音将被安全存储，任何可能用于识别参与者的信息都不会被包括在研究中。

数据保护隐私声明

西苏格兰大学(UWS)为本项目的数据控制者。UWS数据保护办公室对涉及个人数据处理的UWS活动进行监督，UWS的数据保护官员是Emma Cockrow，您可通过与dataprotection@uws.ac.uk联系，了解相关内容。

这项研究的结果将被纳入我的博士论文，并可能以报告或文章的形式发表。但是，您的名字会被匿名处理，永远不会被提及。所设计的研究信息将被保存10年，以便将来发表论文所用。如有任何疑虑，您可以自由地与我联系。

contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. UWS's Data Protection Officer is Emma Cockrow and can be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk.

The findings from this study will be included in my Ph.D dissertation and may be published in the form of a report or article. However, your name will never be mentioned and all participants will remain anonymous. The information that you provide me with will be kept for up to 10 years to allow for potential publication from the thesis at a future date. You are free to contact the researcher and withdraw your data up to the point of anonymization.

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Research Supervisor:

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PA1 2BE

UK

Thank you for taking part in this study.

Appendix 5 Consent Form - for online observation

School of Education and Social Science

RESEARCH INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Title of Project: An exploration of the role of online education in developing oral English skills to facilitate the transnational education experiences of Chinese students progressing to university study in the UK

Ethics Approval Number: 2021-14016

Investigators names: Jing Liu

Researcher Email: Jing.Liu@uws.ac.uk

You have been invited to take part in a study to explore the role of online learning in developing the oral English skills of Chinese university students who are engaging in transnational education in a post-Covid-19 global society. By completing this form and agreeing to give your full consent, you agree that you have read and understood the participant information sheet and understand what is being asked of you in this study.

Please read the following statements and, if you agree, initial the corresponding box to confirm your agreement:

	Initial below:
I confirm that I have read and understand the participant information sheet and Research Informed Consent Form for the study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.	
I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time up to one month after completing the study without giving any reason.	
I understand that the information I give is confidential and any publication resulting from this work will not identify me personally.	
I consent to the researcher observing and recording some of my contributions and reactions during the observed lessons.	
I freely agree to participate in this study.	

Signatures:

Name of participant (block capitals):

Name of researcher (block capitals):

Date:

Date: 27/09/2021

Signature:

Signature:

If you would like a copy of this consent form to keep, please ask the researcher. If you have any complaints or concerns about this research, you can direct these, in writing, to the Chair of the ESS Ethics Committee by email at: ess.ethics@uws.ac.uk. Alternatively, you can contact us by post at: Ethics Committee Chair, School of Education and Social Science, University of West of Scotland, Paisley, PA1 2BE

研究知情同意书

项目名称：探讨在线学习在发展英语口语技能方面的作用，如何运用在线学习促进中国学生在英国大学学习的跨国教育经验

伦理批准号:2021-14016

研究员：刘婧

研究员电子邮件:Jing.Liu@uws.ac.uk

您被邀请参加一项研究关于：“探讨在新冠肺炎后的全球社会中，在线学习对从事跨国教育的中国大学生的英语口语技能的发展和作用”。通过填写此表格来表明您已完全同意：您同意您已经阅读并理解了参与者信息表，并理解本研究对您的要求。

请阅读以下声明，如果您同意，请在相应的方框上签名，以确认您的同意：

	具体如下：
我确认已阅读并理解本研究的参与者信息表和研究知情同意书。我有机会考虑这些信息，提出问题，并得到满意的回答。	
我理解我的参与是自愿的，并且我可以在完成研究后一个月内随时退出，无需给出任何理由。	
我理解我提供的信息是保密的，任何由此研究产生的出版物都不会表明我的个人身份。	
我同意研究人员在观察课程期间观察并记录我的一些行为和反应。	
我完全同意参加本次研究。	

签名：

参与者姓名(拼音大写)：

研究人员姓名(拼音大写)：

日期：

日期：2021年9月27日

签名：

签名：

If you would like a copy of this consent form to keep, please ask the researcher. If you have any complaints or concerns about this research, you can direct these, in writing, to the Chair of the ESS Ethics Committee by email at: ess.ethics@uws.ac.uk. Alternatively, you can contact us by post at: Ethics Committee Chair, School of Education and Social Science, University of West of Scotland, Paisley, PA1 2BE

Appendix 6 Consent Form - for online interview

School of Education and Social Science

RESEARCH INFORMED CONSENT FORM-interview

Title of Project: An exploration of the role of online education in developing oral English skills to facilitate the transnational education experiences of Chinese students progressing to university study in the UK

Ethics Approval Number: 2022-17623

Investigators names: Jing Liu

Researcher Email: Jing.Liu@uws.ac.uk

You have been invited to take part in a study to explore the role of **online learning** in developing the **oral English skills** of Chinese university students who are engaging in **transnational education** in a post-Covid-19 global society. By completing this form and agreeing to give your full consent, you agree that you have read and understood the participant information sheet and understand what is being asked of you in this study.

Please read the following statements and, if you agree, initial the corresponding box to confirm your agreement:

	Initial below:
I confirm that I have read and understand the participant information sheet and Research Informed Consent Form for the study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.	
I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time up to one month after completing the study without giving any reason.	
I understand that the information I give is confidential and any publication resulting from this work will not identify me personally.	
I consent to focus groups and interviews being audio recorded.	
All names and other material likely to identify individuals will be anonymised.	
The material will be treated as confidential and kept in secure storage at all times.	
The material may be used in future publications, both print and online.	
I freely agree to participate in this study.	

Signatures:

Name of participant (block capitals):

Name of researcher (block capitals):

Date:

Date: 28/01/2022

Signature:

Signature:

If you would like a copy of this consent form to keep, please ask the researcher. If you have any complaints or concerns about this research, you can direct these, in writing, to the Chair of the ESS Ethics Committee by email at: ess.ethics@uws.ac.uk. Alternatively, you can contact us by post at: Ethics Committee Chair, School of Education and Social Science, University of West of Scotland, Paisley, PA1 2BE

研究知情同意书-采访

项目名称: 探讨在线学习在发展英语口语技能方面的作用, 如何运用在线学习促进中国学生在英国大学学习的跨国教育经验

伦理批准号: 2022-17623

研究员: 刘婧

研究员电子邮件: Jing.Liu@uws.ac.uk

您被邀请参加一项研究关于: “探讨在新冠肺炎后的全球社会中, 在线学习对从事跨国教育的中国大学生的英语口语技能的发展和作用”。通过填写此表格来表明您已完全同意: 您同意您已经阅读并理解了参与者信息表, 并理解本研究对您的要求。

请阅读以下声明, 如果您同意, 请在相应的方框上签名, 以确认您的同意:

	请打勾
我确认已阅读并理解本研究的参与者信息表和研究知情同意书。我有机会考虑这些信息, 提出问题, 并得到满意的回答。	
我理解我的参与是自愿的, 并且我可以在完成研究后一个月内随时退出, 无需给出任何理由。	
我理解我提供的信息是保密的, 任何由此研究产生的出版物都不会表明我的个人身份。	
我同意对采访进行录音。	
所有可能识别个人身份的姓名和其他材料都将被匿名化。 材料将被视为机密并始终安全存储。	
该材料可用于未来的印刷和在线出版物。	
我完全同意参加本次研究。	

签名:

参与者姓名(拼音大写):

研究人员姓名(拼音大写):

日期:

日期: 2022年1月28日

签名:

签名

If you would like a copy of this consent form to keep, please ask the researcher. If you have any complaints or concerns about this research, you can direct these, in writing, to the Chair of the ESS Ethics Committee by email at: ess.ethics@uws.ac.uk. Alternatively, you can contact us by post at: Ethics Committee Chair, School of Education and Social Science, University of West of Scotland, Paisley, PA1 2BE

Appendix 7 Interview Schedule

English Version

Open questions:

1. Please tell me something about yourself and your academic/professional background.
2. Please tell me about your online learning experiences with UWS.
3. Where do you usually take online classes, at home, in the office or somewhere else?
 - What do you think about physical location during online study?
 - Are there any ways in which your physical location affects your ability to study online?
4. What do you think are the differences between online and campus-based classes? Why?
 - Do you prefer online classes or campus-based classes?
 - Which learning mode do you think you will be more effective in?
5. What do you think are the benefits of taking online classes? Please be specific.
 - In what ways are online courses helpful for your transnational period of study in the UWS?
6. What challenges have you faced in taking online courses in China/UK?
 - How did you overcome them?
 - Have you ever encountered technical problems in online courses? If yes, please give examples.
 - How do you think this kind of problem affects you?
7. In what ways can online courses provide you with a good opportunity to practice speaking? Why?
 - How often do you have to use spoken English in class?
8. How do you feel about the current arrangement of online programmes for international students at the beginning of their studies?
9. Compared with campus-based classes, what responsibilities do you think students should take in online courses?
10. Please share your communication experience with teachers and classmates during the online course.
 - In my previous research I observed some online lessons, and I noticed that some students did speak Chinese to the teachers and students during the lessons. What do you think about this phenomenon?
11. What kind of class mode do you think is more suitable for you, online, offline, or a combination of online and offline? Why?
12. Do you think online courses can satisfy your transitioning to studying in the UK experience?
13. Is there any aspect of your online study experience during the transitional period from China to the UK that you would like to comment on that we have not covered today?

Chinese Version

开放式问题：

- 1.请介绍一下您自己和您的学术/专业背景。
- 2.请分享您在 UWS 的网络学习经历。
- 3.你通常在哪里上网课，在家里、办公室还是其他地方？
 - 您如何看待在线学习期间的物理位置？
 - 您的实际位置是否会影响您在线学习的能力？
- 4.您认为在线课程和校园课程有什么区别？为什么？
 - 你更喜欢在线课程还是校园课程？
 - 您认为哪种学习模式会更有效？
- 5.你觉得参加网课有什么好处？请举例说明。
 - 在线课程在哪些方面对您 UWS 的跨国学习有帮助？
- 6.您在中国/英国学习在线课程时遇到了哪些挑战？
 - 你是如何克服它们的？
 - 您在在线课程中遇到过技术问题吗？如果是，请举例说明。
 - 您认为此类问题对您有何影响？
- 7.在线课程在哪些方面可以为您提供练习口语的好机会？为什么？
 - 您在课堂上多久说一次英语？
- 8.您如何看待目前国际学生在学习初期的在线课程安排？
- 9.与线下相比，您认为学生在网络课程中应该承担哪些责任？
- 10.在参与网课的过程中，请分享您与老师和同学的交流情况。
 - 在我之前的研究中，我观察了一些在线课程，我注意到一些学生在上课时会对老师和学生说中文，您如何看待这种现象？
- 11.你觉得哪种上课模式更适合你，线上、线下，还是线上线下结合？为什么？
- 12.您认为在线课程能满足您过渡到英国留学的经历吗？
- 13.您在从中国到英国的过渡期间的在线学习经历中，您有什么我们今天没有提到的方面想要补充的吗？

Appendix 8 Thematic Analysis Coding Categories

Appendix 8 TA Coding Categories

Thematic analysis

Student's Data:

Participants	Selected Quotes	Themes	Subthemes
P1	Most of my courses are online, but I can also go to the school. Because at the same time the teacher will turn on the online live stream, so students can choose whether they want to go online or come to the school and take the class offline.	Flexibility and Efficiency Coexist	Online vs. offline learning
P1	When participating in online courses, students need to learn more independently as online courses may require students to listen and learn actively.	Autonomy in online learning	The Challenge of Teacher-Student Interaction
P1	In real-time online classes, when I encounter something I don't understand, I can immediately search for the answer in the browser.	Autonomy in online learning	Resource utilisation
P1	I don't actively participate in discussions, but if the teacher directly asks me a question, then I will respond.	Cultural background and communication preferences	Development of communication skills
P1	We often just type and discuss in the application without anyone speaking,	Silent Communication: The Dual Nature of Chatbox Functionality	Diversity of modes of participation
P1	I believe that the education systems in China and the UK are different. In the UK classroom, teachers may pay more attention to each student's own ideas and encourage them to express their own opinions. In China, there are more people in the classroom, and the teacher may not be able to ask every student, so students have relatively fewer opportunities for oral expression.	Cultural Differences, Education Systems, and Cross-Border Learning Experiences	Differences in cultural background
P2	If the tutor is not on campus, we choose online communication; if they are at the school, we communicate face-to-face.	Flexibility and Efficiency Coexist	Online vs. offline communication
P2	My room is not tidy, and my desk is messy, with only space for a computer and a screen. This environment has some impact on my learning efficiency.	Issues with Attention Distraction	Self-management skills
P2	The physical location of students is important. If they take online classes in public places, they may be surrounded by noise, which affects the quality of listening.	Issues with Attention Distraction	Choosing the right place to study

P2	I can remember, the vast majority of my classmates in the language courses, or all of them except me, weren't paying attention to the lectures, they were all just hanging out with their accounts and turning off their cameras, probably playing games or doing something else or whatever.	Self-Discipline and Attendance Issues in Online Learning	Unsupervised Learning Environment
P2	course places more emphasis on practicing English oral skills	Factors Influencing Oral Expression Motivation	Differences in academic disciplines
P2	I think from my experience in the language class, I think it was a bit lacking because the course was not particularly difficult. Yes, the language course was not as difficult as the IELTS preparation courses in China. The language course was more focused on an inspiring way of learning, including some vocabulary and knowledge points that the teacher taught, which were all relatively simple and basic. Yes, then after the five-week language class, the teacher asked us to write a 1,000-word essay straight away. I felt that the difficulty level was a bit wide, because the homework, exercises and vocabulary that we were usually given by the teachers in the language courses were very simple and probably at the same level as our English in junior high school. But for Chinese students, maybe those courses are set up to help us change from Chinese to English education, trying to slowly transform students from bottom English thinking to pure English thinking. But perhaps for students of our age, some of the habits of mind may have been fixed long ago. Then what we need more is specific training and improvement for academic English. Yes, I'm thinking from the point of view of a Chinese student anyway, and I don't think the language counter arrangement is perfect.	Educational and Cultural Influences on Oral Expression	Course Difficulty and Content Focus
P2	But if a student is not in a good mood and doesn't want to talk, then the online class is more friendly.	Emotional impact on oral expression frequency	Flexible Participation Standards
P2	I regularly take the initiative to answer questions and add energy to the classroom, even during group discussions.	Cultural background and communication preferences	Role as a Motivating Peer
P2	In offline environments, you may experience higher levels of engagement and immersion. Interacting well and learning effectively become easier.	Participant and pseudo-participation	Facilitated Effective Learning
P2	Based on my experience, students shouldn't keep their cameras off for the entire class or half of the class without interacting with the teacher. It's like the teacher is performing a monologue.	Participant and pseudo-participation	Reduced Classroom Dynamics

P2	The Chatbox feature greatly facilitates communication among shy students. In online courses, shy Chinese or other Asian students can share their viewpoints through the Chatbox, eliminating the need for oral expression and significantly reducing their pressure.	Silent Communication: The Dual Nature of Chatbox Functionality	Reduced Pressure for Oral Participation
P2	some teachers allow students to communicate in Chinese, which they find friendly.	Attitudes of Teachers towards the Use of L1	Perceived Friendliness of Language Flexibility
P2	English is the language of the classroom, and teachers want to create more opportunities for students to practice English.	Attitudes of Teachers towards the Use of L1	Supporting Language Development
P2	Some students prepare speeches before oral exams, read them off outside the view of the camera, and thus score high marks in the exam.	Issues Regarding the Security of Assessments in Online Presentations	Further Challenges of Online Learning
P3	And also the travel is limited. I can just staying home and switching on the computer and log into the Zooms or Teams for the courses, this is only need 3 to 5 minutes.	Advantages of Online Learning Across Geography and Time	Flexible Learning Environment
P3	I like blended courses because they are flexible. I enjoy taking online classes at home with a relaxed mood, but I also like occasionally going to school to meet teachers and classmates.	Enhanced Interaction and Collaboration	Adaptability of Learning Environment
P3	I find that studying in the library or open learning spaces is more effective than at home. Such environments help me stay more focused.	Issues with Attention Distraction	Effectiveness of Study Spaces
P3	When studying at home, I easily get distracted, always thinking about playing games or what to eat after class.	Issues with Attention Distraction	Difficulty in Maintaining Academic Mindset
P3	In an open study room, I think less about things unrelated to studying and can concentrate better.	Issues with Attention Distraction	Enhanced Focus on Academic Tasks
P3	to get Internet conditions, the devices fault, and also the computer shut down because of the high temperature.	Technical Challenges in Online Learning	Internet Connectivity Issues
P3	I would review the videos recorded during online classes as study materials to better prepare for exams.	Autonomy in Online Learning	Video Recording Feature
P3	Due to the lecturer's Scottish or Indian accent, as well as the lack of intuitive feedback like eye contact, I often find it difficult to understand online content.	Impact of Online Format on Communication Clarity	Subtitling Functionality
P3	Subtitles are very helpful in understanding what the teacher specifically said in lectures or tutorials.	Assistance in Academic Engagement	Reduction of Miscommunication
P3	Online classrooms can enhance self-control because I are forced to learn independently without the supervision and Participant of teachers and classmates.	Autonomy in online learning	the use of Internet resources
P3	I have online communication with the teaching and tutoring staff every week, and the teacher provides me with opportunities for oral communication. Even online, we still understand each other and express our opinions.	Motivation for Oral Expression	Opportunities for Oral Communication

P3	I have a lot of opinions on this, and other group members agree with my ideas. So I think it was a successful conversation, and I also learned a lot from other international students.	Motivation for Oral Expression	Insights Gained from International Peers
P3	Offline courses are more interactive and more interesting. Teachers can ask questions, and you can talk directly to the teachers without a screen. It is less stressful.	Differences in stress levels between online and offline learning environments	Lowered Anxiety in Interaction
P3	If they occasionally speak Chinese, I think it is acceptable. When Chinese people communicate with each other, speaking Chinese is a simpler way without barriers. The communication is effective.	Attitudes toward Using L1	Use of L1
P3	Every university prohibits cheating in offline courses	Issues Regarding the Security of Assessments in Online Presentations	Further Challenges of Online Learning
P3	When studying in China, the Wi-Fi is usually stable, but occasionally I need to use a VPN. In reality, I don't have a legal VPN solution, so it really bothers me.	Legal and Practical Limitations of VPN Use	Frustration with Restricted Internet Access
P4	online courses, some traditional learning materials such as backpacks, notebooks and pens become less important.	Advantages of Online Learning Across Geography and Time	Adaptation to a Digital Learning Environment
P4	If the teacher requires us to attend classes on campus, I don't have the right to choose online courses. We must follow the teacher's instructions. I once asked if I could choose online courses due to the long distance, but was told that as a full-time student, I do not have that choice.	Choice constraints and time management challenges	Lack of Autonomy in Mode of Learning
P4	I feel more confident when studying at home. I don't like meeting a lot of people. But if I go to campus, I feel very nervous and stressed.	Challenges of Emotions and Mental Health	Reluctance Toward In-Person Interaction
P4	Sometimes my course conflicts with work hours, making it hard for me to concentrate. It's challenging for me to listen to lectures while working.	Issues with Attention Distraction	Difficulty in Maintaining Focus
P4	Everyone is hidden behind their computers and phones. I feel like I have become lazy, and that's the main reason why I lose interest in anything...	Self-Discipline and Attendance Issues in Online Learning	Difficulty in Maintaining Focus
P4	It's about one lecture. Back to last time, she suppose to give us a lecture for 2 hours. Every time she's got the technical problems and everybody was trying to help her to fix it. But then somehow she just missed the class, left the class or finished the class. Every single time she tried to teach on there, there should have some technical problems appear. And she don't come back, after she fix it or I don't think she can fix it. Whatever, she just finished class and leave everyone there to wait for her.	Network and Device Stability	Frequent Technical Difficulties

P4	If the teacher didn't have time for online classes, they would pre-record the lecture content and upload it to the school website for students to download and watch on their own.	Autonomy in Online Learning	Video Recording Feature
P4	I will try to speak English in online classes and continue to improve my oral proficiency.	Motivation for Oral Expression	Effort to Practice English Speaking
P4	I don't like speaking Chinese when I am in the English environment. Even though you are in the English environment and you're surrounded by your Chinese classmates. And then I will try and still trying my best to speak English, just for myself benefit to improve myself and to improve others so.	Factors Influencing Oral Expression Motivation	Differences in academic disciplines
P4	Mostly we just silence and we don't talk. Everyone dislikes to talk in my courses. We wait for people to talk, but then nobody talks, so we just silence, don't talk for the whole time.	Emotional impact on oral expression frequency	Reluctance to Initiate Conversation
P4	I don't speak in class. In fact, I barely utter a word during online courses. It's just that I'm too shy to speak up.	Shyness as a communication barrier and the importance of individual differences	Impact of Shyness on Communication
P4	I think physical classrooms are more suitable for international students. You can have them interact more with local students to overcome their fear of speaking, both before and after class.	Participant and pseudo-participation	Support for Overcoming Language Anxiety
P4	I think it is a bit impolite to speak Chinese in public.	Attitudes toward Using L1	Use of L1
P5	When I first started taking courses online in March 2020, I was still quite confused because it was my first time to take courses online. I first experienced not being able to access the online classroom through the link. Then I emailed my teacher and asked my classmates to find out how to access the online classroom. After that, I slowly became familiar with it.	Insufficiencies in Online Courses during the Early Stage of Covid-19	Difficulty Accessing Online Classrooms
P5	The challenge may be that some of our courses will have experiments. The teacher can only do that by doing the experiment herself/himself and other teachers help to record it and then put the video to the online platform. The process is not as familiar as if we were doing it ourselves, so that's a (challenge).	Challenges in Conducting Experiments in Online Courses	Limitations of Watching Demonstrations vs. Hands-On Practice
P5	Students should follow the same rules in online classes as they do in offline classes, as this helps maintain discipline in online classrooms.	Self-Discipline and Attendance Issues in Online Learning	Promotion of Discipline and Order
P5	It is possible that because I didn't read the content of the email sent by the school too carefully at the time, so it led to these problems.	Impact of Insufficient Attention to Communication	Lack of Careful Reading of School Emails

P5	I usually don't use it, but if there's a topic I don't understand well, I would still use it.	Autonomy in Online Learning	Video Recording Feature
P6	If the tutor is not on campus, we choose online communication; if they are at the school, we communicate face-to-face.	Flexibility and Efficiency Coexist	Choice of Communication Mode
P6	There is not much difference between the online and offline class content in terms of the school's curriculum for the initial period of study abroad. However, I think it is possible that students will have a better experience in the offline classes, and they will be able to communicate with the teacher face to face and be more involved in the class. However, online students can only listen to the teacher's lessons in the accommodation by themselves, so they may can't communicate with the teacher about the course content or discuss problems with their classmates, which makes the experience of studying in the UK not particularly good.	Lack of Interaction and Cultural Engagement	Restricted Interaction with Teachers and Peers
P6	When studying abroad in the UK, participating in local courses and activities helped me quickly integrate into the local society, and my oral proficiency also improved significantly. However, it seems that the current online courses cannot provide such opportunities.	Lack of Interaction and Cultural Integration	Restricted Impact on Language Skills Development
P6	Offline courses are more suitable for me because I can concentrate better in a physical classroom.	Issues with Attention Distraction	Enhanced Focus in Physical Classrooms
P6	When taking online classes at home, I tend to relax more and sometimes get distracted by using my phone.	Issues with Attention Distraction	Challenges in Maintaining Focus at Home
P6	Some students only open their computers and enter the online classroom during class time, but they are actually still sleeping because the class starts too early.	Self-Discipline and Attendance Issues in Online Learning	Minimal Engagement in Class
P6	The main problems I have encountered myself are with the network or equipment, and with communication with my supervisors. Not only me, but also my supervisors, have encountered problems with equipment or the network during online meetings. Such as some audio and visual problems, or my supervisor can get disconnected during a meeting with me because the network is unstable, which can be a problem.	Impact on Communication with Supervisors	Disruptions in Supervisor-Student Interaction
P6	If students encounter any problems during online classes, they should promptly inform the teacher, as this will improve the quality of online classes.	Importance of Prompt Communication in Online Classes	Encouragement of Immediate Problem Reporting
P6	There are various learning resources available on the internet, such as a large number of electronic literature, instructional videos, and more. Sometimes, I also utilize the internet to search for information related to my	Autonomy in online learning	Participation in Online Seminars

	research topics and participate in online seminars that interest me.		
P6	There are various learning resources available on the internet, such as a large number of electronic literature, instructional videos, and more. Sometimes, I also utilize the internet to search for information related to my research topics and participate in online seminars that interest me.	Autonomy in online learning	Utilization of Internet for Self-Directed Learning
P6	In offline classrooms, students have more opportunities to interact face-to-face with teachers and classmates. If they encounter unclear concepts, they can directly approach people around them for clarification.	Participant and pseudo-participation	Face-to-Face Engagement with Teachers and Peers
P6	UK classrooms generally revolve around students, while many Chinese classrooms revolve around teachers, where teachers lecture and students listen.	Cultural Differences, Education Systems, and Cross-Border Learning Experiences	Emphasis on Student Engagement in UK
P6	For Chinese students, especially in the early stages of studying in the UK, their language logic is not flexible enough to switch between Chinese and English. Therefore, teachers and students should understand them more and not rush them.	Encouragement of Gradual Language Adjustment	Conscious Use of L1
P6	When I communicate with my first supervisor, we choose to discuss in Chinese so that he can better understand the problems I encounter in my research. This means that there will be no communication barriers between me and my supervisor.	Improved Understanding and Support	Unconscious Use of L1
P7	For me, it is safer to go out less.	Secure Online Learning Environment	Risk Avoidance in Daily Activities
P7	At the beginning, we were not accustomed to online learning. We had not been exposed to online courses before. After the transition, the teachers mainly taught based on PPTs, lacking oral interaction and discussions.	Lack of Interaction and Cultural Engagement	Limited Oral Interaction and Discussion Opportunities
P7	During online learning, we rarely had opportunities for oral practice and face-to-face interaction. Most of the time, the teachers were lecturing, and we were listening.	Lack of Interaction and Cultural Integration	Lack of Face-to-Face Interaction
P7	Online courses tend to decrease students' self-discipline.	Self-Discipline and Attendance Issues in Online Learning	Challenges in Maintaining Motivation
P7	I occasionally miss the time of my online classes, sometimes I miss half an hour of class or 15 minutes late. I also occasionally let my mind wander during class.	Self-Discipline and Attendance Issues in Online Learning	Reduced Engagement with Class Content

P7	At the beginning of online classes, I was very proactive and answered whatever the teacher asked. If I didn't know how to express myself clearly, I would use translation software and then communicate with the teacher. But after a while, I rarely initiated communication. Because some questions can be answered in the pre-reading materials provided by the teacher, I just read them myself.	Motivation for Oral Expression	Active Engagement with Teacher's Questions
P8	Online learning is a very convenient and cost-effective way.	Advantages of Online Learning Across Geography and Time	Flexibility in Learning Environment
P8	I usually watch the course video twice in the first semester, or sometimes even three times. This online record videos has helped me to improve my language and understanding of the course.	Autonomy in Online Learning	Video Recording Feature
P8	Sometimes, the teachers' English accents are not very standard, which makes it hard for us to fully understand what they are saying.	Challenges in Comprehending Non-Standard Accents	Impact on Understanding of Lecture Content
P8	Subtitles can help us Chinese students better understand some teachers' non-standard English accents.	Supportive Role of Subtitles in Language Comprehension	Enhanced Accessibility for Non-Native Speakers
P8	At the beginning, I wasn't accustomed to the British accent and couldn't fully understand what they were saying. In my spare time, I would go to YouTube every day to find some videos to practice English and help improve my listening skills. I believe learning English is a process from difficult to easy.	Autonomy in online learning	Use of Online Resources for Practice
P8	Online, it seems like I'm only having a conversation with the computer screen. The focus of online classes is primarily on training my listening and reading abilities.	Participant and pseudo-participation	Limited Practice of Speaking and Interaction Skills
P8	Initially, it was difficult for me to adapt, especially in a virtual environment where I couldn't establish a genuine face-to-face connection with the teacher, as if we were just online acquaintances.	Participant and pseudo-participation	Difficulty in Adjusting to the Virtual Environment
P9	At that time, we had just transitioned from offline campus courses to online courses, with only a few class hours left. The teachers simply provided us with PPTs. Due to the sudden outbreak of Covid-19, everyone was at a loss, and the teachers did not really consider how to improve online teaching.	Insufficient Online Courses in the Early Stage of Covid-19	Unpreparedness for Online Transition
P9	At that time, we were forced to transition from traditional offline courses to online learning, but it seemed like the teachers were not adequately prepared. Many times, we only received PPTs without substantial interaction and discussions.	Insufficiencies in Online Courses during the Early Stage of Covid-19	Minimal Teacher-Student Interaction

P9	we feel that after going to the UK being bored in the dormitory and taking online classes for most of the year, it looks like we hadn't one abroad. This may also be related to the age of the student, for example, if the student has just arrived abroad, his motivation and mood will be affected if he does not feel very good about studying abroad.	Challenges of Emotions and Mental Health	Emotional Challenges in Adjusting to a New Environment
P9	I think especially when students are in online classes, there is a lack of face-to-face communication between students, and it is difficult for some students take the initiative to communicate with other students.	Issues with Attention Distraction	Challenges in Building Peer Connections
P9	have a negative impact on my learning efficiency.	Self-Discipline and Attendance Issues in Online Learning	Negative Impact on Learning
P9	When students study alone in their dorms, they are easily distracted and lack the motivation to delve into other materials.	Self-Discipline and Attendance Issues in Online Learning	Limited Engagement with Learning Resources
P9	If I have any doubts, I can pause the learning video and search for information on the website to deepen my understanding of that specific topic.	Autonomy in Online Learning	Video Recording Feature
P9	All Chinese students face language barriers when they first come to the UK, even if their IELTS scores are good, their academic English may not be. So, when I first came to the UK, I would search for instructional videos related to my major on YouTube and watch them repeatedly.	Autonomy in online learning	Use of Online Resources for Academic Support
P9	I often participate in online seminars organized by the university, where I listen to other students introducing their research. We are usually busy with our own research, and it's difficult to gather in one physical location. Online academic seminars solve this problem.	Autonomy in online learning	Convenience of Participation
P9	I believe I can better converse in English face-to-face.	Participant and pseudo-participation	Potential Barriers in Virtual Communication
P9	When communicating in English, sometimes I find it difficult to respond quickly, even if I understand the course materials. I unconsciously use my mother tongue because, for me, it is easier to express my thoughts.	Unconscious Use of L1	Struggle with Spontaneous Expression in a Second Language
P10	I once took a course where the online part was from 10 am to 11 am, followed immediately by the offline class from 11 am to 12 pm. This arrangement was not reasonable for me. If I took online classes at home, I had to rush to the school without much buffer time in between.	Choice constraints and time management challenges	Perceived Unreasonableness of Schedule

P10	For offline classes, I might push myself, but for online classes, it doesn't matter. I can just open my phone and log in, and I can take the class in bed, so I don't want to get up.	Self-Discipline and Attendance Issues in Online Learning	Reduced Motivation for Online Classes
P10	It's easier to be late for morning classes. If you don't wake up on time, you'll miss the class.	Self-Discipline and Attendance Issues in Online Learning	Reliance on Personal Discipline for Attendance
P10	allows teachers to have a clear understanding of each student's situation	Self-Discipline and Attendance Issues in Online Learning	Personalized Approach to Student Support
P10	I cannot review videos of offline lectures, and with the passage of time, sometimes information is forgotten.	Autonomy in Online Learning	Video Recording Feature
P10	There are not many opportunities to practise speaking, because in class, it is mainly the teacher who talks. In lab classes, students may have to ask the teacher questions and need to practise speaking. Students need to understand what technical difficulties they have encountered and how to explain this to the teacher, which requires them to practise their English skills.	Factors Influencing Oral Expression Motivation	Differences in academic disciplines
P10	Offline, I can interpret meaning based on the other person's body movements, which heavily relies on eye contact and gestures.	Participant and pseudo-participation	Limitations of Online Communication Lacking Physical Cues
P10	Sometimes we ask each other questions, but we do it through sending text messages via the Chatbox. This method is convenient, but you don't need to speak orally, just send a text message.	Silent Communication: The Dual Nature of Chatbox Functionality	Accessibility of Non-Verbal Communication Methods
P11	As an international student, it is more appropriate for me to stay in China and take online courses in the current situation. Therefore, I prefer online learning.	Advantages of Online Learning Across Geography and Time	Suitability of Online Learning for International Students
P11	At home, a comfortable environment may make me lazy. I prefer studying in the office because it doesn't allow me to lie down and rest.	Issues with Attention Distraction	Office as a Setting for Discipline and Focus
P11	You know that mobile phones are also more convenient nowadays, but the mobile phone is a way that is not so clear (small screen) compared to a computer or a laptop.	Limitations of Mobile Phones for Visual Clarity	Preference for Larger Screens for Detailed Tasks
P11	If I always rely on subtitles to understand course content, I may miss opportunities to exercise my listening and speaking abilities.	Impact of Subtitles on Language Skill Development	Reduced Engagement with Speaking Practice

P11	I think I speak English very much. At least I think I spoke a lot during the three hours of the course, whether it was good or bad. Of course, you know, everyone has a different oral level, everyone has a different way of answering, everyone has a different level of fluency. But in my case, I've said a lot, even though what I've said may be completely different from what the teacher is asking, but the teacher will give me a lot of encouragement. I will continue to increase my frequency of speak and my desire to express my views.	Factors Influencing Oral Expression Motivation	Differences in academic disciplines
P12	Online classrooms are very convenient, and students can participate anytime and anywhere.	Advantages of Online Learning Across Geography and Time	Flexibility of Participation
P12	As I mentioned before, students are more flexible in raising their hands to communicate during online classes, unlike in physical classes where they still need to raise their hands to signal and then wait for the teacher to come over, and then the two of them talk face to face, sometimes he may need to queue up to talk to the teacher.	Enhancing Teaching with Digital Features	Immediate Interaction Opportunities
P12	I think online teaching is more efficient for certain content. Our courses are often divided into two parts: pure theory and experiments. I can preview the theory part on my own, while the experiments require on-campus operations. Although experiments can also be done online, I believe that operating them that way would be more complex and time-consuming.	Flexibility and Efficiency Coexist	Flexibility in Accessing Theoretical Materials
P12	seem less engaged in online assignments, and there are cases of assignments not being submitted.	Self-Discipline and Attendance Issues in Online Learning	Limited Motivation for Online Tasks
P12	such as my home network which sometimes has problems. I can't guarantee that my devices, such as my computer, are always available.	Network and Device Stability	Device Availability Issues
P12	If there is a problem with the network, I think I can install two Wi-Fi at home so that if there is a problem with one network, then I can switch to the other network and continue with my classes. The chances of one network not working are 90%, whereas the chances of both networks not working are only 1%. Of course, I also solve problems with equipment in this way. For example, I have two computers on my desk during online classes.	Network and Device Stability	Use of Multiple Devices
P12	When the teacher has some problems, for example, the microphone is not on, or the screen sharing is not on, or when he/she is presenting the PPT to us, the PPT does not move, we should communicate with the teacher in	Communication in Addressing Technical Issues	Importance of Communication with the Teacher

	these cases and remind him/her of these.		
P12	Some students turn off their camera and microphone during online classes and do other things like playing games, working, or shopping, and then rely on the recorded video or audio to catch up. Although the classroom content is recorded, the synchronous interaction between teachers and students, and among students, as well as group discussions, cannot be made up. Missing out on these opportunities will result in less practice in speaking.	Autonomy in Online Learning	Video Recording Feature
P12	Online reading materials require more time, while offline classrooms allow for direct browsing and note-taking.	Variations in Learning Strategies	Challenges of Online Learning Formats
P12	My supervisor is Italian and sometimes unconsciously uses Italian words. This is because his mind reflects Italian thoughts at that moment. Similarly, if a student blurts out one or two words in their mother tongue, it should be considered normal.	Unconscious Use of L1	Acceptance of Linguistic Diversity in Educational Settings
P13	Online learning is a reasonable choice in response to government requirements for social distancing and avoiding cross-infection policies.	Secure Online Learning Environment	Emphasis on Safety in Learning Environments
P13	The cost of flying from China to the UK during the pandemic has significantly increased, and there is also the risk of infection and high medical expenses. Many students are now unwilling to go to the UK.	Secure Online Learning Environment	Emphasis on Safety in Learning Environments
P13	For me, online courses are very convenient and give me more free time. One of the advantages is that online courses can be recorded anytime and anywhere, which means I can review and revise at any time, and that's a big advantage.	Advantages of Online Learning Across Geography and Time	Accessibility of Courses
P13	Online courses are more flexible and liberating. It's obviously more convenient for students with long commutes.	Advantages of Online Learning Across Geography and Time	Reduction of Travel Time
P13	It's definitely helpful. If you want to study across countries, online learning is the most effective way. Especially during the pandemic, it's almost impossible to attend classes in person due to the geographical distance between China and the UK, so you have to choose online learning.	Advantages of Online Learning Across Geography and Time	Challenges of In-Person Attendance During COVID-19

P13	When exploring content pertinent to my research topic, I frequently utilize online resources. Among these, I have discovered numerous academic lectures that are not only accessible but also offered without cost. Participating in these lectures has been incredibly useful for my studies, as they have provided insightful and pertinent information that has significantly enhanced my research efforts.	Advantages of Online Learning Across Geography and Time	Enhancement of Research Through Insightful Information
P13	For example, in a lesson, the teacher will recommend some online learning resources, then the teacher can show us how to do it in real time on the computer by sharing the screen.	Enhancing Teaching with Digital Features	Facilitation of Resource Accessibility
P13	Taking classes in a noisy environment will definitely affect learning outcomes. Moreover, in a noisy setting, students may be reluctant to turn on their microphones for oral expression.	Issues with Attention Distraction	Difficulty in Concentration
P13	One more convenient thing is that online courses can be recorded at any time and any place, so students can review them anytime, which is a great advantage.	Autonomy in Online Learning	Video Recording Feature
P13	After the presentation, the speaker provides a final Q&A session. It's a chance to participate and I practice my speaking skills during this time.	Participant and pseudo-participation	Encouragement of Audience Participation
P13	Using Chinese means that English speaking practice cannot be relatively strengthened. Because using Chinese in meetings and discussions is not conducive to English speaking practice.	Impact of Language Choice on Speaking Practice	Limited Opportunities for English Speaking
P14	The reason I chose to stay in China for online courses is that my Chinese university has special circumstances, such as a shortage of faculty. Therefore, as long as my energy allows, I will still take on some work.	Advantages of Online Learning Across Geography and Time	Adaptation to Institutional Challenges
P14	Teachers recommend online learning resources in class, such as websites, and show us how to access them in real-time through screen sharing. It's easy for us to understand at a glance. During Zoom classes, teachers also share website links or articles (PDF, Doc) in the Chatbox, and we can open them immediately. This digital learning method is very convenient and timely.	Enhancing Teaching with Digital Features	Real-Time Access to Learning Materials
P14	PhD students, in particular, need self-study skills	Autonomy in online learning	Essential for Independent Research
P14	Apart from the online course modules, I believe we can also access other valuable information from the internet, which can supplement non-real-time classroom learning.	Autonomy in online learning	Flexibility of Learning Opportunities
P14	I actually participate in oral discussions quite often in online classes.	Motivation for Oral Expression	Contribution to Collaborative Learning

P14	mixes Chinese and English when meeting with their supervisor because the supervisor is Chinese.	Attitudes of Teachers towards the Use of L1	Facilitation of Understanding
P14	I believe that every student can benefit from online courses during the pandemic.	Secure Online Learning Environment	Accessibility of Education
P15	when some people ask a question, there will be a special translator or staff member typing in the chat box or sharing some links, and then the Participants can open them directly on their own computers and read the materials for themselves without having to wait for others.	Enhancing Teaching with Digital Features	Promoting Self-Directed Learning
P15	Everyone becomes more isolated and then more vulnerable and less resistant to frustration.	Challenges of Emotions and Mental Health	Lowered Resistance to Stress
P15	The psychological experience for students can vary greatly. In the past, before the pandemic, Chinese students studying in the UK had a positive impression and a fulfilling experience. However, if I had come to study during the Covid-19 pandemic, I would have missed out on many of the joys of studying abroad. If I had faced any minor difficulties or challenges, I would have been confined to my room, attending online classes all the time. I believe this would have resulted in a very negative psychological experience after completing my studies.	Challenges of Emotions and Mental Health	Negative Psychological Outcomes
P15	If it was a problem with the headphones and the network, I don't think it was overcome, I'm not saying that it was overcome because of the nature of some of the conferences or training that I attended.	Limitations of Technical Solutions in Specific Contexts	Inadequacy of Solutions for Certain Conferences
P15	What you see in online meetings and seminars can be easily recorded, and then easily copied and saved, generating electronic notes.		Electronic Notes
P15	With the current online courses, the knowledge I've gained from my PhD, I don't think my speaking has improved much, because I don't rely much on speaking, I don't put a lot of time and effort into improving my speaking.	Factors Influencing Oral Expression Motivation	Differences in academic disciplines
P15	We just type and send messages, and very few people choose to communicate through voice or video	Silent Communication: The Dual Nature of Chatbox Functionality	Influence of Online Environment on Communication Style
P15	But if there are people from other countries in the group, speaking Chinese would exclude non-Chinese students from the discussion, which I think is very bad and very racist.	Concerns About Inclusivity in Communication	Impact on Group Dynamics

P15	The outbreak disrupted my data collection plan. I had intended to visit companies in person, but now I can only conduct interviews through phone or WeChat. This method makes it difficult to establish trust with the interviewees and fails to capture subtle non-verbal communication. It is quite different from my original research design.	Network Restrictions and Time Zone Challenges	Changes to Data Collection Methods
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Appendix 9 Ethics Approval Letter

22/09/2021

Dear Jing Liu,

Your application 16698: An exploration of the role of online education in developing oral English skills to facilitate the transnational education experiences of Chinese students progressing to university study in the UK, submission 14016, has been approved by the Education and Social Sciences SEC. You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr Iain McPhee

18/03/2022

Dear Jing Liu,

Your application 17838: Jing Liu- Research proposal pro forma for interview Revised new, submission reference 15110, has been approved, with conditions, by the Education and Social Sciences SEC. **You may proceed with your study provided you meet the conditions outlined below:**

Please check the details highlighted in the embedded comments with your supervisor. You need to give accurate information about the duration of the interview.

You need to clarify that ethical approval has already been granted for phase one of your project - if not, this should be included in this application

Please also detail how any anxiety provoked will be dealt with in your debrief.

If you wish to make any significant changes to your study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr Julie Clark & Dr Lucy Troup
Co-Chairs, ESS Ethics Committee

Dr Lucy Troup

Appendix 10 Participant Information

Below is the **Participant Information Table**. This table encapsulates the 15 participants' online learning experiences up to October 2021, aligning with the interview period between September and October 2021.

Participant Information Table

Participant	Degree Pursued	Field of Study	Countries Where Courses Were Undertaken	Mode of Online Learning	Duration of Online Learning	Completion of Language Courses
P1	Bachelor	Business	United Kingdom	Entirely Online (2020)	Early 2020 pandemic period	Yes
P2	Bachelor	Education	China	Entirely Online (2020)	Early 2020 pandemic period	Yes
P3	Bachelor	Computing	China (5 months online), United Kingdom	Hybrid (Online & On-campus)	5 months online in 2020, subsequently on-campus	Yes
P4	Bachelor	Business	United Kingdom	Entirely Online (2020)	Early 2020 pandemic period	Yes
P5	Bachelor	Engineering	United Kingdom (2 months online), China	Hybrid (Online & On-campus)	2 months online in 2020, subsequently on-campus	Yes
P6	Master	Business	United Kingdom	Entirely Online (2020)	Early 2020 pandemic period	Yes
P7	Master	Education	United Kingdom	Entirely Online (2020)	Early 2020 pandemic period	Yes

Participant	Degree Pursued	Field of Study	Countries Where Courses Were Undertaken	Mode of Online Learning	Duration of Online Learning	Completion of Language Courses
P8	Master	Sports	United Kingdom	Entirely Online (2020)	Early 2020 pandemic period	Yes
P9	Master	Engineering	United Kingdom	Entirely Online (2020)	Early 2020 pandemic period	Yes
P10	Master	Computing	United Kingdom	Entirely Online (2020)	Early 2020 pandemic period	Yes
P11	Doctoral	Education	China	Entirely Online (2020)	Early 2020 pandemic period	Yes
P12	Doctoral	Computing	China (1 month online), United Kingdom	Hybrid (Online & On-campus)	1 month online in 2020, subsequently on-campus	Yes
P13	Doctoral	Business	China (1 year online), United Kingdom	Hybrid (Online & On-campus)	1 year online in 2020, subsequently on-campus	Yes
P14	Doctoral	Education	China	Entirely Online (2020)	Early 2020 pandemic period	Yes
P15	Doctoral	Biology	China (1 year online), United Kingdom	Hybrid (Online & On-campus)	1 year online in 2020, subsequently on-campus	Yes